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Efficient and Flexible Partitioned Simulation of Fluid-Structure Interactions

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Abstract

Computer simulations of fluid-structure interaction (FSI) phenomena have become an established branch of numerical simulation, with a wide range of applications in engineering, natural, and life sciences. Due to the integration of additional disciplines such as optimization, uncertainty quantification, or the inclusion of new physical fields such as acoustics or thermodynamics, the complexity of such simulations is constantly increasing. The partitioned approach to FSI, a domain decomposition technique, can be used to reduce this complexity. It allows to couple existing and mature flow and structure solvers by a third unit which gathers and provides all coupling related functionality.

A trusted set of algorithms exists for standard problems, while more sophisticated FSI scenarios, particularly those involving incompressible flows, are still regarded as challenging. For those problems more efficient algorithms have been developed recently and are still to be spread among the community. An important observation is that most groups are still developing their own set of application-specific coupling functionality, despite the obvious possibility to reuse existing coupling codes.

This work tries to improve that situation by developing and implementing a coupling library that uses validated state of the art algorithms for partitioned FSI. The library is designed to be generic from scratch, treating solvers as black boxes to fully exploit the inherent flexibility of the partitioned approach. Particular emphasis is set on component-based design to allow for simple future extensions and user friendliness to foster acceptance by FSI application developers. Computations of benchmark and application scenarios validate and show the potential of the implemented functionality.

Zusammenfassung

Die rechnergestützte Simulation von Phänomenen der Fluid-Struktur-Wechselwirkung (FSW) hat sich zu einem etablierten Zweig in der numerischen Simulation entwickelt, mit einem großen Umfang an Anwendungen in den Ingenieurs-, Natur- und Lebenswissenschaften. Durch die Integration zusätzlicher Funktionalitäten wie der Optimierung, von Uncertainty Quantification, oder der Einbeziehung zusätzlicher physikalischer Felder wie der Akustik oder Thermodynamik, steigt die Komplexität solcher Simulationen stetig an. Der partitionierte Ansatz für FSW, eine Gebietszerlegungsmethode, kann genutzt werden um diese Komplexität zu reduzieren. Er erlaubt es bereits existierende und ausgereifte Strömungs- und Strukturlöser durch eine dritte Einheit zu koppeln, die kopplungsrelevante Funktionalitäten sammelt und zur Verfügung stellt.

Während eine zuverlässige Menge an Algorithmen für Standardprobleme existiert, werden fortgeschrittenere FSW Szenarien, im Speziellen solche die inkompressible Strömungen beinhalten, noch immer als herausfordernd eingestuft. Für diese Probleme wurden in letzter Zeit effizientere Algorithmen entwickelt, die noch nicht ganz in den Communities Eingang gefunden haben. Eine wichtige Beobachtung ist, dass viele Gruppen immer noch ihre eigene Menge an anwendungsspezifischen Kopplungsfunktionalitäten entwickeln, trotz der offensichtlichen Möglichkeit existierende Kopplungssoftware wiederzuverwenden.

Diese Arbeit versucht die derzeitige Situation zu verbessern, indem eine Kopplungsbibliothek entwickelt und implementiert wird, die validierte und aktuelle Algorithmen für partitionierte FSW nutzt. Die Bibliothek ist von vorneherein als anwendungsunabhängig gestaltet und behandelt die Löser als Black Boxen um die dem partitionierten Ansatz innewohnende Flexibilität ganz auszunutzen. Besondere Wichtigkeit wird auf ein komponentenbasiertes Design gelegt, um zukünftige Erweiterungen einfach zu ermöglichen und auf Nutzerfreundlichkeit, um die Akzeptanz bei Entwicklern von FSW Applikationen zu erhöhen. Berechnungen von Benchmark- und Anwendungsszenarien validieren und zeigen das Potential der implementierten Funktionalität.

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1 Introduction

This work contributes new efficient software approaches and algorithms for the partitioned numerical simulation of fluid-structure interaction (FSI) phenomena. FSI simulations started to become a major research topic in the middle of the '90s [132, 12, 110, 101, 179, 32, 151, 57, 144, 94, 73] with references therein, while simulations of fluids and structures alone had been done for many years, already. The reason for this time gap can be found in the increase of computational complexity when handling two physical fields at the same time and in the additional complications arising from their interaction. Meanwhile, the simulation of FSI has become an established branch in computational science and engineering and many of the initial problems have been solved. However, while the interest in the beginning was centered on engineering problems mainly, the scope has broadened to fields such as biomedical simulations of hemodynamical systems [13, 75, 55, 162, 35]. Not only the application fields have evolved, also the expectations have grown. While in the beginning, the focus was on obtaining feasible results at all, now, often additional disciplines such as optimization [86, 143, 45] or uncertainty quantification [55, 178, 171] are integrated. Similarly, while the coupling of two physical fields was considered a challenge in the beginning, recently three (or even more) field couplings such as fluid-structure-acoustics [12, 105, 141] are targeted, moving further into the realm of multi-physics. Overall, a constant increase of complexity can be observed and the end of this development is not even in sight.

What computer scientists usually do when a problem becomes too complex, is to break it into smaller manageable pieces, which can be recombined again in a later, hopefully not too complicated step. Applying this approach to FSI naturally results in a domain decomposition into fluid and structure fields. Solving each of the fields separately and combining their solutions to an overall FSI solution is known as the partitioned approach¹ [132, 59, 113]. In fact, the partitioned approach has been used from the beginning, since many groups starting with FSI simulation already had an existing fluid or structure solver (or even both) at hand such that much of their knowledge and codebase could be reused. The idea of code reuse is still one of the major reasons for applying the partitioned approach. However, one of its main drawbacks is the inferior stability when compared to its counterpart, the monolithic approach [64]. Here, recent research has shown that partitioned algorithms can be constructed which extend the applicability to far more demanding scenarios while still pertaining a good overall computational performance [43].

¹The partitioned approach is sometimes also called loose coupling approach [58, 106] in literature.

1 Introduction

The partitioned approach does not only allow to reuse the simulation software for the physical fields, but also provides the possibility to encapsulate the functionality establishing the coupling between the fields in an own, reusable component. The most important groups of features are equation coupling, data mapping, and data communication. If restricting to functionality that requires only minimal access to the solver codes, i.e., treating the solvers as black boxes, only small efforts are required to couple a new solver. An important observation is that many groups are still developing their own set of coupling functionality [70, 125, 142], despite the obvious possibility for reuse. Often, the functionality is implemented directly into the solver codes or is highly application dependent. Furthermore, some of the more recent and highly efficient schemes still have to be spread among the communities. This is where this work sets in.

The main goal of this work is to provide a coupling software for the partitioned coupling approach. Efficient state-of-the art algorithms for all major coupling tasks should be made available to scientists and engineers in order to support their goals. To maximally benefit from the partitioned approach, its inherent flexibility needs to be leveraged. This entails the use of functionalities which are compatible with black box solvers and a proper programming interface in order to keep algorithmic details transparent to the solver codes, i.e., exchangable without solver code adaptations. The software should also be extensible in order to allow for the development and integration of new algorithms related to partitioned coupling. A part of this work is dedicated to the development of new algorithms for partitioned coupling. Another important goal of this work is to provide a query interface to solid geometries for Cartesian grid solvers. Since FSI is a surface coupled problem and solid geometries can be represented by surfaces, too, many data structures and functionalities can be reused. In the following Section 1.1, the main contributions of this work are summarized. Then, a brief overview of the main product of this work, the coupling software preCICE, is given in Section 1.2. Section 1.3 summarizes the remaining chapters of this work.

1.1 Main Contributions

In this work, a new approach to design a software for the partitioned coupling of simulation programs (with focus on FSI) has been developed. A new high-level programming interface leading to an increased flexibility with respect to the chosen coupling functionality has been investigated and applied. It allows to provide all important coupling functionality in a transparent and dynamically configurable way.

A software environment with a modern, efficient, and full feature set for partitioned coupled simulations has been developed according to the above approach. A relevant set of algorithms for coupling the partitioned equations, mapping data between non-matching grids, and communicating data between distributed solver executables has been integrated. The software has been implemented using best-practices from software engineering such as object-oriented-programming, automated unit tests, and design pat-

terns, to achieve a clearly structured and easily extensible design.

A different aspect this work contributes to is to provide a comprehensive overview of partitioned equation coupling schemes for black box coupling. Similar attempts have been made by others, e.g., in [15], but with a different focus or to a lesser extent.

Considering the development of coupling algorithms, a new approach for conservative data mapping based on a data post-processing has been devised, implemented, and tested. The main advantage of the new approach is that it allows to use two independent consistent mappings for the transfer of data between flow and structure solver.

A geometry interface for Cartesian grid solvers with a new algorithm for creating a spacetree and acceleration of positional queries has been developed, implemented, and tested. The approach decouples the spacetree from the solver grid and, thus, widens its range of applicability.

Finally, a set of validation scenarios has been computed to validate the taken approaches and implemented features, ranging from academic benchmarking scenarios to three-dimensional application scenarios with engineering relevance.

1.2 *preCICE* – The Complete Picture

The main outcome of this work is the coupling environment *preCICE* (precise code interaction coupling environment). To get a first idea of the overall concept, an attempt for the complete picture is made here.

preCICE provides an extensive feature set for the partitioned coupling of black box solvers with a focus on FSI and a geometry interface for Cartesian grid solvers. It is designed to be compatible with a wide range of solvers, offering an application programming interface (API) in C++, C, and Fortran. The API consists of high-level library-like methods to abstract from a message-passing paradigm and enables solvers to use coupling functionality in a transparent and, hence, flexible way. After integrating the API calls into a solver code, it is coupled in a peer-to-peer communication approach, i.e., without any central control instance. It can be run sequentially or parallel, without adaptations to the integrated API. The concrete coupling algorithms used in a simulation are selected by an extensive XML configuration mechanism that allows to adapt different solvers in an optimal way.

Figure 1.1 tries to sketch the complete picture. It shows the four main functionality groups in the middle and a coupling of two solvers with involved components. Solver A runs in parallel with n processes while solver B is executed sequentially. The parallel execution of solver A is supported by a (local) client-server approach, where the coupling data are moved to a separate server process.

Fig. 1.1: The complete picture of preCICE. The four main functionality groups are shown in the middle. Furthermore, a two solver coupling of a parallel solver A to a sequential solver B is shown. The parallel execution of solver A is supported by a (local) client-server approach, where its coupling data are stored at a separate server process.

1.3 Chapter Overview

The remainder of this work is organized as follows:

In **Chapter 2**, the relevant state of the art for this work is summarized. Beginning from the physical basis and ending with the partitioned coupling functionality, all relevant modeling and discretization steps are described. While the discretization methods for the physical fields are treated only superficially, more space is reserved for methods of the partitioned approach, in particular equation coupling schemes for black box solvers. Furthermore, literature related to geometry representation and allocation for Cartesian grid solvers is discussed. A brief review and categorization of existing coupling software closes the chapter.

Chapter 3 dives right into the software development considerations for the coupling environment preCICE, the main software product developed in this work. The design goals, requirements analysis, and design decisions are presented. Deployment schemes for the involved components are reviewed and evaluated. A suitable application programming interface is derived and the software architecture is presented. Finally, the achieved software development goals are evaluated.

The implemented functionality as well as newly developed approaches are presented and evaluated in **Chapter 4**. Its sections are about equation coupling schemes, data

mapping methods, and inter-solver communication methods. Furthermore, the geometry interface functionality and additional non-core features are presented. Each group of functionality is evaluated separately with help of simple scenarios.

Chapter 5 goes from single components to overall FSI simulations of benchmark and application scenarios. First, the coupled solvers are presented, followed by the computation of FSI benchmark scenarios. Then, simulations of floating structures under wave action are presented. Finally, explosive blast simulation scenarios are shown.

A summary and ideas for future extensions wrap up this work in **Chapter 6**.

2 Overview of Approaches to Partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction

This chapter summarizes the foundations of partitioned fluid-structure interaction (FSI) simulation and reviews the current state of research. The following topics deal with mathematical modeling, numerical discretization, and computer science aspects. Much of the modeling in FSI can be directly taken from the modeling of the individual fields of fluid and structural mechanics. However, in addition to the single field models, the coupling of the fields needs to be taken into account. This is not only a coupling of the mathematical models, but also a coupling of different points of view (or reference), in which the models are described. For the discretization of the mathematical models, one of the major decisions is whether to choose a monolithic or a partitioned approach. While, for some people, this seems to be an almost religious decision, it can be viewed from a practical point of view, too. Since this work is about the partitioned approach with special emphasis on modularity and flexibility aspects, only corresponding discretization methods are described in depth. One consequence of choosing the partitioned approach is that the discretizations of fluid and structure models are relatively independent and even an overview of discretization methods for the single fields would exceed the scope of this work. Thus, references to standard textbooks are given where helpful.

In the following, Section 2.1 deals with points of view typically used in the description of flows and structures. Furthermore, the standard equations for modeling laminar flows and elastic structures as well as the coupling conditions at their common FSI interface are derived. Section 2.2 gives an overview of discretization methods for FSI, involving an overview of both the monolithic and the partitioned approach. Discretization techniques for the partitioned approach are reviewed in detail in Sections 2.3 and 2.4, followed by a presentation of data structures and algorithms related to the geometry interface functionality in Section 2.5. Finally, existing simulation packages for the partitioned simulation of FSI are presented in Section 2.6.

2.1 Physics and Modelling

The basis of any numerical simulation is a mathematical model for the scenario under consideration. For FSI, this involves the description of fluids, structures, and their interaction. In order to understand these descriptions, we first have to look at the points of view an observer of a physical system can take in Section 2.1.1. Then, we derive the main equations used to model fluids, structures, and their interaction in Section 2.1.2. The following is not ought to be a complete derivation of the models used in FSI. Since the focus of this work is not on modeling, this would exceed its scope. Instead, this section serves as a summary of the basic equations used repeatedly in later chapters.

2.1.1 Points of View

When observing phenomena, the point of view taken by the observer may heavily influence the form of the observations made. All points of view can lead to valid results. However, not all of the results may be equally simple to interpret and comprehend. One of the most prominent examples for this are the observations Nikolaus Kopernikus made in the 16th century. After switching the point of observer from a fixed earth to a fixed sun, the overly complicated (but valid) trajectories of the planets became simple ellipsoidals. This led to the important discovery that our earth is not the center of the universe.

In classical continuum mechanics there are two main points of view: The *Lagrangian* and the *Eulerian* depicted in Figure 2.1. The *arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian* (ALE) point of view has been introduced to simplify the coupling of the two aforementioned views and to combine their advantages. All of the approaches observe the same *spatial domain*, which we denote by $\Omega_x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. The following derivations are based on [52]. A more original source can be found in [109].

Lagrangian Observer

A Lagrangian observer fixes its frame of reference to the (material) domain Ω_X of observation and follows its movements and deformations as depicted in Figure 2.1a. We speak of a *material description*, since we follow the individual material points $\mathbf{X} \in \Omega_X$ in space, measuring their position and properties. Figure 2.2a gives a mesh-based interpretation of the Lagrangian viewpoint, where the mesh points follow the material points. The material domain is often chosen to be the spatial domain at initial configuration, but can be any reference configuration available. Since points of observation are moved with observed material points, the geometric configuration in the material domain does not change. To relate the material and spatial domain and get the current geometric

Fig. 2.1: Lagrangian (a) and Eulerian (b) observers. The Lagrangian observer follows the movement and deformation of each material particle \mathbf{X} in the (fixed) material reference frame Ω_X , while the Eulerian observer fixes its frame of reference to the observed spatial domain Ω_x and observes material particles \mathbf{x} passing through fixed positions.

configuration, a mapping φ is used

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\mathbf{X}, t) &= (\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \varphi: \Omega_X \times \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \Omega_x \times \mathbb{R}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

as depicted in Fig. 2.3. Note the dependency of $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}(\mathbf{X}, t)$, while time t is the same in material and spatial domain. We define the material velocity, i.e., velocity of a material point \mathbf{X} , as

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{x}} \quad (2.2)$$

where $|_{\mathbf{x}}$ indicates that the chosen material point is fixed in the derivative. The Jacobian matrix of φ with respect to \mathbf{X} and t is given as

$$J_\varphi(\mathbf{X}, t) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} & \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial t} \\ \frac{\partial t}{\partial \mathbf{X}} & \frac{\partial t}{\partial t} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \mathbf{X}} & \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{0}^T & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.3)$$

and has to fulfill $\det(\partial \mathbf{x} / \partial \mathbf{X}) > 0$ to guarantee a well defined mapping in both directions.

The advantages of the Lagrangian point of view are due to the fixed material reference frame. It enables the implicit treatment of moving boundaries and allows to easily associate a property history to each material point. However, the requirement for the mapping φ to be well defined limits the deformations of Ω_X . The Lagrangian approach is typically employed in structural mechanics, when the material points of an object undergo only comparatively small deformations.

Eulerian Observer

In the Eulerian approach or spatial description, the observer uses the spatial domain Ω_x as frame of reference and material properties are measured at fixed positions $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega_x$,

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Fig. 2.2: Lagrangian (a), Eulerian (b), and ALE (c) viewpoints illustrated with one-dimensional computational mesh points (dashed circles), material domain (grey thick line) and material points (filled circles). All depicted configurations are seen from the spatial domain Ω_x , i.e., the motion of material and mesh is visible. For every viewpoint there are two configurations of mesh points and material displayed, where the initial configuration is shown on top and the changed configuration at the bottom. The only difference between the different viewpoints is how the mesh is changed. Material and material points are deformed in the same way for every viewpoint. For the Lagrangian approach (a), the mesh points are moved with the initially assigned material points. In the Eulerian approach (b), the mesh points are kept fixed. The ALE approach (c) allows for an arbitrary movement of mesh points, independent of the material, which can be utilized to follow the material boundaries but lessen the internal mesh distortions.

independent from the movement of the material observed (see Figures 2.1b and 2.2b). Despite not used by an Eulerian observer, the material domain and mapping φ are still relevant for deriving mathematical descriptions. First of all, we have to relate a material property $f^*(\mathbf{X}, t)$ to its spatial equivalent $f(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at the same position by using

Fig. 2.3: Material domain Ω_X , mapping φ , and spatial domain Ω_x in the Lagrangian approach. While the geometric setup in the material domain is fixed, displacements and deformations occur when mapped to the spatial domain.

the mapping φ as

$$f^*(\mathbf{X}, t) = f(\varphi(\mathbf{X}, t)) = f(\mathbf{x}, t) \circ \varphi(\mathbf{X}, t). \quad (2.4)$$

We assume f to be a scalar here, but the derivations are equally valid for the vectorial case. Next, to derive the fundamental material equations in the Eulerian point of view, we need the change of f over time t . This change is obtained by the multidimensional chain rule, using the Jacobian matrices of f and φ . Since f is scalar here, the Jacobian matrix will be a row matrix with number of columns equal to the number of variables that f depends on. Oppositely, the Jacobian matrix of a multi-dimensional function with respect to a scalar is a column matrix. Knowing this, we can write the partial derivative of the material property with respect to time as

$$\frac{\partial f^*}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial (f \circ \varphi)}{\partial t} = J_f(\varphi) J_\varphi(t) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} \right) \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{v} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) f. \quad (2.5)$$

Thus, at a given spatial position \mathbf{x} , the change of a property f over time is caused by the change of the property itself over time and by the convective transport of neighboring material with material velocity \mathbf{v} . Note that the convective term only has an influence if the property value changes over space, expressed by the gradient operator. This relation between material and spatial time derivatives is called *material* or *substantial derivative* and defined as

$$\frac{df}{dt} := \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) f. \quad (2.6)$$

Another important relation is the time derivative of an integral over a time-dependent volume, which is given by the *Reynolds transport theorem*. We consider a material volume $V(t)$, i.e., a volume that contains the same material points at all times t , with closed surface $S(t)$. The volume moves with material velocity $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ at $\mathbf{x} \in S(t)$. Furthermore, we assume that $V(t)$ coincides with the fixed control volume V_c for a given time t and that $S(t)$ coincides with the fixed control surface S_c . The material derivative (2.6) of the integral over $V(t)$ of a smooth scalar function $f(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in spatial coordinates is then

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given by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} f dV = \int_{V_c \equiv V(t)} \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} dV + \int_{S_c \equiv S(t)} f \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS, \quad (2.7)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the unit outer normal of the control surface S_c . The material derivative of the integral is hence given by the local time derivative plus the flux of quantity f over surface S_c . For a full derivation see, e.g., [19]. The surface integral can be changed to a volume integral by using Gauss' rule, which results in

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} f dV = \int_{V_c \equiv V(t)} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f \mathbf{v}) \right) dV, \quad (2.8)$$

and the divergence term can be expanded to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} f dV = \int_{V_c \equiv V(t)} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) f + f(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) \right) dV. \quad (2.9)$$

Note that the final form of the Reynolds transport theorem (2.9) contains an additional term $f(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})$ in comparison to the material derivative (2.6). This term can be seen as a compression or expansion of the material, which leads to a change of property f for a material volume.

The practical advantage of the Eulerian description is its ability to handle arbitrary deformations, since the identity of spatial and reference domain removes the necessity of a mapping. Its drawback is the absence of a description of the boundaries of the material observed, which makes the use of special methods necessary when knowledge about boundaries is required. The Eulerian approach has been traditionally employed in fluid mechanics, where large deformations occur in a given domain.

Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) Observer

An observer taking the arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) point of view uses a third reference frame Ω_χ , called *referential domain*. The ALE viewpoint allows to move the points of observation independent of the material, which results in a mesh motion in addition to a material motion in the spatial domain. Figure 2.2c depicts a scenario with ALE viewpoint seen from the spatial domain. The geometry (but not the material) of the referential domain is fixed for an observer of that frame. The difference to the material domain is, that the material is allowed to move relative to the referential domain. While the material frame of reference is used to derive the ALE equations, it suffices to work in the referential domain in practice and to transform it to the spatial domain by a given mapping when required. As mappings, Φ and Ψ are used to transform referential coordinates χ to the material and spatial domain, as illustrated in Figure 2.4. While Φ is used directly to map from referential to spatial domain

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(\chi, t) &= (\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \Phi: \Omega_\chi \times \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \Omega_x \times \mathbb{R}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

we use the inverse mapping of Ψ to express the mapping from material to referential domain

$$\begin{aligned}\Psi^{-1}(\mathbf{X}, t) &= (\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) \\ \Psi^{-1}: \Omega_X \times \mathbb{R} &\rightarrow \Omega_\chi \times \mathbb{R}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.11)$$

We obtain two new velocity expressions by doing so. The first expresses the movement of the referential domain with regards to the spatial domain, often called mesh velocity

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\boldsymbol{\chi}, t) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial t} \right|_{\boldsymbol{\chi}}. \quad (2.12)$$

This velocity can be imagined by fixing the attention to one point $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ of the referential domain (e.g., a mesh node), and observing its movement in the spatial domain. The second velocity measure expresses the material velocity with regards to the referential domain

$$\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{X}, t) = \left. \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}}{\partial t} \right|_{\mathbf{X}}. \quad (2.13)$$

It, thus, expresses the velocity of a fixed material point relative to the mesh in the referential domain. If the mesh velocity equals the material velocity in every point, then \mathbf{w} equals zero, which results in the Lagrangian viewpoint.

Fig. 2.4: Relation of material Ω_X , spatial Ω_x , and referential Ω_χ domain in the ALE approach.

By differentiating the relation $\varphi = \Phi \circ \Psi^{-1}$ with respect to time, we obtain the relationship between the mesh velocity (2.12), material velocity in referential frame (2.13), and material velocity in spatial frame (2.2) as

$$\mathbf{v} = \hat{\mathbf{v}} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} \cdot \mathbf{w}. \quad (2.14)$$

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We define the convective velocity \mathbf{c} as

$$\mathbf{c} := \mathbf{v} - \hat{\mathbf{v}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} \cdot \mathbf{w}, \quad (2.15)$$

which is the relative velocity between material and referential domain seen from the spatial domain. If the referential domain is only changed by translations, then $\partial \mathbf{x} / \partial \boldsymbol{\chi} = \mathbf{I}$, and $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{w}$. By choosing $\boldsymbol{\Psi} = \mathbf{I}$ or $\boldsymbol{\Phi} = \mathbf{I}$, the Lagrangian or Eulerian approach, respectively, are obtained as special cases.

Similar as for the Eulerian approach in (2.5), the change of a scalar referential property f^{**} over time is obtained by chaining the derivatives of $f^{**} = f^* \circ \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1}$ as

$$\frac{\partial f^{**}}{\partial t} = J_{f^*}(\boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1}) J_{\boldsymbol{\Psi}^{-1}}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f^*}{\partial \boldsymbol{\chi}} & \frac{\partial f^*}{\partial t} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{w} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\partial f^*}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\chi}}) f^*, \quad (2.16)$$

where $\nabla_{\boldsymbol{\chi}}$ is the gradient operator in referential coordinates. Since the evaluation of the gradient of f^* in the referential domain is often more difficult than in the spatial domain, we further use (2.15) to get the *fundamental ALE relation* of material time derivatives, referential time derivatives, and spatial gradient

$$\frac{\partial f^{**}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial f^*}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) f. \quad (2.17)$$

An analogous relation as for the Reynolds transport theorem can be derived using the referential time derivative. The results are as in equation (2.7) and (2.9), but with mesh velocity $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ instead of material velocity \mathbf{v} .

The ALE viewpoint has been introduced to combine the Lagrangian and Eulerian points of view, as met in FSI. Instead of using an Eulerian approach for the fluid, the ALE approach can be employed. The fluid mesh velocity $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ is chosen such that, at the common interface of fluid and structure, a Lagrangian behavior is obtained which fits to the structural description. In the fluid interior, the distortions of the interface are balanced out by a suitable mesh smoothing procedure. As in the Lagrangian approach, there is a limit of maximum deformation after which the mappings between domains become ill-conditioned. While a good mesh smoothing allows for relatively large deformations, the ALE approach is still not suitable for arbitrarily large deformations without remeshing techniques.

Summary of Viewpoints

We have seen three different approaches on how to observe a material: the Lagrangian, Eulerian, and arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) points of view. While the mathematical equations are easily set up in the Lagrangian viewpoint, where material points are fixed to points of observation, its limitations are reached when large deformations

occur. While those are overcome in the Eulerian approach through fixed points of observation, information about material boundaries is not available automatically here. The ALE approach tries to combine the best of both worlds by following the material at the boundaries in a Lagrangian way and adapting the interior mesh to keep distortions low. However, even with the ALE approach, limitations are reached when deformations (particularly translations and rotations) become too large, and remeshing techniques have to be used for maximal flexibility.

In the following, first the fluid equations will be derived for the Eulerian and the ALE point of view. Then, the structural equations are derived using the Lagrangian point of view. All three viewpoints occur in different simulation tools employed for numerical experiments in Chapter 5.

2.1.2 Fluid Dynamics

The theory of fluid dynamics is categorized according to flow types. Important categories are compressible or incompressible flows¹, viscous or inviscid flows², and laminar or turbulent flows³. In this thesis, the focus is on incompressible flows, while compressible flows are seen more as a side topic. Note that incompressible flows are regarded as more difficult in the context of FSI simulations due to stability issues (discussed in Section 2.3.3). The coupling methods introduced later are applicable to both compressible and incompressible flows. We derive the main fluid equations including compressibility effects and then simplify them for the incompressible case. Viscous effects are considered at most places in this work such that the derivations include terms related to viscosity. Turbulence, while playing an important role in many real-life applications, is ignored completely within this thesis to lower the overall complexity. To get a more complete view on the topic, the reader is referred to standard textbooks on fluid mechanics such as [11, 63, 62, 133].

The dynamics of fluids is governed by the conservation of mass, momentum, and,

¹In general, a fluid is considered to be incompressible if its density is constant. This is true for fluids with high resistance against compression, but also comprises compressible fluids in flows with low Mach number, i.e., flows where the speed of sound of the fluid is much higher than the flow velocity. Furthermore, fluids with slowly changing density over space can be assumed to be incompressible, despite their density is not constant on the large scale. Oceanic water or the earth's atmosphere under gravitational influence are such cases.

²A fluid cannot statically resist a shear force, but deforms under the influence of it. The viscosity determines the rate of deformation, given a certain amount of shear force. Honey, for example, has a high viscosity in comparison to water. A fluid with no viscosity can resist only normal forces, i.e., pressures. Also, when a viscous fluid is at rest (hydrostatic case), all shear forces vanish and only pressure forces remain (see Section 5.3.1).

³Turbulence is caused by macro- or microscopic disturbances in, e.g., the flow domain geometry. Once a certain limit of flow parameters, characterized by the so-called Reynolds number Re , is exceeded, the disturbances lead to highly irregular flow patterns in space and time. A cascade of eddies from macroscopic to microscopic scale transports kinetic energy into dissipation and increases shear forces compared to the laminar case.

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for compressible flows, of energy. In the following, we discuss the conservation of mass and momentum. We leave out energy conservation, since compressible flows are not the main focus of this work. The conservation laws can be expressed in integral as well as differential (or local) form. The integral forms are obtained by applying the Reynolds transport theorem (2.9) to the properties to be conserved. The differential forms are obtained from the integral ones, by choosing the volume of integration to be infinitesimal which results in dropping the integrals. All forms are derived using spatial representation, i.e., Eulerian point of view. Small modifications of the derived equations yield the corresponding ALE forms.

Conservation of Mass

The conservation of mass states that the total amount of mass in a closed system is constant over time and leads to the so-called continuity equation. The change of mass M of a (time-dependent) volume $V(t)$, hence, must be zero and is given by the Reynolds transport theorem (2.9) as

$$\frac{d}{dt}M = \frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho \, dV = \int_{V(t)} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \right) dV = 0. \quad (2.18)$$

Choosing $V(t)$ to be infinitesimal enables us to drop the integrals and to get the differential form of the continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \rho + \rho (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) = 0. \quad (2.19)$$

For incompressible flows, the partial derivatives of ρ with respect to time and space vanish and (2.19) can be simplified to

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0. \quad (2.20)$$

Conservation of Momentum

The conservation of momentum is derived from Newton's second law that states that a change of momentum in a system is always due to a force \mathbf{F} acting on it. Again, using the Reynolds transport theorem (2.8), we can write

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{v} \, dV = \int_{V(t)} \left(\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho \mathbf{v} \mathbf{v}) \right) dV = \mathbf{F}. \quad (2.21)$$

Using the continuity equation (2.19) and the material derivative (2.6), we can rewrite this equation to

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{v} \, dV = \int_{V(t)} \rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) dV = \int_{V(t)} \rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} \, dV = \mathbf{F}. \quad (2.22)$$

In fluid dynamics, we express \mathbf{F} as a sum of surface forces \mathbf{F}_S and volume forces \mathbf{F}_V such as gravity, reading

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_S + \mathbf{F}_V = \int_{S(t)} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS + \int_{V(t)} \rho \mathbf{f} dV, \quad (2.23)$$

where the second order tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is called Cauchy stress tensor, \mathbf{n} is the surface normal, and \mathbf{f} the distributed volume force. The surface stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is further subdivided into a unidirectional pressure p and a traceless viscous (or deviatoric) stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -p\boldsymbol{\delta} + \boldsymbol{\tau}, \quad (2.24)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the unit tensor and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is symmetric to conserve the momentum of torque. The viscous stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ vanishes in case of inviscid fluids which results in the Euler equations of motion. Expanding (2.22) by the force terms and converting the surface into volume integrals by Gauss' rule of integration yields

$$\int_{V(t)} \rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) dV = \int_{V(t)} (-\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{f}) dV. \quad (2.25)$$

For the differential form of the momentum conservation, we choose $V(t)$ to be infinitesimal in (2.25) and obtain

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{f}. \quad (2.26)$$

The remaining question is how to obtain the viscous stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$. For Newtonian fluids⁴, the constitutive law relating the stress tensor to strain rates is given (in tensor notation) by

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (2.27)$$

where μ is the shear viscosity of the fluid. For incompressible flows, only the first two terms in (2.27) are non-vanishing, which leads to the momentum equations for incompressible flows

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \Delta \mathbf{v} + \rho \mathbf{f}. \quad (2.28)$$

The momentum equation for Newtonian fluids together with the continuity equation are called the *Navier-Stokes equations*.

⁴Newtonian fluids are characterized by a linear relationship between stress and strain rate and a vanishing strain rate for zero stress. The characterizing quantity for the relation between stress and strain rate is the viscosity, which is constant for Newtonian fluids. Water or air are examples for Newtonian fluids.

Conservation in ALE Form

The conservation laws in ALE form are derived analogously to those in Eulerian form by using the ALE form of the Reynolds transport theorem. In the resulting equations, the only difference to the Eulerian form is that the material convective velocity \mathbf{v} , defined in (2.2), is replaced by the convective velocity \mathbf{c} , defined in (2.15). The integral continuity and momentum equations for compressible flows in ALE form are given by

$$\int_{V(t)} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{c} \right) dV = 0, \quad (2.29)$$

$$\int_{V(t)} \rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) dV = \int_{V(t)} (-\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{f}) dV. \quad (2.30)$$

Differential forms of the same balance equations in ALE form read

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{c} = 0, \quad (2.31)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{f}. \quad (2.32)$$

We again simplify the equations for the incompressible case, reading

$$\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{c} = 0, \quad (2.33)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \Delta \mathbf{v} + \rho \mathbf{f}. \quad (2.34)$$

As already mentioned in the beginning of this section, we omit the energy conservation equations here, since compressible flows play only a minor role within this work.

Boundary and Initial Conditions

To close the set of partial differential equations describing fluids, we need to define proper boundary and initial conditions. The usual choice for boundary conditions is to split the boundary into a Dirichlet part Γ_D and a Neumann part Γ_N as

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_D \cup \Gamma_N \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma_D \cap \Gamma_N = \emptyset. \quad (2.35)$$

The Dirichlet boundary conditions, also called essential, fix the kinematic variables, while the Neumann boundary, also called natural, prescribes dynamic variables as

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_D \quad \text{on } \Gamma_D, \quad (2.36)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{f}_N \quad \text{on } \Gamma_N. \quad (2.37)$$

\mathbf{v}_D is the prescribed flow velocity at the boundary, and \mathbf{f}_N the prescribed force or integrated pressure. A further boundary type mixes Dirichlet and Neumann conditions and

is called Robin boundary condition. As initial conditions for time dependent problems, the flow velocity \mathbf{v} and (for compressible flows only) density ρ at time t_0 have to be provided for the whole fluid domain Ω as

$$\mathbf{v}(t_0) = v_0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (2.38)$$

$$\rho(t_0) = \rho_0 \quad \text{in } \Omega. \quad (2.39)$$

Note that the initial conditions need to satisfy the continuity equation (2.18) or (2.29).

2.1.3 Structural Mechanics

Structural mechanics for technical applications is often restricted to comparatively small strains, since material failures are occurring otherwise. Thus, a linear strain-stress relationship can often be used and the Lagrangian point of view, described in Section 2.1.1, is an appropriate choice. However, small strains do not imply small deformations, where translations and rotations play an additional role. To handle large deformations typically occurring in FSI, we employ a non-linear geometric description. We further assume a homogenous and isotropic continuum. These assumptions are expressed mathematically by the Saint-Venant-Kirchhoff material model. The following derivations are standard and can be found, e.g., in [24, 180].

Kinematics

The kinematics of a structure describe its deformations without their cause. A vectorial displacement field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t)$ is used to describe the deformation of each material point \mathbf{X} to a spatial point \mathbf{x} and, thus, to define the mapping $\varphi(\mathbf{X}, t)$ given in (2.1) as

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}, t). \quad (2.40)$$

Furthermore, we have to relate the deformation of an infinitesimal line element $d\mathbf{X}$ in the material domain to the deformed line element $d\mathbf{x}$ in the spatial domain. We do this by introducing the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} as

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\mathbf{X}}. \quad (2.41)$$

Rewriting the deformation gradient using (2.40) yields

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{d(\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{u})}{d\mathbf{X}} = \boldsymbol{\delta} + \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{d\mathbf{X}} = \boldsymbol{\delta} + \mathbf{H}, \quad (2.42)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the unit tensor and \mathbf{H} the displacement gradient. Using the deformation gradient, we can set up a strain tensor \mathbf{E} which does not contain rigid body deformations

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{F} - \boldsymbol{\delta}). \quad (2.43)$$

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Thus, strain is expressed as the difference of the areas of squares in material and spatial configuration. To express \mathbf{E} by the deformation gradient \mathbf{H} , we substitute \mathbf{F} by (2.42) and obtain

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{H} + \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H}), \quad (2.44)$$

where $\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H}$ makes the relation non-linear. In linear geometric theory, where the deformations are assumed to be small ($\|\mathbf{H}\| \ll 1$), this term is omitted, resulting in the linear strain tensor

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{H} + \mathbf{H}^T). \quad (2.45)$$

\mathbf{E} is a sufficient measure to describe the geometric non-linear deformations of a structure, while $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ suffices to describe geometric linear deformations.

Constitutive Equations

The constitutive equations relate strains with stresses. We consider the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{S} which uses the material domain areas and forces as a reference. The relation to the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is given by a push-forward or pull-back operation

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \frac{1}{\det \mathbf{F}} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^T \quad \text{or} \quad \mathbf{S} = \det \mathbf{F} \mathbf{F}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \mathbf{F}^{-T}, \quad (2.46)$$

respectively. A relation between strains and stresses is found in hyperelasticity or Green's elasticity as

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{E}}, \quad (2.47)$$

where W is a non-linear strain-energy density function. Linearizing this relation leads to

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{C} : \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.48)$$

with the elasticity (fourth order) tensor $\mathbf{C} = C_{ijkl}$. This tensor can be reduced to just two parameters by taking into account the following three considerations: i) The material under consideration is isotropic and linearly elastic. ii) \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{E} are symmetric. iii) W has potential character. The two parameters are denoted by λ and μ , called Lamé constants, and give us the final form of the constitutive relations for a Saint-Venant-Kirchhoff material in tensor notation as

$$S_{ij} = \lambda E_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\mu E_{ij}. \quad (2.49)$$

The parameters are directly related to material parameters such as Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν by

$$E = \frac{\mu(3\lambda + 2\mu)}{\lambda + \mu}; \quad \nu = \frac{\lambda}{2(\lambda + \mu)}. \quad (2.50)$$

Note that strain tensor \mathbf{E} and Young's modulus E use similar symbols. This notation is used to stay consistent with common literature.

Dynamics

The dynamics of a structure describe the causes of its deformation. By (virtually) cutting out a control volume V of a structure, we can state that there must be an equilibrium of forces (otherwise the structure would be torn apart). This equilibrium is derived similarly as the momentum equation in fluid mechanics (2.21), but in the Lagrangian point of view, i.e., without convective term. The resulting equation in differential form is

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{S} + \rho \mathbf{f}. \quad (2.51)$$

The acceleration of a material point is given by the second derivative of its displacement \mathbf{u} . Surface forces are modeled by the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{S} , which is linked to the non-linear deformations (2.44) by (2.49) for a linear elastic behavior. Body forces such as gravity are contained in the distributed force \mathbf{f} . The density of the material is characterized by ρ , as for fluids.

Boundary and Initial Conditions

It remains to choose proper boundary and initial conditions for the structural dynamics equation (2.51). As for fluids, the structural boundary is partitioned into a Dirichlet (or essential) and Neumann (or natural) type as

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_D \cup \Gamma_N \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma_D \cap \Gamma_N = \emptyset, \quad (2.52)$$

with the boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_D \quad \text{on } \Gamma_D, \quad (2.53)$$

$$\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{f}_N \quad \text{on } \Gamma_N. \quad (2.54)$$

A fixed displacement is prescribed by \mathbf{u}_D , while \mathbf{f}_N prescribes a forcing vector. In case of a time dependent problem, initial conditions for the material displacement and velocity have to be given as

$$\mathbf{u}(t_0) = \mathbf{u}_0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (2.55)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}(t_0)}{\partial t} = \mathbf{v}_0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (2.56)$$

where \mathbf{u}_0 is the initial displacement and \mathbf{v}_0 the initial velocity.

2.1.4 Coupling of Fluids and Structures

After describing the equations for fluid and structural domains, this section discusses their coupling. Since both domains have been introduced with similar notation, we

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annotate variables by an F to denote affiliation to the fluid domain and S for affiliation to the structural domain. The coupling of the fluid domain Ω_F with boundary $\Gamma_F = \partial\Omega_F$ and the structural domain Ω_S with boundary $\Gamma_S = \partial\Omega_S$ occurs at their common interface

$$\Gamma_{FS} = \Gamma_F \cap \Gamma_S, \quad (2.57)$$

also called wet surface (see Figure 2.5). Kinematic and dynamic conditions are enforced at the wet surface as described in the following.

Fig. 2.5: Schematic drawing of the coupling interface or wet surface Γ_{FS} at the common boundary of fluid and structural domain Ω_F and Ω_S . The outer normals of fluid and structural domain, \mathbf{n}_F and \mathbf{n}_S , have opposite sign.

The *kinematic interface conditions* state that the displacements and velocities at Γ_{FS} are the same for fluid and structure.

$$\mathbf{x}_F = \mathbf{u}_S, \quad \mathbf{v}_F = \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_S}{\partial t} \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.58)$$

The equality of displacements follows from the assumption that the fluid and structure continuously fill their domains up to the coupling interface and neither overlaps nor gaps of material can occur. The equality of velocities results from the assumption that fluid molecules in contact with the structural surface are bound to it by molecular attraction forces. For non-viscous flows, the flow velocity parallel to the wall is not related to that of the wall and, thus, the second equality is only valid for flow velocities normal to the wet surface

$$\mathbf{v}_F \cdot \mathbf{n}_F = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_S}{\partial t} \cdot \mathbf{n}_S \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.59)$$

The *dynamic interface condition* requires a balance of forces at the interface, which is expressed point-wise by the surface stresses

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_F \cdot \mathbf{n}_F = -\boldsymbol{\sigma}_S \cdot \mathbf{n}_S \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.60)$$

2.2 Discretization of the Mathematical Models

After deriving the mathematical models used to describe fluids, structures, and their interaction, this section deals with the discretization process. In order to compute non-trivial solutions for the mathematical models derived, we need to transform the differential equations into algebraic forms with a finite number of unknowns. While discretization is necessary to compute a solution on a computer at all, it also introduces an additional source of error. Hence, an appropriate discretization needs to be chosen to keep the error at tolerable size.

The discretization process is typically split into a spatial and a temporal step. First, the spatial discretization transforms the partial differential equations (PDEs) into ordinary differential equations (ODEs) or differential-algebraic equations (DAEs). These can then be discretized in time and solved by a numerical integration scheme. The space-time finite element method is different in that respect, since it discretizes space and time together (see, e.g., [154, 155, 115]). Another important decision is, whether a common discretization is chosen for fluid, structure, and their coupling, or whether two separate discretizations for fluid and structure are coupled together externally. These approaches are called monolithic and partitioned, respectively, and influence the types of spatial and time discretizations used. In the following, we first look at the spatial discretization in Section 2.2.1, then at the time discretization in Section 2.2.2 and, finally, consider the discretization approaches of the overall coupled system in Section 2.2.3.

2.2.1 Spatial Discretization

Since a wide range of methods for spatial discretization exists, only a short overview is given here. After that, we look at one particularly important question concerning the coupling of the spatial discretizations of fluid and structure, namely that of fixed or moving meshes.

Overview

Spatial discretization is the transformation of a continuous representation of space with an infinite number of degrees of freedom (DOFs) to a discrete representation with finite number of DOFs. A problem with a finite number of DOFs becomes computable. However, the solution will in general not be the same as for the continuous representation. Thus, one goal of spatial discretization methods is to provide an accurate enough approximation to the real system, while keeping the amount of computations in reasonable bounds. Popular spatial discretization methods are, e.g., the finite element method (FEM), the finite volume method (FVM), and the finite difference method (FDM). While the FEM and the FVM work with a partitioning of space into elements or cells, the FDM is based on a point-wise representation. In fluid mechanics, the FEM and the FVM are

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most popular, while for structural mechanics the FEM alone is the dominating method. We do not go into more details of these methods here, but refer the interested reader to common literature. Textbooks about spatial discretization for PDEs are, e.g., [156] for the FDM, [6] for the FEM, and [103] for the FVM. CFD specific literature can be found in [51, 79, 63, 62, 61, 80] and structural mechanics textbooks focussed on the FEM are, e.g., [23, 182].

One important aspect of the spatial discretization is whether it is based on a mesh (or grid) or is meshless. We focus on mesh-based methods within this work. In mesh-based methods, a mesh consisting of nodes, faces, and cells is set up. Mesh types are differentiated according to their structuredness, as shown in Figure 2.6. Fully structured meshes have an implicit ordering of nodes, faces, and cells. The connectivity information between the mesh elements needs, hence, not to be stored and access of mesh elements can be done by fast index computations. Unstructured meshes need to explicitly store connectivity information, e.g., in form of pointer lists. The advantage of unstructured meshes is, however, that they can closely adapt to the geometry of mesh boundaries or interfaces and allow for simple adaptivity of the cell size in critical regions. Hybrid meshes, such as block-structured ones, try to get the advantages of both worlds by applying simple transformations to structured meshes to adapt them to the boundaries, while keeping an implicit ordering and comparatively simple indexing rules for mesh elements.

Fig. 2.6: Different two-dimensional mesh types. Mesh (a) is a structured Cartesian mesh, mesh (b) a structured mesh with applied transformation, and mesh (c) an unstructured triangular mesh. Several structured meshes can be connected to form a block-structured mesh of higher complexity.

The unknowns of the discrete equations are associated to mesh cells, faces, or nodes. Figure 2.7 shows different unknown layouts for a rectangular mesh. Typically, the distribution of variables to mesh elements is driven by numerical stability considerations.

In contrast to mesh-based methods, meshless methods do not establish fixed connectivities between the nodes. Well known instances are smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) [118] or the particle finite-element method (PFEM) [127]. Here, the influence of the nodes on each other is not given by a fixed connectivity, but has to be recomputed regularly. The advantage of meshless methods comes from the lack of explicit

Fig. 2.7: Rectangular two-dimensional mesh with different unknown layouts. Mesh (a) shows a cell-centered layout, where all unknowns are associated to the cell centers (denoted by squares). Similarly, mesh (b) is node-centered, with all unknowns located at the mesh nodes (denoted by circles). In (c), the unknowns are splitted to nodes and cell centers, which results in a semi-staggered layout. The mesh in (d) has distributed the components of vectorial values to separate cell faces (denoted by arrow heads) and is called fully-staggered.

connectivities between nodes, which allows for arbitrary deformations while keeping a Lagrangian view on the material. Their disadvantage is the computationally expensive recomputation of influences of the nodes on each other.

Coupling of Spatial Discretizations

A decisive aspect in the spatial discretization for FSI is how the individual spatial discretizations of fluid and structure are combined. This is closely related to the points of view used for fluid and structure (see Section 2.1.1). Most common are a Lagrangian viewpoint for the structure and an Eulerian or ALE viewpoint for the fluid.

When an Eulerian point of view is used for the fluid, a common way to include the structure in the flow is by *immersed boundary (IB)* methods [117, 73], originally applied in [130]. In IB methods, the structure is represented in the fluid mesh as a set of nodes, connected by fibers or cells. The structural representation is overlayed to the fluid mesh which stays fixed. Flow velocities are influencing the structural movement, while structural forces act as body forces in the fluid equations. The influences are interpolated between structural nodes and neighboring fluid mesh cells. While IB methods allow to use structured fixed meshes, the interpolation of influences in a given neighborhood of the structural nodes blurs the interface. This can be weakened by, e.g., adaptive mesh refinement at the FSI interface which diminishes the advantage of fixed grids to some extent again. Similar techniques as IB methods are the *fictitious domain (FD)* methods, originally applied in [76] and later extended for FSI in [181]. Lagrange multipliers are used to enforce an equality of fluid and structure velocities in the domain occupied by the structure.

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Another way of including the structure in the flow is by the *cut-cell* method [136, 71]. Here, fluid mesh cells overlapped by the structural boundary are cut in a way to approximate (or match) the structural boundary. Completely overlapped cells are disabled and ignored in the solution process of the fluid. In contrast to IB or FD methods, the interface to the structure is sharp. Nitsche's method [20, 21] provides an approach to prescribe boundary conditions on such cut cells in a consistent way in a finite element setting. A *marker-and-cell* based fixed grid approach without any cell cutting is presented in [161] and its use for FSI is part of this thesis. In [31, 29] (see also Section 5.1.1), intersected as well as covered fluid cells are disabled and the fluid FSI interface is represented by Cartesian flow mesh cells directly. Automatic adaptive mesh refinement is used to achieve a satisfying accuracy at the boundary.

A moving (or dynamic) mesh approach can be employed when the ALE viewpoint or space-time FEM is used for the fluid. Fluid mesh nodes at the FSI boundary are treated as Lagrangian nodes then, moved by the structural displacements. Internal nodes are moved such that mesh distortions are minimized, resulting in reduced numerical errors. The mesh motion, also referred to as mesh smoothing, can be done by a variety of methods. A spring analogy is used in [14] where mesh edges are springs. This technique is refined in [41] to include torsional forces for three-dimensional simulations. The mesh can also be treated as an elastic body as done in [107] which results in a pseudo-structural system of equations for the mesh motion. Laplacian or Biharmonic operators can be used to perform the mesh smoothing as in [85]. Radial basis function interpolation has been applied for mesh motion in [38]. An overview of most aforementioned mesh motion schemes is given in [52]. If a mere mesh movement does not suffice, renoding or remeshing techniques become necessary. Renoding only changes the mesh cells and faces, but leaves existing mesh nodes untouched. Remeshing destroys and creates also mesh nodes. These techniques can introduce oscillations into a transient solution since unknowns are modified, created, or destroyed. In [155], renoding was found to cause smaller oscillations than remeshing.

In [173], the ALE and the fixed grid approach are combined to form an overlapping domain decomposition/Chimera-like method. The structure is surrounded locally by a moving mesh as in the ALE approach, which follows the rigid body motions of the structure while deforming as in the moving mesh approach to handle local structural deformations. The ALE mesh is embedded into a global Eulerian mesh with a certain overlap and fluid mesh cells covered by the structure are disabled. A Chimera technique is used to compute the flow solutions on the fixed and the moving mesh which involves an iteration process. This overcomes the restriction of structural incompressibility present for IB and FD techniques. It also preserves a good mesh quality at the structural surface in case of large translations and rotations.

So far, we assumed that fluid and structure are described in different viewpoints. However, it is also possible to model both fields in the same point of view. In [53, 137], both domains are described with Eulerian viewpoints and discretized using the FEM method. While the method performs twice as slow when compared to an implementation

of a moving mesh method, it allows for arbitrary deformations. Particle methods allow to model structure and fluid in the same Lagrangian domain, as done in [88, 89]. One difficulty is then to define the interface between fluid and structural domain.

2.2.2 Time Discretization

After discretizing the model equations of fluid or structural mechanics in space, the time discretization remains to be done for a transient problem. We also speak of semi-discrete equations or simply ordinary differential equations (ODEs) to be discretized in time. As for the spatial discretization, the continuous time is split into discrete timesteps Δt , for which solutions are sought for. These solutions are not to be computed at once, as for the spatial discretization, but in a sequential manner involving a time integration method. Even the timestep lengths are not necessarily to be known in advance, but can be chosen adaptively, e.g., by error estimators.

Mathematically, we can express the semi-discrete equations as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}}{\partial t} - \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0, \quad (2.61)$$

where \mathbf{B} denotes the discretized spatial terms and \mathbf{x} the spatial unknown vector. The goal of a time integrator I is to compute solutions \mathbf{x}^n at discrete times t^n , with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Depending on the times of the solutions used, it can be categorized as explicit or implicit. Explicit methods take into account only solutions of $m + 1$ past timesteps to compute the solution of the next timestep

$$\mathbf{x}^{n+1} = I(\Delta t^n, \mathbf{x}^n, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{n-m}, \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}^n, t^n), \dots, \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}^{n-m}, t^{n-m})). \quad (2.62)$$

Implicit methods also involve the future timestep solution as

$$\mathbf{x}^{n+1} = I(\Delta t^n, \mathbf{x}^{n+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{n-m}, \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}^{n+1}, t^{n+1}), \dots, \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}^{n-m}, t^{n-m})). \quad (2.63)$$

The parameter m depends on the specific method chosen. In case of the fluid or structural equations considered here, implicit methods result in a non-linear equation system to be solved by, e.g., Newton's method. The advantages of implicit methods are their better stability leading to the possibility to choose larger timesteps. An implicit method will be more efficient computationally, if the gain in timestep size outweighs the additional costs per timestep. Since both, spatial and time discretization, are an approximation to the exact solution of the mathematical equations describing fluids and structures, they both contribute to the discretization error. A balance of investments into accuracy of spatial and time discretization is, thus, desirable and requires to choose the accuracy order of both methods similarly. For further reading, the following standard textbooks on the solution of ODEs are recommended. General texts are [81, 82], while structural specific publications can be found in [50, 153] and fluid specific publications are [51, 63, 62, 61].

2.2.3 Coupling Approaches to FSI

We have discussed fluid and structural discretizations so far. Now, we look at the discretization of the FSI coupling. There are two main approaches commonly taken: the monolithic approach and the partitioned approach. While in the monolithic approach, the goal is to obtain one global system of equations including the coupling of fluid and structure, in the partitioned approach separate systems of equations are set up for the fluid and the structure domain and the coupling is established externally. As a consequence, one discretization method is used for both fields in the monolithic approach, while the discretizations of fluid and structure in the partitioned approach are often different. Some words have to be said about the terminology used for the coupling schemes. In literature, the partitioned coupling approach is also denoted as loose coupling [106], segregated coupling [84], or staggered approach [56]. Depending on the algorithms used for the partitioned equation coupling, the coupling can be strong or weak [112, 113, 174]. Also, to denote the strength of the interactions between fluid and structure, the terms weak and strong interaction are used [43]. In the following, an overview of monolithic and partitioned approaches and their advantages and disadvantages are given. A review of state of the art partitioned equation coupling and data mapping methods follows in Sections 2.3 and 2.4.

Monolithic Coupling Approach

Monolithic coupling approaches are driven by the idea of a closed discretization of the overall FSI system. The result of a monolithic discretization of an FSI problem is an overall system of equations, comprising the discrete flow variables \mathbf{y}_F , discrete structural variables \mathbf{y}_S , and their coupling

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{y}_F, \mathbf{y}_S) = 0. \quad (2.64)$$

System (2.64) is solved simultaneously for all unknowns. If \mathbf{A} is linear, we can write (2.64) as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_F & \mathbf{A}_{FS} \\ \mathbf{A}_{SF} & \mathbf{A}_S \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_F \\ \mathbf{y}_S \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{b}_F \\ \mathbf{b}_S \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.65)$$

where the diagonal blocks \mathbf{A}_F and \mathbf{A}_S represent the fluid and structure internal equations. The off-diagonal blocks \mathbf{A}_{FS} and \mathbf{A}_{SF} contain the coupling of the unknowns between fluid and structure. Boundary and volume conditions (such as gravity) independent from the coupling are contained in \mathbf{b}_F and \mathbf{b}_S for fluid and structure. When non-linearities are present in system (2.64), often Newton's method is employed ([48, 162, 83, 154]). This results in the repeated solution of the linear system

$$\begin{pmatrix} J_{\mathbf{A}_F}(\mathbf{y}_F) & J_{\mathbf{A}_{FS}}(\mathbf{y}_S) \\ J_{\mathbf{A}_{SF}}(\mathbf{y}_F) & J_{\mathbf{A}_S}(\mathbf{y}_S) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{y}_F^k \\ \Delta \mathbf{y}_S^k \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_F^k \\ \mathbf{y}_S^k \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.66)$$

and update of the k -th iterate solution of (2.64) by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_F^{k+1} \\ \mathbf{y}_S^{k+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_F^k \\ \mathbf{y}_S^k \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{y}_F^k \\ \Delta \mathbf{y}_S^k \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.67)$$

The system matrix of (2.66) contains the Jacobian matrices J of the non-linear analogs of the fluid, structure, and coupling blocks in (2.65).

In [162], a damped Newton method was used to solve the monolithic system (2.64). Finite differences were used to approximate the Jacobian matrices and a geometric multi-grid solver was applied to solve the linear system similar to (2.66). The influence of the omission of one or both coupling blocks between fluid and structure in the Jacobi block matrices in (2.66) has been investigated in [83]. It has been found that the resulting block-triangular system can be used as a good preconditioner for a GMRES solver of system (2.66). Three different Newton iteration-based solution methods for (2.64) are presented (but not compared) in [154]. The first method uses the exact Jacobian matrices of (2.66). The second method neglects the grid motion due to the structural displacements. In the third method, the off-diagonal terms are neglected completely which is equivalent to a partitioned solution algorithm.

Partitioned Coupling Approach

The partitioned coupling approach to FSI is based on a domain decomposition into a fluid and a structure component. We use the terms *component*, *solver*, and *participant* interchangeably in the following, all referring to the same concept of a subpartition of the overall coupled problem. If the ALE point of view (see Section 2.1.1) or space-time FEM are used for the fluid, the mesh motion scheme can be seen as a third component. We assume the mesh motion to be integrated into the fluid solver here. As FSI is a surface coupled problem, the components are coupled by their common boundary values. These are the dynamic and kinematic boundary values of fluid and structure, as described in Section 2.1.4. In the partitioned approach, the coupling has to be done in an explicit way, i.e., each component takes the boundary values from the other component as fixed during its solution. The boundary values are either obtained by some predictor rule such as extrapolation or handed over after the solution of the respective other component. Irrespective of the chosen methodology, the goal of the partitioned approach is to re-establish the solution of the monolithic system (2.64) or a suitable approximation of it. To achieve this task, a variety of equation coupling schemes exists, which define rules on how to combine solutions of the partitioned components. State of the art equation coupling schemes are discussed in detail in Section 2.3.

An important use case of the partitioned approach is when existing (and independent) simulation tools for flows and structures are to be coupled to perform FSI simulations. In such a case, it is often difficult to create a matching surface discretization at the coupling interface, even if the simulation tools use the same spatial discretization and mesh type. This gives rise to a second important task in the partitioned approach which

is the data mapping between the surface representations of the fluid and structure components. Critical points in data mapping are to avoid introducing significant errors into the solver solutions, the conservation of overall forces and energy, and the preservation of rigid body motions and momentum of torque. Data mapping methods are discussed in Section 2.4. When two independent solvers are coupled, they are usually provided in the form of two separate executable programs. Some form of communication needs to be established between the executable programs in order to exchange coupling data and state information. We refer the reader to standard textbooks about remote communication methods such as [152] and discuss their application for this work in Section 4.3.

The choice of schemes to be used in the partitioned approach depends very much on the accessibility of the fluid and structure components. Increased access to internals enables the use of more sophisticated methods. However, when the access to solver internals is exploited, the time needed to prepare a component for the coupling increases and coupling flexibility lessens. Reduced access limits the methods to be used but retains coupling flexibility and minimal preparation time. While for in-house or open-source software mostly high accessibility is given, commercial software usually have very limited programming interfaces. If the interfaces are reduced to a minimum, we speak of black box solvers. Nonetheless, even a black box solver has to offer some interface in order to be usable for FSI.

Partitioned vs Monolithic

A question reappearing is, whether the monolithic or the partitioned coupling approach is preferable. The answer depends, as often, on the concrete application problem to be solved. This section serves as a summary of experiences, opinions, and results found in literature. The intent is to give ideas for further investigations, which is definitely necessary if a mature decision is to be drawn. Although this work is dedicated to the partitioned approach, the following points are not meant to express a favoring for it.

Two points of concern often mentioned in literature are, first, the ability of a coupling approach to deal with high amounts of instabilities and, second, the efficiency of a coupling approach in terms of computational efforts. The monolithic approach is usually said to be able to handle a higher amount of coupling instabilities [43, 84]. Recently, however, new schemes for implicit coupling have been developed which extend the range of applicability of the partitioned approach for strong coupling [43, 116, 97]. In test scenario comparisons, it has been shown that the monolithic approach is more computationally efficient when a high amount of interaction is present, although not by orders of magnitude [43]. For weak interactions between fluid and structure, the partitioned approach is widely believed to be more efficient than the monolithic approach. In recent publications, monolithic methods have been proposed [84] that come very close or superceed the partitioned schemes in some test scenarios.

An important difference between the monolithic and the partitioned approach is how

they can be implemented in practice. While the monolithic approach usually entails the implementation of a new simulation tool, the partitioned approach is able to reuse existing simulation tools and, in particular, commercial software. However, in the partitioned approach two simulation tools and coupling algorithms have to be understood, while in the monolithic approach only one software with one philosophy is involved. This drawback of the partitioned approach can be alleviated and even utilized if two different teams with own solvers for fluid and structural equations, respectively, collaborate to perform FSI simulations. Also, the coupling functionality used in the partitioned approach can be nicely encapsulated in an own software, as done in this thesis.

The partitioned approach is said to offer more flexibility with respect to the physical models and the numerical schemes employed. This is due to the fact that the coupled solvers can be exchanged with alternative solvers without having to adapt the remaining solver. While this is an advantage on the one hand, it possibly induces the problem that two chosen solvers do not match very well. In the monolithic approach, the solvers are usually matched very well since the whole FSI framework is developed together. On the contrary, certain mismatches such as different time scales can be taken into account easier in the partitioned approach than in the monolithic approach.

When a new numerical method is to be implemented for fluid or structure, the effects on the coupling might be unclear. In this case, the monolithic approach has the potential to reduce the amount of methods and schemes involved which results in a lower numerical and technical complexity and a lower amount of instabilities arising from the coupling. The question is, whether the new method is suitable for a common discretization and how easy it is to implement the method in a monolithic setup.

2.3 Partitioned Equation Coupling Schemes

In the next two sections, we focus on partitioned coupling methods for FSI. We start with the coupling of the partitioned equations in this section, where we express the fluid and structure solvers mathematically as operators \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{S} . Input and output values for the operators are the discrete vectors of kinematic values \mathbf{s} and dynamic values \mathbf{f} of the solvers at the FSI interface Γ_{FS} . As derived in Section 2.1.4, the kinematic values \mathbf{s} comprise displacements and velocities, while the dynamic values \mathbf{f} comprise forces or stresses. The Dirichlet-Neumann decomposition yields the following input-output assignment

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{f} \tag{2.68}$$

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}) = \mathbf{s}, \tag{2.69}$$

i.e., the fluid operator \mathbf{F} takes the kinematic values \mathbf{s} as input to compute dynamic values \mathbf{f} while the structure operator \mathbf{S} takes dynamic values \mathbf{f} as input to compute kinematic values \mathbf{s} . We assume the dynamic mesh component to be formally included in

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the fluid operator \mathbf{F} . Some partitioned algorithms require access to the time integration done in the fluid and structural components. A semi-discrete notation of fluid and structure as introduced in (2.61) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial t} - \mathbf{B}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) = 0 \quad (2.70)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}}{\partial t} - \mathbf{B}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) = 0, \quad (2.71)$$

with $\mathbf{B}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ and $\mathbf{B}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ being the fluid and structure spatial discretization operators. Note that when using the fully discrete notation (2.68) and (2.69) in the following, the semi-discrete form (2.70) and (2.71) would be equally applicable, but is not mentioned every time. The goal of equation coupling schemes is to couple the partitioned equations of fluid and structure, (2.68) and (2.69), to regain the solution of the overall (monolithic) equation system (2.64). This section describes important coupling schemes found in literature while no claim for completeness is made. The coupling schemes are categorized into two sections: *explicit (or weak) coupling schemes* are described in Section 2.3.1 and *implicit (or strong) coupling schemes* in Section 2.3.2. Explicit schemes employ a fixed number of solver evaluations per timestep and do enforce an equilibrium between the coupled components only up to a certain error order in terms of the discrete timestep length. Implicit schemes enable to regain the monolithic solution (2.64) of the overall system by performing an iteration process of solver evaluations in every timestep until the convergence of coupling values is achieved.

An important issue in partitioned equation coupling is that of stability. Depending on the FSI scenario parameters, the interaction between fluid and structure can be weak or strong. In particular, for incompressible flow FSI, where the density of the structure is similar or less than that of the fluid, stability problems occur. The source of those instabilities is to be found in the coupling of the components, and cannot be removed by changes in the solution algorithms for the fluid or the structure component. Some of the coupling schemes described in the following are very susceptible to this kind of instabilities while others have been designed to specifically deal with the issue of coupling instabilities. Different analyses have been performed in literature, which we review in Section 2.3.3 after discussing the coupling schemes.

In [59], parallelism in partitioned equation coupling schemes is addressed and a differentiation is made between *interfield-parallelism* and *intrafield-parallelism*. While interfield-parallelism allows to solve the fluid equations in parallel with the structure equations, intrafield-parallelism means the parallel solution of a solvers' internal equations. All schemes described here allow for intrafield-parallelism, but only a subset can make use of interfield-parallelism. This is not of practical relevance when the computational runtime (per evaluation) of either fluid or structural solver is dominating the other solver. However, when the computational runtime of the solvers becomes balanced after intrafield-parallelization of one or both of the solvers, an additional interfield-parallelization can increase the overall performance.

An important technique in partitioned equation coupling is *subcycling*, i.e., the subdivision of a solver timestep into m smaller steps, independent from the other solver (e.g., [73]). Subcycling allows to decouple the time scales required in fluid and structure solvers. Often, the fluid solver has to use smaller timesteps due to stability restrictions. During the subcycling steps, no exchange of coupling data between the solvers takes place. However, data of the other solver can be interpolated over the subcycling steps to achieve better stability and accuracy. For simplicity, we assume that the runtime of a solver employing subcycling are multiplied by the number of subcycles m used per timestep. Thus, even if this assumption does not hold exactly, subcycling significantly influences the distribution of computational resources to solvers when intrafield-parallelism is used.

2.3.1 Explicit Coupling Schemes

Explicit coupling schemes compute an approximation to the solution of (2.64) by solving the partitioned equations (2.68) and (2.69) only a fixed number of times per timestep. A balance of energy, forces, and kinematic values between fluid and structural domain is, hence, not given in general. In the following, we assume to solve a transient simulation with discrete timesteps, where n is the timestep number. We denote the fluid and structural FSI interface variable solutions at timestep n as \mathbf{f}^n and \mathbf{s}^n . Furthermore, to denote the fluid and structure solvers' internal state at timestep n , we annotate the partitioned operators as \mathbf{F}^n and \mathbf{S}^n .

In [132, 102, 131, 59, 56, 58], a set of explicit coupling schemes has been developed and tested in the framework of aerodynamical simulation, i.e., compressible flow FSI computations. In the following, the conventional serial staggered (CSS), conventional parallel staggered (CPS), improved serial staggered (ISS), improved parallel staggered (IPS), and generalized serial staggered (GSS) schemes are presented. Note that staggered is a synonym for partitioned in this context. Furthermore, in [167, 170] explicit coupling schemes employing higher order mixed implicit/explicit (IMEX) solver time integration schemes are developed and validated. Multi-level schemes are presented in [169] for explicit coupling and extended in [168] to implicit coupling (see Section 2.3.2). The IMEX and explicit multi-level schemes are summarized in the last part of the section.

To describe the sequential computational runtime of one evaluation of the fluid and structure solver, we use c_F and c_S , respectively. We assume an ideal linear scaling behavior for intrafield-parallelism in the fluid and structure solvers. Thus, the computational runtime of a solver is divided by the number of computational resources (e.g., processors or cores) k used to parallelize it. As another simplification, we assume that interfield-communication times are negligible in the overall computational costs. This assumption is valid since only data at the surface of fluid and structure are communicated, while the solvers need to compute solutions in a higher-dimensional space, given by the surface dimension plus one.

Conventional Serial Staggered (CSS) Scheme

The conventional serial staggered (CSS) procedure is one of the most widely used explicit schemes to compute solutions to problems in FSI. Its computational steps are given in Algorithm 2.1 and are represented graphically in Figure 2.8. Characteristic for the procedure is the interfield-sequential execution of fluid and structure solvers. While the fluid solver uses the structural values of the last timestep \mathbf{s}^n , the structure solver uses the updated values of the fluid solver \mathbf{f}^{n+1} in an implicit fashion.

```

1  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
2      solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ 
3      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure
4      solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1}) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ 
5      transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid

```

Alg. 2.1: Conventional serial staggered (CSS) procedure. Lines 2–5 have to be executed sequentially.

Fig. 2.8: Conventional serial staggered (CSS) procedure. A full computation cycle (as in lines 2–5 of Algorithm 2.1) from timestep n consists of 1) the solution of the fluid solver $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n)$ to obtain \mathbf{f}^{n+1} , 2) the transfer of \mathbf{f}^{n+1} to the structure solver, 3) the solution of $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1})$ to obtain \mathbf{s}^{n+1} , and 4) the transfer of the kinematic values \mathbf{s}^{n+1} to the flow solver.

In [132], the CSS procedure is shown to be first order accurate in time, regardless of the accuracy of the fluid and structure solver time integrators used. Furthermore, it is shown for a one-dimensional linear piston problem with compressible flow that unconditional stability is achieved for a specific choice of implicit time integrators in the fluid and structure solvers. When an explicit time integrator is used for the fluid solver and an implicit time integrator for the structure solver, the overall stability depends on the stability in the fluid solver. Note that these statements are true for FSI with

2.3 Partitioned Equation Coupling Schemes

compressible fluid only. In case of incompressible fluids, the CSS procedure is very sensitive to the instabilities described in Section 2.3.3.

When intrafield-parallelism is used in the CSS procedure and k computational resources are distributed exclusively among fluid and structure solver $k = k_F + k_S$, where $k_F, k_S \geq 1$, the computational runtime c per timestep is given as

$$c = \frac{m_F c_F}{k_F} + \frac{m_S c_S}{k_S}, \quad (2.72)$$

Note that m_F and m_S denote the number of subcycling steps performed by the fluid and the structure solver, respectively, where $m = 1$ corresponds to no subcycling. An optimal distribution of resources

$$\frac{k_F}{k_S} = \sqrt{\frac{m_F c_F}{m_S c_S}} \quad (2.73)$$

results in the optimal runtime per timestep

$$c_{opt} = \frac{m_F c_F + m_S c_S + 2\sqrt{m_F c_F m_S c_S}}{k}. \quad (2.74)$$

Conventional Parallel Staggered (CPS) Scheme

The conventional parallel staggered (CPS) scheme depicted in Figure 2.9 is a straightforward attempt to allow for interfield-parallelism of the solvers. Algorithm 2.2 shows the CPS procedure, where both, fluid and structure solvers, use coupling values from timestep n . Thus, lines 2 and 3 as well as 4 and 5 can be executed in parallel. To balance the overall computational efforts, fluid and structure solver should require approximately the same computational time. If interfield- and intrafield-parallelism are used and the

```

1  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
2      solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ 
3      solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^n) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ 
4      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure
5      transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid

```

Alg. 2.2: Conventional parallel staggered (CPS) procedure. Lines 2 and 3 as well as 4 and 5 can be executed in parallel.

computational resources k are distributed as described for the CSS scheme, the computational runtime of the CPS procedure for one timestep is given by

$$c = \max\left(\frac{m_F c_F}{k_F}, \frac{m_S c_S}{k_S}\right). \quad (2.75)$$

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Fig. 2.9: Conventional parallel staggered (CPS) procedure. A full computation cycle (as in lines 2–5 of Algorithm 2.2) from timestep n consists of **1)** the solution of the fluid solver $F^n(s^n)$ to obtain f^{n+1} and at the same time the solution of the structure solver $S^n(f^n)$ to obtain s^{n+1} , **2)** the transfer of f^{n+1} to the structure solver and at the same time the transfer of the kinematic values s^{n+1} to the flow solver.

An optimal distribution of computational resources is then given by

$$\frac{k_F}{k_S} = \frac{m_F c_F}{m_S c_S}, \quad (2.76)$$

leading to an optimal computational runtime of

$$c_{opt} = \frac{m_F c_F + m_S c_S}{k}. \quad (2.77)$$

Thus, the optimal runtime of the CPS scheme is smaller than that of the CSS scheme. The drawback of using only old timestep values, however, is a loss of accuracy and stability in comparison to the CSS scheme, as shown in [56], which can require significantly smaller timestep sizes in case of compressible flows. In practice, the use of the CPS scheme is reasonable only when a close to optimal distribution of computational resources is possible. Otherwise, the costs will be dominated by one of the solvers and will be similar to that of the CSS scheme.

Improved Serial Staggered (ISS) Scheme

In [56], it is shown that the CSS scheme possibly violates the velocity kinematic interface conditions (2.58). We assume that at the wet surface Γ_{FS} the fluid displacements \mathbf{x} are set from the structural displacements \mathbf{u} . Often, the fluid velocities \mathbf{v} at the wet surface are computed as a first order approximation from the fluid displacements of two successive timesteps

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\mathbf{x}^{n+1} - \mathbf{x}^n}{\Delta t} \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.78)$$

This can be a requirement to conserve the geometric conservation law [101, 157, 95], when using the ALE approach in the fluid solver. If, in addition, the structure solver

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uses a higher order time integration scheme with time derivative $\hat{\partial}/\hat{\partial}t$, the interface velocities of fluid and structure do not match

$$\frac{\hat{\partial}\mathbf{u}}{\hat{\partial}t} \neq \frac{\mathbf{u}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}^n}{\Delta t} = \mathbf{v} \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.79)$$

As a remedy, the improved serial staggered (ISS) procedure is proposed in [56], depicted in Figure 2.10. The fluid and structure solvers are offset by half a timestep $\Delta t/2$ and the structure solver has to use the midpoint rule for time integration. Algorithm 2.3 shows the steps to be performed. Of particular importance are the rules for setting kinematic interface values in the fluid solver (from \mathbf{s}^n in line 3), which read

$$\mathbf{v}^n = \frac{\hat{\partial}\mathbf{u}^n}{\hat{\partial}t}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{n+1/2} = \mathbf{x}^{n-1/2} + \Delta t\mathbf{v}^n \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.80)$$

Fig. 2.10: Improved serial staggered (ISS) procedure. A full computation cycle (as in lines 3–6 of Algorithm 2.3) from timestep n (or $n - 1/2$) consists of **1**) the solution of the fluid solver $\mathbf{F}^{n-1/2}(\mathbf{s}^n)$ to obtain $\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$, **2**) the transfer of the dynamic values $\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$ to the structure solver, **3**) the solution of the structure solver $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2})$ using the midpoint rule to obtain \mathbf{s}^{n+1} , and **4**) the transfer of \mathbf{s}^{n+1} to the fluid solver.

```

1  set  $\mathbf{x}^{-1/2} = \mathbf{u}^0 - \frac{\Delta t}{2} \frac{\hat{\partial}\mathbf{u}^0}{\hat{\partial}t}$ 
2  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
3      solve  $\mathbf{F}^{n-1/2}(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$ 
4      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$  to structure
5      solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  using midpoint rule
6      transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid

```

Alg. 2.3: Improved serial staggered (ISS) procedure.

Using the rules given in (2.80) to update the fluid kinematic values and the midpoint rule as time integrator for the structure solver, it can be shown that the kinematic

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coupling conditions for both displacements and velocities are fulfilled. As a result, the ISS scheme shows better accuracy and stability than the CSS scheme, as demonstrated in numerical tests in [56]. The computational runtime is similar to that of the CSS scheme, including the use of subcycling in either solver.

Improved Parallel Staggered Scheme

To improve the stability and accuracy of the CPS scheme, the improved parallel staggered (IPS) scheme is proposed in [56]. Shown in Figure 2.11 and Algorithm 2.4, the scheme consists of two interfield-sequential computational parts (lines 2–5 and 6–9), where each part can be computed employing interfield-parallelism. The first part is as in the CPS scheme, but the fluid solver computes only half the timestep. In the second part, the interface values from the first part are used and the fluid solver computes another half timestep, while the structure solver repeats the full timestep.

Fig. 2.11: Improved parallel staggered (IPS) procedure. A full computation cycle (as in lines 2–9 of Algorithm 2.4) from timestep n consists of **1)** the solution of the fluid solver $F^n(s^n)$ to obtain $f^{n+1/2}$ and at the same time the solution of the structure solver $S^n(f^n)$ to obtain \bar{s}^{n+1} , **2)** the exchange of $f^{n+1/2}$ and \bar{s}^{n+1} at the same time, **3)** the solution of the fluid solver $F^{n+1/2}(\bar{s}^{n+1})$ to obtain f^{n+1} and at the same time the repeated solution of the structure solver $S^n(f^{n+1/2})$ to obtain s^{n+1} , **4)** the exchange of s^{n+1} and f^{n+1} at the same time.

In terms of accuracy and stability, the IPS scheme is shown (in numerical examples) to be superior to the CPS scheme. As a drawback, the runtime is doubled to

$$c_{opt} = 2 \frac{m_F c_F + m_S c_S}{k}. \quad (2.81)$$

In [56], no direct comparison to the CSS scheme is done. However, the performance appears to be similar. The ISS scheme is superior to the IPS scheme in terms of stability and accuracy. Regarding practical usability, the same considerations as for the CPS scheme hold.

```

1  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
2      solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$ 
3      solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^n) = \bar{\mathbf{s}}^{n+1}$ 
4      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}$  to structure
5      transmit  $\bar{\mathbf{s}}^{n+1}$  to fluid
6      solve  $\mathbf{F}^{n+1/2}(\bar{\mathbf{s}}^{n+1}) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ 
7      (re)solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1/2}) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ 
8      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure
9      transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid
    
```

Alg. 2.4: Improved parallel staggered (IPS) procedure. The fluid solver is advanced with half timestep size, while the structure solver computes the full timestep twice. Lines 2–3, 4–5, 6–7, and 8–9 can be executed in parallel.

Generalized Serial Staggered (GSS) Scheme

A common drawback of all aforementioned schemes is their first order accuracy with respect to time, regardless of the accuracy used for the solver time integrators. In [58], a framework for second order explicit staggered schemes is presented. Starting from a CSS or ISS scheme, the main ingredients added are a predictor for the structural displacement values \mathbf{u}_p used in the fluid solver and a fluid force correction \mathbf{f}_c before using the fluid values in the structure solver. The structural displacement predictor is formed by

$$\mathbf{u}_p^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^n + \alpha_0 \Delta t \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^n}{\partial t} + \alpha_1 \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^n}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}^{n-1}}{\partial t} \right), \quad (2.82)$$

where α_0 and α_1 depend on the fluid time integration and mesh motion scheme. As fluid force correctors, the following methods are proposed

$$\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1} = \mathbf{f}^n, \quad (2.83)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1} = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}, \quad (2.84)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{f}^n + \mathbf{f}^{n+1}), \quad (2.85)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1} = 2\mathbf{f}^{n+1} - \mathbf{f}^n. \quad (2.86)$$

Predictor (2.83) leads to a scheme similar to the CPS scheme, while (2.84) corresponds to the CSS scheme. Predictors (2.85) and (2.86) are not further evaluated in [58].

The choice of fluid, structure, and, if present, mesh motion time integration scheme are crucial and have to be of (at least) second order. Algorithm 2.5 shows the GSS scheme based on the CSS scheme, where prediction and correction steps are added to lines 2 and 5. A similar scheme based on the ISS scheme is given in [58] which has a shifted time integration of fluid and structure solvers. For both schemes, a three-point backward difference scheme is employed for the fluid. The structure solver uses the

```

1  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
2      compute prediction  $\mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$  by (2.82)
3      solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ 
4      transmit  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure
5      compute correction  $\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1}$  by one of (2.83) – (2.86)
6      solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}_c^{n+1}) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ 
7      transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid

```

Alg. 2.5: Generalized serial staggered (GSS) procedure with synchronized time integration in fluid and structure solvers.

midpoint rule for time integration. The structural predictor is obtained with second order accuracy by choosing α_0 and α_1 appropriately (depending on the particular scheme) and the fluid force corrector (2.84) is used. Numerical examples of full three-dimensional aerodynamics simulations show the second order time accuracy of the derived schemes.

Higher Order Implicit/Explicit (IMEX) Schemes

In [167, 170], third-, fourth-, and fifth-order time integration schemes are derived. They are based on explicit Runge-Kutta methods (ERK) and explicit first stage, singly diagonally implicit Runge-Kutta (ESDIRK) methods. Fluid and structural operators are given in semi-discrete form as in (2.70) and (2.71), where the spatial discretizations of fluid and structure are summarized as operators $\mathbf{B}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ and $\mathbf{B}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$. An s -stage ESDIRK scheme is used to integrate the semi-discrete forms in time, which involves computing $k = 2, \dots, s$ implicit stages

$$\frac{\mathbf{f}^{(k)} - \mathbf{f}^n}{\Delta t} + \sum_{i=1}^k a_{ki} \mathbf{B}_F^{(i)}(\mathbf{f}^{(i)}, \mathbf{s}^{(i)}) = 0, \quad (2.87)$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{s}^{(k)} - \mathbf{s}^n}{\Delta t} + \sum_{i=1}^k a_{ki} \mathbf{B}_S^{(i)}(\mathbf{f}^{(i)}, \mathbf{s}^{(i)}) = 0, \quad (2.88)$$

where $\mathbf{f}^{(k)}$, $\mathbf{s}^{(k)}$, and $\mathbf{B}_{F/S}^{(k)}$ are at time level $t^{(k)} = t_n + c_k \Delta t = \sum_{i=1}^k a_{ki} \Delta t$. The first stage ($k = 1$) solutions $\mathbf{f}^{(1)}$, $\mathbf{s}^{(1)}$, and $\mathbf{R}_{F/S}^{(1)}$ are obtained explicitly from the solutions at time t_n , i.e., $a_{11} = 0$. All following steps combine solutions of previous stages $\mathbf{R}_{F/S}^{(i)}$ with a solution at time t_{n+1} . The coefficients a_{ki} are listed in Butcher-tableaus and depend on the order of the ESDIRK method. The diagonal coefficients (a_{ki} for $k = i$, $k > 1$) are constant.

When, at a stage k , the structure stage (2.88) is computed before the fluid stage (2.87), $\mathbf{f}^{(k)}$ is not available and has to be predicted. For this prediction, the coefficients \hat{a}_{ki} are taken from a corresponding s -stage ERK method and combined with those of

the ESDIRK method to obtain

$$\mathbf{f}_p^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \frac{\hat{a}_{ki} - a_{ki}}{a_{kk}} \mathbf{f}^{(i)}. \quad (2.89)$$

If $\mathbf{B}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ is linear with respect to \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{s} , it can be shown that the predicted $\mathbf{f}_p^{(k)}$ is integrated by an ERK scheme.

If a moving mesh is used in the fluid solver, as in the ALE approach, the mesh motion has to be done for the computation of every stage, following the ESDIRK scheme of the fluid solver. The next timestep t_{n+1} is computed as a combination of stage solutions

$$\mathbf{f}^{n+1} = \mathbf{f}^n - \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^s b_i \mathbf{B}_F^{(i)}, \quad (2.90)$$

$$\mathbf{s}^{n+1} = \mathbf{s}^n - \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^s b_i \mathbf{B}_S^{(i)}, \quad (2.91)$$

where the factors b_i are given for a specific ESDIRK/ERK scheme. Algorithm 2.6 lists the steps in the IMEX scheme.

```

1  for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$ 
2      init stage  $k = 1$ 
3      for  $k = 2$  to  $s$ 
4          compute prediction (2.89)
5          transmit prediction  $\mathbf{f}_p^{(k)}$  to structure
6          compute structure stage (2.88)
7          transmit  $\mathbf{s}^{(k)}$  to fluid
8          compute fluid stage (2.87)
9          advance flow (2.90) and structure (2.91)
    
```

Alg. 2.6: Higher-order implicit/explicit time integration (IMEX) procedure.

Several numerical test cases, ranging from one to three spatial dimensions, are computed in [167, 170] to evaluate the performance of IMEX methods. The numerical error orders are close to the theoretical results and the computational performance of the fourth- and fifth-order IMEX schemes is claimed to be superior in terms of accuracy over runtime compared to a monolithic second order BDF scheme. The drawback of the IMEX methods is their requirements on accessibility of fluid and structure solvers in order to use ESDIRK methods (which are new for structural dynamics) and to compute each stage in a partitioned manner. Furthermore, it is not clear whether the results will still be obtained when the structure solver has to compute non-linear equations. In a test case, where the ERK predictor is replaced by simply taking the solution of the last timestep, the order of a fifth-order IMEX scheme is reduced to two.

Multi-Level Schemes

In [169], multi-level coupling schemes based on a multigrid solver for the fluid component are investigated. An implicit Euler or the Runge-Kutta schemes described for the IMEX coupling method [167] are used for time integration. In the following, the multi-level schemes are derived using the simpler implicit Euler method. To compactify notation, an overall unknown vector for fluid and structure is introduced

$$\mathbf{w} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_S \\ \mathbf{y}_F \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.92)$$

where \mathbf{y}_S and \mathbf{y}_F contain all unknowns of the structure and the fluid domain Ω_S and Ω_F , respectively, as in (2.64). As starting point, a linearized semi-discrete monolithic FSI model is used

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{w}_h}{\partial t} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_S & \mathbf{A}_{SF} \\ \mathbf{A}_{FS} & \mathbf{A}_F \end{pmatrix}_h \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_S \\ \mathbf{y}_F \end{pmatrix}_h = \mathbf{A}_h \mathbf{w}_h, \quad (2.93)$$

with \mathbf{A}_h being the spatial discretization matrix consisting of blocks for fluid, structure, and their coupling, as in (2.65), and subindex h denoting the fine grid level. The implicit Euler method is used to integrate (2.93) from timestep n to $n + 1$ as

$$(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{A}_h) \mathbf{w}_h^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}_h^n = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.94)$$

In the following, two multi-level approaches are discussed: a coarse grid correction algorithm and a coarse grid prediction algorithm.

The *coarse grid correction* algorithm improves the solution of (2.94) obtained after a partitioned fine grid iteration by a coarse grid approximation of the partitioning error. The partitioned timestep on the fine grid level is written in matrix form as

$$\left(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_S & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{FS} & \mathbf{A}_F \end{pmatrix}_h \right) \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \Delta t \mathbf{A}_{SF} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \end{pmatrix}_h \mathbf{w}_h^n = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.95)$$

Note that the matrix block \mathbf{A}_{SF} , which couples the fluid unknowns to the structure equations, is moved to the solution of the old timestep \mathbf{w}_h^n . Solving (2.95) corresponds to the CSS procedure introduced at the beginning of this section. Substituting the partitioned solution $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1}$ of (2.95) into (2.94) yields a residual expression on the fine grid

$$(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{A}_h) \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}_h^n = -\Delta t \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{SF}(\mathbf{f}^n - \mathbf{f}^{n+1}) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}_h = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{r}_S \\ \mathbf{r}_F \end{pmatrix}_h = \mathbf{r}_h, \quad (2.96)$$

where an overall residual vector \mathbf{r} is formed by structural and fluid residuals \mathbf{r}_S and \mathbf{r}_F . The residual of the fluid \mathbf{r}_F is zero, which corresponds to the block Gauss-Seidel type of partitioning, where the fluid equation block is solved with already computed structural unknowns. The error of the fine grid solution

$$\mathbf{e}_h = \mathbf{w}_h - \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h \quad (2.97)$$

is then obtained by subtracting (2.96) from (2.94)

$$(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{A}_h) \mathbf{e}_h^{n+1} = -\mathbf{r}_h. \quad (2.98)$$

A solution to (2.98) is computed on the coarse grid level by using classical multigrid restriction and prolongation operators

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{R}_S & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R}_F \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{P}_S & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{P}_F \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.99)$$

where the non-diagonal blocks are zero to retain the partitioning of fluid and structural blocks. The restriction operator \mathbf{R} transforms fine grid variables to the coarse grid, while the prolongation operator \mathbf{P} performs the opposite task. The coarse grid relation for the error (denoted by subindex H) is then given as

$$(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_h \mathbf{P}) \mathbf{e}_H^{n+1} = \mathbf{R} \mathbf{r}_h, \quad (2.100)$$

where we can formally write $\mathbf{A}_H = \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_h \mathbf{P}$. After computing the coarse grid error \mathbf{e}_H^{n+1} , the fine grid solution can be corrected corresponding to the error formulation (2.97) by

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_h = \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h + \mathbf{P} \mathbf{e}_H. \quad (2.101)$$

The corrected solution $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_h$ is not the exact solution \mathbf{w}_h since, usually, the error \mathbf{e}_H on the coarse level is an approximation, too. Even if \mathbf{e}_H is computed exactly, the restriction and prolongation introduce additional errors.

The second multi-level approach is based on a *coarse grid prediction*. An initial prediction is done on the fine grid level by performing a CPS scheme step with explicit time integration in the solvers. Following that, a correction of the fine grid prediction is done by a coarse grid solution of the fine grid error. Finally, the corrected prediction is used in a standard CSS scheme step on the fine grid level. The explicitly computed CPS step is written as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I} + \Delta t \mathbf{A}_F & \Delta t \mathbf{A}_{SF} \\ \Delta t \mathbf{A}_{FS} & \mathbf{I} + \Delta t \mathbf{A}_S \end{pmatrix}_h \mathbf{w}_h^n = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.102)$$

The residual on the fine grid level is obtained in the same way as for the coarse grid correction method, by inserting the predicted solution $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1}$ into the monolithic formulation of the system (2.94)

$$(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \mathbf{A}_h) \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}_h^n = -\Delta t \mathbf{A}_h (\mathbf{w}_h^n - \tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1}) = \mathbf{r}_h. \quad (2.103)$$

A coarse grid correction of $\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1}$ is performed as in (2.97) – (2.101), yielding the corrected predictor \mathbf{w}_h^* . In a final CSS step, this corrected predictor is used to compute a better partitioned solution $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1}$ as

$$\left(\mathbf{I} - \Delta t \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_S & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{A}_{FS} & \mathbf{A}_F \end{pmatrix}_h \right) \hat{\mathbf{w}}_h^{n+1} - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \Delta t \mathbf{A}_{SF} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}_h \mathbf{w}_h^* - \mathbf{w}_h^n = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.104)$$

The presented two-level methods are also used in combination with the IMEX solver time integration methods discussed above. There, each stage is treated in a multi-level fashion. In [169], the methods are evaluated using a one-dimensional linear piston problem. In [168], the schemes are extended to two-dimensional non-linear problems, and a coarsening is applied only for the fluid solver. Also, the applicability of multi-level schemes for implicit coupling iterations is investigated there. A short discussion of these implicit variants is given in Section 2.3.2. A partitioned realization of the multi-level schemes obviously requires access to each mesh level of a solver. Thus, despite the use of partitioned solution procedures such as the CSS and CPS schemes on each level, the multi-level schemes might not be applicable in black box codes.

Summary

We have seen different explicit equation coupling schemes in this section. Distinguishing factors are their stability, accuracy order, computational costs, and suitability for black box coupling. While some of the schemes are rather simple to be implemented such as the CSS or CPS procedures, others require more access to solver internals and assume specific time integration methods, mesh adaption techniques, or equation solvers. However, from a stability point of view, all schemes suffer from the same problem. When a certain strength of interaction between fluid and structure is reached and timestep restrictions are infeasible, they become unstable. While these instabilities can be controlled rather well in compressible flow FSI, they become a real problem in incompressible flow scenarios, where a reduction of timestep size results in a further decrease of stability (see Section 2.3.3). A remedy can be found in implicit coupling schemes, which are reviewed in the next section.

2.3.2 Implicit Coupling Schemes

Implicit coupling schemes try to compute the solution of the monolithic system (2.64) in an iterative process, involving the repeated solution of the flow and structure partitioned systems of equations (2.68) and (2.69). While the motivation to prefer implicit over explicit schemes can be to obtain a solution closer to that of the monolithic system, their main application is found when instabilities forbid the use of explicit coupling schemes. Then, particular schemes have to be applied to stabilize the implicit coupling iterations. To denote the coupling iteration number, we use the letter k to write \mathbf{f}_k^{n+1} and \mathbf{s}_k^{n+1} for the k -th iterate coupling value solutions of timestep $n + 1$. To avoid further index clutter, we henceforth omit the timestep index $n + 1$ when an iteration index is given such that, e.g., $\mathbf{s}_k := \mathbf{s}_k^{n+1}$.

In the following, we look at a variety of implicit schemes which are more or less suitable for black box coupling. We first consider Schwarz procedures and iteration post-processings that stabilize and accelerate their convergence. Then, we review the

group of quasi-Newton methods, which deal with the problem of unavailable derivative information (for black box solvers) in different ways. Finally, we look at a multi-level scheme which is a straightforward extension to that described in Section 2.3.1.

Schwarz Procedures

Schwarz procedures use the partitioned systems of equations (2.68) and (2.69) directly to set up a fixed-point iteration. Additionally, stabilization and acceleration techniques are employed. There are two basic Schwarz procedures used for FSI, which originate in domain decomposition. If both systems of equations (2.68) and (2.69) are solved in parallel, one speaks of an additive or parallel Schwarz procedure [147]. If the systems are solved sequentially, where the output of the first system is used as input when solving the second system, one speaks of a multiplicative Schwarz procedure [145, 147]. Due to the resemblance with iterative equation solvers, the additive Schwarz procedure is also called block Jacobi method and the multiplicative Schwarz procedure is called block Gauss-Seidel method. Note also the relation to the explicit CSS and CPS procedures (Section 2.3.1) which are basically one iteration versions of the block Gauss-Seidel and the block Jacobi methods.

Algorithm 2.7 shows the steps of the block Jacobi method and Algorithm 2.8 the steps of the block Gauss-Seidel method. Note that we henceforth omit data transfer statements in algorithms to simplify the more complex implicit scheme descriptions. Another detail omitted in the algorithms is the internal state of the fluid and structure operators \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{S} . There are two possibilities how the internal state is treated. If a solver can use internal iterations to compute the solution of one coupling iteration, the internal variable state can be advanced with every coupling iteration, such that we can write \mathbf{F}_k^n and \mathbf{S}_k^n . If a solver is not able to perform iterations, but can only compute timesteps, simulation checkpoints have to be used to return to the old timestep. The fluid and the structure operator state is then kept at timestep n as \mathbf{F}^n and \mathbf{S}^n , independent of the coupling iteration k .

In any case, the block Jacobi method reduces to the computation of two simultaneous decoupled block Gauss-Seidel iterations, as shown in [165]. Thus, if the computation times per solver are the same for block Jacobi and block Gauss-Seidel, the overall computation time will be the same. In the following discussions, we always use the block Gauss-Seidel scheme as a basis for further explanations.

One crucial ingredient of any iteration method is to measure its convergence. For this purpose, we write the iteration in fixed-point notation as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)) = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k). \quad (2.105)$$

We write $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1}$ to differentiate the result of the chained solvers from the later introduced result of the post-processing, which is denoted by \mathbf{s}_{k+1} . When no post-processing is used, $\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1}$ holds. Note that the sequence of system solves could also be inverted

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```

1   $\mathbf{f}_0 = \mathbf{f}_p^{n+1}$ 
2   $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$ 
3   $k = 0$ 
4  while not converged
5       $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) = \mathbf{f}_{k+1}$ 
6       $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_k) = \mathbf{s}_{k+1}$ 
7       $k = k + 1$ 

```

Alg. 2.7: Additive (or parallel) Schwarz procedure, also called block Jacobi iterations, of one timestep. Lines 5 and 6 can be executed in parallel, i.e., employing interfield-parallelism, since they both use input values from the last iteration. Thus, two predictors \mathbf{f}_p^{n+1} and \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1} are needed for the first iteration, which are assigned in lines 1 and 2.

```

1   $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$ 
2   $k = 0$ 
3  while not converged
4       $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) = \mathbf{f}_{k+1}$ 
5       $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}) = \mathbf{s}_{k+1}$ 
6       $k = k + 1$ 

```

Alg. 2.8: Multiplicative Schwarz procedure, also called block Gauss-Seidel iterations, of one timestep. Since the structure solve in line 5 uses the fluid output of line 4, no interfield-parallelism is possible. The fluid solver needs a prediction \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1} (assigned in line 1) for the first iteration.

to

$$\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F} \circ \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_k). \quad (2.106)$$

We stay with the sequence in (2.105), which is most commonly used in practice. The residual of iteration (2.105) is given as

$$\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) - \mathbf{s}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \mathbf{s}_k \quad (2.107)$$

and becomes zero when the fixed-point \mathbf{s} is reached

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}) - \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.108)$$

Thus, the residual can be used as a convergence measure for the fixed-point iteration, since the error of the iteration is not known in general. The discrete L^2 -norm can be used to obtain a scalar representative of the vectorial residual $\mathbf{r} = (r_1, \dots, r_m)^T$ as

$$\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_{L^2} = \sqrt{\sum_i (r_{k+1,i})^2} = \sqrt{\sum_i (\tilde{s}_{k+1,i} - s_{k,i})^2}. \quad (2.109)$$

Directly using (2.109) yields an absolute convergence criterion

$$\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_{L^2} < \epsilon_{abs}, \quad (2.110)$$

with $\epsilon_{abs} > 0$ as absolute convergence limit and convergence being obtained when the above condition renders valid. However, since the absolute value of \mathbf{r} can change by orders of magnitude during one simulation, an absolute measure is not appropriate in all situations. A relative measure solves this problem by setting the residual in relation with the current coupling iterate values as

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_{L^2}}{\|\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1}\|_{L^2}} < \epsilon_{rel}. \quad (2.111)$$

Since a relative convergence measure can fail to work properly when the coupling iterate values are close to zero and rounding errors come into play, a combination of absolute and relative measure, where the absolute measure takes care of close to zero cases and the relative handles all other cases, is often a good choice.

As stated above, one of the main reasons why implicit equation coupling schemes are used is to stabilize the coupling. However, the instabilities found in explicit equation coupling schemes fully carry over to the Schwarz procedures (which basically apply the explicit CSS or CPS procedures repeatedly per timestep). Thus, the mere use of a Schwarz procedure does not result in the desired stabilization, as it fails to convergence in cases where the explicit schemes are instable, and additional efforts need to be made. In the following, we first discuss different post-processing techniques which stabilize the coupling iterations. After that, the interface artificial compressibility method and Robin boundary conditions are presented which modify the coupled problem to become more stable.

Constant Underrelaxation. One of the most straightforward ways to stabilize an iterative method is to use constant underrelaxation. The relaxation is performed by combining the input and output of (2.105) as

$$\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = (1 - \omega)\mathbf{s}_k + \omega\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k + \omega\mathbf{r}_{k+1}, \quad (2.112)$$

where ω is the relaxation factor to be chosen in the range $0 < \omega < 1$ to achieve a stabilizing effect (which corresponds to an underrelaxation). Algorithm 2.9 shows a block Gauss-Seidel scheme enhanced by constant relaxation. Constant underrelaxation works well if ω is close to 1, but leads to a slow convergence if ω has to be chosen close to 0. Thus, the constant underrelaxation method leads to unmanageable computational costs for severe instabilities. The optimal ω is not necessary the largest stable one (see Section 4.1.4) and has to be set empirically. In the following, alternative methods are discussed, which try to decrease the number of iterations necessary while still keeping stability.

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```

1   $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$ 
2   $k = 0$ 
3  while not converged
4       $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) = \mathbf{f}_{k+1}$ 
5       $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}) = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1}$ 
6      compute  $\mathbf{s}_{k+1}$  by relaxation (2.112)
7       $k = k + 1$ 

```

Alg. 2.9: Constant underrelaxation applied to the block Gauss-Seidel scheme.

Aitken Relaxation. The Aitken relaxation technique tries to accelerate the convergence of the coupling iterations by using a dynamic relaxation factor in comparison to the aforementioned constant relaxation. The technique originates in Aitken’s Δ^2 (delta square) method for scalar iteration sequences. Two previous iterates are linearly extrapolated to find the position of zero residual $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$, which corresponds to the Secant method for rootfinding problems. In the scalar case the extrapolation reads

$$s_{k+1} = \frac{s_{k-1}\tilde{s}_{k+1} - \tilde{s}_k s_k}{(s_{k-1} - \tilde{s}_k) - (s_k - \tilde{s}_{k+1})}. \quad (2.113)$$

If reformulated as relaxation (2.112), the relaxation factor has to be computed as

$$\omega_k = \frac{s_{k-1} - s_k}{(s_{k-1} - \tilde{s}_k) - (s_k - \tilde{s}_{k+1})}, \quad (2.114)$$

which can be rewritten in recursive form as

$$\omega_k = \omega_{k-1} \frac{s_{k-1} - \tilde{s}_k}{(s_{k-1} - \tilde{s}_k) - (s_k - \tilde{s}_{k+1})} \quad (2.115)$$

$$= -\omega_{k-1} \frac{r_k}{r_{k+1} - r_k}. \quad (2.116)$$

The vector case has been investigated in [90]. There, the following modification to (2.116) is proposed

$$\omega_k = -\omega_{k-1} \frac{(\mathbf{r}_k)^T (\mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k)}{\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k\|_{L_2}^2}, \quad (2.117)$$

which corresponds to a projection of the coupling iterate values in the direction of $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k$ before performing the scalar extrapolation. In the first iteration, there is not enough information available to perform the Aitken step. Thus, for the very first timestep, a value ω_{init} needs to be provided. In the following timesteps, the relaxation factor can be chosen as

$$\omega_0 = \max(\omega_k^{n-1}, \omega_{init}), \quad (2.118)$$

where ω_k^{n-1} denotes the relaxation factor from the last timestep’s last iteration. Algorithm 2.10 shows one timestep of the block Gauss-Seidel scheme with Aitken relaxation.

```

1   $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$ 
2   $k = 0$ 
3  if  $n = 0$ 
4       $\omega_0 = \omega_{init}$ 
5  else
6      set  $\omega_0$  according to (2.118)
7  while not converged
8       $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k) = \mathbf{f}_{k+1}$ 
9       $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}) = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1}$ 
10     compute  $\mathbf{r}_{k+1}$  according to (2.107)
11     if  $k > 0$ 
12         compute  $\omega_k$  according to (2.117)
13     compute  $\mathbf{s}_{k+1}$  by relaxation (2.112)
14      $k = k + 1$ 
    
```

Alg. 2.10: Aitken relaxation applied to the block Gauss-Seidel scheme at timestep n .

The suitability of this method for FSI simulations has been investigated in [97]. For a two-dimensional driven cavity test case with flexible bottom, the Aitken method shows a better computational performance than the steepest descent method and Newton Krylov solvers (presented later in this section). For a three-dimensional flexible tube setup, the Newton Krylov solvers beat the Aitken method with regards to computational runtime by a factor of 1.5. However, the Aitken method is much simpler to implement and has only minimal memory requirements.

Several alternative vector versions of the scalar Aitken acceleration have been proposed in [108]. Different to the above version [90], those are based on a sequence of three iterations $\mathbf{s}_k, \mathbf{s}_{k+1}, \mathbf{s}_{k+2}$ to construct an extrapolation. The dynamic relaxation factor ω_k can, hence, be updated only after every second coupling iteration. In [98], a two-dimensional driven cavity scenario with flexible bottom is used to perform numerical experiments using different Aitken versions. There, the alternative versions of Aitken acceleration [108] need almost twice as many coupling iterations until convergence compared to the version presented in [90].

Vector Extrapolation. Vector extrapolation methods for the convergence acceleration of block Gauss-Seidel type FSI iterations are proposed in [98] based on [148]. From a given FSI interface vector \mathbf{s}_k , a converging sequence of m iterates $\mathbf{s}_{k+1}, \mathbf{s}_{k+2}, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{k+m}$ has to be created by using the block Gauss-Seidel scheme with constant underrelaxation as in (2.112). An extrapolation for the coupling iterates can then be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} = \mathbf{s}_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \omega_i (\mathbf{s}_{k+i+1} - \mathbf{s}_{k+i}) = \mathbf{s}_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \omega_i \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1}, \quad (2.119)$$

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with $m - 1$ extrapolation factors ω_i . Since the differences $\Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1} = \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1} - \mathbf{s}_{k+i}$ in (2.119) vanish on convergence of the coupling iterates

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (2.120)$$

an extrapolation can also be performed for the difference vectors

$$\Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} := (\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} - \mathbf{s}_{k+m}) \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+1} + \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} \omega_i (\Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1} - \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i}). \quad (2.121)$$

Since we know the convergence limit of sequence (2.120) is the zero vector, we can write a minimization problem

$$\|\Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m}\|_{L_2}^2 \rightarrow \min, \quad (2.122)$$

which corresponds to a least-squares problem for finding the extrapolation factors ω_i . To improve the condition of the least-squares problem when $\Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$, an alternative notation of (2.121) is proposed as

$$\Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \gamma_i \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1}, \quad (2.123)$$

with constraint

$$\sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \gamma_i = 1 \quad (2.124)$$

to exclude the trivial solution $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{0}$. The original extrapolation factors are related to the alternative ones by $\gamma_i = \omega_i - \omega_{i+1}$, with $\omega_0 = 1$ and $\omega_m = 0$.

In [98], three different extrapolation methods are described, which belong to the class of polynomial extrapolation methods. All three methods solve a linear system, resulting from the least-squares solution of (2.122) as

$$\mathbf{A} \boldsymbol{\gamma} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (2.125)$$

to obtain the extrapolation factors γ_i . The difference between the methods is how they construct the elements a_{ij} of the system matrix \mathbf{A} . This is done as

$$a_{ij} = \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+j} \quad (2.126)$$

in the minimal polynomial extrapolation (MPE) method, as

$$a_{ij} = (\Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i} - \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+i-1}) \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+j} \quad (2.127)$$

in the reduced rank extrapolation (RRE) method, and as

$$a_{ij} = \mathbf{y}^i \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+j} \quad (2.128)$$

in the modified minimal polynomial extrapolation (MMPE) method, where \mathbf{y}^i is a set of linearly independent vectors. Once the linear system (2.128) is solved, the extrapolation factors γ_i are used to extrapolate the iterate values as

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \gamma_i \mathbf{s}_{k+i+1}. \quad (2.129)$$

One timestep of the extrapolation is given in Algorithm 2.11. There, an extrapolation is computed after every coupling iteration, but only used when the resulting residual is small enough (see line 12).

```

1   $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p^{n+1}$ 
2   $k = 0$ 
3   $m = 0$ 
4  while not converged
5       $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_{k+m}) = \mathbf{f}_{k+m+1}$ 
6       $\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+m+1}) = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m+1}$ 
7      compute  $\mathbf{s}_{k+m+1}$  by relaxation (2.112)
8       $m = m + 1$ 
9      compute  $\Delta \mathbf{s}_{k+m}$ 
10     update and solve linear system (2.125)
11     compute  $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m}$  by extrapolation (2.129)
12     if  $\mathbf{r}_{k+m} = \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m} - \mathbf{s}_{k+m-1}$  small enough
13          $\mathbf{s}_{k+m} = \hat{\mathbf{s}}_{k+m}$ 
14         reset linear system (2.125)
15          $k = k + m$ 
16          $m = 0$ 

```

Alg. 2.11: Vector extrapolation applied to the block Gauss-Seidel scheme in one timestep.

A comparison of the MPE and RRE methods with the Aitken relaxation is done in [98] for a two-dimensional driven cavity problem with flexible bottom. It shows that the Aitken method results in similar or better convergence acceleration than the vector extrapolation methods. Since the Aitken method is simpler to implement, the suggestion is to favor Aitken relaxation instead of other vector extrapolation methods.

Steepest Descent Relaxation. In [97], a steepest descent based relaxation method is investigated. The goal is to find an optimal value ω_k for every iteration k and to use it in the relaxation (2.112). A convex scalar merit function $\phi(\mathbf{s})$ is assumed to exist, to be minimal at the solution \mathbf{s}^{n+1} , and to be sufficiently smooth. This merit function is not defined in [97], only its derivative is used within the algorithm which is defined to be the coupling iteration residual

$$\phi'(\mathbf{s}_k) := \mathbf{r}_{k+1}, \quad (2.130)$$

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such that $\phi'(\mathbf{s}^{n+1}) = \mathbf{0}$. Using the merit function, an optimal relaxation factor can be found by

$$\omega_k = \arg \min_{\omega} \phi(\mathbf{s}_k + \omega \mathbf{r}_{k+1}) \quad (2.131)$$

and a sufficient condition for the optimal ω_k is given by

$$\frac{d\phi}{d\omega_k} = (\phi'(\mathbf{s}_k + \omega_k \mathbf{r}_{k+1}))^T \mathbf{r}_{k+1} \stackrel{!}{=} \mathbf{0}. \quad (2.132)$$

An approximation for the optimal relaxation factor can be obtained from a truncated Taylor expansion of its first derivative

$$\phi'(\mathbf{s}_k + \omega_k \mathbf{r}_{k+1}) \approx \underbrace{\phi'(\mathbf{s}_k)}_{=\mathbf{r}_{k+1}} + \omega_k \phi''(\mathbf{s}_k) \mathbf{r}_{k+1}, \quad (2.133)$$

where $\phi''(\mathbf{s}_k)$ is the symmetric matrix of second order partial derivatives of $\phi(\mathbf{s}_k)$ or the Jacobian of \mathbf{r}_k with respect to \mathbf{s}_k .⁵ Transposing (2.133) and multiplying it from the right with \mathbf{r}_{k+1} , the optimal relaxation factor can be obtained by

$$\omega_k = -\frac{(\mathbf{r}_{k+1})^T \mathbf{r}^{k+1}}{(\mathbf{r}^{k+1})^T J_{\mathbf{r}_k}(\mathbf{s}) \mathbf{r}_{k+1}}. \quad (2.134)$$

The remaining problem is how to determine the interface Jacobian $J_{\mathbf{r}_k}(\mathbf{s})$, since it is not accessible when black box solvers are used. Two approximations for the matrix vector product $J_{\mathbf{r}_k}(\mathbf{s}) \mathbf{r}_{k+1}$ are proposed in [97]. The first approximation is obtained by using a finite difference approach as

$$J_{\mathbf{r}_k}(\mathbf{s}) \mathbf{y} \approx \frac{\mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k + \delta \mathbf{y}) - \mathbf{s}_k - \delta \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{r}_{k+1}}{\delta}, \quad (2.135)$$

with

$$\delta = \frac{\lambda(\lambda + \|\mathbf{s}_k\|_{L_2})}{\|\mathbf{r}_{k+1}\|_{L_2}} \quad (2.136)$$

and λ chosen small enough⁶. The evaluation of (2.135) needs one more call of fluid and structure solvers per coupling iteration. To decrease the computational costs for the extra evaluation, it is proposed to reduce the accuracy within the field solvers. The second approximation uses approximated fluid derivatives and exact structure derivatives, which are not available for black box coupling and, thus, this alternative is not considered here.

A comparison of the steepest descent relaxation with Aitken relaxation and Newton Krylov solvers is shown in [97]. In a two-dimensional driven cavity test case with flexible bottom, the Aitken method shows the best computational runtime, despite the steepest descent method needed fewer coupling iterations. Overall, the computational runtime of all compared solvers is similar.

⁵In [97], the Taylor approximation is done for the merit function directly. It is not explained there, how to obtain the optimal relaxation factor from that.

⁶It is not further defined in [97] how a suitable λ can be obtained in a general case.

Interface Artificial Compressibility (IAC) Method. The interface artificial compressibility (IAC) method for incompressible flow FSI [47] tries to include the structural influence into the fluid continuity equation. The continuity equation of the ALE viewpoint fluid equations is written in integral form as

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \int_S \mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS = 0, \quad (2.137)$$

where the first term models the change of cell-volume over time, \mathbf{c} is the ALE velocity (2.15), and \mathbf{n} is the outer surface normal of the control surface S . The structural influence is included in the form of an additional source term for fluid mesh cells which have faces at the FSI boundary. This source term can be seen as an artificial compressibility. The modified continuity equation (2.137) reads

$$\frac{\Delta vol}{p_b - p_a} \frac{p_{k+1} - p_k}{\Delta t} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \int_S \mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS = 0, \quad (2.138)$$

where Δvol is the swept cell volume which is caused by two structural deformation states a and b . The deformation states are caused by the two sample pressures p_a and p_b and are computed once, prior to or at the beginning of the simulation. In [47], two constant sample pressure vectors are used, which are an estimate for the highest and lowest pressure occurring during the simulation. The face of a fluid mesh cell at the FSI interface undergoes a displacement according to the structural deformation states a and b . The swept volume Δvol of such a cell is constructed by taking the faces as volume top and bottom and connecting identical face nodes of state a and b with lines. Furthermore, $p_{k+1} - p_k$ is the pressure difference between the last and the current coupling iteration and Δt is the discrete timestep size. Since the source term involves p_{k+1} , it is introducing an implicitness into the continuity equation. An important property of the method is consistency, i.e., the source term vanishes when the coupling iterations (and hence pressure iterates) have converged, since then $p_{k+1} = p_k$. Thus, the solution of the coupling iterations is that of the original, incompressible problem.

To see the stabilizing nature of the source term, we note that the source term is a linear approximation for

$$\frac{\Delta vol}{p_b - p_a} \frac{p_{k+1} - p_k}{\Delta t} \approx \frac{V_{k+1} - V_k}{\Delta t} \quad (2.139)$$

and, moreover, we assume that the time derivative in the continuity equation is approximated by a first order finite difference as

$$\frac{\partial V_k}{\partial t} \approx \frac{V_k - V^n}{\Delta t}. \quad (2.140)$$

The combination of (2.139) and (2.140) yields

$$\frac{V_{k+1} - V_k}{\Delta t} + \frac{V_k - V^n}{\Delta t} = \frac{V_{k+1} - V^n}{\Delta t} \approx \frac{\partial V_{k+1}}{\partial t} \quad (2.141)$$

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and, hence, the source term approximates the continuity equation to be implicit as

$$\frac{\partial V_{k+1}}{\partial t} + \int_S \mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS = 0. \quad (2.142)$$

In [47], a comparison between the IAC method and the IBQN-ILS method, a quasi-Newton method described in the next section, is performed. The IAC method needs less coupling iterations per timestep within the computed tests. As a drawback, it is less suitable for black box coupling, since it requires to set a source term in the continuity equation of FSI boundary cells in the fluid solver.

Generalized Robin Boundary Conditions. The classical assignment of the FSI coupling conditions (shown in Section 2.1.4) as boundary conditions of fluid and structural equations is called Dirichlet-Neumann (DN) decomposition (see Section 2.2.3). In the DN decomposition the fluid FSI boundary is of Dirichlet type, prescribing the kinematic boundary values computed by the structure, while the structure FSI boundary is of Neumann type, with forces or pressures from the fluid. As mentioned above, using this decomposition with standard explicit or implicit partitioned coupling methods results in instabilities for a variety of simulation scenarios. A particularly critical application is that of hemodynamics, where the fluid is incompressible and the structure is comparatively thin. While most methods reviewed so far try to overcome those instabilities by applying some form of relaxation, in [124, 9] generalized Robin boundary conditions are evaluated as an alternative approach. The following discussion is based on [9] and summarizes the method and the results found.

A flexible pipe flow scenario with incompressible Newtonian flow bounded by a circular thin-walled elastic structure is given. Implicit block Gauss-Seidel iterations are performed by using the standard fluid and structure solver chaining as in (2.106). The equations are discretized in time by the implicit Euler method with timestep size Δt , denoted by operator δ_t , while the spatial discretization is omitted first. Given this setup and a DN decomposition, the FSI boundary condition for the fluid reads

$$\mathbf{v}_{k+1} = \delta_t \mathbf{u}_k \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}, \quad (2.143)$$

where k denotes the block Gauss-Seidel iteration number of the fluid velocity \mathbf{v} and the structure displacement \mathbf{u} . The structure FSI boundary condition is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{k+1}^S \cdot \mathbf{n}^S = -\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{k+1}^F \cdot \mathbf{n}^F \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}, \quad (2.144)$$

with the surface stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the outer surface normal \mathbf{n} .

Robin boundary conditions are basically a linear combination of Dirichlet and Neumann boundary types. Using Robin boundary conditions for the fluid reads

$$\alpha^F \mathbf{v}_{k+1} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{k+1}^F \cdot \mathbf{n}^F = \alpha^F \delta_t \mathbf{u}_k - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_k^S \cdot \mathbf{n}^S \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS} \quad (2.145)$$

and for the structure reads

$$\frac{\alpha^S}{\Delta t} \mathbf{u}_{k+1} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{k+1}^S \cdot \mathbf{n}^S = \frac{\alpha^S}{\Delta t} \mathbf{u}^n + \alpha^S \mathbf{v}_{k+1} - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{k+1}^F \cdot \mathbf{n}^F \quad \text{at } \Gamma_{FS}. \quad (2.146)$$

Depending on how the parameters α^F and α^S are chosen, a Neumann ($\alpha^{F/S} = 0$), Dirichlet ($\alpha^{F/S} = \infty$) or Robin boundary condition ($0 < \alpha^{F/S} < \infty$) can be obtained for either of the fields. Thus, the Robin boundary conditions provide a framework of decomposition methods.

In [9], this framework is used to test different decompositions for their stability and convergence with block Gauss-Seidel iterations. In particular, the Robin type boundary conditions are used to include a simplified linearized model of the structure in the fluid while solving the fluid part of the equations and vice versa. The structure simplification uses a membrane model under the assumptions of small deformations, negligible bending terms, and only normal displacements. The fluid model assumes an incompressible inviscid flow, negligible structural deformations, and, hence, a fixed domain. From the inclusion of the simplified models, parameters for α^F and α^S are derived to be used for more complex fluid and structure models. For the fluid Robin boundary condition, α^F is to be chosen as

$$\alpha^F = \frac{\rho^S H^S}{\Delta t} + \beta \Delta t, \quad (2.147)$$

with the structure parameters density ρ^S , thickness H^S normal to the interface. β is determined as

$$\beta = \frac{H^S E}{1 - \nu^2} (4\rho_1^2 - 2(1 - \nu)\rho_2), \quad (2.148)$$

where, E and ν are the Young modulus and the Poisson ratio of the structure, ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the mean and Gaussian curvatures at the wet surface Γ_{FS} . The influence of the fluid on the structure is summarized in the so-called added-mass operator \mathcal{M}_A which we discuss in more detail in Section 2.3.3. An approximation of the added-mass operator by $\mathcal{M}_A \approx \gamma \mu_{max} \mathbf{I}$ suggests that

$$\alpha^S = \gamma \frac{\rho^F \mu_{max}}{\Delta t}, \quad (2.149)$$

where γ is a parameter to be chosen suitably, μ_{max} is the maximal eigenvalue of the added-mass operator \mathcal{M}_A , \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix, and ρ^F is the fluid density.

Analytical and numerical analyses are done in [9] to compare different decompositions created by (2.145) and (2.146). The Robin-Neumann (RM) decomposition, including the effect of the structure in the fluid Robin boundary condition by (2.147), is found to be superior to the classical DN decomposition using constant underrelaxation. For the RN decomposition, the coupling iterations always converge, independent of the added-mass effect (discussed in Section 2.3.3). Much less coupling iterations are needed compared to the DN decomposition. The Robin-Robin decomposition, also including the effect of the fluid in the structure by (2.149), even yields better convergence. The parameter

γ is observed to be independent of most simulation parameters and, hence, robust. Concerning black box coupling, it has to be noted that the inclusion of simplified models can only be done if the respective solver features Robin boundary conditions and allows external access to modify its parameters.

Newton-Raphson Schemes

Newton-Raphson schemes, in the following denoted as Newton schemes, can be applied to the partitioned FSI system either by considering the chained overall fixed-point notation (2.105) or by writing up a blocked system consisting of coupled structural and fluid fixed-point iterations. In order to apply a Newton scheme to the overall chained fixed-point iteration (2.105), we define the residual operator from (2.107) as

$$\mathbf{R} := \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I}, \quad (2.150)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix of suitable size. The Newton scheme tries to find the root \mathbf{s} such that $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{0}$, assuming a linear behavior of \mathbf{R} described by its Jacobi matrix $J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s})$. An iterative scheme, consisting of repeatedly solving

$$J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k) \Delta \mathbf{s}_k = -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_k) \quad (2.151)$$

for $\Delta \mathbf{s}_k$ and updating the iterate

$$\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k + \Delta \mathbf{s}_k \quad (2.152)$$

is performed.

In case of writing up a separate fixed-point iteration for fluid and structure systems, a fluid residual operator $\mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ and, in addition, a structure residual operator $\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ are obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) &= \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}) = 0, \\ \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) &= \mathbf{s} - \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.153)$$

From this, a block Newton iteration can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{f}_k) & J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{s}_k) \\ J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}_k) & J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{s}_k) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{f}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{s}_k \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k) \\ \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.154)$$

and the update of the iteration variables reads

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{f}_{k+1} \\ \mathbf{s}_{k+1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{f}_k \\ \mathbf{s}_k \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{f}_k \\ \Delta \mathbf{s}_k \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.155)$$

Every iteration of the Newton scheme involves at least one invocation of flow and structure solvers when computing $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ or both $\mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k)$ and $\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k)$. While in (2.151) the flow and structure solvers have to be executed sequentially, (2.154) allows for interfield-parallelism, i.e., the solvers can be executed at the same time. The critical point for black box equation coupling is how to obtain the derivative information in the Jacobi matrices in (2.151) or (2.154). In the following, methods are presented which find approximations for the required Jacobian times vector products in different ways.

Interface-GMRES. In [116], a Krylov-subspace method is proposed to approximate the solution $\Delta \mathbf{s}_k$ of system (2.151), which results in a Newton-Krylov solver for the partitioned FSI system. A review of Newton-Krylov methods in general is given in [93]. For the interface-GMRES method, the Krylov-subspace of order m is written as

$$\mathcal{K}_m := \text{span}\{\mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_k\}_{i=1}^m = \text{span}\{\Delta \mathbf{s}_i\}_{i=1}^m, \quad (2.156)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{s}_i := \mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_k$ and the \mathbf{s}_i are generated during the Krylov iterations as $\mathbf{s}_{i+1} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_i)$. \mathbf{s}_k is associated to the outer Newton iteration and fixed during the Krylov iterations. Using the Krylov-subspace approximation, equation (2.151) can be written as

$$J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k) \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \Delta \mathbf{s}_i \approx -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_k). \quad (2.157)$$

The weights α_i , yet to be determined, combine the Krylov-subspace vectors in an appropriate way. Since the Jacobian matrix $J_{\mathbf{R}}$ is not accessible for black box flow and structure solvers, a finite-difference approach

$$J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k) \Delta \mathbf{s}_i \approx \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_i) - \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_k) =: \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_k =: \Delta \mathbf{r}_i \quad (2.158)$$

is employed to further approximate (2.157) as

$$J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k) \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \Delta \mathbf{s}_i \approx \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \Delta \mathbf{r}_i \approx -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{s}_k) = -\mathbf{r}_k. \quad (2.159)$$

The α_i are then determined by solving (2.159) in a least-squares sense as

$$\bar{\alpha} = \arg \min_{\alpha} \left\| \mathbf{r}_k + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_i \Delta \mathbf{r}_i \right\| \quad (2.160)$$

and the quality of the obtained approximation is quantified by the norm of the residual of (2.151) as

$$\xi = \left\| \mathbf{r}_k + \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{\alpha}_i \Delta \mathbf{r}_i \right\|. \quad (2.161)$$

Orthogonalizing a new Krylov-vector $\Delta \mathbf{s}_m$ with respect to all previous ones using the Arnoldi process, as shown in Algorithm 2.12, completes the connection to the generalized minimal residual method (GMRES). Furthermore, to stabilize the solver subiterations when setting up the Krylov-subspace approximation, constant underrelaxation by ω can be employed as

$$\Delta \mathbf{s}_m = \omega \Delta \mathbf{s}_m. \quad (2.162)$$

Algorithm 2.13 puts all parts of the Interface-GMRES for one coupling timestep in proper order. The Krylov-vectors can be reused between different coupling iterations k or even between different timesteps n .

```

1  for  $j = 1, \dots, m - 1$ 
2       $\Delta \mathbf{s}_m = \Delta \mathbf{s}_m - \Delta \mathbf{s}_j \frac{\Delta \mathbf{s}_m \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}_j}{\Delta \mathbf{s}_j \cdot \Delta \mathbf{s}_j}$ 
3   $\Delta \mathbf{s}_m = \Delta \mathbf{s}_m / \|\Delta \mathbf{s}_m\|$ 

```

Alg. 2.12: Arnoldi process to orthonormalize interface deltas.

Using a transient piston flow FSI scenario with one spatial dimension and compressible flow as described in [166], the interface-GMRES method is tested in [116] and compared to block GS iterations for three scenario parameters leading to increasing instabilities of the GS iterations. The Interface-GMRES method with reuse of Krylov-vectors from old iterations and timesteps outperforms the block GS iterations in all scenarios and provides solutions where the block GS iterations diverge. Initially, the Interface-GMRES needs more iterations per timestep, to accumulate a proper set of Krylov-vectors. In later timesteps, the number of iterations goes down significantly due to the reuse of Krylov-vectors.

Interface Block Quasi-Newton Method (IBQN-LS). Linear reduced order models for the fluid solver and the structure solver are used in [172] to speed up the convergence of the FSI coupling iterations. As important feature, the reduced order models are set up from solver input and output deltas (or sensitivities) during the coupling iterations. The resulting method for two black box solvers is called interface block quasi-Newton method with least-squares approximation (IBQN-LS) in [42]. The following elaboration is based on the version of the method presented in [42].

In the IBQN-LS method, the block Newton system (2.154) is approximated by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \widehat{\mathbf{F}}' & -\mathbf{I} \\ -\mathbf{I} & \widehat{\mathbf{S}}' \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}} \\ \Delta \hat{\mathbf{f}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) \\ \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s}) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.163)$$

and solved in a block Gauss-Seidel manner. Here, $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'$ and $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}'$ are linear reduced order models for the (interface) Jacobians of the fluid and structure solver that are updated in every coupling iteration.

To realize this idea, the fluid and structure solvers do not directly compute the coupling values used as input by the other solver as in (2.68) and (2.69), but only provide intermediate values $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}$. The block Gauss-Seidel solution of (2.163) implies an ordering of the solver inputs and outputs by the coupling iteration index k , reading

$$\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k), \quad (2.164)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}). \quad (2.165)$$

For solving (2.163), we assume that (2.164) and (2.165) have been evaluated in the last coupling iteration $k - 1$. As a first step of coupling iteration k , $\Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}}$ is computed by

```

1   $k = 0$ 
2  if not reuse timesteps or  $n = 0$ 
3      clear all  $\Delta \mathbf{s}_i, \Delta \mathbf{r}_i$ 
4       $m = 0$ 
5       $\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_0)$ 
6       $\mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}_0$ 
7      while  $\|\mathbf{r}_k\| > \epsilon_1$ 
8          if not reuse iterations
9              clear all  $\Delta \mathbf{s}_i, \Delta \mathbf{r}_i$ 
10              $m = 0$ 
11              $\xi = \|\mathbf{r}_k\|$ 
12         else
13             compute  $\bar{\alpha}$  (2.160) and  $\xi$  (2.161)
14              $\mathbf{s}_{m+1} = \mathbf{s}_1$ 
15         while  $\xi > \epsilon_2$ 
16              $m = m + 1$ 
17              $\Delta \mathbf{s}_m = \mathbf{s}_m - \mathbf{s}_0$ 
18             orthogonalize (Alg. 2.12) and relax  $\Delta \mathbf{s}_m$  (2.162)
19              $\mathbf{s}_m = \mathbf{s}_0 + \Delta \mathbf{s}_m$ 
20              $\mathbf{s}_{m+1} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_m)$ 
21              $\Delta \mathbf{r}_m = (\mathbf{s}_{m+1} - \mathbf{s}_m) - \mathbf{r}_k$ 
22             compute  $\bar{\alpha}$  (2.160) and  $\xi$  (2.161)
23          $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{\alpha}_i \Delta \mathbf{s}_i$ 
24          $k = k + 1$ 
25          $\mathbf{s}_1 = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_0)$ 
26          $\mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{s}_1 - \mathbf{s}_0$ 

```

 Alg. 2.13: Timestep n of the Interface-GMRES method.

solving the system

$$(\mathbf{I} - \widehat{\mathbf{S}}'_{k-1} \widehat{\mathbf{F}}'_{k-1}) \Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}} = -\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_{k-1}) - \widehat{\mathbf{S}}'_{k-1} \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_{k-1}). \quad (2.166)$$

The fluid solver input is then computed by $\mathbf{s}_k = \mathbf{s}_{k-1} + \Delta \hat{\mathbf{s}}$ and an updated residual $\mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k)$ by solving the fluid (2.164). Furthermore, the fluid reduced order model is updated to $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'_k$. Then, $\Delta \hat{\mathbf{f}}$ is computed from the updated system (2.163) by solving system

$$(\mathbf{I} - \widehat{\mathbf{F}}'_k \widehat{\mathbf{S}}'_{k-1}) \Delta \hat{\mathbf{f}} = -\mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k) - \widehat{\mathbf{F}}'_k \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_{k-1}). \quad (2.167)$$

Finally, the structure solver (2.164) is invoked with input $\mathbf{f}_{k+1} = \mathbf{f}_k + \Delta \hat{\mathbf{f}}$, the structure residual $\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_{k+1}, \mathbf{s}_k)$ is computed, and the structure reduced order Jacobian is updated to $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}'_k$.

In the following, we derive the reduced order model for the fluid solver interface Jacobian. Input coupling value deltas $\Delta \mathbf{s}_k := \mathbf{s}_k - \mathbf{s}_{k-1}$ and (intermediate) output

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coupling value deltas $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k := \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{k+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k$ are computed during the coupling iterations. The deltas are collected as columns of the matrices

$$\mathbf{V}_F := (\Delta \mathbf{s}_1, \Delta \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{s}_k), \quad (2.168)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_F := (\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2, \dots, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k). \quad (2.169)$$

A new fluid input delta $\Delta \mathbf{s}$ can be approximated by a linear combination of the columns of \mathbf{V}_F as

$$\mathbf{V}_F \mathbf{c}_F \approx \Delta \mathbf{s} \quad (2.170)$$

and a corresponding output delta $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ can then be constructed by using the computed coefficients \mathbf{c}_F to linearly combine the columns of \mathbf{W}_F as

$$\Delta \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{W}_F \mathbf{c}_F. \quad (2.171)$$

The \mathbf{c}_F are determined from a minimization

$$\mathbf{c}_F = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}} \|\Delta \mathbf{s} - \mathbf{V}_F \tilde{\mathbf{c}}\| \quad (2.172)$$

which is a least-squares problem, solved in [172] by the normal equations and in [42] by using the economy-size QR -decomposition. The action of $\widehat{\mathbf{F}}'$ on a vector can then be written as

$$\widehat{\mathbf{F}}' \Delta \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{W}_F \mathbf{c}_F. \quad (2.173)$$

The process to set up the reduced order model for the interface Jacobian of the structure solver $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}'$ is analogous to that described for the fluid solver. Input deltas $\Delta \mathbf{f}_k := \mathbf{f}_{k+1} - \mathbf{f}_k$ and output deltas $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k := \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k$ are collected in matrices \mathbf{V}_S and \mathbf{W}_S . After solving a corresponding least-squares problem to find optimal coefficients \mathbf{c}_S , the action of $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}'$ on a vector is written as

$$\widehat{\mathbf{S}}' \Delta \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{W}_S \mathbf{c}_S. \quad (2.174)$$

Algorithm 2.14 shows the IBQN-ILS method for one timestep. Initially, a prediction \mathbf{s}_p is computed by extrapolation from old timesteps and two block Gauss-Seidel iterations are performed using constant underrelaxation. Then, the initial reduced order models for fluid and structure are set up and the main coupling iteration loop with computation steps as described above starts. A comparison of the IBQN-LS to other implicit coupling methods is given in the following description of the closely related IQN-ILS method.

Interface Quasi-Newton Method (IQN-ILS). An interface quasi-Newton method based on (2.151) and (2.152) is presented in [43]. The method is called interface quasi-Newton with approximation of the inverse of the interface Jacobian matrix by least-squares (IQN-ILS). Its origin, the IBQN-LS method presented in [172], is derived from

```

1  predict  $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p$ 
2   $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1 = \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1 = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_0)$ 
3   $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1 = \mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_1)$ 
4  compute  $\mathbf{s}_1$  by relaxation (2.112)
5   $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2 = \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2 = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_1)$ 
6   $k = 1$ 
7  update  $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ 
8   $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_2 = \mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_2)$ 
9  update  $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$ 
10 while not converged
11      $k = k + 1$ 
12     compute  $\mathbf{s}_{k+1}$  as in (2.166)
13      $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ 
14     update  $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ 
15     compute  $\mathbf{f}_k$  as in (2.167)
16      $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_k)$ 
17     update  $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$ 
    
```

Alg. 2.14: One timestep of the interface block quasi-Newton algorithm with least-squares approximation (IBQN-LS) of the interface Jacobians of fluid and structure solvers.

the block Newton method (2.154) and uses two reduced order models for fluid and structure to approximate their interface Jacobians directly. In contrast, the IQN-ILS method provides one reduced order model for the inverse of the overall interface Jacobian matrix of the Newton system (2.151) applied to the right-hand side vector. The following elaborations are based on the newer description of the method in [42].

Similarly as for the IBQN-ILS method, input and output deltas are used to construct a reduced order model. In the interface residual formulation (2.107) of the chained solvers, the input is given by the structural coupling values \mathbf{s} and the output by the interface residual \mathbf{r} . Input and output deltas are defined by

$$\Delta \mathbf{r}_k = \mathbf{r}_{k+1} - \mathbf{r}_k, \quad (2.175)$$

$$\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k, \quad (2.176)$$

i.e., not the actual input deltas $\Delta \mathbf{s}$ are gathered, but the intermediate chained solver outputs $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}$ are used to construct the $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}$. This enables to approximate the inverse of the interface Jacobian applied to the right-hand side vector of the Newton system, as we will see later. The deltas are collected in matrices

$$\mathbf{V}_k = (\Delta \mathbf{r}_k, \Delta \mathbf{r}_{k-1}, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{V}^{n-1}, \dots, \mathbf{V}^{n-l}), \quad (2.177)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_k = (\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k-1}, \dots, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1, \mathbf{W}^{n-1}, \dots, \mathbf{W}^{n-l}), \quad (2.178)$$

with inversed ordering of the columns compared to the original IBQN-LS method. The matrices $\mathbf{V}^{n-1}, \dots, \mathbf{V}^{n-l}$ and $\mathbf{W}^{n-1}, \dots, \mathbf{W}^{n-l}$ represent the (optional) reuse of columns

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from l old timesteps. Reusing old timestep information can improve the approximation of the inverse of the Jacobian, particularly in the first iterations of a timestep.

A linear combination of residual deltas from \mathbf{V}_k is used to approximate

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} \approx \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{c} \quad (2.179)$$

which is defined to be $\Delta \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0} - \mathbf{r}_{k+1}$, in order to get a new residual \mathbf{r}_{k+2} that is zero. As in the IBQN-LS method, the desired linear combination is found by the least-squares solution

$$\mathbf{c} = \arg \min_{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}} \|\Delta \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{V}_k \tilde{\mathbf{c}}\|, \quad (2.180)$$

which can be computed, e.g., by an economy size QR -decomposition. Here, a possible problem is that the columns of \mathbf{V}_k can become linearly dependent such that a column removal becomes necessary. Adding new columns as first columns, as in (2.177) and (2.178), enables to detect and remove older columns as linearly dependent during the least-squares solution. This is particularly important when columns are reused from old timesteps since, then, the newer columns better represent the current state of the residual operator (2.150).

A $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}$ corresponding to a $\Delta \mathbf{r}$ is then constructed by using the coefficients \mathbf{c} in combination with the matrix \mathbf{W}_k as

$$\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{c}. \quad (2.181)$$

In order to construct an approximation for the inverse of the interface Jacobian, we rewrite the interface residual formulation (2.107) using $\Delta \mathbf{r}$, $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}}$, and $\Delta \mathbf{s}$, reading

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} = \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{s}} - \Delta \mathbf{s}. \quad (2.182)$$

Inserting (2.181) into (2.182) yields the desired approximation for the inverse of the interface Jacobian $\widehat{J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k)^{-1}}$ applied to the right-hand side residual delta

$$\Delta \mathbf{s} = -\widehat{J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k)^{-1}} \mathbf{r}_{k+1} := \mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{r}_{k+1}. \quad (2.183)$$

Algorithm 2.15 shows the IQN-ILS method for one timestep of the coupled simulation. As for the IBQN-LS method, when no delta columns are gathered yet, constant relaxation is used once to ensure stability.

In [46], a comparison of the IQN-ILS method with other popular implicit coupling algorithms is done. A two-dimensional flexible beam FSI scenario and a three-dimensional flexible tube scenario are used to compare the IQN-ILS method to the Aitken acceleration method, the Interface-GMRES method, and the IBQN-LS method. The best performance for IQN-ILS, IBQN-LS, and Interface-GMRES occurs when deltas from up to 10 old timesteps are reused. Then, the IQN methods perform best in all scenarios, followed closely by Interface-GMRES and trailed (with some one digit factor of computational costs) by Aitken acceleration. Comparing the IQN-ILS and IBQN-LS methods to Interface-GMRES, the main difference is that in the IQN methods only one update of the reduced order models per coupling iteration is performed, while in the Interface-GMRES method an inner loop of block Gauss-Seidel steps is performed to construct a least-squares approximation up to a prescribed convergence criterion.

```

1  predict  $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}_p$ 
2   $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1 = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_0)$ 
3   $\mathbf{r}_1 = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_1 - \mathbf{s}_0$ 
4  if not reuse timesteps or  $n = 0$ 
5      clear  $\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W}$ 
6      compute  $\mathbf{s}_1$  by relaxation (2.112)
7  else
8      compute  $\mathbf{s}_1$  as in (2.183)
9   $k = 1$ 
10 while not converged
11      $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ 
12      $\mathbf{r}_{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_{k+1} - \mathbf{s}_k$ 
13     update to  $\mathbf{V}_k, \mathbf{W}_k$ 
14     compute  $\Delta \mathbf{s}$  as in (2.183)
15      $\mathbf{s}_{k+1} = \mathbf{s}_k + \Delta \mathbf{s}$ 
16      $k = k + 1$ 
    
```

Alg. 2.15: Timestep n of the interface quasi-Newton with approximation of the inverse of the Jacobian matrix by least-squares (IQN-ILS).

Block-Newton Method. In [112], the partitioned systems of fluid and structure are written as two separate fixed-point iteration residual forms, as in (2.153). The Jacobian matrix of the overall Newton iteration can then be represented in block matrix form (2.154) and the coupling iterates are updated as in (2.155). To solve system (2.154), the Schur complement is computed, i.e., a symbolic Gaussian elimination is performed. Dropping the iteration index k and using $\mathbf{R}_F = \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$, $\mathbf{R}_S = \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{s})$ to simplify the notation, the symbolic solution for $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ in dependence on $\Delta \mathbf{s}$ can be obtained from the first line of (2.154) as

$$\Delta \mathbf{f} = \underbrace{-J_{\mathbf{R}_F}^{-1}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{R}_F}_{=: \mathbf{q}} - \underbrace{J_{\mathbf{R}_F}^{-1}(\mathbf{f}) J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{s})}_{=: \mathbf{C}} \Delta \mathbf{s}. \quad (2.184)$$

Inserting this solution in the second line of system (2.154) yields the Schur complement, a system with only $\Delta \mathbf{s}$ as unknowns, reading

$$\underbrace{(J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{s}) - J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{C})}_{=: \mathbf{S}} \Delta \mathbf{s} = \underbrace{-\mathbf{R}_S - J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{q}}_{=: \mathbf{p}}. \quad (2.185)$$

System (2.185) is solved in four steps:

1. \mathbf{q} is computed by solving the system $J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{q} = -\mathbf{R}_F$.
2. The right-hand side \mathbf{p} is computed as $\mathbf{p} = -\mathbf{R}_S - J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{q}$.
3. $\Delta \mathbf{s}$ is computed by solving the Schur complement system as $\mathbf{S} \Delta \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{p}$.
4. $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ is computed as $\Delta \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{C} \Delta \mathbf{s}$.

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Since the Jacobi matrices are not available for black box solvers, the following strategies are applied to perform the four solution steps. Step one is interpreted as one Newton iteration in the solution of

$$\mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k + \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{s}_k) = 0, \quad (2.186)$$

where \mathbf{f}_k and \mathbf{s}_k are fixed. The fluid solver can be used to compute the solution $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}$ of system (2.186), which is then used as an approximation for $\mathbf{q} \approx \tilde{\mathbf{f}} - \mathbf{f}_k$. When the outer Newton iterations are converged, then $\mathbf{q} = 0$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{f}} = \mathbf{f}_k$. In step two, a finite difference approach is used as

$$\mathbf{p} = -\mathbf{R}_S - J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{q} \approx -\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k + \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{s}_k), \quad (2.187)$$

which involves the solution of the structure solver with modified fluid variables $\mathbf{f}_k + \mathbf{q}$. The third step is computed with an iterative solver such as Bi-CGStab or GMRES. These solvers only require the action of matrix \mathbf{S} on a vector \mathbf{w} , which is, again, approximated by finite differences, but now using a small scalar step-size h as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{h} \mathbf{S}(h\mathbf{w}) &= \frac{1}{h} (J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{s})(h\mathbf{w}) - J_{\mathbf{R}_S}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{C}(h\mathbf{w})) \\ &\approx \frac{1}{h} (\mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k - \mathbf{C}(h\mathbf{w}), \mathbf{s}_k + h\mathbf{w}) - \mathbf{R}_S(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k)). \end{aligned} \quad (2.188)$$

The concrete choice of a step-size h is not further elaborated in [112]. To compute $\mathbf{C}(h\mathbf{w}) = J_{\mathbf{R}_F}^{-1}(\mathbf{f}) J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{s})(h\mathbf{w}) =: \mathbf{c}$, the solution of

$$J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{f}) \mathbf{c} = J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{s})(h\mathbf{w}) \quad (2.189)$$

is required. This can be seen as a Newton iteration and solved analogously to step one, but needs an additional finite difference approximation of

$$J_{\mathbf{R}_F}(\mathbf{s})(h\mathbf{w}) \approx \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k + h\mathbf{w}) - \mathbf{R}_F(\mathbf{f}_k, \mathbf{s}_k). \quad (2.190)$$

Finally, the fourth step can be computed by approximating $\mathbf{C} \Delta \mathbf{s}$ analogously to \mathbf{p} in the third step.

Overall, the block-Newton approach presented in [112] requires a comparably large number of solver evaluations per coupling iteration. Already without the Krylov-solver applied to approximate solution step three, four flow and two structure solver evaluations have to be performed in every Newton iteration. The Krylov-solver needs additional two flow and one structure solver call per matrix-vector product with matrix \mathbf{S} . The block Newton method is compared against simple block Gauss-Seidel iterations in [112] and found to need less solver evaluations per timestep. However, the block Newton method needs more evaluations of the flow solver than of the structure solver, where the flow solver is the more expensive part in a typical FSI simulation. Compared to the Interface-GMRES method presented in [116], no reuse of Krylov-subspace vectors in solution step three is mentioned, which could reduce the overall solver evaluations significantly.

Inexact Newton. In [75], a similar approach as in the Interface-GMRES method presented in [116] is taken. The Jacobian matrix $J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}_k)$ is, however, not approximated by a first order finite-difference, but computed by using a linearized incompressible fluid model $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}$ and the exact Jacobian matrix from the structure model as

$$J_{\mathbf{R}}(\mathbf{s}) \approx \mathbf{s} - J_{\mathbf{S}}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s}))J_{\tilde{\mathbf{F}}}(\mathbf{s}). \quad (2.191)$$

The authors of [75] claim that the structural Jacobian matrix is easy to construct for a linear structural model and simple to extract from the structural solver in case of using the FEM method. However, the use of the exact structural Jacobian can make the method difficult to use or incompatible for a black box coupling approach. In numerical test cases using an incompressible flow in a two- or three-dimensional flexible pipe, the proposed method needs 3 to 5 times less iterations than the Aitken method.

Projection Based Semi-Implicit Scheme. A semi-implicit coupling scheme, based on the Chorin-Temam projection in the fluid solver, is presented in [60]. Within the Chorin-Temam method, first the fluid mesh is updated and intermediate velocities are computed ignoring the incompressibility constraint. Then, a projection step computes pressures such that the incompressibility of the flow is satisfied. In the semi-implicit scheme proposed, only the projection step is coupled implicitly to the structure solver and, hence, computed repeatedly during a timestep. Based on the observation that the added-mass effect (Section 2.3.3) is mainly caused by the incompressibility constraint, the stability of the overall scheme is close to an implicit coupling scheme. The method is considered semi-black box here, since it requires a rather specific fluid solution method and also needs control over its execution steps.

A theoretical stability analysis with linearized fluid and structure models is done in [60] and confirmed by numerical experiments. Furthermore, a computational performance comparison is done using a three-dimensional flexible pipe flow with incompressible fluid. Implicit coupling iterations endowed with i) an Aitken scheme as shown in [97], ii) the quasi-Newton scheme presented in [75] and iii) an exact block-Newton scheme are compared to the semi-implicit scheme using an exact block-Newton scheme for the coupling iterations. The overall computational time of the coupled simulation is shortest for the semi-implicit scheme, followed by iii), ii) and i). The overall runtime (computing 50 timesteps) relative to the semi-implicit scheme is longer by a factor of 4.77 for iii), 6.05 for ii), and 24.86 for i). The overall acceleration compared to iii) of the fluid solver alone is given as 7.3. Note, however, that these speedups are dependent on the number of coupling iterations performed, which are not given in [60].

Multi-Level Schemes. In [168], the explicit multi-level scheme derived in [169] (see Section 2.3) is combined with Aitken relaxation as in [97] to form an implicit coupling scheme. A two-level scheme is constructed that performs implicit iterations on the coarse as well as the fine level in adjustable amounts. Only the fluid grid is actually coarsened,

while the structure fine grid is used on both levels. The Aitken relaxation factor is computed on the fine grid level and applied to both. Two two-dimensional FSI scenarios are simulated based on [87], but with a compressible flow and flow turbulence in the second scenario. The devised two-level scheme is compared to a fine-grid-only Aitken relaxation scheme using different numbers of coarse- and fine-grid iterations. The best performance is achieved when chaining three to four coarse grid iterations with one fine grid iteration. Then, the number of fine grid iterations could be reduced by 65% - 70% compared to the Aitken scheme while the overall amount of iterations (fine plus coarse) per timestep increased by 30%. No comparison is done on how this iteration differences relate to actual runtime differences. The scheme shares the same disadvantages with respect to black box coupling as that in [169], i.e., it needs access to each grid level of the flow solver in terms of interface data and timestepping control.

Summary of Implicit Coupling Schemes

In this section, we have considered implicit equation coupling schemes which repeatedly compute solutions of fluid and structure solver in every timestep until convergence is achieved. First, we have considered the block Jacobi and block Gauss-Seidel Schwarz decomposition method which are iterated versions of the CSS and CPS explicit schemes. To stabilize the iterations, methods with increasing numeric complexity to compute a relaxation for the coupling iterates have been considered. Furthermore, schemes that try to modify the standard Dirichlet-Neumann coupling decomposition in order to increase stability have been reviewed. Then, we have looked at a second group of implicit methods which is based on Newton-Raphson iterations. As the solver Jacobians are usually not available in black box coupling, the presented schemes differ in how they approximate the Jacobian (or its influence on a vector) in the Newton scheme. Finally, we have mentioned a multi-level scheme that performs implicit coupling iterations on different mesh levels.

In the following, we are going into more details for the root of the coupling instabilities, the added-mass effect, and review different contributions found in literature.

2.3.3 Instabilities and the Added-Mass Effect

One of the most challenging problems of the partitioned approach is that of instabilities created by the partitioning of the equations. For many FSI scenarios instabilities are not a big issue, while for some they can have a devastating effect. The reason for the instabilities is the staggered solution of fluid and structural equations, where one (or both) of the solvers has to use an explicit prediction for the boundary values of the other solver. This introduces an explicitness into the solution method, regardless of how the solver internal equations are computed. For compressible flow FSI simulations, this results in an upper limit for the timestep size [56], depending on the particular methods

employed. For incompressible flow FSI, the restrictions are more complex and can lead to unconditional instabilities. The following paragraphs summarize analyses done in literature.

Stability Analysis by Causin et al.

In [128], the influence of the coupling has been studied mathematically and numerically by considering a scenario from hemodynamics which consists of a flexible channel with internal, incompressible flow (similar as the scenario described in Section 4.1.4). Simulations with full non-linear physical models for fluid and structure are performed with explicit and implicit equation coupling schemes. For a given numerical scheme and fixed fluid density, the following causes for divergence of the coupling are observed for explicit coupling:

- i) The structure density falls below a certain threshold for a fixed geometry.
- ii) The length of the channel superceeds a certain limit for a fixed structure density.

For an implicit coupling scheme, based on underrelaxed block Gauss-Seidel iterations (see Section 2.3.2), the number of iterations increases when

- i) The structural density is decreased.
- ii) The length of the channel is increased.

A mathematical study is performed to find the cause of the instabilities. In the study, a simplified linear and inviscid fluid model is coupled to a linear generalized string model for the structure. Using a weak formulation, the added-mass operator \mathcal{M}_A is derived⁷. The added-mass operator summarizes the fluid equations, mapping velocities at the FSI boundary to forces on the structure. It is included in the structural dynamics equations and has the form of an additional mass term (which explains its name). The largest eigenvalue μ_{max} of \mathcal{M}_A is analyzed for a given time discretization (but no spatial discretization). In the limit case, when the channel radius r and length L go to zero, the following relation holds

$$\mu_{max} \approx \frac{2L^2}{\pi^2 r}. \quad (2.192)$$

This shows the influence of the geometry of the channel. Furthermore, for explicit equation coupling, unconditional instability is obtained when

$$\frac{\rho_S h_S}{\rho_F \mu_{max}} < 1, \quad (2.193)$$

where ρ_S and ρ_F are the structural and fluid densities and h_S is the thickness of the channel walls. For the implicit case, a condition for the relaxation factor ω is derived, in order to make the coupling iterations converge. This condition reads in the limit case

⁷The added-mass operator is defined in this work by (2.195), based on another publication.

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of timestep size $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$

$$0 < \omega < \frac{2}{1 + \rho_F \mu_{max} / (\rho_S h_S)}. \quad (2.194)$$

By considering (2.193), it is concluded that the implicit iterations need a relaxation factor $\omega < 1$ whenever the explicit coupling is unconditionally unstable.

Stability Analysis by Förster et al.

In [64], the very same added-mass effect is examined for FEM based explicit equation coupling schemes, using the ALE point-of-view for the fluid domain. The mathematical analysis is performed independent of a geometrical problem description. Also here, first some observations are made:

- i) Increasing the structural stiffness decreases instabilities.
- ii) Increasing the fluid viscosity increases instabilities.
- iii) Increasing the accuracy (order) of the time integration method increases instabilities.
- iv) Decreasing the timestep size increases instabilities.

Very interesting is observation iv), which is contrary to the usual behavior of explicit time integration schemes. For a mathematical study, linearized models are used again and, different to [128], also the fluid viscosity is considered. Added-mass operators \mathcal{M}_A are derived for different FEM-based spatial discretizations of the fluid equations, reading

$$\mathbf{f}_{\Gamma_{FS}} = m_F \mathcal{M}_A \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_{\Gamma_{FS}}}{\partial t}. \quad (2.195)$$

The operator maps structural velocities at the FSI interface to forces acting on the structure and the scalar m_F is a characteristic mass taken from the fluid discretization to give \mathcal{M}_A proper scale and dimensions. Concrete forms of \mathcal{M}_A are derived for unstabilized and stabilized FEM fluid spatial discretizations, with and without mass lumping applied. It is shown analytically that, for every sequentially staggered equation coupling scheme with a given time discretization, a mass ratio between fluid and structure exists which marks the transition to instability. Two instability conditions are derived, depending on the time integration scheme used in the fluid and on the derived predictor for the interface accelerations of the structure. If the fluid time integrator yields an expression for the interface accelerations that depends on a limited number of old interface displacements, the instability condition reads

$$\frac{m_F}{m_S} \mu_{max} > C, \quad (2.196)$$

where m_S is a characteristic mass for the structure, μ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue of \mathcal{M}_A as in [128], and C is a constant that depends on the time integration scheme used. For fluid time integration schemes that result in a dependence on all old interface displacements (fully recursive) to compute a prediction of the interface accelerations,

the instability condition reads

$$\frac{m_F}{m_S} \mu_{max} > \frac{C}{n}. \quad (2.197)$$

Here, n denotes the timestep number, i.e., any such time integration method will become unstable after a finite number of timesteps. To get a rough idea, the authors of [64] propose the following relation to include the timestep size Δt , structural stiffness, and fluid viscosity in the instability condition (2.196) as

$$\frac{m_F + a\Delta t k^F}{m_S + b\Delta t^2 k^S} \mu_{max} > C. \quad (2.198)$$

The constants a and b are influenced by the time integration schemes in fluid and structure, while k_S represents a characteristic structural stiffness, and k_F a characteristic fluid stiffness (directly related to the viscosity). They confirm this relation in numerical experiments. Finally, they conclude that the added-mass operator may change during a simulation when non-linearities and changing geometries are taken into account.

Stability Analysis by Degroote et al.

Another stability analysis for a similar pipe-flow problem as in [128] is performed in [44] for block-iterative implicit equation coupling schemes. In this study, the structural model is linearized and substituted into the fluid model. A centered finite volume discretization is performed for the resulting model using a pressure stabilization. After formulating the implicit iteration scheme for the discretized model, a Fourier error analysis is performed. The following observations are made from the analysis:

- i) Low spatial frequencies of the FSI interface values are responsible for the instabilities.
- ii) A decrease of the structural stiffness increases the number of coupling iterations.
- iii) A decrease of the timestep size increases the number of coupling iterations.
- iv) The spatial discretization width has a small influence on the instabilities.

Summary

To summarize, a list of sources for added-mass instabilities observed and analyzed in literature is given. The added-mass instabilities are increased when

1. The ratio of structural density to fluid density is decreased.
2. The structural stiffness is decreased.
3. The fluid viscosity is increased.
4. The timestep size for explicit equation coupling schemes is increased.
5. The timestep size for implicit equation coupling schemes is decreased.
6. The geometric aspect ratio of the FSI interface is increased.

Using underrelaxed implicit coupling iterations can help to handle a low to medium amount of instabilities. For stronger instabilities, in particular those bound to specific frequencies of the coupling values, Newton-like methods are better suited. These, however, are more demanding to implement.

With this, we end the discussion on equation coupling schemes for the fluid and the structure. In the next section, we come to another important aspect of partitioned coupling which is the data mapping between non-matching solver grids.

2.4 Data Mapping for Non-Matching Grids

Coupling two distinct simulation programs for FSI involves the coupling of two discretized representations of the common wet surface. Typically, the discretizations are surface meshes consisting of nodes and faces. Displacement, velocity, or force data values are usually associated to nodes, while pressures are linked to faces. Often, data values are interpolated by basis functions to form a continuous representation. In the case of matching meshes, i.e., meshes where the mesh nodes carrying data values and the basis functions equal each other, a simple copying of the values is sufficient to transfer data between the solvers. This case is, however, not very common when two distinct simulation programs are to be coupled. The case of non-matching grids is displayed in Figure 2.12, splitted up into two subcases. In 2.12a, the non-conforming case is shown, where the two surface representations coincide in the geometrical surface, but have nodes at different locations. In this case, simple interpolation algorithms on the coupling surface are sufficient. The general non-matching case is displayed in 2.12b, where the grids can have overlaps and gaps. This case either needs some form of projection between the surfaces paired with an interpolation on one of the surfaces or an interpolation in the same spatial dimension as the overall coupled problem. Methods for the general non-matching case are of course applicable in the simpler non-conforming case, too.

In the following Section 2.4.1, we first discuss the mapping problem in mathematical form and mention desired properties such as consistency, conservation, and balance of virtual work at the interface. Then, we review two mapping approaches that try to obtain some of the desired properties in Section 2.4.2. Finally, in Section 2.4.3, we review several important data mapping methods found in literature.

2.4.1 Problem Formulation

We consider the continuous vector fields of displacement $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$, force $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, and the continuous scalar field pressure $p(\mathbf{x})$ with coordinate \mathbf{x} in d -dimensional space. Furthermore, we consider discrete versions of the same quantities at n positions which are denoted by subindices, e.g., \mathbf{u}_i at position \mathbf{x}_i , where $i = 1, \dots, n$. Finally, to denote all discrete vectors, we use matrices which consist of one row for each discrete vector and

Fig. 2.12: Coupling surface (dashed line) discretized by two coupled solvers. (a) shows a mesh interface with coinciding geometry but different node positions, which is called non-conforming. (b) shows a more general non-matching mesh interface consisting of an adaptive Cartesian (left) and a triangular (right) mesh. Overlaps and gaps occur between the two meshes (grey areas).

columns for each spatial dimension. E.g., for three spatial dimensions, the matrix of all discrete displacement vectors is written as

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} u_{1,x} & u_{1,y} & u_{1,z} \\ u_{2,x} & u_{2,y} & u_{2,z} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ u_{n,x} & u_{n,y} & u_{n,z} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}. \quad (2.199)$$

This notation is useful for the following derivations, since all dimensions of the data fields will be treated in the same way. To distinguish between fluid and structure side, the subscripts \cdot_F and \cdot_S are used such that, e.g., $\mathbf{u}_F(\mathbf{x})$ is the continuous displacement vector at the fluid side.

For further discussion, we assume that the quantities of interest are represented by a weighted linear sum of continuous basis functions $N_i(\mathbf{x})$, which is a valid assumption for most discretization methods. The quantities can then be written as

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{u}_i N_i^u(\mathbf{x}), \quad (2.200)$$

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{p}_i N_i^p(\mathbf{x}), \quad (2.201)$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{f}_i N_i^f(\mathbf{x}), \quad (2.202)$$

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where $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$ is the outwards facing normal vector which, together with the scalar pressure $p(\mathbf{x})$, forms the directed pressure $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x})$. The basis functions may be different on fluid and structure side. We express the mapping of displacements from structure to fluid by

$$\mathbf{U}_F = \mathbf{H}_{SF}\mathbf{U}_S, \quad (2.203)$$

and that of directed pressures from fluid to structure by

$$\mathbf{P}_S = \mathbf{H}_{FS}\mathbf{P}_F, \quad (2.204)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{SF} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_S \times n_F}$, $\mathbf{H}_{FS} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_F \times n_S}$, $\mathbf{U}_F, \mathbf{P}_F \in \mathbb{R}^{n_F \times d}$, $\mathbf{U}_S, \mathbf{P}_S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_S \times d}$. Forces can be mapped alternatively to pressures analogously to (2.204).

The mapping of displacements and pressures is usually required to be a *consistent mapping*. This implies that constants should be interpolated exactly, such that

$$\beta_B = \mathbf{H}_{AB}\beta_A, \quad (2.205)$$

with $\beta_{A,i} = \beta_{B,j} = \beta = \text{const}$, $i = 1, \dots, n_A$, $j = 1, \dots, n_B$, and A, B as placeholders for fluid and structure. This property is obtained only if the rowsums in matrix \mathbf{H}_{AB} are equal to 1, since then we can write

$$\beta_{B,i} = \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^{n_A} H_{AB,ij}}_{=1} \beta_{A,j} = \beta \quad \forall i. \quad (2.206)$$

A *conservative mapping* ensures that the sum of the data values (in each spatial direction) is equal on both sides. Conservativity is important only for integral values such as forces, where we would like to have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_B} \beta_{B,i} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} \beta_{A,j}. \quad (2.207)$$

This is obtained only if the column sums of matrix \mathbf{H}_{AB} equal 1, since then

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_B} \beta_{B,i} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_B} (\mathbf{H}_{AB}\beta_A)_i = \sum_{i=1}^{n_B} \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} H_{AB,ij} \beta_{A,j} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^{n_B} H_{AB,ij}}_{=1} \beta_{A,j} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} \beta_{A,j}. \quad (2.208)$$

A feature often discussed in literature is the *balance of virtual work* δW , a balance of energy at the coupling surface, reading

$$\delta W_F = \delta W_S \quad (2.209)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \int_{\Gamma_F} \mathbf{u}_F(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{p}_F(\mathbf{x}) \, ds = \int_{\Gamma_S} \mathbf{u}_S(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{p}_S(\mathbf{x}) \, ds. \quad (2.210)$$

Inserting the basis function representations (2.200) and (2.201), we get for one side of the interface

$$\delta W = \int_{\Gamma} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{u}_j N_j^u(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{p}_i N_i^p(\mathbf{x}) ds \quad (2.211)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\Gamma} N_i^p(\mathbf{x}) N_j^u(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{u}_j \cdot \mathbf{p}_i ds \quad (2.212)$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n M_{ij} \mathbf{u}_j \cdot \mathbf{p}_i \quad (2.213)$$

$$= \text{tr} ((\mathbf{M}\mathbf{U})^T \mathbf{P}), \quad (2.214)$$

with matrix trace $\text{tr}(\mathbf{A}) = \sum_{i=1}^n A_{ii}$, $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$, and

$$M_{ij} = \int_{\Gamma} N_i^p(\mathbf{x}) N_j^u(\mathbf{x}) ds. \quad (2.215)$$

Thus, the discrete balance of virtual work can be written as

$$\text{tr} ((\mathbf{M}_F \mathbf{U}_F)^T \mathbf{P}_F) = \text{tr} ((\mathbf{M}_S \mathbf{U}_S)^T \mathbf{P}_S). \quad (2.216)$$

Note that this result is slightly different to the one presented in [40], where no trace operator is used and the layout of the data vectors $\mathbf{U}, \mathbf{P}, \mathbf{F}$ is not specified. The numbers of discrete positions n_F and n_S differ in general, leading to differently sized matrices and vectors on fluid and structure side. Also, we assumed here that all coupling variables of one discrete coupling interface (fluid or structure side) are located at the same positions and occur in the same amount, which might not be true in general.

In the following, we look at two important approaches for the overall bi-directional FSI mapping problem. These approaches are still formulated in a generic way and are, thus, independent of the concrete mappings employed. We evaluate the approaches with respect to the properties introduced in this section.

2.4.2 Conservative and Consistent Mapping Approach

In [57], an energy conserving approach is presented according to (2.216) for data mapping in FSI. It is called *conservative data mapping approach*. As first step in this approach, a consistent interpolation of displacements from structure to fluid interface is chosen conforming to (2.203). Then, a numerical pressure flux is defined as

$$\Phi_j := \sum_{i=1}^{n_F} M_{F,ij} \mathbf{p}_{F,i}, \quad (2.217)$$

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with \mathbf{M}_F as in (2.215), to express the virtual work at fluid side in dependence of the mapped structural displacements as

$$\delta W_F = \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \Phi_j \cdot \mathbf{u}_{F,j} \quad (2.218)$$

$$= \text{tr} \left((\mathbf{M}_F \mathbf{U}_F)^T \mathbf{P}_F \right) \quad (2.219)$$

$$= \text{tr} \left((\mathbf{M}_F \mathbf{H}_{SF} \mathbf{U}_S)^T \mathbf{P}_F \right). \quad (2.220)$$

Writing the sum of virtual work at structure side with nodal forces (interpreted as pressure flux analog to (2.217) in [40]) instead of pressures

$$\delta W_S = \sum_{i=1}^{n_S} \mathbf{f}_{S,i} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{S,i} = \text{tr} \left(\mathbf{U}_S^T \mathbf{F}_S \right) \quad (2.221)$$

and equating this with δW_F yields a computation rule for the forces

$$\mathbf{F}_S = \mathbf{H}_{SF}^T \mathbf{M}_F^T \mathbf{P}_F, \quad (2.222)$$

with

$$\mathbf{f}_{S,i} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \Phi_j H_{SF,ji}. \quad (2.223)$$

If every column sum of \mathbf{H}_{SF} equals 1, then the row sums of \mathbf{H}_{SF}^T equal 1, too. An interpolation method that creates such an \mathbf{H}_{SF} is called consistent and choosing such a method does not only conserve virtual work, but also the total amount of numerical pressure flux as can be seen from summing up all structure forces

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_S} \mathbf{f}_{S,i} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_S} \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \Phi_j H_{SF,ji} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \Phi_j. \quad (2.224)$$

When, in addition, the basis functions of the displacements on the fluid side sum up to one ($\sum_{i=1}^{n_F} N_{F,i}^u(\mathbf{x}) = 1$), then the sum of the numerical pressure flux equals the sum of the forces on the fluid side

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \Phi_j &= \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \sum_{i=1}^{n_F} M_{F,ij} \mathbf{p}_{F,j} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \sum_{i=1}^{n_F} \int_{\Gamma} N_{F,i}^u(\mathbf{x}) N_{F,j}^p(\mathbf{x}) ds \mathbf{p}_{F,j} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \int_{\Gamma} \underbrace{\sum_{i=1}^{n_F} N_{F,i}^u(\mathbf{x}) N_{F,j}^p(\mathbf{x})}_{=1} \mathbf{p}_{F,j} ds \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{n_F} \mathbf{f}_{F,j}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.225)$$

Hence, also the forces on the fluid and the structure side are conserved.

The conservative approach presented in [57] assumes that the forces at the FSI interface in the structure solver can be set directly. This might not be possible for a black box structure solver, as typically tractions are set in form of pressures or stresses. Thus, in [40], the mapping for the pressures is derived from (2.222) within the conservative method, reading

$$\mathbf{P}_S = \underbrace{(\mathbf{M}_F \mathbf{H}_{SF} \mathbf{M}_S^{-1})^T}_{=: \mathbf{H}_{FS}} \mathbf{P}_F. \quad (2.226)$$

Regardless of mapping forces as in (2.222) or pressures as in (2.226), the conservative approach of [57] needs access to the Ansatz functions that interpolate the coupling values at the FSI interface. This might not be possible for a black box solver and, in addition, a general mapping method does not guarantee that \mathbf{H}_{SF} as well as \mathbf{H}_{FS} are both consistent mapping matrices. A mapping approach using two independent consistent mapping matrices \mathbf{H}_{FS} and \mathbf{H}_{SF} is, thus, the only way to perform the spatial coupling in many cases. This approach is called *consistent data mapping approach* in [57, 40]. Both, the conservative as well as the consistent data mapping approach are generic in the sense that they do not prescribe the actual mapping method(s) to be used. In the following section, we focus on popular mapping methods found in literature.

2.4.3 Data Mapping Methods

A great variety of methods for data mapping between non-matching grids exists in literature and let alone the list of methods used in FSI simulations is not exactly short. The following overview of data mapping methods for FSI is based to a big extent on the mapping comparisons done in [39, 40]. While it represents a popular subset of mapping methods used in FSI simulations, it cannot and does not aim to be exhaustive. In particular, we consider nearest neighbor, nearest projection, weighted residual, and radial basis function data mapping methods. These methods differ in certain aspects. Relevant for this work are conservation and consistency properties as discussed above, numerical accuracy, computational efficiency, and black box compatibility. Some of them need full geometric surface representations to perform geometric projections while others only work with the nodes holding the FSI data. We have a look at these properties while reviewing the methods in the following. Other properties such as the suitability for mappings between surface representations with very different error orders, e.g., of concern here [73], are not discussed in the following.

Before we start, we abstract from the FSI notation, since the mappings can be used in more general cases. We denote the solver surface meshes to be mapped between by A and B and consider generic, possibly vectorial data $\mathbf{w}(\mathbf{x})$ at position \mathbf{x} to be mapped. The resulting system reads

$$\mathbf{W}_B = \mathbf{H}_{AB} \mathbf{W}_A. \quad (2.227)$$

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As above, we assume that data values are interpolated by basis functions $N(\mathbf{x})$ at each solver's side.

Nearest Neighbor Mapping

The simplest data mapping method using geometric projections is the nearest neighbor (NN) mapping. It is based on data nodes only, i.e., the data nodes of the solver surface meshes suffice to set up the mapping relations. If data should be mapped from mesh A to mesh B consistently, then, for every node of mesh B , the geometrically closest neighbor on mesh A needs to be determined as depicted in Figure 2.13a. The data value of the closest node in mesh A is simply copied to that in mesh B . As a result, every row of mapping matrix \mathbf{H}_{AB} in (2.227) consists of only one entry 1 and zeros otherwise. If data should be mapped conservatively from mesh B to A , the transposed mapping \mathbf{H}_{AB}^T can be used, i.e., the same neighbor relations are used and the data values of the nodes of mesh B are added up in the nodes of mesh A .

Fig. 2.13: Illustration of nearest neighbor (NN) mapping. (a) shows the consistent mapping from a mesh A (blue empty circles) to a mesh B (red filled circles). A closest neighbor from mesh A is associated to every node of mesh B . The data values from every closest node are then assigned to the neighbor in mesh B , indicated by arrows. In (b), a typical problem of projection methods is shown, namely the omission of nodes with no projection partner. Since nearest neighbors are searched for nodes of mesh B only, nodes in mesh A can be omitted.

While with the NN method a single mapping can be consistent or conservative, it is shown in [40] that when using the conservative approach as presented in Section 2.4.2, the mapped pressures will not be consistent. In fact, for the exact interpolation of a constant pressure with nearest neighbor interpolation, (2.226) leads to the conditions

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n_F} H_{FS,ij} \frac{\int_{\Gamma_F} N_{F,j}^p(\mathbf{x}) ds}{\int_{\Gamma_S} N_{S,i}^p(\mathbf{x}) ds} = 1, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, n_S. \quad (2.228)$$

For an equidistant surface mesh, the integrals will be constant $\int_{\Gamma_F} N_{F,j}^p(\mathbf{x}) ds =: \Delta x_{F,j} = \Delta x_F$ and $\int_{\Gamma_S} N_{S,i}^p(\mathbf{x}) ds =: \Delta x_{S,i} = \Delta x_S$. Since each row of \mathbf{H}_{FS} has only one entry 1,

condition (2.228) becomes

$$\frac{\Delta x_F}{\Delta x_S} = 1, \quad (2.229)$$

which is only true for conforming meshes with same basis functions.

Another problem, common to all projection based methods presented here, is the omission of nodes in case of non-uniform mesh sizes or concave geometries between mesh A and mesh B , as illustrated in Figure 2.13b. This can lead to the omission of local data variations and to the loss of conservativity, since certain data values are not taken into account. A workaround for this problem is presented for the weighted residual methods which are also based on projections and suffer from similar problems.

Accuracy-wise, the NN mapping is usually considered to be the worst choice compared to other mapping methods. However, it can be an efficient choice, e.g., in case of matching meshes with differently indexed nodes. The mapping then establishes the correct relations to coinciding nodes. The computational efficiency of the mapping is determined by the efficiency of the neighbor search which has an $O(n_A \cdot n_B)$ runtime complexity. This complexity can be reduced to $O(\log n_A \cdot n_B)$ by employing spacetrees (see Section 2.5).

Nearest Projection Mapping

A nearest projection (NP) mapping finds geometrical projections of a set of mesh nodes to a set of mesh elements of another mesh consisting of surfaces or volumes. It employs interpolations from the nodes of the mesh elements to the projected nodes (or vice versa) to compute the data values to be assigned. Compared to the nearest neighbor mapping, it is similar with respect to finding closest neighbors. It is different as the projections are done to surfaces or volumes instead of points and as the data interpolations involve several data nodes. NP mappings are described, e.g., in [2], [25], and [40]⁸. In the following, we mainly focus on the description in [25], which is closely related to the rest of this work.

The NP mapping described in [25] is based on polygonal surface meshes in the two-dimensional space, or triangulated surface meshes in the three-dimensional space. In a consistent mapping from mesh A to mesh B , as depicted in Figure 2.14a, only the nodes of mesh B are required, while for mesh A faces are required in addition. For every node in mesh B the nearest element in mesh A is determined, where nearest is interpreted as shortest valid projection distance in [25] and as shortest weighted sum of orthogonal and tangential distances in [2]. We follow the measure of [25], which further expresses a projected node's coordinates by a face parametric description. For triangles, barycentric coordinates α, β, γ are used to write the projected point \mathbf{d} as

$$\mathbf{d} = \alpha \mathbf{a} + \beta \mathbf{b} + \gamma \mathbf{c} \quad (2.230)$$

⁸In [40], the name nearest neighbor projection is used.

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Fig. 2.14: Illustration of nearest projection (NP) mapping as in [25]. Node data values are mapped by finding closest orthogonal projections (dashed lines with right angles), followed by linear interpolations based on the parametric description of the projected nodes. In (a), the consistent mapping from mesh A to mesh B in two dimensions is shown. (b) illustrates the same mapping in three dimensions with a triangle surface element.

with $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ the triangle node coordinates. The barycentric coordinates have the normalization property

$$\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1 \quad (2.231)$$

and \mathbf{d} lies within the triangle only if $0 < \alpha, \beta, \gamma < 1$. The projection can, thus, be performed to the plane (or line) containing the face and the parametric description can be used to check whether the projected point is actually contained in the face. A projection point is only considered to be valid if it is contained in the face. Otherwise, projections to elements with lower dimensionality are considered, i.e., first edges and then nodes. Once the nearest mesh element is determined, linear interpolation is used to determine the data value to be assigned. The parametric weights can be directly used as interpolation weights such that for triangles three data values are interpolated, for edges two, and for nodes a simple assignment as in the NN method is used.

The NP mapping results in a non-consistent mapping of pressures for general non-matching meshes and solver discretizations when the conservative approach described in Section 2.4.2 is used. This is due to the fact that the interpolations used are not derived from the basis functions representing the coupling data in the solvers' discretizations. Only for linear basis functions the interpolation schemes match. Also, as for the NN mapping, nodes can be omitted when the mesh widths differ too much locally, which violates conservativity. Despite this drawbacks, the NP mapping can be a good option for black box coupling, since it does not require access to the solver basis functions while providing an often sufficient amount of accuracy. Similar as for the NN mapping, space-trees can be employed to improve the asymptotic runtime complexity of the mapping from the default $O(n_A \cdot n_B)$ to $O(\log n_A \cdot n_B)$.

Weighted Residuals Mapping

Weighted residual methods express the balance of FSI coupling values in a weak formulation. They use geometric projections to transfer quantities between non-matching meshes, similar as the NN and NP methods, but derive their data interpolation weights from the basis functions employed by the solvers. In the following, we look at the mathematical formulation and discuss different projection methods as presented in [40, 57, 32, 2].

The starting point of the weighted residual method is the weak form of (one of) the coupling conditions at the FSI surface, reading

$$\int_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{w}_B(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{w}_A(\mathbf{x})) \lambda(\mathbf{x}) ds = 0, \quad \mathbf{w} \in \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{p}\}, \quad (2.232)$$

where $\lambda(\mathbf{x})$ is a Lagrange multiplier. To discretize (2.232), the coupling values are represented by discrete vectors $\mathbf{w}_{A,j}$, $\mathbf{w}_{B,i}$ and interpolated by nodal basis functions $N_{A,j}(\mathbf{x})$, $N_{B,i}(\mathbf{x})$ according to

$$\mathbf{w}_A(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} N_{A,j}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{w}_{A,j}, \quad \mathbf{w}_B(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_B} N_{B,i}(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{w}_{B,i}. \quad (2.233)$$

The Lagrange multiplier is represented by basis functions $N_{\alpha,k}(\mathbf{x})$ as

$$\lambda(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\alpha}} N_{\alpha,k}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (2.234)$$

Following the Mortar approach [22], the parameter α in (2.234) is later chosen to be either A or B such that the same basis functions as in one of the solvers are used. The basis function representations (2.233) and (2.234) are inserted into the weak form (2.232). Reformulating the such discretized weak form as a balance of FSI quantities for every $k = 1, \dots, n_{\alpha}$ yields

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_B} \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma} N_{\alpha,k}(\mathbf{x}) N_{B,i}(\mathbf{x}) ds}_{C_{\alpha B, ki}} \mathbf{w}_{B,i} = \sum_{j=1}^{n_A} \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma} N_{\alpha,k}(\mathbf{x}) N_{A,j}(\mathbf{x}) ds}_{C_{\alpha A, kj}} \mathbf{w}_{A,j}, \quad (2.235)$$

where each integral corresponds to an entry in one of the coupling matrices $\mathbf{C}_{\alpha B}$ and $\mathbf{C}_{\alpha A}$. When mapping from mesh A to mesh B , we choose $\alpha := B$ to get a square system matrix and, consequently, have to compute the solution of

$$\mathbf{W}_B = \underbrace{\mathbf{C}_{BB}^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{BA}}_{\mathbf{H}_{AB}} \mathbf{W}_A, \quad (2.236)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_{BB} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B \times n_B}$, $\mathbf{C}_{BA} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B \times n_A}$, $\mathbf{W}_B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B \times d}$, and $\mathbf{W}_A \in \mathbb{R}^{n_A \times d}$.

2 Overview of Approaches to Partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction

We have left open the question at which solver surface mesh(es) the integrals of (2.235) are to be evaluated. To achieve a consistent mapping, it is shown in [40] that all integrals need to be computed at the same surface. Choosing surface mesh B for the integrations requires projections only for the computation of \mathbf{C}_{BA} . When all involved sets of basis functions sum up to 1 in addition, the weighted residual mapping ensures a consistent mapping of pressures in the conservative mapping approach for non-conforming meshes and for non-matching meshes with converging surface representation. Two meshes have a converging surface representation if they converge to the same geometrical surface for increasing mesh refinements. While the computation of the integrals of \mathbf{C}_{BB} is straightforward, the integrals of \mathbf{C}_{BA} involve basis functions from different meshes. Two integration approaches for \mathbf{C}_{BA} based on geometric projections are described in literature.

In the Gaussian integration approach [57, 32, 2], the Gaussian integration points at surface mesh B are projected orthogonally to mesh A with the projection operator $\Pi_A(\cdot)$, leading to the approximation

$$\begin{aligned} C_{BA,kj} &= \int_{\Gamma_B} N_{B,k}(\mathbf{x}) N_{A,j}(\mathbf{x}) ds \\ &\approx \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} \sum_{g=1}^{n_{gp,k}} w_g N_{B,k}(\mathbf{x}_{g,k}) N_{A,j}(\Pi_A(\mathbf{x}_{g,k})) ds, \end{aligned} \quad (2.237)$$

where $n_{gp,k}$ is the number of Gaussian integration points $\mathbf{x}_{g,k}$ with non-zero contributions from $N_{B,k}(\mathbf{x}_{g,k})$ and w_g are the weights of the integration points. The second integration approach projects the faces of mesh A onto mesh B , followed by an intersection with the faces of mesh B [2]. Using a projection operator $\Pi_B(\cdot)$, the intersection of face $\Gamma_{B,j}$ with face $\Gamma_{A,k}$ at mesh B can be written as

$$\Gamma_{B,kj} = \Pi_B(\Gamma_{A,k}) \cap \Gamma_{B,j}. \quad (2.238)$$

Using the intersected faces, the entries of \mathbf{C}_{BA} are approximated by

$$C_{BA,kj} \approx |\Gamma_{B,kj}| \bar{N}_{B,k}(\Gamma_{B,kj}) \bar{N}_{A,j}(\Gamma_{B,kj}), \quad (2.239)$$

where $|\cdot|$ returns the size of an area and $\bar{N}(\cdot)$ is the average value of N within an area.

As with the other projection based methods, potential problems with omitted data nodes or faces can occur also for the weighted residual mapping. For the Gaussian integration approach, two workarounds can be found in literature. The first uses an overlay mesh [40], i.e., the mesh nodes of mesh A are projected on mesh B and new mesh elements with corresponding quadrature points are created from projected and original mesh nodes. A second approach presented in [32] adaptively increases the number of Gaussian integration points in mesh B when a node in mesh A is not taken into account. Both workarounds ensure the overall conservativity of the mapping.

The weighted residual mapping requires knowledge about the surface geometry and the basis functions at the FSI surface used by the coupled solvers. Either a solver provides

a way to evaluate the basis functions via a programming interface, which cannot be considered as black box, or the basis functions have to be implemented separately for the mapping. Similar knowledge is necessary to perform the Gaussian integration. When higher order basis functions are used to represent the surface geometry, the projections have to be performed with respect to that higher order geometry and not just based on the geometry of triangular or polygonal mesh elements.

Radial Basis Function Mapping

Radial basis function (RBF) mappings build up an interpolant with the same spatial dimensionality as the overall coupled problem. The interpolant is created from the mesh nodes and data of one coupling surface and is evaluated at the nodes of the other surface mesh. Thus, no projections are needed as with the methods presented above and problems related to the projections are not occurring. RBF mappings have first been applied to FSI in [17] and were further investigated in [1, 149, 39, 40]. In the following paragraphs, we review the mathematical foundations and suitability for the conservative approach.

The main ingredient of the mapping are the RBFs, point-symmetric functions

$$\phi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \|\mathbf{x}\| \mapsto \phi(\|\mathbf{x}\|), \quad (2.240)$$

where $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ is the Euclidean norm of the position $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ in d -dimensional space. When mapping data values from a mesh A to a mesh B , an interpolant $s(\mathbf{x})$ is built up at the nodes of mesh A as

$$s(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_A} \gamma_i \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{A,i}\|) + q(\mathbf{x}), \quad (2.241)$$

with the interpolation weights γ_i , the FSI surface mesh nodes $\mathbf{x}_{A,i}$ of mesh A , and a polynomial $q(\mathbf{x})$. The γ_i and the polynomial q are determined by the interpolation conditions

$$s(\mathbf{x}_{A,i}) = w_{A,i}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n_A \quad (2.242)$$

and the condition

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_A} \gamma_i p(\mathbf{x}_{A,i}) = 0 \quad (2.243)$$

for all polynomials p with degree less than or equal to that of q . The different spatial components of discrete d -dimensional data \mathbf{w}_i are mapped separately, such that we always deal with discrete scalar data w_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$. When ϕ is conditionally positive definite of order $m \leq 2$, according to Definition 3.1 in [17], a linear polynomial q can be used to ensure a unique interpolant s . A linear q ensures the exact interpolation of constant and linear functions, which results in the exact transfer of rigid body motions when mapping displacements. Furthermore, it conserves force and momentum when

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using the transposed mapping. In the three-dimensional case where $\mathbf{x} = (x \ y \ z)^T$, we write the linear polynomial as

$$q(\mathbf{x}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \beta_2 y + \beta_3 z \quad (2.244)$$

and denote the four-component vector of polynomial coefficients by $\boldsymbol{\beta}$. The interpolation weights $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ and the polynomial coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ for one spatial dimension of the data to be mapped can be computed by solving the system of equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{AA} & \mathbf{Q}_A \\ \mathbf{Q}_A^T & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\gamma} \\ \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{w}_A \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.245)$$

where vector $\mathbf{w}_A \in \mathbb{R}^{n_A}$ contains all data values $w_{A,i}$ of one spatial dimension, square matrix $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{AA} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_A \times n_A}$ contains the evaluations of the radial basis function $\Phi_{AA,ij} = \phi(\|\mathbf{x}_{A,i} - \mathbf{x}_{A,j}\|)$, and the i -th row of matrix $\mathbf{Q}_A \in \mathbb{R}^{n_A \times d+1}$ looks like $(1 \ x_{A,i} \ y_{A,i} \ z_{A,i})$ in the three-dimensional case $d = 3$. The evaluation of the interpolant $s(\mathbf{x})$ computed by (2.245) at the surface mesh nodes of B can be written in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{w}_B = (\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{BA} \ \mathbf{Q}_B) \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\gamma} \\ \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.246)$$

with vector $\mathbf{w}_B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B}$ of data values in one dimension at nodes $\mathbf{x}_{B,i}$, matrix $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{BA} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B \times n_A}$ of radial basis function evaluations $\Phi_{BA,ij} = \phi(\|\mathbf{x}_{B,i} - \mathbf{x}_{A,j}\|)$, and matrix $\mathbf{Q}_B \in \mathbb{R}^{n_B \times d+1}$ with i -th row as $(1 \ x_{B,i} \ y_{B,i} \ z_{B,i})$ in the three-dimensional case. The overall mapping can, thus, be written as

$$\mathbf{w}_B = \underbrace{(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{BA} \ \mathbf{Q}_B) \begin{pmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{AA} & \mathbf{Q}_A \\ \mathbf{Q}_A^T & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1}}_{=: \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{AB}} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{w}_A \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.247)$$

where, theoretically, we can obtain matrix \mathbf{H}_{AB} by taking the first n_B rows and n_A columns of $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{AB}$, such that $\mathbf{w}_B = \mathbf{H}_{AB} \mathbf{w}_A$. In contrast to the mappings introduced before, it is not possible to map all dimensions of the data with the same \mathbf{H}_{AB} at once $\mathbf{W}_B \neq \mathbf{H}_{AB} \mathbf{W}_A$ and, thus, it is not desirable to extract the matrix \mathbf{H}_{AB} . However, the system matrix of (2.245) is the same for every spatial dimension of a dataset to be mapped and a once performed decomposition can be reused to speed up the solution for the remaining dimensions.

In the following, we consider three different RBF types which are all conditionally positive definite of order $m \leq 2$ as discussed before. Figure 2.15 gives illustrations for the RBFs. We first consider RBFs with global support, which lead to a dense system matrix in (2.245). In [149], several RBFs with global support are compared. The Multi-quadric biharmonic spline (MQ)

$$\phi_{MQ}(\|\mathbf{x}\|) = \sqrt{\|\mathbf{x}\|^2 + a^2} \quad (2.248)$$

Fig. 2.15: (a) shows different one-dimensional RBFs from (2.248) - (2.250). (b) shows the two-dimensional compactly supported CP of (2.250) with a support radius $r = 1$, where the contourlines mark values of $\phi(\|\mathbf{x}\|) = 0.9, 0.9 \cdot 2^{-1}, 0.9 \cdot 2^{-3}, 0.9 \cdot 2^{-7}$ (from inside to outside). Note that all functions extend beyond the unit intervals and only the compactly supported CP vanishes outside its support radius r .

with parameter $a \in [10^{-5}, 10^{-3}]$ for a domain size of 1, and the thin-plate spline (TPS)

$$\phi_{TPS}(\|\mathbf{x}\|) = \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \ln(\|\mathbf{x}\|) \quad (2.249)$$

are regarded to be the most robust, cost effective, and accurate among the tested types. Furthermore, in [17] different compactly supported RBFs are tested. These lead to a more and more sparse system matrix in (2.245), the smaller the support radius is chosen. However, the support radius has to be chosen at least big enough to include the next couple of neighbors in the surface meshes of A and B of every surface mesh node $\mathbf{x}_{A,i}$. As additional concern, increasing the radius to very large values (compared to the domain of interpolation) leads to a singular system, since then all entries are close to 1. The best results in [17] are obtained with the compact polynomial-based C^2 function (abbreviated by CP in [40]) reading

$$\phi_{CP}(\|\mathbf{x}\|) = \left(1 - \frac{\|\mathbf{x}\|}{r}\right)_+^4 \left(4 \frac{\|\mathbf{x}\|}{r} + 1\right) \quad (2.250)$$

Note that the $+$ in (2.250) is a subindex and realizes the compact support by setting non-positive values of $\left(1 - \frac{\|\mathbf{x}\|}{r}\right)_+^4$ to zero. Thus, the CP function vanishes when $\|\mathbf{x}\| \geq r$, with $r > 0$ being the support radius.

In [40], it is shown that the conservative mapping approach, using the transposed mapping of the displacements for the pressures, does not work in general. Particularly, when higher order basis functions are used in fluid and structure solvers, it creates oscillating mapped pressures and forces. This behavior does not decrease when refining the meshes, as long as no conforming and matching meshes are achieved.

Summary of Data Mapping Methods

In this section, we have seen four data mapping methods. Three of them are based on geometrical projections and interpolations in a submanifold. One performs an interpolation directly in the full spatial dimensions. Three methods employ interpolation methods independent of the solver basis functions and, thus, achieve no consistent mapping of pressures in the conservative approach. These methods are, however, better suited to black box coupling, as they do not require access or knowledge about the solver basis functions.

In the following section, we leave the domain of coupling numerics and focus on surface geometries, which were also required for some of the data mapping methods.

2.5 Geometry Interface for Cartesian Grid Generation

A goal of this work is to bring complex geometries into the PDE solver framework Peano [176, 31]. First, this requires the representation of the geometries in some suitable form. Peano interacts with geometries by issuing positional point and volume queries. Thus, an interface fitting to these queries is a second requirement. As third requirement, fast geometrical algorithms are needed to answer the queries with respect to the used geometry representation. To fit the software design of Peano, the geometry functionality is gathered in an own component called geometry interface henceforth. In this section, we review ways for geometry representation, fast methods to answer the positional queries, and spacetrees to speedup the query processing.

In the following, we first consider some main principles of spacetrees in Section 2.5.1. Then, in Section 2.5.2, we look at the way Peano's computational grids are composed, in order to better understand the origin of the geometrical queries. Efficient methods to answer the geometrical queries are discussed in Section 2.5.3 and, finally, we consider spacetrees to accelerate those queries in Section 2.5.4.

2.5.1 A brief Introduction to Spacetrees

Since spacetrees are used to manage the computational grid in Peano as well as for the geometrical query acceleration, we review important concepts here. To understand the basic principles of spacetrees, we focus on one specific class, namely quadtrees, and generalize to other important classes later. A tutorial review on quadtrees and their applications can be found in [138] and a comprehensive book on (mainly) quadtrees is presented with [139]. We focus on the most important principles in the following, based on the descriptions in [139].

Quadtrees are a class of hierarchical tree data structures that recursively divide the

2.5 Geometry Interface for Cartesian Grid Generation

two-dimensional space into four subtrees, in order to represent a given data type. Quadtrees can be distinguished by the type of data they represent, the rules guiding the recursive division, and their adaptiveness of resolution. The quadtrees of interest here represent the geometry of the computational domain Ω . We consider quadtrees consisting of axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABBs) as cells. Starting from a root cell covering the domain of interest, a recursive divisioning process takes place until the desired resolution is achieved. On division, a parent-cell is tessellated into four equally sized child-cells. An example of such a quadtree with regular resolution is shown in Figure 2.16.

Fig. 2.16: Regular quadtree with three levels. (a) shows the three levels (separated) in spatial representation, while (b) shows the tree representation. Level 0 is the enclosing cell in (a) and the root node in (b). Level 2 contains only leaf nodes (or leaf cells). They are marked by squares in (b), in contrast to internal nodes represented as circles. An ordering of nodes (or cells) can be imposed by a depth-first traversal as indicated in (b) and a lexicographical ordering of the four quadrants of one cell as indicated in (a).

For geometry representation, adaptive resolution trees can have advantages due to their more compact size. There, the subtrees can have varying refinement levels, which allows to, e.g., get a refined representation of the boundaries of the geometry while keeping a coarse(r) representation of its interior and exterior. Figure 2.17 shows an adaptive quadtree approximating a quarter-circle geometry.

So far, we have considered quadtrees in two-dimensional space. In three dimensions, the according analog is called octree and, as the name suggests, the recursive divisioning rule for an octree results in eight subtrees. A further possible generalization are k -partite spacetrees. These apply a splitting into k equally sized subtrees in each dimension, which leads to a total number of k^d subtrees in d -dimensional space. Also, the shape of a spacetree cell must not be rectangular nor axis-aligned, other shapes such as triangles are

Fig. 2.17: Adaptive quadtree approximating the upper left quadrant of a circle (blue). Cells which are intersected by the circle are subdivided until tree level 3. (a) shows the decomposition of the domain into leaf cells. Cells which are completely inside or outside of the circle are colored, while leaf cells intersected by the circle remain white. (b) is the according tree representation with dimension-wise node ordering, where, due to the adaptivity, leaf cells can occur at all levels.

also possible, as long as the recursive divisioning yields an infinitely repetitive pattern. Figure 2.18 shows a few examples of other spacetree types.

Fig. 2.18: Three examples for adaptively refined spacetrees: (a) shows an octree as three-dimensional spacetree, (b) a nonaltree in two dimensions, and (c) a two-dimensional spacetree composed of triangles.

The obtained spacetree can be used in a variety of applications, e.g., as (basis for an) adaptive computational grid, to quickly get positional information about points in the represented domain, or to perform collision detection tests. In the following, we see how spacetrees are used in Peano to represent the computational grid.

2.5.2 Cartesian Grid Discretization of Boundary Represented Geometries

In this section, we review the Cartesian grid discretization used to represent the computational domain in Peano and see how it can be derived from a boundary represented geometry.

2.5 Geometry Interface for Cartesian Grid Generation

First a summary and interpretation of Definitions 2.5 and 2.6 in [176] is given, which describes the core of Peano's Cartesian grid. In Peano, the spatial discretization of the computational domain Ω is formed by an adaptive Cartesian grid Ω_h , represented by a spacetree. A spacetree level index is associated to every spacetree cell c and vertex v . Thus, several vertices with coinciding spatial position can be differentiated by its level index and unambiguous relations between vertices and cells of varying levels can be made. A cell c is adjacent to a vertex v , if v is a corner vertex of that cell and if both are at the same spacetree level. A vertex v in d -dimensional space has, thus, 2^d adjacent cells. A cell c is inside Ω if $c \subseteq \overline{\Omega}$, where $\overline{\Omega}$ means the closure of Ω . Otherwise, it is considered as outside. A vertex is inside, if all adjacent cells are inside. If v 's position is inside and it has mixed type adjacent cells, it is considered a boundary vertex. In all other cases, v is considered outside. These definitions ensure that the discretized computational domain Ω_h is always contained in the computational domain $\Omega_h \subseteq \Omega$. Furthermore, a refinement of cells leads to a monotonous growth of Ω_h towards Ω , as more and more cells fit into the gap between the original Ω_h and Ω .

The (main) grid implementation in Peano is an adaptive Cartesian grid based on a d -dimensional nonalgebraic tree (see Figure 2.18b). Using a spacetree to represent and manage the computational grid has several advantages such as an inherent hierarchy of resolution levels [176, 7, 8]. Important for this work is that the computational grid is created by a recursive subdivision as discussed in the previous section. As a consequence, the geometrical operations performed during the grid generation act on very different spatial scales. Starting from the spacetree root cell which covers the whole computational domain Ω and going down to the leaf cells that need to be small enough to guarantee a good numerical accuracy for the PDE to be solved. The geometrical operations performed during the grid generation are further discussed in the following Section 2.5.3. Figure 2.19 shows an example Peano grid with spacetree structure in two dimensions.

The implementation of the representation of the computational domain Ω is separated from the implementation of the computational grid Ω_h in Peano for reasons of modularity and flexibility. A geometry interface is used to couple the two implementations. It mainly consists of inside/outside tests for volumes in form of axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABBs) and of tests for points. The AABB tests are used to test the position of grid cells as well as grid vertices with environment. The point tests are used to determine the position of grid vertices. Thus, to create a computational grid Ω_h through the geometry interface, the implementation needs to answer a sequence of positional volume and point queries [104]. This requires a suitable representation of Ω and fast algorithms for computing the answers to the positional queries.

The computational domain Ω can be represented by a method from solid modeling, which provides an unambiguous classification of every point in space to be either inside or outside of Ω . Several geometry representation methods such as constructive solid geometry (CSG) or boundary representation (BRep) are given in [139]. Relevant for this work is the BRep which represents the geometry by its surface, modeled by a topology of oriented faces, edges, and vertices. A big variety of choices for the faces exists,

Fig. 2.19: Computational domain Ω with boundary $\delta\Omega$ (in blue) discretized by a Peano adaptive Cartesian grid Ω_h . In this example, a spacetree cell is refined only when it is intersected by $\delta\Omega$. The refinement of cells in current versions of Peano is handled slightly different. There, refinements are triggered based on grid nodes. If one of the adjacent cells of a grid node intersects $\delta\Omega$, all adjacent cells are refined. The Peano spacetree covers the whole domain Ω , but only its inside cells (colored in red) contribute to Ω_h .

ranging from linear elements such as planes to elements with higher approximation order. The big advantage of the lower order elements is that geometrical operations such as intersections can be performed much more easily. In this work, a polygon BRep is used in two-dimensional space and a triangulation in three-dimensional space. The geometrical queries, thus, need to be answered with respect to these BRep elements.

Note that the overall efficiency of creating the adaptive Cartesian grid in Peano does not only depend on an efficient implementation of the geometry interface, but also on the efficient usage of the information gained from each query. For example, the hierarchical structuring of the spacetrees employed in Peano can be used to cache inside and outside information for child cells in order to avoid further queries for those cells. This topic is, however, not part of this work. It is treated, e.g., in [104]. In the following, we go into more details of the positional geometrical queries.

2.5.3 Geometrical Queries

In order to construct the Peano computational grid, geometric queries regarding the position of points and volumes (in the form of AABBs) with respect to the BRep have to be answered. Three positional predicates are used to classify the query results: a point or volume can be inside (IN), outside (OUT), or neither inside nor outside (NIO) with respect to the BRep of the computational domain Ω . Since the BRep often is an approximation of the computational domain, we denote it by S to distinguish it from Ω . δS denotes the boundary of the BRep approximating $\delta\Omega$, accordingly. For some

geometrical object G (point or volume), the query tests with respect to S can be defined by set operations as

$$\text{IN}(G; S) := G \cap S = G, \quad (2.251)$$

$$\text{OUT}(G; S) := G \cap S = \emptyset, \quad (2.252)$$

$$\text{NIO}(G; S) := \neg \text{IN} \wedge \neg \text{OUT}. \quad (2.253)$$

Note that these definitions make sense for point queries only, if G and S are open. Then, a point is NIO if it is located at δS . In the following, an efficient intersection test between to geometrical objects is reviewed. Further details on the realization of point queries are given in Section 4.4.2.

The methodology presented here first performs an intersection test of the AABB with S . If no intersection is found, the AABB must be either inside or outside of S , which can be determined by using a point query with any point in the AABB. A computationally fast way to perform the intersection test is by using the separating axis theorem (SAT, by Herrman Minkowski, here according to [54]). The SAT says: if, for two compact and convex geometrical objects, there exists a line where the projection intervals of the objects do not overlap, then the objects do not overlap and the line is called a separating axis. Figure 2.20 illustrates the concept. We can represent a compact and

Fig. 2.20: Illustration of the separating axis theorem (SAT). Two compact and convex geometrical objects C_0 and C_1 do not overlap if their projection intervals I^{C_0} and I^{C_1} on a line (as in (2.254)) do not overlap according to (2.255). In this case, the line is called a separating axis.

convex geometrical object by the set C of contained points $\mathbf{x} \in C$. Given a line with direction \mathbf{d} , the projection interval I of C on the line can be written as

$$I = [\lambda_{\min}(\mathbf{d}), \lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{d})] = [\min\{\mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbf{x} : \mathbf{x} \in C\}, \max\{\mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbf{x} : \mathbf{x} \in C\}]. \quad (2.254)$$

Two such objects C_0 and C_1 are separated, i.e., they do not intersect nor touch, if

$$\text{sep}(C_0, C_1, \mathbf{d}) := (\lambda_{\min}^{C_0}(\mathbf{d}) > \lambda_{\max}^{C_1}(\mathbf{d})) \vee (\lambda_{\max}^{C_0}(\mathbf{d}) < \lambda_{\min}^{C_1}(\mathbf{d})). \quad (2.255)$$

The SAT itself does not describe a complete intersection test, since it does not specify the directions \mathbf{d} to be used and makes no statement about when two objects do overlap.

By geometrical considerations, it can be shown that for the intersection of two convex polyhedra,⁹ two sets of axes need to be tested. First, all face normals define possible separation axes. Second, all mutually different pairs of edges, where one edge is taken from the first and the other from the second geometry, define an axis by their cross-product. To perform the intersection test of (2.255) for the two sets of axes suffices to find out whether the two objects intersect. The presented method also works for testing intersection with non-solid linear objects, such as isolated triangles. In two dimensions, only the face normals need to be taken into account. With this, we can now formulate a complete intersection test. Given a sufficient set of directions $D(B, s)$ for a convex polyhedron B and every surface element $s \in S$, we get

$$\text{NIO}(B, S) := \bigwedge_{s_i \in \delta S} \bigwedge_{\mathbf{d}_j \in D(B, s_i)} \neg \text{sep}(B, s_i, \mathbf{d}_j). \quad (2.256)$$

Directions \mathbf{d} that can be transferred into each other by a scaling are equivalent in D and, hence, need to be checked only once. In the process of testing all axes, an early drop-out happens at first occurrence of a separating axis in (2.256).

A fast SAT-based three-dimensional triangle-AABB overlapping test is described in [3]. There, three groups of tests are distinguished. Before performing the tests, the coordinate system is shifted such that the AABB center is located at the coordinate origin. The first group of tests is performed with respect to the AABB face normals, which coincide to the three unit vectors of the Cartesian coordinate system. The projections in (2.254) are, hence, trivial to compute. In the second group, the triangle plane normal is used as axis. The third group consists of nine tests from the combinations of all triangle edges with AABB edges. Only three different AABB edges need to be considered here, since all other edges are in coinciding directions. This ordering of groups is measured to be computationally fastest in [3].

The computational complexity of one point or volume query is $O(M)$, if M is the sum of triangles, edges, and faces in the BRep. For N queries, a quadratic runtime complexity $O(NM)$ results. In the next section, spacetrees are considered to speedup the whole process of grid generation.

2.5.4 Spacetrees to Accelerate Geometrical Queries

We have discussed positional point and volume queries used in order to create an adaptive Cartesian grid. The runtime complexity of a naive grid generation process with geometrical queries for each Cartesian cell to be created is $O(NM)$. Here, N is the number of grid cells to be created and M the number of geometrical primitives in the BRep S of the computational domain Ω . As mentioned above, this work only focuses on

⁹A polyhedron is a three-dimensional solid geometry consisting of linear faces and edges. Representatives are, e.g., cubes, tetrahedrons, or pyramids.

the implementation of the geometry interface and, thus, has no influence on the complexity induced by the number of queries M . However, the queries themselves can be accelerated and this is the context in which we consider spacetrees in this section.

On an abstract level, we use spacetrees to limit the number of features to a relevant subset for a given operation. In our context, the operations are the geometrical queries and the features of relevance are the BRep elements close to a geometrical query. If the number of BRep elements can be kept to a constant small amount for each query, the computational complexity of the overall grid generation can be reduced to sub-quadratic complexity. In literature, spacetrees have been used in a number of different cases to speed up grid generation [8, 158, 119]. Often the resulting spacetree is not directly used as computational grid, but an unstructured grid is created, taking the spacetree as a basis [158].

As first step in using a spacetree for query acceleration, the spacetree needs to be created and the BRep elements distributed to the spacetree cells. In [92], an efficient algorithm for creating an octree representation from a BRep is described. During the octree creation, octree cells are divided only when classified as NIO according to (2.253) and until a certain resolution is reached. Additionally, the BRep elements are divided at intersecting octree faces, such that each (divided) element is contained in one octree cell only. The algorithm uses an explicit representation of octree cell faces, edges, and vertices. These entities are shared between different octree cells (e.g., an inner face is shared by two octants) and carry positional predicates (IN, OUT, or NIO) as the cells do. To classify an octree cell's position as IN, OUT, or NIO, the octree cell's faces δO are classified with respect to the BRep S and the BRep's faces δS with respect to the octree cell O . The classification of a face F with respect to a solid S is denoted by $\text{ClassFace}(F, S)$ and is defined as

$$\text{ClassFace}(F; S) := \begin{cases} \text{IN}, & \text{if } F \cap S = F \\ \text{ON}, & \text{if } F \cap \delta S = F \\ \text{OUT}, & \text{if } F \cap S = \emptyset \\ \text{NIO}, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (2.257)$$

When F consists of several faces, an according list of positional predicates is returned from ClassFace . The classification of an octree cell can then be written as

$$\text{IN}(O; S) := \begin{cases} \text{ClassFace}(\delta O; S) = \text{IN}/\text{ON} \\ \text{ClassFace}(\delta S; O) = \text{OUT}/\text{ON} \end{cases} \quad (2.258)$$

$$\text{OUT}(O; S) := \begin{cases} \text{ClassFace}(\delta O; S) = \text{OUT}/\text{ON} \\ \text{ClassFace}(\delta S; O) = \text{OUT}/\text{ON} \end{cases} \quad (2.259)$$

An additional predicate NIO is defined analog to (2.253).

Classification (2.257) contributes most to the costs of setting up the spacetree, since it consists of expensive intersection operations. A significant reduction of the number of

face classifications, hence, leads to a significant reduction of the overall octree creation time. This can be achieved by cleverly using the positional information of the octree cell entities. The proposed algorithm in [92] classifies all geometric entities of an octree cell bottom up, i.e., starting with the vertices, continuing with the edges, faces, and finally treating the cell. Due to the explicit representation of the geometric entities, a once classified vertex, edge, or face can be reused in all adjacent octree cells. Additionally, an entity classified as IN or OUT can be subdivided into subentities with same classification directly. By doing so, the number of face classifications can be reduced significantly during the octree creation. A pointer data structure is used to manage the explicitly represented spacetime cells, faces, edges, and vertices. Similarly, the BRep elements are stored in pointer lists that are associated to the corresponding spacetime cells.

In this work, a similar algorithm to efficiently build up a spacetime data structure is developed. This algorithm, described in Section 4.4, uses an alternative approach for avoiding unnecessary octree cell classification, based on the classification of adjacent octree cells. Also, it does not intersect BRep elements to achieve a unique association, since this is not necessary when the BRep elements are explicitly used to represent the computational grid boundary as in Peano.

After creating the octree and distributing the BRep elements to the octree cells, incoming geometrical queries can be accelerated. This step consists of the association of queries with spacetime cells and the derivation of positional predicates to answer the queries. The realization of such accelerating algorithms for geometrical queries within this work is presented in Section 4.4.

2.6 Existing Coupling Software for Partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction

In the recent sections we have seen a survey of approaches and techniques on how to solve FSI scenarios in a partitioned way. We will now look at a brief overview of existing software, which have implemented a smaller or larger part of the aforementioned methods using different software design approaches. Please note that the aim of this section is not to evaluate these software packages. Most of the information given here is taken from publications, user manuals, or web pages of the presented software. Without really using a software, only a partial impression can be obtained. The choice of coupling software described in the following section is limited to relevant ones for partitioned simulation of FSI scenarios. Problem solving environments for monolithic simulations or multiphysics packages have been omitted here.

2.6.1 Software Projects

MpCCI [2, 91, 67] is the commercial standard coupling environment for partitioned multiphysics simulations. It is one of the first successful coupling libraries for partitioned multiphysics simulations and originates in the fusion of the two older libraries COCOLIB [179] and GRISLi Coupling-Interface [16]. While its main focus seems to be the coupling of commercial codes by providing ready-to-use adapters, it also offers the possibility to integrate a C application programming Interface (API) into a solver without existing adapter. MpCCI uses its own coupling mesh representation, to be provided by a coupled solver, with a variety of different mesh elements. For data mapping, a library based on the coupling meshes offers several interpolation methods, ranging from nearest neighbor to shape function based interpolation and a simple conservative mapping. A coupling supervisor program is the central control instance for a coupled simulation with MpCCI. Communication between a coupled solver and the server is done via sockets and parallel solvers as well as a parallel running server are supported. MpCCI does not include equation coupling schemes directly, they need to be implemented into the solver code. While a constant (or decreasing) underrelaxation is built-in for coupling value iterates, no implicit convergence acceleration is provided.

The **Model Coupling Toolkit (MKT)** [100] is an open-source Fortran-based software library to couple several simulation components for multiphysics simulations. The application background of the software is climate simulation, but the library is written in a generic way. There is no coupling control logic implemented into the MKT in form of a supervisor or similar. Instead, each solver has to implement a control and communication scheme to other coupled solvers using a message passing like API. Particular importance is put on simulations with parallel components and scalable data mapping between non-matching meshes. Spatial and temporal data mapping routines are provided to map data between non-matching meshes and non-synchronized solver time levels.

FSI*ce (fluid-structure interaction coupling environment) [26, 28, 25, 72] is an FSI coupling environment developed in-house. It was the first attempt to include the equation coupling schemes in the coupling software and to enable a plug-in mechanism for coupled solvers. FSI*ce consists of a C/C++ library for communication, data mapping, and coupling control. A central coupling supervisor program steers the overall coupled simulation as for MpCCI. The solvers are treated as servers that have to compute the commands of the coupling supervisor, seen as client. This approach is, hence, also referred to as client-server coupling approach. Communication between the solvers and the supervisor is done either via sockets or by MPI (including sub-communicators). Solvers can run in parallel, however, there is no communication concept on how to connect more than one solver process to the supervisor. FSI*ce is able to perform three-dimensional FSI simulations in combination with a fixed-grid flow solver, where an additional triangular surface mesh is used to provide geometry information to the flow solver. The triangular surface mesh has to be created from the surface representation of the struc-

ture solver. Data is mapped from the flow solver grid nodes to the surface mesh by orthogonal projections and linear interpolations. The mapping supports consistency and conservation. Spacetree partitionings are used to speed up geometry creation and data mapping queries. An explicit CSS scheme and an implicit block-GS scheme are supported, while no convergence acceleration scheme is implemented for the latter.

CoMA (coupling for multiphysics analysis) [70, 69] has been created with similar goals than FSI*ce. It is written in C++ and offers an API for that language. The coupling supervisor is able to deal with parallel running solvers by using MPI subcommunicators. Each parallel solver process coupled to the supervisor is represented as entity in the supervisor. The coupling surface mesh is distributed among these entities. Nearest-neighbor and nearest-projection based data mappings with shape function interpolation for non-matching meshes are offered. For equation coupling, the explicit CSS scheme as well as an implicit block-Gauss Seidel scheme with the Aitken relaxation and the IQN-ILS scheme are implemented.

Tango [42] is a C++ coupling tool that focuses on implicit coupling convergence acceleration schemes for black box solvers. It uses a central coupling supervisor, and MPI to spawn the solver processes. C++ solver codes adapt to Tango by implementing a C++ interface class, i.e., a framework-like strategy. File-based communication is used to adapt non-C++ codes. For data mapping, nearest neighbor, nearest projection, and radial basis function mappings are provided. Data mapping is done by using mesh nodes only, i.e., no connectivity information has to be provided by the solvers. For the nearest projection mapping, a number of closest nodes is selected to construct a surface on the fly. To avoid wrong node selection for thin geometries and corners, the provided nodes need to be partitioned into face groups. The expensive coupling supervisor operations are shared memory parallelized and solvers can run in parallel, too.

FLECS [125] is another coupling tool using a client-server approach with coupling supervisor. It is written in C, and provides a rather low-level message passing-like API. The coupling server communicates to the solvers using MPI, with separate startup and connection using MPI ports. Since the solvers and the supervisor are automatically partitioned into different MPI communication spaces, the solvers can be run in parallel. The coupling supervisor includes support for data mapping, where a nearest neighbor and a radial basis function mapping are implemented. A shared memory parallelization of the mapping methods in the supervisor is available. Equation coupling schemes are not included in FLECS. While one supervisor can deal with a pair of coupled solvers only, several supervisors can be run at the same time to connect more solvers.

Uintah [129] is a coupling framework written in C++ and is developed within the C-SAFE project. Its aim are highly parallel simulations of multi-physics problems based on structured meshes and particle methods. The basic idea of Uintah is that simulation components and their dependencies can be represented as a task graph, where each node represents a computation task and each edge represents data dependencies between the tasks. A scheduler can analyze the dependencies and trigger the computations in a

suitable way to obtain maximal parallelism. A data warehouse abstraction provides all required coupling data to a computation component. Solutions are provided for data communication and parallel I/O, as well as dynamic load balancing. A simulation scenarios including dependencies is configured by XML. Typical partitioned coupling tasks such as interpolation and equation coupling are not directly supported, but can be integrated in a reusable way as own computation components. A simulation with Uintah includes a coupling supervisor, which acts as scheduler for the computation tasks.

The **Component Template Library (CTL)** has been used in [111] to create a coupling tool for FSI. It is a middleware that is meant to connect distributed software components by remote procedure calls. An interface definition language is used to define the coupling API by C preprocessor commands, which can be automatically converted into different programming languages such as C/C++, Fortran, Java, or Python. The CTL does not provide any FSI related functionality.

2.6.2 Categorization of Approaches

In this section, we find categorizations for the above reviewed coupling software. The obtained categories will be used in the next chapter to motivate the development of a new coupling software.

First of all, we can distinguish *library* and *framework* type of approaches. While in the library approach, a given API has to be used at appropriate places in the code to be coupled, the framework approach predefines a set of methods to be implemented with proper solver functionality. While the former approach allows for a simple integration into an existing structure of code, the latter more clearly predefines a certain structure and form of functionality to be implemented. Coupling tools using the library approach are MpCCI, FSI*ce, CoMA, the MKT, and FLECS. The framework approach is used in Tango, Uintah, and the CTL.

A further categorization is that into *low-level* and *high-level* coupling APIs. In a low-level API, message passing type functionality has to be used in a solver code, the coupling control might not be given as ready-to-use, and other type of functionality is given in rudimentary form only, to be combined by the user in a suitable way. A high-level API might completely hide communication and other coupling methods from a user code. The actual coupling functionality performed within a high-level method is configured outside of the code. While a low-level API gives more freedom on how to implement the coupling, a high-level API reduces the integration efforts and can increase inter-operability of different codes. Low-level API coupling tools are the MKT, the CTL, and FLECS. Intermediate-level APIs are offered by MpCCI, FSI*ce, and CoMA. A high-level API is provided in Tango and Uintah.

Finally, a coupling software can be categorized into application *generic* or *specific*. The origin of a coupling software is often found to be the lack of a suitable one for a given

2 Overview of Approaches to Partitioned Fluid-Structure Interaction

application. As a result of limited manpower and experience, a tool centered around a specific and limited set of solver codes and their needs is created. Using an application specific coupling software in a different context can induce incompatibilities. On the other hand, too much genericity can increase the efforts of tailoring the functionality for a specific application case. It is not easy to assign a software to one of the categories, since there are different levels of genericity. One measure can be the compatibility with different types of programming languages. Another one could be the range of coupling schemes and communication forms supported. A third measure could be the type of compute platform a software can be employed, e.g., a personal workstation, local cluster of compute nodes, or some remote supercomputer. A classification is omitted here, and the reader is left to make an own choice.

3 preCICE – A Software Environment for Black Box Coupling

In this chapter, the simulation coupling environment preCICE (precise Code Interaction Coupling Environment) is introduced, which has been developed within this work. preCICE has been created to facilitate the partitioned coupling approach for surface coupled problems. Its focus is on the coupling of existing black box simulation software and its main application area within this work is fluid-structure interaction (FSI). It provides ready to use solutions for the main problems occurring in partitioned coupling and supports immersed boundary type solvers by a surface geometry representation along with a positional query functionality. Being a software environment, preCICE consists of a whole set of tools. However, the main part of preCICE is a conventional software library and the following sections concentrate on software engineering aspects related to that library. Details of the implemented functionality are discussed in Chapter 4.

We consider the software design goals of preCICE in Section 3.1. From the design goals, we derive the requirements on the software in Section 3.2. Next, we evaluate important design decisions and the eligibility to develop preCICE in Section 3.3. Section 3.4 is more technical and we discuss deployment schemes used at runtime. Considerations of the programming interface are presented in Section 3.5 and the software architecture as well as internal structure of the preCICE library is shown in Section 3.6. Finally, an evaluation of the achieved goals is given in Section 3.7.

3.1 Software Design Goals

The main software design goals for preCICE are given here, using a rather abstract formulation. These goals are translated into more concrete requirements in the next Section 3.2. The main software design goals of preCICE are summarized in the following points:

1. Minimize the effort of preparing an existing solver for partitioned coupling.
2. Maximize the coupling flexibility coming with the partitioned approach.
3. Provide a surface geometry interface with query functionality for fixed-grid solvers.
4. Provide a maintainable and extensible platform for research environments.

For a developer of partitioned FSI simulation software, the benefit of using a dedicated coupling software is measured by how much it can reduce the overall efforts. The first design goal induces, on the one hand, the need for a full feature set for partitioned coupling. On the other hand, it means to keep the integration efforts of the provided functionality into a solver code as low as possible. Particular importance is put on the preparation of existing solvers, which already have a given source code structure.

The second design goal addresses the possibility to flexibly exchange simulation codes that have been adapted once. This flexibility enables to have a pool of ready-to-use solvers, which can be employed in any (physically meaningful) combination. Thus, the capabilities of different solvers can be optimally employed for a given problem by choosing the best combination of solvers available. This plug-in capability can be particularly handy for commercial software, which is usually coupled by an adapting piece of code. The adapter connects the coupling software with the simulation software by using their respective application programming interfaces (APIs). A once adapted commercial solver can be reused by different groups when providing the adapter code and can be combined with any solver that is also adapted to the coupling software.

The third design goal is an additional non-coupling related objective of this work. A surface geometry representation has to be provided to an in-house fixed-grid flow solver based on Cartesian grids (described in Section 5.1.1). Since this functionality also overlaps with other coupling functionality such as data mapping, the geometry interface can be integrated into the coupling software and a common code base can be shared. Considerations related to the geometry interface functionality will show up in the following sections side by side with coupling functionality.

The last design goal comes at no surprise. Since the use of *preCICE* is in a research environment, naturally there will be the wish to extend its functionality by new approaches. A typical end of a research software is the decision to rewrite it from scratch, since maintenance costs would be too high otherwise. This is often due to the limited amount of structuring, lack of automated tests, and documentation employed during its development.

3.2 Requirements Analysis

We have seen the design goals of *preCICE* in Section 3.1. In the following, we derive from that more concrete requirements. To structure them, they are split into functional (Section 3.2.1) and non-functional requirements (Section 3.2.2).

3.2.1 Functional Requirements

The functional requirements listed here prescribe *what* the coupling software should be able to do. They do not say how the functionality should be implemented, which is topic of the next section. We consider the coupling of the partitioned equations, the mapping of coupling data for non-matching meshes, the communication of data between solvers, the coupling control, and the surface geometry interface.

Equation Coupling. To couple the partitioned equations, as discussed in Section 2.3, is the most important functional requirement, since every partitioned FSI simulation depends on it. Explicit coupling schemes have to be provided to efficiently compute FSI problems with weak interactions. Implicit schemes with convergence accelerating techniques have to be provided to obtain an acceptable overall performance for problems that exhibit instabilities due to strong interactions. For large problems, expensive operations in, e.g., convergence acceleration routines, need to be parallelized.

Data Mapping. For the spatial coupling of solvers with non-matching meshes, data mapping schemes have to be employed, as discussed in Section 2.4. In FSI problems, data are mapped between discrete surface representations. Employed mapping schemes have to pertain the accuracy order of the computed values and have to fulfill additional constraints such as consistency and conservation of overall values. For large problems with a large number of coupled degrees of freedom, the data mappings need to be parallelized.

Data Communication. In most cases the flow and structure solvers will be available as separate executable programs. In order to exchange data values and state information between the programs at runtime, a suitable communication scheme is required. For non-parallel execution, the communication consists of block-wise exchange of data between the solver timesteps or iterations. When parallel codes are involved, data need to be synchronized and gathered in a possibly asynchronous and efficient way in order to not to diminish the speedup obtained for the solvers.

Coupling Control. Since the coupled solvers are only sub-components of an overall partitioned simulation, they do not have all information necessary to control the simulation. Thus, a coupling control instance is necessary, which gathers coupling state information and steers the simulation. The control instance decides on what kind of computation step has to be done next by a solver. Furthermore, it is responsible to trigger synchronized events such as writing output on the convergence of a timestep or writing a simulation checkpoint for later restart. The necessary control depends on the complexity of the coupling schemes applied and must be scalable on demand.

Geometry Interface. A solid geometry representation has to be provided for Cartesian fixed-grid type solvers in the form of a BRep. Spatial queries have to be answered efficiently to determine the position of points and volumes relative to the BRep geometry. The surface elements have to be able to carry material parameters such as boundary identifiers to distinguish different surfaces and sub-surfaces intersecting, e.g., with dis-

cretization cells of a solver. The surface geometry must be readable from a suitable file format, as well as being provided by a coupled solver for FSI simulation.

3.2.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements give constraints on *how* the functionality should be implemented and which qualities it should have. We consider coupling flexibility, minimal invasiveness, maintainability and expandability, as well as portability.

Coupling Flexibility. The partitioned coupling approach offers the inherent capability of flexibly exchanging coupled solvers. While this is a basic requirement to be able to build a generic coupling library at all, certain requirements have to be met in order to use the full potential of that flexibility. The most important one is to hide the specific choice of coupling functionality used by a solver for a specific simulation scenario behind an API. The actual functionality chosen must be configurable at simulation runtime by some form of user input files and/or scripts. The API of the library must be such that the configuration requires no changes in the code of the simulation programs once adapted for coupling. Furthermore, the coupling library has to be compatible with different programming languages typically used in scientific computing.

Minimal Invasiveness. To integrate the API of the coupling library should require only minimal changes to a solver code. This requirement is supported by treating the solvers as black boxes with minimal access to solver internals. As a consequence, equation coupling schemes should use only input and output coupling values from the solvers. Data mapping schemes should use as little information of the solver surface discretization as possible, by, e.g., working with data points only. As for the coupling flexibility requirement, minimal invasiveness is fostered by an encapsulation of functionality into the coupling library. Since the level of invasion necessary depends on the coupling functionality used, there should be the possibility to use only those parts of the library's API which are necessary to enable a certain functionality.

Maintainability and Expandability. Typical research software is written in a way that scientific results can be obtained with small investments into software development. This is fine as long as the overall software stays small and its use is limited to a certain objective and time frame. For large scale projects, this however leads to unmanageable software with growing efforts put into maintenance of the codes. For a library developed as generic coupling tool and to be used with a variety of different codes, the aspects of maintenance and extension have to be considered in a software engineering manner. Using state of the art software design techniques to create a hierarchical component structure and clear interfaces for each component helps to keep future development costs low. Proper documentation of source code gives a similar contribution. An automated test harness with unit and integration tests is essential to prevent the intrusion of bugs in the course of extensions. Even with tests, it happens from time to time that a bug has managed to hide. Proper logging traces at entrance and exit of used methods and

runtime error tests by assertions are a very vital help to track them down.

Portability. Scientific computing environments are known to be rather heterogeneous. This is, on the one hand, due to the variety of used Linux distributions with different library environments. On the other hand, it is driven by the need for large parallel machines which are operated through custom environments with limited choice of compilers and libraries installed. Thus, a software intended for such an environment has to be carefully augmented with third-party libraries it builds on and also with immature (or not wide spread) programming language features used. As possible workaround, certain problematic features have to offer the possibility to be omitted when building the software on a critical environment.

3.3 Design Decisions and Eligibility

In this section, the requirements analysis and the categorizations of existing coupling software approaches are used to draw some major design decisions for preCICE in Section 3.3.1. Considering the requirements and the drawn design decisions as a good choice to achieve the desired design goals, we will see that none of the here considered existing coupling software can be considered as an optimal tool for partitioned coupling of black box solvers in Section 3.3.2.

3.3.1 Design Decisions

Taking into account the requirements formulated in Section 3.2 and the categorizations of coupling software done in Section 2.6.2, the following design decisions are made:

1. Use a library approach (in favor of a framework approach).
2. Provide a high-level coupling API.
3. Employ generic concepts as much as design goal 1 (Section 3.1) is not contradicted.
4. Use C++ as programming language.

The first design decision supports the goal of minimizing development efforts to couple existing codes. A framework approach can require solver code restructurings, when it does not comply to the interface implied by the framework. For commercial codes with no access to the source code, the only possibility in case of mismatch is to convert the framework interface into a library-like interface.

The second design decision supports the first and second design goal (Section 3.1). A high-level API is simpler to integrate into a simulation code than a low-level API and encapsulates coupling logic to a higher degree. It, thus, can speed up the adaption of a code compared to a low-level API. Additionally, it has less potential to be misused in some unwanted way, since more logic is hidden from the user.

The third design decision widens the spectrum of applications the coupling software can be used for. A potential pitfall when trying to write a software in a generic way is to be too generic, which results in a waste of time for goals which turn out to be of little significance. The level of employed genericity should also not contradict with the design goal of minimal coupling efforts. In this work, the focus on surface coupled problems can be a meaningful generalization, since the spectrum of methods used is comparable.

Design decision number four enables the use of object-oriented programming techniques, which can lead to lower maintainance and extension costs when used properly. Furthermore, compatibility with other typical programming languages used in simulation codes, such as C or Fortran, is given in principle.

3.3.2 Eligibility

By considering the above design goals and the derived requirements and design decisions, we now look at the eligibility to write another coupling software for partitioned simulations. Writing a coupling software is no new idea, as can be seen in Section 2.6. In particular, in the presence of an already existing in-house developed library, namely *FSI*ce*, it is interesting to see why *preCICE* has its own justification.

Table 3.1 shows an attempt to rate the coupling tools presented in Section 2.6 according to different categories. The criteria used for the rating are the design goals, requirements, and design decisions stated above. Note that the rating does not reflect actual usage experience, but is based on theoretical considerations only. The rating shows, that no existing coupling software really shines in all categories. Particularly in the API category existing software shows possibilities for improvement. This is due to the fact that many tools are offering a message passing like API. Exceptions are *Tango* and *Uintha*, but these have a framework-like interface, which is not ideal for existing solvers.

One requirement in this work is to provide a surface geometry interface for a Cartesian mesh fixed-grid flow solver. This requirement is not reflected in Table 3.1, since it is not a typical goal for a coupling software. The only software offering such an interface is the in-house developed *FSI*ce*. Within *FSI*ce*, an octree geometrical data structure is used to construct Cartesian grids for a specific in-house flow solver. The currently used type of grids is based on a three-partitioning instead of a two-partitioning per dimension done in an octree. The geometry interface in *preCICE* is constructed such that it deals with arbitrary point and hexahedral geometric queries, independent of the actual structuring of cells in the solver. This guarantees a much higher level of flexibility with different kinds of Cartesian mesh based solvers.

Summarizing the above findings, we can see that there are coupling tools which have particular strengths in some of the required areas of interest. There is, however, no software available which fully uses the potential of the partitioned approach and offers

Software	Equation	Mapping	Comm.	Control	Flexibility	HPC	API
MpCCI	o	+	+	+	o	++	o
MKT	--	+	o	--	--	+	-
FSI*ce	o	o	+	+	+	o	+
CoMA	+	+	o	+	+	+	o
Tango	++	++	o	+	+	+	o
FLECS	o	++	o	+	o	+	o
Uintha	-	-	o	+	-	++	o
CTL	--	--	+	--	--	-	-

Tab. 3.1: Rating of coupling software with respect to the design goals, requirements, and design decisions done in this work. The range of ratings is, ordered from lowest to highest: --, -, o, +, ++. Category "Equation" rates the equation coupling schemes, "Mapping" the data mapping routines, "Comm." the communication mechanisms, "Flexibility" is a measure for coupling flexibility (as in the non-functional requirement), "HPC" means the ability to perform parallel simulations, and "API" the form of the application programming interface to be integrated into existing open- and closed-source solvers.

it in an optimal interface. Particularly, there is no external software offering a surface geometry interface capability. The motivation of preCICE is, thus, to take up the best ideas of its predecessor FSI*ce and to make it a more full-featured and flexible tool for surface coupled problems.

3.4 Deployment Schemes

In this section, the approach of preCICE to the runtime deployment of simulation components is shown, i.e., the assignment of the involved software components to physical and executable programs. One of the main design goals of preCICE is to maximize the flexibility coming with the partitioned approach. To achieve this goal, a proper decoupling of simulation codes has to be done. In the following Section 3.4.1, possible schemes are analyzed with respect to this goal. Another point of interest is the deployment of components in parallel simulations, discussed in Section 3.4.2.

To illustrate the proposed approaches, component and deployment diagrams are used, which show the connections of software components and executed programs. Within such diagrams, three-dimensional boxes represent running program instances, while two-dimensional boxes represent (selected) software components of the programs. Solid line connections represent using-relationships between logical components, while dashed line connections represent remote connections between running programs.

3.4.1 General Considerations

A peer-to-peer approach is used in *preCICE* for connecting the partitioned simulation programs. In the following, the characteristics and differences between this approach and its alternative, the client-server approach, are discussed.

The *client-server approach* is a commonly used solver connection scheme. It is shown in Figure 3.1. Within that approach, an additional program is used as central communication instance. All solvers are connected to this central instance by some form of remote communication. Data are mediated from solver A to solver B via the central instance, i.e., there is no direct communication between the solver programs. To couple the solvers with the central instance, an additional adapter component is used, which can be a framework or library. A solver code interfaces with the API of the adapter only and does not know about the central instance or other coupled solver(s).

In *preCICE*, the solver connection scheme used is a *peer-to-peer approach* as shown in Figure 3.2. Here, the central instance is omitted and the solver programs are communicating directly with each other. An adapter component is used as in the client-server approach. Now, however, it also contains the coupling functionality of the central coupler used in the client-server approach. Since early approaches on coupling software employed this approach with low-level API adapters mainly, this approach is commonly assumed to have the drawback of not decoupling the solver programs enough to enable flexible exchanges of solvers. We will see in the following that the peer-to-peer approach enables to hide the solver codes from each other in the same way as the client-server approach and that the central coupling instance has, in fact, little to do with the decoupling of the solver codes.

Fig. 3.1: Deployment diagram of a (library) client-server approach. A central coupler program is used to mediate data between the coupled solvers. Each solver program consists of a solver code component using a coupling adapter. In a framework approach, the adapter would use the solver code, i.e., the uses-relationship is inverted. The coupling logic is put in the adapter and the central coupler. The responsibilities of the central coupler program can range from being a pure data repository to a control instance for the whole coupled simulation (also called supervisor). Typical instances of this approach are MpCCI, FSI*ce, CoMA, Tango, and FLECS.

The decoupling of a solver code means that there are no dependencies on a specific other solver code. Of course, within the environment of FSI there are certain premises, e.g., on which coupling data is expected by a flow or structure solver. The decoupling of a

Fig. 3.2: Deployment diagram of a (library) peer-to-peer approach as used in preCICE. Coupled solver programs directly exchange data between each other. Each solver program is composed of a solver code component using a coupling adapter. In a framework approach, the adapter would use the solver code, i.e., the uses-relationship is inverted. The coupling logic is put in the adapter components. The responsibilities of the adapters can range from being pure communication interfaces to full control instances. Typical instances of this approach are the MKT and the CTL.

solver code actually happens through the coupling adapter component. It is primarily a logical decoupling, while the physical decoupling into distinct programs is an orthogonal issue. The API of the adapter has to be such that there is no direct knowledge of what is taking place behind. The used coupling functionality needs to be transparent to the solver code. Whether the communicated data is transferred to the coupling partner by a detour of a central coupling component or directly, is not of importance from a solver's perspective. Similarly, the location of coupling data at runtime does not matter to a solver, as long as it is available (fast enough) on demand. A coupled solver also does not need to know if the transferred data is mapped onto another mesh, or post-processed to accelerate convergence of coupling iterations. Whether all this information can be hidden from a solver is dependent on the API of the coupling adapter, which is the topic of Section 3.5.

We have seen that a solver decoupling is possible with both, the client-server and the peer-to-peer approaches. Now, we want to look at some differences in the two approaches. Implementation wise, the client-server approach requires to duplicate coupling logic in the adapter and central coupler. The events of communication, e.g., have to be matched accordingly in adapter and central coupler. The peer-to-peer approach only requires one logic in the adapter, which has similar complexity as that in the client-server central component. Looking at communication, the client-server approach requires two send and receive operations to transfer data from one solver to another, since the central coupler component acts as mediator of data. The peer-to-peer approach directly transmits data between source and target, which halves communication. From a data synchronization point-of-view, the client-server approach might look favorable, since it gathers all coupling data and information in a central place. However, the usual data deployment scheme in the client-server approach duplicates the coupling information in the coupled solver programs at runtime for efficiency reasons. Similarly, in the peer-to-peer approach, a coupled solver also knows the coupling data of its coupling partner. Coupling data output can be done by one peer and, thus, include all coupled data. The next section discusses possible deployment schemes when running intra-parallel simulations.

3.4.2 Parallel Deployment

When a simulation code to be coupled is run in parallel with several processes or threads, an intra-parallel coupling results and the deployment schemes described in Section 3.4.1 have to be modified. This section discusses the deployment options and shows the approach taken in *preCICE*. The main question is, if the coupling data are kept locally at the solver instances or have to be retrieved from a remote place.

Fig. 3.3: Deployment diagram of the peer-to-peer approach for intra-parallel simulation with coupling data held remotely on a dedicated server. Solver A is running intra-parallel with n instances and uses a coupling server. Solver B is running sequentially and is in contact with the server of solver A only. Coupling server A is not a central instance as in the client-server approach, but only runs the coupling adapter of solver A on a dedicated process. The coupling adapters in the solver A processes are not holding any coupling data (besides simple control information).

A first option for the parallel deployment is to keep the coupling data remotely from solver processes. Every access to the data requires a communication then, which makes it inefficient for solver codes to read and write coupling data incrementally in small pieces. For the client-server approach it is a natural option, since a central program does already exist. For the peer-to-peer approach, a data server can be introduced as shown in Figure 3.3. The server is not a central instance, as in the client-server case, but belongs to only one intra-parallel solver. It can be seen as the coupling adapter, but run on a separate process. The parallel solver then communicates to its server, and the server represents the solver to other coupled solver(s). Every coupled solver running

intra-parallel can have its own server. When using proper communication means with non-busy waiting mechanisms (see Section 4.3.1), the server process does not introduce a significant memory or runtime overhead (albeit from the communication overhead, of course). When the server becomes a bottleneck for the solver processes, it can be run in parallel, too. Then, the question is whether a master-worker approach should be used, or if all server processes are directly linked to solver processes. For massively parallel systems, the usage of a master collecting and synchronizing all data has to be avoided, as it presents a bottleneck preventing proper scalability.

Fig. 3.4: Deployment diagram of the peer-to-peer approach for intra-parallel simulations, with coupling data held locally at the solver instances. Solver A is running in parallel with n instances, while Solver B is running sequentially. The coupling data of Solver A is either copied to all processes or is distributed among them. Synchronization of coupling data at Solver A is necessary. Communication to Solver B is done via the adapter in Solver A process 1 (other options are possible).

When coupling data is kept locally at the solver processes as shown in Figure 3.4, a whole range of questions does arise. One important question is, whether the data is partitioned among the solver instances or duplicated at every instance. If duplicated, a memory overhead is created and the synchronization of written data becomes necessary to obtain a global representation for a solver. However, the duplication gives every solver process local and, thus, fast access to all coupling data. If data is partitioned, the question of an optimal partitioning is not at all trivial to answer. The basic problem for black box coupling is that the coupling adapter does not know a priori which solver process requires what coupling data. Furthermore, communication might become neces-

sary again when data is not located at the process where it is required. Solver processes might also dynamically adapt their spatial discretization and require access to different coupling data subsets during a simulation. If not all processes are in contact with the coupled surface, load-imbalances are threatening to diminish the parallel speedup.

In *preCICE*, the remote approach with dedicated coupling servers (as depicted in Figure 3.3) is employed currently. The adapter component can be run as server program and provides coupling data such as forces and displacements remotely to a parallel solver's processes. Data can be read and written efficiently in block-wise formats. Coupling state and control information is, however, kept locally at every solver instance. This enables fast access, while it does not increase memory requirements significantly. When *preCICE* is used as a geometry interface only and no data is written to *preCICE*, the local approach with duplicated coupling data at every solver process can also be used. No synchronization is needed in this case, since data is only read. Up to now, the coupling server itself is not parallelized.

3.5 Interface Considerations

We have seen in Section 3.4 that the decoupling of solver codes is achieved by the API of the coupling adapter. Since the decoupling is closely tied to the requirement of coupling flexibility, the form of the API is of high importance. Furthermore, a proper form of the API reduces the efforts for its integration into a solver code. The technical realization of the API decides about how easy it is to link the adapter code to a solver code written in a potentially different programming language. In this section, we discuss the API of the *preCICE* adapter library. We first look at the interface of a typical black box solver in Section 3.5.1, then see the API of *preCICE* in Section 3.5.2, and, finally, review technical design decisions for simple linking to solvers written in different programming languages in Section 3.5.3.

3.5.1 Interface of a Black Box Solver

Before we consider the form of the API in *preCICE*, we look at where it is supposed to be integrated in. Since within this work the focus is on black box solvers, the limited access to solver internals has to be considered. The following discussion will first be about *where* access to a solver program needs to be given and then comes to the question of *what* needs to be accessed.

We assume that any simulation software to be coupled by *preCICE* has a logical structuring as given in Algorithm 3.1. It consists of an initialization (line 1), a solution (lines 2–5), and a finalization (line 6) phase. The task of the initialization is, e.g., to read input data and set up data structures needed for the simulation. The finalization in turn has to write output data such as a checkpoint and tear down the used data

structures. The actual computation is taking place in the solution phase and consists of a series of steps executed repeatedly, as indicated in form of a loop (line 2). This loop can be a sequence of timesteps in a transient simulation, solver iterations in a stationary simulation, or anything combined. The main part within the loop is the actual solution of the governing equations in line 4, i.e., the solution of the current timestep or iteration. It is surrounded by pre- and post-processing phases (lines 3 and 5), in which, e.g., the spatial discretization is adapted or output is written. For the discussion here, it is not important how Algorithm 3.1 is realized in source code. It suffices that a solver to be coupled provides access to the places before and/or after the logical steps shown, in order to integrate the library API of preCICE. For an accessible solver, this can mean that the source code is modifiable directly, while for a commercial solver, some form of callback mechanism has to be given.

```

1  initialization
2  while ongoing
3      pre-processing
4      solution
5      post-processing
6  finalization

```

Alg. 3.1: Logical structure of a simulation program. The loop from lines 2 to 5 can be a sequence of timesteps in a transient simulation, solver iterations in a stationary simulation, or anything combined.

The above discussion was about *where* access needs to be granted to a simulation program. We now look at the question of *what* needs to be accessed. The data to be accessed can be categorized into physical and control data.

The absolutely minimal requirement to have a coupled simulation is to be able to set and get the physical data through which the coupling is established. For FSI, these are the data discussed in Section 2.1.4. With this information alone, a simulation with an explicit equation coupling scheme, matching meshes at the coupling interface and a matching timestep size (if transient) can already be computed. When the meshes are not matching, data mapping needs to be employed, which requires knowledge about the interface mesh of a solver. For some mappings only data point locations are needed. Other mappings require also topological information to perform projections or similar operations. We will see in Section 4.2.3 that it can be helpful to get additional global information such as the total mechanical energy or force at the coupling interface. Access to derivative information and Jacobians of a simulation software is considered to be not black box coupling any more, since this information is usually not available through the API of closed software.

While the above mentioned physical data is sufficient to perform explicit simulations with matching timestep size, it is necessary to access and modify simulation control information of a solver when performing more complicated coupling schemes. This allows

not only to use more complicated coupling schemes, but also enables better synchronization and steering of a coupled solver. A simple form of steering is to control the execution of the main solution loop (line 2 in Algorithm 3.1). When the timestep size can be retrieved and an upper limit for it can be prescribed, the subcycling technique described in Section 2.3 can be implemented and steered by the coupling library. Triggered reading and writing of coupling data at time synchronization points becomes possible, too. Implicit equation coupling introduces the concept of coupling iterations (see Section 2.3.2). When the coupling scheme is hidden from the solver, some form of steering is required to inform and control a solver whether another coupling iteration or a new timestep has to be done. Synchronized output of simulation data as well as checkpointing data can be triggered by the coupling library, too, if a solver allows for it. Figure 3.5 summarizes all mentioned interfaces a solver can have and links them to the mentioned coupling functionality.

Fig. 3.5: Component diagram of connections from black box solver interface to coupling functionality. On the left-hand side are possible interfaces a black box solver can have. On the right-hand side are the coupling features of a coupling library. The connections between show the use of interfaces in coupling features or, seen from the other side, show the requirements on interfaces to realize certain features.

3.5.2 Application Programming Interface (API) of *preCICE*

In this section, an overview of the *preCICE* API is given. The API is provided in three different programming languages: C++, C, and Fortran. Thus, direct support is given to most existing simulation software. We focus on the C++ API here, which is nested in the namespace `precice`, as shown in Algorithm 3.2. The main class within there is

called `SolverInterface` and its methods provide the functionality of preCICE. In the following, the C++ syntax is weakened up slightly to be more readable. In particular, the prefix `SolverInterface::` is omitted from method declarations, since all described methods are members of class `SolverInterface`.

```

1 namespace precice {
2     class SolverInterface;
3     class ClosestMesh;
4     class VoxelPosition;
5
6     namespace constants {
7         // global constants
8     }
9 }

```

Alg. 3.2: C++ API elements of preCICE nested in the namespace `precice`. The class `SolverInterface` contains the main API in form of methods. `ClosestMesh` and `VoxelPosition` are classes used to return results of geometrical positional queries. The namespace `constants` contains global constants, such as standard names for physical data or the names of certain actions a solver has to perform. Use of the constants increases compatibility between solvers using the same physical data sets and performing the same actions.

We first consider the main methods in `SolverInterface` which are used to set up, advance, and tear down the coupling between the solvers. Algorithm 3.3 lists these methods. The constructor (lines 1–3) creates an instance of a `SolverInterface`. All further methods have to be called from that instance. In a parallel simulation, every solver process has to use an own instance of `SolverInterface`. The configuration of the coupling parameters is done by XML files (see Section 3.6) and is invoked by the method `configure`. After the configuration, the method `initialize` is used to create all data structures such as surface meshes and data vectors. It furthermore establishes a connection to the coupling partner and possibly receives first coupling data values. Most important is the method `advance`. Within that the coupling state is updated, data is mapped between non-matching grids, and exchanged between the coupled solvers. Furthermore, iteration acceleration schemes are applied for implicit coupling and the convergence of coupling iterations is measured. To realize a synchronization and control of solver time integration, `initialize` and `advance` return an upper limit for the length of the next solver time integration. The solver, in turn, has to provide its actually used timestep length to the method `advance`. In case of subcycling, a solver simply supplies a smaller timestep length than the upper limit. No data exchange and manipulation functionality is executed in such a case after a subcycling step. It is also possible that one of the solvers provides the timestep length limit for the other solver. Then, the upper limit is set to be infinity for the solver providing the timestep. More details on the actual coupling logic are given in the next chapter in Section 4.1. To shut down the

coupling to the other solver and tear down the data structures used for the coupling, `finalize` is used.

```

1  SolverInterface( string solverName ,
2                    int      solverRank ,
3                    int      solverCommSize )
4
5  void   configure( string xmlConfigFile )
6
7  double initialize ()
8  double advance( double computedTimestep )
9  void   finalize ()

```

Alg. 3.3: Main API methods of `preCICE`. The main coupling tasks are performed in the method `advance` which includes data mapping, data exchange between solvers, and coupling scheme algorithmics. All shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`.

To establish the spatial coupling, a solver needs to provide information about its coupling mesh to `preCICE`. This can be done by just providing the vertices (or positions) of the data values, or by providing a surface mesh description in addition. The surface mesh description currently consists of edges in two dimensions and of triangles in three dimensions. Surface descriptions can be obtained not only from the solvers, but also from other sources described in Section 4.4.1. The main part of the `preCICE` API for solver mesh creation is given in Algorithm 3.4. To support a flexible adaption of a solver to different coupled simulation types, a solver can query whether a mesh is required in the current simulation using the method `hasMesh`. It is important to understand that a solver only inquires about his own interface meshes and not about those of other solvers. The connection to another solver’s mesh is done in the `preCICE` XML configuration by using the names of the meshes. A solver, thus, only has to know (or define) the names of its own meshes. This allows to keep any knowledge about other solvers outside of a solver code. In order to refer to a specific mesh in other API methods, mesh IDs can be retrieved (lines 2 and 3). It is also possible to obtain information about the spatial dimensionality of the coupled problem by the method `getDimensions`. The remaining methods in Algorithm 3.4 have to be used to specify the mesh vertices (or data value positions) and the surface mesh description in two or three dimensions. `setMeshVertex` and `setMeshVertices` return the indices of each set vertex, which is unique for a mesh and has to be used when setting edges and as value index when writing or reading coupling data (in Algorithm 3.5). In an intra-parallel simulation, the indices can be a subset of the overall indices for one mesh and allow each solver process to exactly specify its own data value positions.

To enable a solver to deal with coupling data, a further set of methods is provided in `SolverInterface`. Algorithm 3.5 shows the subset that is responsible for getting

```

1  bool      hasMesh( string meshName )
2  int       getMeshID( string meshName )
3  set<int>  getMeshIDs ()
4  int       getDimensions ()
5
6  int  setMeshVertex( int    meshID ,
7                      double position [] )
8
9  void setMeshVertices( int    meshID ,
10                       int    count ,
11                       double positions [] ,
12                       int    ids [] )
13
14 int  setMeshEdge( int meshID ,
15                  int firstVertexID ,
16                  int secondVertexID )
17
18 void setMeshTriangle( int meshID ,
19                      int firstEdgeID ,
20                      int secondEdgeID ,
21                      int thirdEdgeID )

```

Alg. 3.4: Part of the coupling mesh API of preCICE. The shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`.

information about data and writing vector data values. Corresponding variants exist for reading and scalar type data. Similar as for the coupling meshes, a solver can find out which of its data are required in a simulation by using method `hasData`. Every data set has a unique ID to be obtained by `getDataID`, which has to be used in operations to specify a data set. Data can be written in block form, i.e., several data values at once or as individual datum. The block form allows for a more efficient implementation particularly when the coupling data are placed remotely at a coupling server (Section 3.4.2).

By default, the data mapping in preCICE takes place within the method `advance` (see Algorithm 3.3). In some cases, however, it can be necessary to perform the write mapping before calling `advance` or the read mapping afterwards. preCICE provides two API methods, given in Algorithm 3.6, for such cases. Each method takes a mesh ID that is known by the solver. In `mapReadDataTo`, the solver has to specify the mesh where data is mapped to, while in `mapWriteDataFrom` the solver has to give the mesh where data is mapped from. Thus, the specified meshes are both meshes of the solver. The connection to the other solver's mesh involved in a mapping has to be done by the user in the preCICE XML configuration. This cuts any direct dependencies to another solver and also to the simulation context, e.g., an FSI simulation, and allows for a higher flexibility. An example for shifting the mapping of read data outside of `advance` is when

```

1  bool hasData( string dataName, int meshID )
2  int  getDataID( string dataName, int meshID )
3
4  void writeBlockVectorData( int    dataID ,
5                             int    count ,
6                             int    valueIndices [] ,
7                             double values [] )
8
9  void writeVectorData( int    dataID ,
10                        int    valueIndex ,
11                        double value [] )

```

Alg. 3.5: Part of the data API of *preCICE* for writing of vector type data. The shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`. Corresponding methods exist for reading data and scalar type data.

the read positions of a solver change based on the geometry of the coupling surface. Since both, the read positions and geometry are updated in advance by default, there is no possibility to update the read positions of the solver in between. Thus, the read mapping has to be executed outside of `advance`, after updating the solver read positions from the new geometry. This is the case for fixed grid solvers with Cartesian geometry as described in Section 5.1.1.

```

1  void mapReadDataTo( int meshID )
2  void mapWriteDataFrom( int meshID )

```

Alg. 3.6: Data mapping API of *preCICE*. The shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`. In a typical use case, these methods are automatically invoked in the `advance` (see Algorithm 3.3).

So far, we have only considered coupling functionality APIs. The geometry interface functionality of *preCICE* is provided to solvers in form of a positional query API, shown in Algorithm 3.7. Given a surface mesh in *preCICE*, a solver can obtain positional information relative to that surface for points and axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABBs), as well as closest distance information to the surface. The method `inquirePosition` returns whether a point is inside, on, or outside of a solid geometry. The parameter `meshIDs` determines which meshes should be considered for the query and is used in the other methods as well. For obtaining mesh IDs, see Algorithm 3.4. In addition to the relative position, the method `inquireClosestMesh` also computes the distance to the closest mesh. The result is returned as an object of the class `ClosestMesh`, defined in the namespace `precice`. Volumetric queries can be issued by the method `inquireVoxelPosition` which returns its results as an object of the class `VoxelPosition`. The details about the positional queries are given in Section 4.4.2.

```

1  int inquirePosition( double   point [],
2                      set<int> meshIDs )
3
4  ClosestMesh inquireClosestMesh(
5                      double   point [],
6                      set<int> meshIDs )
7
8  VoxelPosition inquireVoxelPosition(
9                      double   center [],
10                     double   halfLengthVoxel [],
11                     bool     includeBoundaries ,
12                     set<int> meshIDs )

```

Alg. 3.7: Positional geometry query API of preCICE. The shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`.

Finally, we consider some auxiliary API methods shown in Algorithm 3.8. The methods in lines 1–4 can be used by a solver to get additional information about the coupling state, e.g., to find out whether coupling data should be written or read. The method `isActionRequired` is used as an extensible means to convey required actions to a solver. E.g., coupling iterations for implicit equation coupling require a solver to store and load iteration checkpoints, i.e., old timestep states, while iterating. A solver has to query for the actions `write-iteration-checkpoint` and `read-iteration-checkpoint`, and confirm their execution by using the method `fulfilledAction`. Other coupling tools often have a dedicated method "iterate" to signal a solver to perform a coupling iteration. However, when subcycling is included and implemented in the coupling library, this is not sufficient. Further actions are provided for synchronized checkpoint writing and reading, as well as regular data output writing. The mechanism is easy to extend by further required solver actions and a solver needs to implement only those actions which correspond to used functionality. In order to avoid errors from not properly adapted solvers, `fulfilledAction` acts as a checking mechanism. In case a solver does not fulfill a required action, preCICE can detect the missing call of `fulfilledAction` and report an error. All required action names are gathered in the namespace `precice::constants`.

```

1  bool isCouplingOngoing()
2  bool isReadDataAvailable()
3  bool isWriteDataRequired( double computedTimestep )
4  bool isTimestepComplete()
5  bool isActionRequired( string action )
6  void fulfilledAction( string action )

```

Alg. 3.8: Auxiliary API methods of preCICE. The shown methods are members of the class `SolverInterface`.

3.5.3 Technical Considerations for Linking

A good programming interface is created by not only taking into account logical considerations, but also technical points of view. In particular, programming language compatibility issues with solver codes are of importance. Non-standard data structures from external libraries used in *preCICE* should not pollute a solver code. Otherwise, additional compile time dependencies and possibilities for name collisions are created. This is, first, prevented by nesting all code into an own namespace called `precice`, as given in Algorithm 3.2. As a further step, the pointer-to-implementation (Pimpl) idiom, pictured for the C++ API in Figure 3.6, is employed to hide all implementation (i.e., non-public) details from the API of *preCICE*. This removes all compile time dependencies from non-standard language features. As a consequence, any code changes to the internals of *preCICE* do not require to recompile a solver code. However, the Pimpl idiom also has some drawbacks, namely the added complexity and efforts to have two interface classes and the performance loss introduced by the additional indirection. At least for block based data operations this overhead should be insignificant. The C and Fortran interfaces of *preCICE* are able to hide the implementation details by an additional layer of code analog to `SolverInterface`, written in the respective language.

Fig. 3.6: The Pimpl idiom applied for the *preCICE* C++ API. The interface class `SolverInterface` only has a pointer to its actual implementation `SolverInterfaceImplementation`, which hides all state variables and non-public implementation details from a solver code.

3.6 Software Architecture

In this section, we look at the software architecture of *preCICE*. *preCICE* consists of hierarchically structured components with a loose layering, i.e., a component can only access other components from a lower layer. Figure 3.7 shows the functional components used in *preCICE* and its dependencies. Note the dependencies form a tree graph structure without cycles, which is important for unit testing. A component which is connected by an arrow pointing to another component is dependent on methods and/or data structures from that component. Furthermore, the component might also use features of a component further down the dependency path. In addition to the components shown in Figure 3.7, there is a utility component `util`, providing basic functionality used in all other components. Similarly, a group of components called `tarch` (technical

architecture) is used which is a common effort of several people to develop an in-house utility library [160, 177, 30]. The Boost C++ libraries [36] are employed for additional advanced features such as parsing, multi-threading, and platform-independent TCP/IP communication. Depending on the demanded functionality, preCICE uses additional external libraries such as Python [66] for scripted data actions (see Section 4.5.1) and MPICH2 [99] or OpenMPI [68, 134] for MPI communication. In the following, we consider the general structure of a component and have a brief look at each component in preCICE. A more detailed description of the main features is given in Chapter 4. In addition to the functional components, we also review the unit test and configuration mechanisms in preCICE, which are part of the utility component `utils`.

Fig. 3.7: Component structure of preCICE, with dependencies marked by arrows. A component may also use other components down the dependency graph, which results in a weak layered architecture.

A component in preCICE consists of a publicly available part forming its interface to the other components and a private part used to realize the implementation of the interface. Furthermore, every component has a dedicated set of unit tests. When a component provides functionality that can be configured in a simulation using preCICE, configuration classes are given, which integrate into the overall configuration system described later in this section. Algorithm 3.9 shows a template for the directory and file structure of a component in preCICE.

The most basic component in preCICE is `mesh`. It defines a mesh data structure consisting of vertices, edges, and triangles, which offers top-down connectivities from triangles to edges and vertices. Furthermore, data containers are defined that hold the coupling data values and associate them to the elements of a mesh. A hierarchical property mechanism is given, in order to assign material parameter values to individual or groups of mesh elements.

The leftmost branch in Figure 3.7 continues with the component `query`. It provides geometrical projection and intersection operations for the mesh data structures defined

```

1  component/
2      ClassA
3      ClassB
4      ..
5      Constants
6
7      impl/
8          ImplementationClassA
9          ImplementationClassB
10         ..
11
12     tests/
13         TestCaseClassA
14         TestCaseClassB
15         TestCaseImplementationClassA
16         TestCaseImplementationClassB
17         TestCaseConfigurationClassA
18         TestCaseConfigurationClassB
19         ..
20
21     config/
22         ConfigurationClassA
23         ConfigurationClassB
24         ..

```

Alg. 3.9: Template file and directory structure of a component in *preCICE*. Classes and constants in the root directory of a component form its public interface. Implementation classes are gathered in directory `impl`, unit tests in directory `tests`, and configuration classes in directory `config`.

in `mesh`. The functionality consists of finding closest distances to vertices, edges, and triangles from a point and volume queries for axis-aligned bounding boxes in two and three dimensions. On top of the `query` component operates the component `spacetree`. It provides spatial data structures to reduce the number of query operations necessary and, thus, speed up the query computation times. In particular, it consists of a static, i.e., offline created, and a dynamic octree/quadtree data structure, as well as functionality to export the trees for visualization purposes. The topmost component `mapping` is responsible for data mapping between non-matching meshes. It contains implementations of nearest-neighbor, nearest-projection, and several radial basis function methods. Since some of the data mapping methods require projections on closest mesh elements or finding vertices in a given proximity, the functionality of `query` and `spacetree` are used.

The second-left branch in Figure 3.7 contains the remote communication and equa-

tion coupling scheme features of preCICE. The component `com` defines an interface for different communication methods based on MPI, files, and TCP/IP sockets. `cplscheme` contains equation coupling schemes that use the communication interface to exchange control information and coupling data between coupled solvers. There are classes for explicit coupling, implicit coupling, and no coupling, when preCICE is used as pure geometry interface. The implicit coupling scheme uses further classes for iteration convergence measurement and convergence acceleration.

On the second-right position in Figure 3.7 are components for input and output of meshes and data, as well as the creation of meshes. The component `io` provides classes for input and output of the mesh data structures given in `mesh` from and to files. Furthermore, coupling state information can be imported or exported and matrix, vector, or table data can be written to text files. preCICE provides the possibility to directly create geometric primitives such as spheres or cuboids by the functionality given in the component `geometry`.

Finally, the component `action` on the very right provides a set of auxiliary features that can modify coupling data or coupling meshes at specific times during the call of `advance`. To support rapid solver adaption, Python scripted actions are possible.

The automated unit test framework used in preCICE is provided by the `tarch` library. It consists of three main classes depicted in Figure 3.8, where `TestCase` and `TreeTestCaseCollection` form a composite pattern. All unit test classes used in preCICE derive from the class `TestCase`. A global registration instance is provided by the class `TestCaseRegistry` to automatically gather all unit test classes and structure them according to their level of namespace nesting. Error reports are created when one of the validation macros fails during a test run. The unit test framework is also used to create automated integration tests that make use of the preCICE API.

Fig. 3.8: Class diagram with the main classes of the unit test framework provided by `tarch`. Every concrete test class derives from `TestCase` and implements its methods using test macros. A global registry instance modeled by `TestCaseRegistry` gathers tests in collections formed by the class `TreeTestCaseCollection` according to their namespace nesting.

The configuration of preCICE for a particular simulation is done by XML files. Algorithm 3.10 gives an overview of a configuration file with the main items. The configura-

tion is structured such that items first need to be defined before they can be referenced in other items. For example, each coupling data has to have a unique name used to assign it to one or several meshes and each mesh has a unique name again to assign it to the participants (which are the coupled solvers). This allows to check for logical errors in the configuration and imposes a clear structure. As mentioned before, the configuration classes are not gathered at a central place, but distributed among the components that offer configurable functionality. To provide an automated process of parsing an XML file, testing for wrong input, and generating documentation, a small configuration framework has been created within this work. The framework consists of the classes depicted in Figure 3.9. The main class within that framework is `XMLTag` and models an XML tag. The XML tree is expanded hierarchically from a root tag, by adding attributes modeled by `XMLAttribute` and further XML subtags. An attribute has to be specialized for a certain value type by using C++ templates, where the following types are possible: string, scalar or vectorial floating point number, scalar or vectorial integer, boolean value. An attribute can have a default value and a validator that checks a parsed value. Two implementations of validators are available at the moment that are used to model a limited set of available attribute values. This can be useful, e.g., when string attributes are used to select a specific algorithm or functionality. In this case, a possible attribute value is prescribed using the class `ValidatorEquals<Type>` and all possible values are concatenated using the class `ValidatorOr<Type>`. The XML framework uses the exception mechanism of C++ to enhance configuration errors by their occurrence in a given tag hierarchy. This enables a user to figure out errors in his configuration easily. The documentation of XML tags and attributes has to be done in code by using the method `setDocumentation`. The framework then allows to automatically create an up-to-date configuration reference with proper documentation.

3.7 Evaluation of Achieved Goals

In this chapter, the design goals, requirements, and design decisions for the coupling environment *preCICE* have been discussed. When evaluating existing coupling software by the found criteria, it was shown that none of the considered existing tools can be regarded as optimal.

The client-server coupling deployment scheme for the solvers and the coupling tool has been compared to the peer-to-peer scheme for intra-sequential and -parallel simulations. Both offer the same amount of abstraction from the employed coupling functionality and, hence, provide the same amount of flexibility to exchange any of the coupled solvers. The peer-to-peer scheme, however, needs only one coupling logic.

A high-level coupling API has been presented which moves away from the message-passing like APIs of many existing coupling tools. It better abstracts from the employed coupling functionality, as it hides the coupling scheme, data mapping calls, and the communication of coupling data. The API is also simpler to integrate into a solver code,

```

1 <precice-configuration>
2   ... logging configuration ...
3   <solver-interface>
4     ... data ...
5     ... meshes ...
6     ... geometries of meshes ...
7     ... spacetrees ...
8     ... participants ...
9     ... used meshes ...
10    ... data exports ...
11    ... data mappings ...
12    ... data actions ...
13    ... communication ...
14    ... coupling-scheme ...
15    ... convergence measures ...
16    ... convergence acceleration ...
17  </solver-interface>
18 </precice-configuration>

```

Alg. 3.10: Overview of XML configuration template for preCICE. The configuration is structured such that items have to be defined first before they are referenced in other items. For example, each coupling data has to have a unique name used to assign it to a mesh and each mesh has to have a unique name again to assign it to a participant.

Fig. 3.9: Class diagram of the XML configuration framework in the component utils of preCICE. Class XMLTag is used to create a hierarchical structure of the XML configuration. The types of parameters a tag can have are defined by the class XMLAttribute. Validators are used to ensure and document attribute values, when only a limited choice is allowed.

3 preCICE – A Software Environment for Black Box Coupling

as it does not require knowledge about coupling logic.

An overview of the software architecture of preCICE has been given, which consists of a weakly layered component structure. Each component also shows a clear structure into public and implementation parts, as well as unit tests and configuration. The unit test and configuration class frameworks have been explained, as well as the XML configuration mechanism itself.

Overall, the design approach of the coupling environment preCICE provides a real benefit over existing coupling software for partitioned simulations. Due to the clear software design and use of automated tests, the maintainability as well as expandability are possible without too much efforts.

4 preCICE – Algorithms for Black Box Fluid-Structure Interaction

We have defined the goals and software requirements of preCICE and derived from that a suitable implementation approach, software design, and application programming interface (API) in Chapter 3. In this chapter, we focus on the details of the functional components of preCICE from a software design as well as an algorithmic point of view. The implemented functionality is either based on state of the art research presented in Chapter 2 or is newly developed within this work. The integration of the features into preCICE is shown. Furthermore, the implemented algorithms are evaluated in form of component tests with the help of simple numerical scenarios to show important differences in, e.g., computational performance or numerical accuracy.

In the following, we first discuss the core functionality for partitioned FSI coupling, namely equation coupling schemes in Section 4.1, data mapping algorithms in Section 4.2, and interprocess communication methods in Section 4.3. The geometry interface functionality is described in Section 4.4. Section 4.5 mentions further features that contribute to the environment of preCICE.

4.1 Equation Coupling Schemes

In this section, the implementation of equation coupling schemes for which we reviewed the state of the art in Section 2.3 is described. We start in Section 4.1.1 by repeating some important concepts and then look at an overview of the realization of the coupling numerics in preCICE. In Section 4.1.2, we dive into more details for explicit coupling and in Section 4.1.3 for implicit coupling. A comparison and evaluation of the implemented implicit coupling schemes is presented in Section 4.1.4. Section 4.1.5 describes the multi-solver coupling concept and capabilities of preCICE.

4.1.1 Overview and Implementation Concepts

The main goal in partitioned coupling is to re-establish or approximate the solution of the original monolithic system of equations given for FSI in (2.64), page 28. To achieve this goal, the solutions of the partitioned field solvers are combined via equation cou-

pling schemes (in Section 2.3) which were categorized into explicit and implicit. Explicit schemes approximate the solution of the monolithic system with a certain error order in terms of the discrete timestep length. Implicit schemes can compute the original monolithic solution up to arbitrary accuracy and allow for stabilization measures that are often inevitable. While explicit schemes perform only one or a few solver computations per timestep, implicit schemes iterate over solver computations until convergence. Thus, explicit schemes often need much less solver calls than implicit ones, but might not be applicable for scenarios with strong instabilities. Since *preCICE* has been developed to facilitate black box coupling (see Section 3.1), only a subset of coupling schemes remains relevant. Within this work, the conventional serial staggered (CSS) procedure has been implemented as a representative of an explicit coupling scheme. For implicit coupling, a block Gauss-Seidel type coupling scheme with constant relaxation, Aitken-based dynamic relaxation, and an interface quasi-Newton approach has been implemented. These schemes are amongst the most commonly employed methods for partitioned FSI simulations with black box solvers. An important feature is that they only deal with input and output data from the coupling surface and are independent from the spatial and time discretization used in the solvers. Furthermore, no derivative information is needed from solver internals as required by some Newton methods. Black box coupling is, thus, perfectly supported.

The separation of the solvers in the partitioned equation coupling schemes leads to (potentially) different execution threads for each of them. Since the API of *preCICE* hides specific execution threads, they need to be defined elsewhere. Furthermore, the peer-to-peer communication logic of the coupled solvers is tightly related to the actual coupling scheme employed. Hence, it makes sense to integrate the communication logic into the coupling scheme logic. The implementation of coupling schemes in *preCICE*, thus, includes the equation coupling numerics, execution logic, and peer-to-peer communication logic for each of the coupled solvers. A solver may execute only a part of a coupling scheme’s functionality, depending on its role in the specific scheme employed. In the following, we consider the coupling scheme implementation in a static and in a dynamic view. The static view illustrates the involved classes and their relations, while the dynamic view shows their interactions during the execution of a coupling.

Static View

In *preCICE*, all equation coupling schemes are gathered in the component `cplscheme`¹. Its main classes, methods, and variables are depicted in a class diagram in Figure 4.1. The interface of a coupling scheme is defined by the class `CouplingScheme` and every *preCICE* solver adapter² is associated to one implementation of `CouplingScheme` (hidden

¹See Section 3.6, page 116, for an overview of all components in *preCICE*.

²A solver adapter for *preCICE* is the component or piece of code that connects the solver code with the *preCICE* API (see Section 3.4.1, page 104).

by the API). Its main methods' names equal those in the API of preCICE³ and are actually embedded into those. A call of such an API method always results in a call of the corresponding method in `CouplingScheme`.

preCICE provides four implementations of coupling schemes which implement the main methods of `CouplingScheme` displayed in Figure 4.1. `ExplicitCouplingScheme` and `ImplicitCouplingScheme` implement the CSS and block-Gauss Seidel algorithms, respectively. `UncoupledScheme` is employed when preCICE is used as a geometry interface (see Section 4.4), where no coupling to another solver is established. Multi-coupling simulations, discussed in more detail in Section 4.1.5, are achieved by a component pattern with the container class `CompositionalCouplingScheme`. Except from the latter, the coupling scheme implementation classes share a common code base by inheriting from `BaseCouplingScheme`. The `ImplicitCouplingScheme` uses two further interfaces for convergence measurement and iteration post-processing, which are discussed in Section 4.1.3. Not displayed in Figure 4.1 is the interface for data communication, the class `Communication` (see Section 4.3), which abstracts any communication detail from the coupling scheme component and is used by the explicit and the implicit scheme classes.

Fig. 4.1: Main classes of the component `cplscheme` and their relations. `cplscheme` gathers all equation coupling schemes and provides them via the interface of the class `CouplingScheme`. For clarity, inherited methods and variables are not displayed in subclasses.

A coupling scheme only works with raw coupling data coming from outside of the component. It does not know about the context of the data, i.e., associated surface meshes or solver details. Technical and numerical details such as communication, convergence measurement, and iteration post-processing are hidden by interfaces. Thus, the four coupling scheme implementation classes (mainly) implement the execution logic and the associated state of a coupled solver. Writing a new communication mechanism, con-

³Parts of the API of preCICE are shown in Algorithm 3.3, page 112.

vergence measurement method, or post-processing can be done without changing the coupling scheme classes by inheriting from the appropriate interfaces. Similarly, writing a new coupling scheme instance can be done without adapting communication, convergence measure, or post-processing classes. Of course, in order to use a newly written functionality, the *preCICE* configuration mechanism (mentioned in Section 3.6) needs to be extended by a corresponding entry. This modularity and extensibility is one of the strong points of *preCICE* compared to other coupling software.

Dynamic View

So far, we have considered a static view on the coupling scheme implementation. To better understand the dynamic behavior, we now look at the transient interaction of two coupling scheme instances (one for each of the two coupled solvers) as appearing in a coupled simulation. The currently implemented equation coupling schemes entail a sequentialized execution order of the coupled solvers. The resulting pattern of method calls is the same for explicit and for implicit coupling schemes. Figure 4.2 shows two sequence diagrams of communicating coupling scheme instances. The instances and, thus, solvers are differentiated into first and second to denote their execution order. In Figure 4.2a, the second solver initializes its coupling data for the first solver. This is necessary if the first solver starts with non-zero coupling values (given by the second solver). For example, in FSI the structure solver could start with a non-zero initial velocity that needs to be transferred to the starting flow solver. To perform the initialization, the second solver writes the initial values to *preCICE* between the calls of `initialize` and `initializeData`. The initial values are transferred to the first solver which can start with the first computation after `initialize`. The second solver has to wait in `initializeData` until the first solver has computed its values and they are transferred in `advance` to the second solver. Then, the second solver can perform its first computation and a sequence of alternating calls to `advance` follows. Each solver computes new values in between, until the simulation ends with a call to `finalize`. Note that the first solver needs no dedicated `initializeData` call, since the sequential execution already entails an initialization of the values for the second solver.

Figure 4.2a represents a coupled simulation where coupling data is exchanged after every solver computation. Thus, either no solver subcycling⁴ is involved or the subcycling is implemented in the solvers' code. The latter is, however, not how *preCICE* is meant to be used. Figure 4.2b shows another sequence of two coupling schemes without data initialization but with subcycles performed by the first solver. When no data is initialized, the second solver waits for values of the first solver in `initialize` and no call to `initializeData` has to be performed⁵. The subcycling is visible through the repeated

⁴A solver is said to perform subcycles if it computes several timesteps with smaller timestep length (compared to the other solver's timestep length or a reference timestep length) until it exchanges data with its coupling partner.

⁵A solver is told by *preCICE* to perform the data initialization using the request-action API introduced

Fig. 4.2: Sequence diagrams illustrating the use of the class `CouplingScheme`. (a) shows a coupling data exchange on every call of `advance`, while, in (b), the first solver performs subcycles. Solver timestep or iteration computations are done before every call of `advance`.

calls of `advance` without any data exchange. In the example, the first solver computes three subcycle solutions before being coupled to the second solver. The second solver in turn has to wait until those three solutions are computed, before leaving `initialize`. More details on the implementation of the methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, and `advance` are given in the following two sections that are focussed on the specific realization of the classes `ExplicitCouplingScheme` and `ImplicitCouplingScheme`.

One particular advantage of preCICE is its high-level API given by the methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, `advance`, and `finalize`. In contrast to most other coupling software, no explicit communication calls for interface mesh transmission or coupling data exchange are present in the API. Hence, the introduction of new coupling schemes with different communication logic does not entail a change of the solver codes. This concept has been validated in recent works, where preCICE has been extended by an interfield-parallel coupling scheme [165, 114] with simultaneous execution of the coupled solvers.

in Algorithm 3.8, page 115. If a solver does not perform the initialization despite asked by preCICE, the simulation stops with a proper error message.

4.1.2 Explicit Coupling

A conventional serial staggered (CSS) scheme, as described in Section 2.3.1, is realized through the class `ExplicitCouplingScheme`. The CSS scheme requires a single invocation of each solver per timestep, where the solver executions are ordered sequentially, i.e., there is no interfield-parallelism. This execution logic is implemented in the methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, and `advance` according to Algorithm 4.1. The method `finalize` is omitted here since it is mainly responsible to tear down communication channels and does not contain any coupling scheme logic. The methods `initialize` (lines 1–3) and `initializeData` (lines 5–8) implement the startup logic as described in the sequence diagrams of Figure 4.2. The method `advance` (lines 10–14) implements the *preCICE* controlled subcycling, which is basically a wrapping of the functionality into an if-clause (line 11) that checks if the solver subcycles are completed. In order to perform the check, a solver needs to tell *preCICE* about the lengths of its computed timesteps⁶. Then, data are sent and received from the coupling partner, where the receive is only issued if the coupled simulation is still ongoing for the second participant. Thus, the last call of `advance` of the second participant results in no receive, as depicted in Figure 4.2a.

```

1  initialize():
2      if second participant xor initialize data
3          receiveData()
4
5  initializeData():
6      if second participant and initialize data
7          sendData()
8          receiveData()
9
10 advance():
11     if subcycling completed
12         sendData()
13         if ongoing or first participant
14             receiveData()

```

Alg. 4.1: Main parts of methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, and `advance` of class `ExplicitCouplingScheme`.

As already mentioned, there is a mechanism to inform *preCICE* about the computed solver timestep length. There is another mechanism that prescribes the maximal timestep length of the next solver timestep. The API methods `initialize` and `advance` both return this limit to the solver, which enables two ways of timestep control. First, a constant timestep length can be prescribed by *preCICE*. Any of the two coupled solvers can perform a smaller timestep than prescribed which makes the step

⁶A solver tells *preCICE* about its computed timestep by using the API method `advance`. This timestep is forwarded to the coupling scheme instance.

a subcycle. However, none is allowed to perform a larger timestep than the prescribed one. A synchronization and coupling data exchange takes place when the sum of subcycle lengths reaches the preCICE timestep length. Second, the timestep length can be given dynamically by the first solver and is used as prescribed upper limit for the second solver. This allows preCICE controlled subcycles only for the second solver, since every computed step of the first solver is taken as a full timestep. The two ways of timestep control enable all common types of subcycling found in literature. By letting preCICE control the timestepping mechanism, it can be flexibly configured and needs not to be implemented into the solver codes.

4.1.3 Implicit Coupling

In the class `ImplicitCouplingScheme`, an iterative equation coupling scheme is implemented based on the block Gauss-Seidel (or multiplicative Schwarz decomposition) scheme described in Section 2.3.2. The block Gauss-Seidel scheme iterates over solver solutions for every timestep until the coupling data values have converged. It employs a sequentialized execution order of solvers as in the explicit CSS scheme. In the implicit scheme, a call of the method `advance` relates to a coupling iteration. Subcycling and timestep control by preCICE or the first solver are supported in the same way as for the explicit coupling scheme. Four additional types of functionality are used in the implicit coupling scheme: convergence measurements have to be performed in order to determine the convergence state of the iterations. Stabilization and acceleration techniques such as dynamic Aitken relaxation or the IQN-ILS scheme can be used in form of a coupling data post-processing. Initial value extrapolation can be used to improve the starting values of the coupling iterations. In order to steer the solver computations, a solver needs to get feedback about the iterations state. In the following, we first review the execution logic of the implemented implicit coupling scheme and, then, go into more details for each of the mentioned .

Execution Logic

The main logic of the implemented implicit scheme is split into the methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, and `advance`, where the first two are the same as for the explicit scheme. Note that the data initialization also has effects on coupling data convergence measurements and post-processings using old coupling iterates. Algorithm 4.2 shows the method `advance` which performs a subcycling check (line 2) and has a separate execution logic for the first and the second participant. The first participant's logic (lines 4–7) is similar to the explicit coupling with an additional receive of the convergence state from the second participant (line 5). The second participant (lines 9–17) performs all coupling numerics. The convergence state is measured (line 9), an iteration post-processing is applied (line 11), and data is extrapolated (line 15). Note that convergence can be measured for several coupling variables, also those of the first participant. The iteration

post-processing and the data extrapolation are optional. In case of convergence, both participants receive the first iterates of the next coupling timestep in the same call of `advance`. The first participant obtains extrapolated data if extrapolation is used. Otherwise, the converged data of the last timestep is kept which can be interpreted as constant extrapolation. The last timestep of an implicit coupled simulation ends when the first participant receives convergence (line 5) from the second participant (line 12) which makes both “ongoing” statements (lines 6 and 13) evaluate to false.

```

1  advance():
2      if subcycling completed
3          if first participant
4              sendData()
5              receiveConvergence()
6              if ongoing
7                  receiveData()
8          else
9              measureConvergence()
10             if not convergence
11                 iterationPostProcessing()
12             sendConvergence()
13             if ongoing
14                 if convergence
15                     extrapolateData()
16                 sendData()
17                 receiveData()

```

Alg. 4.2: Implicit coupling scheme logic implemented in the method `advance` of the class `ImplicitCouplingScheme`.

In order to perform an implicit coupling, a solver needs to be able to repeatedly solve the same timestep taking into account changing coupling boundary conditions. There are several ways to achieve this behavior. Often, a solver performs the computation of a timestep with an iterative solver anyhow and we can directly use this mechanism for the coupling iterations. If this is not the case a checkpointing mechanism needs to be used and old timesteps need to be reloaded at the beginning of every iteration. If subcycling is used by a solver, only a checkpointing mechanism can be used to get back to the state at the beginning of an iteration. `preCICE` conveys the convergence state of the coupling iterations to a solver by using the request-action API introduced in Algorithm 3.8, page 115. The two actions `write-iteration-checkpoint` and `read-iteration-checkpoint` are used, where the first signals the beginning of a new timestep and the second the beginning of a repeated implicit iteration. If a solver does not use the checkpointing paradigm, the two actions can also be used to derive a timestep/iteration logic for the solver.

Convergence Measurements

To determine the coupling iteration convergence, the difference of two subsequent coupling iteration data vectors \mathbf{w}^n and \mathbf{w}^{n+1} can be used as a measure for the residual (2.109), page 46. The class `ConvergenceMeasure` (see Figure 4.1) defines the interface for convergence measurement implementations. Four measurement types have been implemented: an absolute, two relative, and a fixed number of iterations convergence measure. To measure absolute convergence, the discrete l^2 -norm $\|\cdot\|$ is used as

$$\|\mathbf{w}^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}^n\| = \sqrt{\sum_i (\mathbf{w}_i^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}_i^n)^2} \stackrel{!}{<} \epsilon_{abs}, \quad (4.1)$$

with $\epsilon_{abs} > 0$ as convergence limit. A relative convergence measurement is implemented by setting the relation to the current coupling iterate values as

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{w}^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}^n\|}{\|\mathbf{w}^{n+1}\|} \stackrel{!}{<} \epsilon_{rel}. \quad (4.2)$$

Furthermore, a relative convergence measure with respect to the first residual of a coupling iteration sequence in a timestep is implemented, reading

$$\frac{\|\mathbf{w}^{n+1} - \mathbf{w}^n\|}{\|\mathbf{w}^1 - \mathbf{w}^0\|} \stackrel{!}{<} \epsilon_{r-rel}. \quad (4.3)$$

Finally, a criterion prescribing a fixed minimal number of coupling iterations has been implemented, that yields convergence after a defined number of coupling iterations. Since in an FSI (or other typical multiphysics) simulation several data values are exchanged between the coupled solvers, also several convergence measurements can be employed. The total convergence is then defined by the convergence of all single convergence measurements. This behavior can be used to combine absolute and relative measures, in order to prevent unreasonably small convergence limits of relative measures in case of close-to-zero coupling values.

Aitken-based Relaxation and Quasi-Newton as Iteration Post-Processings

Implicit coupling iterations are mostly employed when explicit coupling leads to an unstable solution. For FSI, the added-mass effect is identified as a source of the instabilities (see Section 2.3.3). Applying a pure block Gauss-Seidel approach does not improve the situation, since the instabilities carry over to the coupling iteration's (non-)convergence. Thus, a more sophisticated implicit coupling method needs to be used. We have reviewed several suitable methods in Section 2.3.2. Most of them can be applied in form of a coupling iteration post-processing, i.e., modifying the coupling value sequence produced by the block Gauss-Seidel method. This approach has been implemented in preCICE using the class `PostProcessing` (Figure 4.1) as an implementation interface. A constant relaxation, dynamic Aitken-based relaxation [90], and an interface quasi-Newton scheme

(IQN-ILS) [42] have been implemented. The numerical operations involved range from discrete scalar products for the Aitken-scheme up to a modified Gram-Schmidt based QR -decomposition (based on [135]) for the IQN-ILS scheme. In order to efficiently enable the dynamic insertions and deletions of the columns in the \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{V} matrices of the IQN-ILS scheme, a dynamic column based matrix has been implemented. The linear algebra routines have been implemented such that they are compatible with any matrix or vector type that supports a random access to its components. This behavior is enabled using advanced C++-template techniques such as type traits and allows for a later integration of optimized and parallelized linear algebra libraries without having to adapt the coupling scheme implementation.

In FSI with a fixed grid fluid solver (see Section 5.1.1), it can be necessary to not only pass displacements from the structure to the flow solver, but also velocities and accelerations. The implemented post-processings can deal with several coupling data sets. One (primary) data set is used to compute the relaxation factor(s) in the Aitken or IQN-ILS scheme. The computed factor(s) are used to relax the other (secondary) data sets. In case of the IQN-ILS scheme, an own \mathbf{W} matrix for each additional data set has to be set up.

One could naively think that it suffices to provide one state of the art implicit coupling scheme such as the IQN-ILS. The choice of three post-processing schemes in *preCICE* relates to their increasing complexity and computational costs. First of all, it is often good to have lower complexity methods when testing new scenarios. Higher complexity increases the possibility for unexpected behavior or failure. Additionally, we will see in Section 4.1.4 that weakly instable scenarios can be efficiently solved with lower complexity schemes which then leads to lower overall costs.

Initial-Value Extrapolation

To achieve a better initial guess for the coupling iterations of one timestep, an extrapolation of coupling values from previous timestep solutions $\mathbf{w}^n, \mathbf{w}^{n-1}, \dots$ can be employed. Only the coupling values used as boundary values for the solver doing the first computation are extrapolated. In FSI, usually the flow solver needs displacement and velocity data values as starting values in a new timestep. The simplest extrapolation is to take the solution of the previous timestep, reading

$$\mathbf{w}_p^{n+1} = \mathbf{w}^n. \quad (4.4)$$

In addition, a first order extrapolation according to

$$\mathbf{w}_p^{n+1} = 2\mathbf{w}^n - \mathbf{w}^{n-1}, \quad (4.5)$$

and a second order extrapolation, reading

$$\mathbf{w}_p^{n+1} = 2.5\mathbf{w}^n - 2\mathbf{w}^{n-1} + 0.5\mathbf{w}^{n-2}, \quad (4.6)$$

have been implemented in the class `ImplicitCouplingScheme`. The second order extrapolation falls back to the first order method in the first completed timestep, since no two timestep solutions are available by then.

4.1.4 Comparison of Implicit Equation Coupling Schemes

In [44], a flow and a structure solver have been developed and coupled with different implicit coupling schemes to confirm theoretical stability investigations (presented in Section 2.3.3). The same solvers have been coupled by preCICE within this work in order to validate and compare the properties of the implemented implicit coupling schemes. In the following, we first review the scenario setup with respect to the used physics, the discretization, and important characteristic quantities. We then evaluate and interpret three experiments performed with the coupled solvers and the coupling scheme implementation described in Section 4.1.3.

Scenario Description

The FSI scenario described in [44] consists of an internal flow in a flexible tube as shown in Figure 4.3, where the flow is unsteady and incompressible. Due to the axisymmetry, the flow can be described by quasi-two-dimensional continuity and momentum equations as

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(av)}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (4.7)$$

$$\frac{\partial(av)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(av^2)}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial(ap)}{\partial x} - p \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} \right) = 0, \quad (4.8)$$

where $a = a(x) = r(x)^2\pi$ is the cross-sectional area, $v = v(x)$ the flow velocity in x -direction, $p = p(x)$ the fluid pressure, and ρ the constant fluid density. The structure equations for the tube walls are given by a linear elastic constitutive relation with the (scalar) circumferential stress

$$\sigma_{\varphi\varphi} = E \frac{r - r_0}{r_0} + \sigma_0, \quad (4.9)$$

where E is Young's modulus and σ_0 the circumferential stress at reference position r_0 . The motion of the tube wall is, thus, limited to radial direction. The dynamic FSI interface conditions are given by

$$pr = \sigma_{\varphi\varphi}h, \quad (4.10)$$

where h is the thickness of the tube wall.

In the discretization of the scenario, a mesh is created by a one-dimensional tessellation of the tube of length L into N cells, such that each cell is of length $\Delta x = L/N$. The velocity and pressure unknowns are located at the center of each cell. Central finite

Fig. 4.3: Schematic drawing of a deformed tube with flow in x -direction, inner radius $r = r(x)$, length L , and wall thickness h . The fluid pressure $p = p(x)$ acting on the inner tube walls is causing scalar circumferential stresses $\sigma_{\varphi\varphi} = \sigma_{\varphi\varphi}(x)$ in the tube walls which lead to a deformation in radial direction.

differences are used for all terms in the fluid and structure equations besides for the convective flow terms. Here, a first order upwind scheme is used to stabilize the equations. An additional pressure stabilization term is added to the continuity equation (4.7). At the in- and outflow boundaries at $x = 0$ and $x = L$, respectively, a linear extrapolation of values from the cell centers is used. The time discretization for the fluid and structure equations is both done by a first-order backward Euler scheme with time step size Δt . The final equations are made dimensionless.

To study the behavior of different coupling schemes, two relevant characteristic quantities are defined in [44]. These are the dimensionless structural stiffness κ and dimensionless time step τ , reading

$$\kappa := \frac{1}{U_0} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{Eh}{2\rho r_0} - \frac{p_0}{2\rho}}}{u_0}, \quad \tau := \frac{U_0}{D_0 N} = \frac{u_0 \Delta t}{L}. \quad (4.11)$$

The initial velocity u_0 , the dimensionless initial velocity U_0 , the dimensionless spatial discretization width D_0 , and the initial pressure p_0 are used in the definition of κ and τ . A transient dimensionless inflow velocity is prescribed as

$$U_{in} = U_0 + \frac{U_0}{100} \sin^2\left(\pi \frac{n}{T}\right), \quad (4.12)$$

where n is the timestep number and T the oscillation period. The total number of timesteps computed is given by n_{end} .

Experiments

In the following, we look at the results of three experiments performed within this work to validate and compare the implemented implicit equation coupling schemes of Section 4.1.3. The first experiment investigates the influence of selected scenario parameters on the coupling iteration's convergence. The second experiment compares the

implemented methods' performance for increasingly unstable scenario parameters. The third experiment investigates the influence of initial value extrapolation on the number of required coupling iterations.

Experiment 1. The influence of the dimensionless structural stiffness κ , the number of spatial discretization cells N , and the dimensionless timestep τ on the number of coupling iterations is investigated using a block Gauss-Seidel scheme. Details and results of the experiment are given in Table 4.1. The results show that a smaller structural stiffness κ and, hence, larger reaction of the structure on the fluid pressure, results in an increased number of coupling iterations. An increase of the number of spatial cells, i.e., unknowns, also leads to more coupling iterations. Finally, the decrease of the timestep τ leads to more instabilities and, thus, a higher iteration number. These observations correspond to other results mentioned in Section 2.3.3. In particular, the increase of instabilities for decreasing timestep size is surprising in the light of similar analyses for PDEs, but typical for partitioned FSI simulations involving incompressible flows.

κ	N	τ	\bar{k}
1000	100	1e-0	3.92
		1e-1	4.88
		1e-2	6.96
		1e-3	50.71
	1000	1e-0	3.98
		1e-1	4.97
		1e-2	7.98
		1e-3	156.01
100	100	1e-0	4.98
		1e-1	7.98
		1e-2	202.86
		1e-3	div
	1000	1e-0	4.98
		1e-1	8.90
		1e-2	div
		1e-3	div

Tab. 4.1: Experiment 1. Investigation of the influence of the dimensionless structural stiffness κ , the number of spatial discretization cells N , and the dimensionless timestep τ on the average number of coupling iterations per timestep \bar{k} . A block Gauss-Seidel iteration scheme is used to establish the equation coupling. As coupling iteration convergence measure, a residual-relative measure (4.3) with a tolerance $\epsilon_{r-rel} = 10^{-7}$ for the pressure values is used (see Section 4.1.3). The number of timesteps computed is $n_{end} = 100$, which equals one inflow period T . The stiffness κ is modified by changing the dimensionless initial velocity U_0 . To modify τ independent from κ , the dimensionless spatial step D_0 is adapted. Unstable cases are marked with “div” for divergence.

Experiment 2. Different implicit equation coupling schemes are compared in terms of coupling iteration numbers and simulation runtime. Table 4.2 gives the details and results of the experiment. Several observations can be made from the measurements. Regarding the overall performance of the coupling schemes, a clear ordering is achieved. The most efficient scheme is the IQN-ILS, where a higher timestep reuse count yields better performance⁷. Next comes the Aitken-based dynamic relaxation, followed by the

⁷Despite not tested, the performance benefit is expected to vanish for a given problem when the number of reused timesteps is increased above some point. This is due to two arguments: first, the

$\tau \rightarrow$	1×10^{-3}		5×10^{-4}		1×10^{-4}	
	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}
block GS	156.0	35.8	div	div	div	div
const (0.9)	48.3	10.5	div	div	div	div
const (0.8)	25.8	5.7	div	div	div	div
const (0.7)	15.9	3.5	div	div	div	div
const (0.6)	14.8	3.3	96.2	24.3	div	div
const (0.5)	18.9	4.3	26.9	6.9	div	div
const (0.4)	25.7	5.8	24.3	6.2	div	div
const (0.3)	36.3	7.9	34.5	8.6	div	div
Aitken	7.0	1.8	9.4	2.5	26.6	6.4
IQN-ILS (0)	5.6	1.6	6.0	1.7	9.0	2.3
IQN-ILS (1)	4.1	1.3	4.2	1.3	5.8	1.7
IQN-ILS (2)	3.2	1.0	3.1	1.0	4.0	1.2
IQN-ILS (4)	3.2	1.0	3.2	1.0	3.1	1.0

Tab. 4.2: Experiment 2. Comparison of different implicit equation coupling schemes for three values of the dimensionless timestep τ . The average number of coupling iterations per timestep \bar{k} and runtime t relative to the fastest runtime t_{min} for one value of τ are measured. As coupling iteration convergence measure, a residual relative measure (4.3) with a tolerance of $\epsilon_{r-rel} = 10^{-7}$ measuring pressure values is used. The number of timesteps computed is $n_{end} = 100$ which equals one inflow period T . The initial velocity is $U_0 = 1.0$. To modify τ independent from κ , the dimensionless spatial step D_0 is modified as in Experiment 1 (Table 4.1). The table entry "div" denotes divergence of the coupling iterations. The coupling schemes used are a block Gauss-Seidel scheme (entry "block GS"), a constant underrelaxation scheme for block GS with relaxation factor ω (entry "constant (ω)"), a dynamic underrelaxation scheme for block GS using Aitken's extrapolation method (entry "Aitken"), and the interface Quasi-Newton scheme with approximation of the inverse of the Jacobian matrix by a least squares method with different numbers of timesteps reused (entry "IQN-ILS (timesteps reused)").

constant relaxation block Gauss-Seidel scheme. For the latter, there exists an optimal relaxation factor which is dependent on the scenario parameters. The difference in performance between the schemes is smaller for cases with larger timestep τ and becomes more and more pronounced for decreasing τ . Comparing the relative runtimes t/t_{min} with the average iteration count \bar{k} shows the difference in costs per iteration for the used coupling schemes. In an average iteration, the IQN-ILS scheme is about a factor of two slower than constant relaxation for block GS, and about a quarter slower than Aitken-based relaxation. The (relative) difference in runtime per iteration is expected to become smaller for problems with more expensive solver computations, particularly

IQN-ILS computational costs scale quadratically with the number of columns in the matrices \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} . Second, the benefit of reused timesteps relies on the resemblance of the computational model over a range of timesteps which becomes smaller and smaller for increasing transient distances.

for two- and three-dimensional surface coupled problems. Then, the coupling algorithms have to deal with data in one dimension lower than the overall coupled problem.

Experiment 3. The influence of the coupling value extrapolation order (see Section 4.1.3) on the convergence of the coupling iterations is investigated. Table 4.3 gives the details and results of the experiment. Different to Experiments 1 and 2, a coupling value relative convergence measure (4.2) is employed here, since a residual relative tolerance (4.3) would diminish the effect of the extrapolation. This is due to the fact that the residual relative measure determines convergence relative to the residual of the first coupling iteration which is obtained using the extrapolated values. When the extrapolation works better, the first residual becomes smaller which in turn requires a smaller iteration residual to pass the convergence test. Thus, the better initial residual does not show when looking at the overall coupling iteration numbers. The results of Experiment 3 show a clear improvement for the constant underrelaxation and dynamic Aitken methods, but little to no influence on the already close to optimal performance of the IQN-ILS scheme.

order →	0		1		2	
scheme	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}	\bar{k}	t/t_{min}
const (0.4)	23.24	71.4	18.28	5.6	17.20	5.2
Aitken	9.70	3.4	8.04	2.7	7.76	2.6
IQN-ILS (0)	5.98	2.1	5.92	2.3	5.90	1.9
IQN-ILS (4)	2.50	1.0	2.52	1.0	2.54	1.0

Tab. 4.3: Experiment 3. The influence of the coupling value extrapolation order (see Section 4.1.3) on the coupling iteration's convergence is investigated. The average number of coupling iterations per timestep \bar{k} and the runtime t relative to the fastest runtime t_{min} for one extrapolation order are measured for different coupling schemes used in Experiment 2 (Table 4.2). A relative convergence measure (4.2) with a tolerance of $\epsilon_r = 10^{-13}$ is employed to measure convergence of pressure coupling iterates. The dimensionless timestep is chosen to be $\tau = 0.0005$, the dimensionless structural stiffness to be $\kappa = 1000$, the number of spatial segments is $N = 1000$, and half of the inflow period $T = 100$ is computed, i.e., $n_{end} = 50$.

We summarize the findings of the experiments. First of all, the more severe the instabilities become, the larger is the advantage of more sophisticated schemes such as the IQN-ILS. For weakly instable cases, simpler schemes might lead to equivalent or better overall runtimes. To provide a choice of methods as implemented in preCICE makes it possible to adapt the coupling scheme to the problem to be solved. The experiment results obtained with the implemented methods agree well similar results found in literature [46].

4.1.5 Multi-Coupling Schemes

So far, we have only considered a coupling between two solvers. This is the typical FSI setup and the main focus of this work. However, many other multi-physics scenarios include more than just two physical fields or solvers which leads to multi-couplings. For example, a three-field coupling is given by fluid-structure-acoustic (FSA) interaction [105, 141, 96]. While the acoustic physics is basically inherent to the fluid physics, it can be beneficial to use different mathematical models for each of them, since they have different spatial and temporal scales. The acoustic sources are given by the structure in a surface-based coupling and by the fluid in a volume-based coupling. One way to achieve a decoupling of scales is to partition the acoustic domain into a near-field, coupled to the fluid and structure, and a far field, coupled to the near-field, where simplified linearized or wave equations are used. Figure 4.4a depicts an FSA scenario with an immersed structure that is partitioned into three surface-coupled fields. Multi-coupling does not necessarily imply an increasing number of different physical fields, but can also originate from multiple fields of the same type. An application example for this case is the FSI coupling with multiple separated fluids, as given by a fluid with a fully (or partially) immersed structure that is (partially) filled with another fluid. This situation occurs, e.g., for container ships with partially filled tanks [78]. Here, the surrounding fluid is not directly coupled to the inner fluid, but the interaction occurs via the coupling to the separating structure as depicted in Figure 4.4b. In this section, we look at the realization of such multi-coupling scenarios with *preCICE*.

Fig. 4.4: Illustration of a fluid-structure-acoustic (FSA) coupling (a) and a multi-fluid FSI coupling (b). In (a), the structure S is coupled to the fluid F and the acoustic near-field A_n via the boundary Γ_{FSA_n} . The acoustic near-field is coupled to the acoustic far-field A_f at the boundary $\Gamma_{A_n A_f}$. In (b), the inner fluid F_i is coupled to the structure S at Γ_{SF_i} and the structure to the outer fluid F_o at $\Gamma_{F_o S}$.

First of all, we consider the basic concept of multiple couplings applied in this work. We use graphs to visualize the coupling dependencies where the involved solvers are the

graph nodes. A coupling between two solvers defines one or two (anti-)directed edges between them, depending on whether the coupling is uni- or bi-directional. Incoming edges represent data to be read by a solver and outgoing edges represent data to be written. As illustrated in Figure 4.2, in a sequential execution logic one solver starts with a computation before writing data and waiting for data to be read, while the other solver has to wait for data to be read before computing and writing in turn. One end of a coupling is marked with a star $*$ to denote a solver that starts with a computation. We further have to distinguish explicit and implicit couplings. Implicit coupling dependencies are marked with an i and have to be executed repeatedly until convergence of the involved coupling scheme. With these definitions, we could depict single-coupling simulations. The standard Dirichlet-Neumann decomposed block Gauss-Seidel type FSI coupling (2.105), page 45, results in a fluid and a structure node connected by two anti-directed edges, as depicted in Figure 4.5.

Fig. 4.5: Block Gauss-Seidel type FSI coupling dependency graph with fluid node F , structure node S , implicit coupling annotation i , and starting solver annotation $*$.

As a next step, we have to come up with rules for the case of several couplings. In this work, a sequential ordering of coupling schemes is assumed. Every coupling (uni- or bi-directional) gets a global index which defines an ascending order. If one solver has several couplings, the global order defines its execution sequence. This does, however, not necessarily lead to a global sequentialization of solver computations. It remains to be defined how one solver executes the sequence of coupling schemes assigned to it. The following rules apply for a coupling timestep:

1. A sequence of explicit coupling schemes is executed together.
2. A sequence of implicit coupling schemes is repeatedly executed together, until convergence of all schemes.
3. If a sequence of implicit coupling schemes directly follows a sequence of explicit coupling schemes, the first iteration of the implicit schemes is executed together with the explicit coupling schemes.
4. If a sequence of explicit coupling schemes directly follows a sequence of implicit coupling schemes, the explicit schemes are executed together with the last iteration of the implicit schemes.

When speaking of "executing" a coupling scheme, a call of its method `advance` is meant. A sequence of schemes directly following another sequence means that there are no other schemes between. Also a single scheme is considered as a sequence here. We go through an example for clarification. In the example, we consider a solver with six (of eight global) couplings assigned. E_i denotes an explicit scheme, I_i an implicit scheme, and i the global coupling scheme index. The sequence of schemes assigned to the solver shall

be

$$(E_1, E_3, I_4, I_5, E_7, I_8). \quad (4.13)$$

Note that the indices must not be contiguous, since not every coupling scheme is related to every solver in general. In this sequence, first, schemes E_1, E_3, I_4, I_5 would be executed together, then schemes I_4, I_5 are executed repeatedly until both have been converged. In the last (converging) iteration of I_4, I_5 , schemes E_7, I_8 are already executed, followed by the repeated execution of scheme I_8 until its convergence.

Fig. 4.6: FSA (a) and multi-fluid (b) coupling dependency graphs.

We can now reconsider the FSA example from Figure 4.4a and draw the dependency graph for it. We assume that the coupling of the structure S to the fluid and the near-field acoustics FA_n is implicit and the fluid to the acoustic far-field A_f coupling is one-way explicit. Figure 4.6a shows the dependencies of such a three-field FSA coupling. The implicit coupling precedes the explicit coupling here. Thus, in one timestep first the FA_n - S coupling is iterated, followed by the computation of the acoustic far-field. The multi-fluid example of Figure 4.4b is set up using two implicit couplings in Figure 4.6b. Here, both implicit couplings are iterated at the same time. Since both fluid solvers (F_i and F_o) are starting their coupling, an interfield-parallel execution of F_i and F_o results, followed by the structure solver S .

The above described multi-coupling features are implemented in *preCICE* in the class `CompositionalCouplingScheme` (see Figure 4.1). All coupling schemes and participating solvers in the coupled simulation are defined in the XML configuration. The sequence of coupling schemes in the configuration defines the global order of schemes in the simulation. `CompositionalCouplingScheme` obtains all schemes of its local participant and manages the execution of them according to the rules discussed above. The dependencies between the solvers are implicitly imposed by the data read and write dependencies, i.e., a solver is blocked automatically when waiting for data from another solver. A careless setup of coupling schemes and participants can lead to a deadlock in the coupled simulation. The described implementation keeps the coupling connections and data exchange transparent to the solvers, i.e., a solver does not know how many other solvers it is coupled to, besides from the data to be read and written.

4.2 Data Mapping for Non-Matching Grids

Besides the coupling of the partitioned equations, another important group of functionality is the mapping of data between non-matching or non-conforming (interface) meshes of the coupled solvers. The basis of any mapping are meshes and we review their realization and handling within preCICE in Section 4.2.1. Then, we consider the design and implementation of data mapping methods in Section 4.2.2. A new method to ensure the conservativity of a mapping is presented in Section 4.2.3. Finally, numerical experiments are performed to evaluate and compare the different methods implemented in Section 4.2.4.

4.2.1 Coupling Meshes and Data

As every coupling data mapping occurs between two meshes, these form the basis to be considered first. In this section, the realization of meshes in preCICE is reviewed. A mesh in preCICE can consist of vertices, edges, and triangles, where the use of triangles is restricted to three-dimensional scenarios. Thus, the meshes represent one- or two-dimensional surfaces in a two- or three-dimensional space. The choice of linear surface elements, i.e., edges and triangles, greatly simplifies geometric operations such as projections. Since only one of the implemented mapping methods requires a surface description, it will often be feasible to only use a cloud of vertices without connections by edges and triangles, called vertex mesh in the following. Coupling data are associated to vertices in preCICE. No cell centered data description exists currently, but cell centered data values can be modeled by vertex meshes.

Fig. 4.7: Main classes of the component mesh and their relations.

Meshes are realized in the component `mesh` and comprise the description of mesh elements, i.e., vertices, edges, and triangles, as well as the coupling data associated to these. Figure 4.7 shows a class diagram with the relevant parts of `mesh`. The class `Mesh`

is responsible for creating, managing, and destroying mesh elements and coupling data. It uses the class `Group` as container to hold the created mesh elements. `Group` allows to assemble related mesh elements in subgroups, which is used for the spacetime functionality described in Section 4.4. The mesh elements are represented by the classes `Triangle`, `Edge`, and `Vertex`. The mesh topology is established in a singly-linked fashion. Edges are represented explicitly in a triangular mesh. This allows to work on edges directly and avoids checks for multiple treatments of the same edge, which would be necessary in case of a mesh description with triangles and vertices only. The additional memory overhead is not critical, since the coupling mesh lives in a sub-manifold compared to the overall computation. Coupling data are modeled by the class `Data` which holds a vector of values. Each data vector corresponds to one coupling data type such as forces or displacements associated to a mesh. Thus, several coupling meshes can be used where each mesh can have an own set of coupling data with possibly same type. Coupling data values are associated to a vertex via the vertex ID. Coupling data can be of scalar or vectorial type, where both are stored in a linearized form. In some cases, it is necessary to determine the mesh that a vertex is associated to. To enable this functionality, each vertex holds a reference to the mesh it belongs to.

It remains to be described how meshes are created in *preCICE*. Three ways have been implemented: a mesh can be created either by a generating piece of source code, it can be read from a file, or it can be provided by a solver using the API. Since for coupled simulations the latter is of biggest importance, we focus on solver mesh creation here. The other mechanisms are discussed in more detail in Section 4.4. A solver has to use the API methods given in Algorithm 3.4, page 113, in order to provide its surface mesh to *preCICE*. By default, the provided mesh exists for the providing solver only. In order to perform a data mapping, the involved meshes need to be at the same place, i.e., at the same peer in the peer-to-peer communication scheme used in *preCICE*. To resolve this situation, a communication mechanism has been implemented that performs the transfer of selected meshes to the coupling partner. Which meshes are communicated is selected through the configuration and is, hence, transparent to a solver. Figure 4.8 shows an FSI example mesh setup, where the flow solver provides its vertex nodes and cell center positions to *preCICE* and the structure solver provides its triangular surface mesh. The structure mesh is transferred to the flow solver such that a mapping from flow nodes to structure nodes and from structure nodes to flow cell centers becomes possible.

4.2.2 Realization of Data Mapping

We have seen how meshes are represented in *preCICE* and how they can be provided by the solvers. As next step, we consider the realization of the data mappings in *preCICE*. We first review general properties of the implemented mappings and then go into the details of each. Currently, three different mappings are implemented: a nearest-neighbor, a nearest-projection, and a radial basis function mapping, based on the reviewed methods

Fig. 4.8: Example of a preCICE mesh and data mapping setup of an FSI simulation. The boxes represent the flow and structure executables. The structure solver provides a full surface mesh which is transferred to the flow solver. The flow solver locally provides node and cell center positions (crosses and circles) to preCICE. Two mappings take place on the flow side which are between the structure surface mesh and flow surface nodes and surface cell centers.

in Section 2.4.

In Section 2.4.1, mappings are distinguished into consistent and conservative types. Consistent mappings interpolate constant values exactly while conservative mappings conserve the overall sum of the values. All implemented mappings can be used as consistent and conservative type. To switch between types, the transposed mapping relations are computed. Choosing a consistent mapping for both data transfer directions yields the consistent data mapping approach mentioned in Section 2.4.2. To realize the conservative data mapping approach, access to the interpolating basis functions of the flow solver is necessary. With this, the flow solver can provide pressure fluxes according to (2.217), page 73, instead of pressures. If the consistent and conservative versions of the same mapping are used, the conservative mapping approach according to [57] is achieved. Note that the structure solver needs to be able to take forces instead of pressures as input in that case.

Different coupled simulations can require to perform the data mappings at different moments of the simulation. For example, in simulations where both solvers have a Lagrangian coupling surface description, the relative position of the solver surface meshes changes only due to numerical errors. This is the case, e.g., in FSI simulations with an ALE flow description and a Lagrangian structure description. It is best in such a case to compute the data mapping relations only once in the initial setting of the meshes and to use these relations throughout the simulation. On the other hand, if the coupling surface is subject to remeshings as for fixed-grid solvers with Eulerian coupling surface description, the mapping relations need to be computed anew whenever the surface mesh changes. If remeshing occurs only occasionally, driven by solver-internal measures, a solver might decide when to trigger a recomputation of mapping relations. For some mappings it is possible to perform a mapping incrementally, i.e., no global mapping matrix is established and stored, but each data value is mapped independently. An incremental approach is more efficient in terms of memory usage. All above mentioned scenarios have been realized in preCICE within this work. The use of a particular strategy is determined by the configuration and, hence, transparent to a solver.

Fig. 4.9: Main classes of the component `mapping` and their relations. `mapping` gathers all data mapping methods between two meshes and provides them via the abstract class `Mapping`. For clarity, inherited methods and variables are not displayed in subclasses.

The mapping functionality is gathered in the component `mapping`, as depicted in the class diagram of Figure 4.9. To make the employed mapping exchangeable, the class `Mapping` acts as interface. A mapping does not know about its context, it only obtains two meshes from outside which are defined at configuration time. The methods `computeMapping` and `map` are responsible for computing the mapping relations (potentially in form of a mapping matrix) and transferring the values using the relations. This decomposition into two methods enables the different mapping timings mentioned in the last paragraph. The concrete mappings are encapsulated in the classes `NearestNeighborMapping`, `NearestProjectionMapping`, and `RadialBasisFunctionMapping`. We have a more detailed look at each of them in the following.

Nearest Neighbor Mapping

The nearest neighbor mapping is based on the search for the geometrically nearest neighbor, i.e., a vertex with shortest Euclidean distance to a given vertex. This geometrical functionality is required at several other places in `preCICE` and is put into a separate component called `query`. To perform the mapping, obviously only vertex meshes are required. The explicit representation of vertices in `preCICE` allows to iterate over them without taking into account triangles or edges. The mapping of data values can be performed incrementally, since each value is mapped independently. When the vertex relations are to be stored, a vector of indices suffices and the explicit creation of a mapping matrix \mathbf{H} is not required. This dramatically reduces the memory required by the mapping, since every row of \mathbf{H} would contain only one entry.

Nearest Projection Mapping

The nearest projection mapping is implemented based on [25]. Its core functionality is finding the mesh element with shortest orthogonal projection distance. As for the nearest

neighbor mapping, these features are put into the component `query` and consist of finding the closest projection on triangles, edges, and vertices. The latter functionality coincides with that of the nearest neighbor mapping. All three are executed independently on their corresponding mesh element type. After this step, among the three results the element with shortest projection distance is chosen. If this is a triangle, the three triangle vertices are involved. In case of an edge, the edge vertices are used. In case of a vertex, the nearest neighbor method is used. Algorithm 4.3 illustrates this procedure.

```

1  find nearest vertex
2  find shortest projection to edge
3  find shortest projection to triangle
4  if triangle is nearest
5      store triangle vertices and weights
6  else if edge is nearest
7      store edge vertices and weights
8  else
9      store vertex

```

Alg. 4.3: Algorithm for computing mapping relations in nearest projection mapping. Each group of mesh elements is queried independently (lines 1-3).

In order to perform the projections, a full mesh description is required for one of the involved meshes. When a consistent mapping is performed, the input mesh can be a vertex mesh while the output mesh has to be a full mesh. For a conservative mapping, the reverse is true. This allows to employ the mapping in a typical FSI setup (as depicted in Figure 4.2.2), where the structure solver provides a full surface mesh description to the flow solver, while the flow solver provides only the positions for pressures and displacements. Since the individual values are independent again, no mapping matrix \mathbf{H} needs to be set up, but a mere storage of the vertex relations in form of an array of linked lists is used.

Radial Basis Function Mapping

Different radial basis functions have been implemented based on the approach in [17]. The class `RadialBasisFunction` (see Figure 4.9) implements the frame of the RBF mapping, i.e., the setup and the solution of the involved interpolation and evaluation matrices. The concrete RBF type is plugged in as a C++ template parameter which prevents the overhead of virtual function evaluations. Several RBF types with varying accuracy, continuity, and compact or global support have been implemented. The implemented RBF types are summarized in Table 4.4. A thin-plate spline (no 1), multi-quadrics (no 2), inverse multiquadrics (no 3), a volume spline (no 4), a Gaussian (no 5), a compact thin-plate spline of C^2 continuity (no 6), a compact polynomial of C^0 continuity (no 7), and a compact polynomial of C^6 continuity (no 8) have been implemented.

no	type	$\phi(\ \mathbf{x}\)$
1	<i>TPS</i>	$\ \mathbf{x}\ ^2 \log(\ \mathbf{x}\)$
2	<i>MQ</i>	$\sqrt{a^2 + \ \mathbf{x}\ ^2}$
3	<i>IMQ</i>	$1/\sqrt{a^2 + \ \mathbf{x}\ ^2}$
4	<i>VS</i>	$\ \mathbf{x}\ $
5	<i>G</i>	$\exp(-(a \ \mathbf{x}\)^2)$
6	<i>CTPS, C²</i>	$1 - 30\xi^2 - 10\xi^3 + 45\xi^4 - 6\xi^5 - 60\xi^3 \log \xi$
7	<i>CP, C⁰</i>	$(1 - \xi)^2$
8	<i>CP, C⁶</i>	$(1 - \xi)^8 (32\xi^3 + 25\xi^2 + 8\xi + 1)$

Tab. 4.4: Implemented RBFs with global support (no 1–5) and compact support (no 6–8). Some RBFs use a shape parameter a for tuning. The compact support RBFs have a support radius r , i.e., $\phi(\|\mathbf{x}\|) = 0$ for $\|\mathbf{x}\| > r$ and use $\xi := \|\mathbf{x}\|/r$.

To compute the mapping relations, the interpolant matrix is set up and an *LU*-decomposition is performed. Since every data transfer (for every spatial dimension) in the RBF approach requires to solve the interpolation system with a different right-hand side, the *LU*-decomposition reduces the costs of each subsequent solution to quadratic runtime complexity with respect to the number of involved interpolation nodes. The matrix is transposed in case of a conservative mapping type. Due to the interdependence of the mapped values, an incremental mapping cannot be supported.

The implemented mapping methods are compared in Section 4.2.4 together with a new approach for conservative data mapping presented in the following section.

4.2.3 A New Method for Conservation of Mapped Values

In Section 2.4.2, we have reviewed the conservative mapping approach presented in [57]. It is shown in [40] that, when a generic mapping is applied in the conservative approach, the mapped pressures are non-consistent and the mapped pressure fluxes as well as pressures can have large oscillations. Additionally, often only pressures can be set at numerical integration points of a structure solver such that the conservative approach as presented in [57] is not applicable.

Within this work, an alternative scheme to ensure the conservativity of virtual work at the coupling interface has been developed. It is based on the consistent approach, i.e., the use of two independent consistent mappings for the fluid and for the structural values. The difference of virtual work is measured afterwards and the error is shifted to the mapped pressure values by re-scaling them. This approach still requires access to (or knowledge of) the basis functions of the mapped displacements and pressures on the fluid and the structure side as well as the solvers' FSI surface geometries.

We have seen in Section 2.4.2 that the discrete virtual work δW at the FSI interface Γ can be expressed as a double sum over basis functions

$$\delta W = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \underbrace{\int_{\Gamma} N_i^p(\mathbf{x}) N_j^u(\mathbf{x}) ds}_{=: M_{ij}} \mathbf{u}_j \cdot \mathbf{p}_i, \quad (4.14)$$

with discrete displacement vectors \mathbf{u}_j , discrete directed pressure vectors \mathbf{p}_i , and their basis functions $N_j^u(\mathbf{x})$, $N_i^p(\mathbf{x})$. The pressure and the basis functions are combined to a pressure flux Φ_j in [57] (see (2.217), page 73), in order to perform the conservative mapping in the conservative approach. Equation (4.14) can then be written as

$$\delta W = \sum_{j=1}^n \Phi_j \cdot \mathbf{u}_j, \quad \text{with } \Phi_j := \sum_{i=1}^n M_{ij} \mathbf{p}_i, \quad (4.15)$$

where the pressure flux variables are associated to the displacements. In this work, an alternative combination of basis functions with displacement variables is proposed as

$$\delta W = \sum_{i=1}^n \Psi_i \cdot \mathbf{p}_i, \quad \text{with } \Psi_i := \sum_{j=1}^n M_{ij} \mathbf{u}_j. \quad (4.16)$$

The Ψ_i can be interpreted as displacement fluxes. If pressures and displacements are located at different positions at a solver's FSI interface, (4.15) and (4.16) allow to make use of either the displacement or the pressure positions for the computation of the virtual work. In particular, (4.16) allows to work with the mapped pressures on the structure side that occur in the consistent mapping approach.

Applying the consistent mapping approach results in two different amounts of virtual work at the fluid and the structure FSI boundary

$$\delta W_F - \delta W_S \neq 0. \quad (4.17)$$

This difference results from the discrete representation of the continuous variables by basis functions, the mapping errors of displacements and pressures, and from the approximations of the surface integrals. In a reasonably set up application scenario, all these errors have the same order. Thus, we can assume that the difference of virtual work on the fluid and the structure side is given as

$$\delta W_F - \delta W_S = O(h^p), \quad (4.18)$$

where h defines the (maximum) mesh width of a solver's mesh at the FSI surface and p the error order. To correct the balance of virtual work, we can modify the mapped pressures (4.16) on the structure side as

$$\delta W_S^c = \sum_{i=1}^n \Psi_i \cdot (1+s) \mathbf{p}_i \quad (4.19)$$

$$\delta W_S^c = (1+s) \sum_{i=1}^n \Psi_i \cdot \mathbf{p}_i \quad (4.20)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \delta W_S^c = (1+s) \delta W_S. \quad (4.21)$$

The scaling factor s is chosen such that the corrected virtual work fulfills the balance

$$\delta W_F^c - \delta W_S = 0 \quad (4.22)$$

which is equivalent to

$$(1 + s)\delta W_S - \delta W_F = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad s = \frac{\delta W_F - \delta W_S}{\delta W_S} = O(h^p). \quad (4.23)$$

This implies in particular that the pressure correction is of acceptable size since it is of the same order as already present errors. Using a constant scalar scaling s for all values results in an equal change of relative errors of the coupling quantities, pertains the smoothness of the mapped values, and preserves their zero-crossings. To give an illustration, Figure 4.10 shows a function $f(x)$ with three different scalings.

Fig. 4.10: Constant scalar scaling of a function $f(x)$ with a factor s . The scaling $s = 1$ corresponds to the original function, while $s = 0.5$ halves the function values and $s = 2$ doubles them.

In the next section, we look at an example where the pressure post-processing is applied and see its effect on the pressure errors.

4.2.4 Comparison of Mapping Methods

In the following, we consider a simple mapping scenario to compare the accuracies of the implemented mappings. We furthermore evaluate the conservation of virtual work when considering the consistent mapping approach with these mappings and the effect of the pressure (flux) post-processing approach described in the previous Section 4.2.3.

To evaluate the different mapping methods, we use a two-dimensional FSI scenario with spatial variables x and y . The fluid and structure surface meshes in the scenario

Fig. 4.11: Coupling surface geometry (a) and (scalar) coupling data values pressure and displacement to be mapped (b).

consist of vertices connected by linear edges that approximate the exact FSI wet surface given by

$$y(x) = 0.5 \sin(2\pi x), \quad x \in [-0.5; 0.5] \quad (4.24)$$

and depicted in Figure 4.11a. Both, structure and fluid have mesh vertices spread equidistantly in x -direction, i.e., $x_{F,i} = \frac{i}{n_F-1} - 0.5, i = 0, 1, \dots, n_F - 1$ and $x_{S,j} = \frac{j}{n_S-1} - 0.5, j = 0, 1, \dots, n_S - 1$, with the number of fluid and structure vertices n_F and n_S . The meshes are non-matching, as n_F and n_S differ according to

$$n_F = 40 \cdot 2^k, \quad n_S = 10 \cdot 2^k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, 8, \quad (4.25)$$

where k is the refinement index. Due to the linear geometric approximation, the discretization error of the fluid and the structure mesh is $O(1/n_F^2)$ and $O(1/n_S^2)$, respectively. An exact pressure function $p(x)$ and displacement function $u(x)$ is given according to

$$p(x) = 0.05 \cos(2\pi x), \quad u(x) = 0.05(x + 0.5) \cos(2\pi x), \quad x \in [-0.5; 0.5], \quad (4.26)$$

as depicted in Figure 4.11b. The functions are sampled at the fluid and the structure vertices to give the exact values $u(x_{F,i}), p(x_{F,i})$ and $u(x_{S,j}), p(x_{S,j})$. The exact displacements are mapped from the structure to the fluid and denoted there by $u_{F,i}$. The exact pressures are mapped from the fluid to the structure and denoted there by $p_{S,j}$. As described in the previous section, a post-processing is applied to the pressures to ensure the conservation of virtual work. The corrected pressures are denoted by $p_{S,j}^c$.

We first consider the relative errors of the consistently mapped displacements and pressures in comparison to the exact values. The relative error of the mapped displacements

Fig. 4.12: Relative error of the mapped displacements at the fluid mesh (a) and relative error of the mapped pressures at the structure mesh (b).

ments is given by

$$e_{rel}^u = \frac{\sum_i^{n_F} (u(x_{F,i}) - u_{F,i})^2}{\sum_i^{n_F} u(x_{F,i})^2} \quad (4.27)$$

and that of the pressures by

$$e_{rel}^p = \frac{\sum_i^{n_S} (p(x_{S,i}) - p_{S,i})^2}{\sum_i^{n_S} p(x_{S,i})^2}. \quad (4.28)$$

Figure 4.12 shows the relative errors for mapped displacements and pressures using the aforementioned data mapping methods in consistent mode. For the mapped displacements (Figure 4.12a), the NN mapping shows the largest errors and the lowest convergence order of approximately one. Most of the other mappings are comparable with an error order of approximately two. The CP6 mapping shows the fastest convergence of order six, after an initial period with too few points. The mapped pressures (Figure 4.12b) show similar results. Here, the TPS mapping performs slightly better and the CP6 mapping reaches numerical rounding error level already. Overall, the pressures show better accuracy, due to the finer resolution of the source mesh, which is used to establish the interpolant of the consistent mappings.

As a second experiment, we concentrate on the balance of virtual work and the effect of the post-processing introduced in Section 4.2.3. The virtual work is computed at fluid and at structure side by using one native and one mapped set of data values. The difference of the virtual work on fluid and on structure side is computed and scaled by the virtual work on structure side to get a relative error measure. In Figure 4.13a, the relative

Fig. 4.13: Relative error of the virtual work (a) and relative error of the scaled pressures at the structure mesh (b).

errors of the virtual work balance are displayed for the employed mappings. The errors show a maximal convergence order of two, limited by the second order approximation order of the surface integrals. After the post-processing, the difference in virtual work is zero. However, now the error has been shifted to the pressure values. Figure 4.13b shows the relative errors of the corrected pressures on the structure side. The errors are limited by the errors of the virtual work, i.e., the errors of the surface integrals and both mapping errors play a role.

In conclusion, a set of data mappings has been implemented with varying computational complexity and approximation orders. All methods support the consistent and conservative data mapping approach. Furthermore, a new method to support conservation of virtual work has been deduced and tested. It works with pressure or displacement positions and two (potentially) independent consistent mappings and, thus, gives a greater flexibility than the conservative approach. However, in case of non-constant basis functions, it still requires access to the basis function surface integrals of the coupled solvers.

4.3 Inter-Solver Communication Methods

The preceding sections 4.1 and 4.2 have dealt with numerical methods required for partitioned coupling. These methods work with the data provided by the partitioned simulation programs, which are typically executed as separate processes or groups of

processes on a computer. In order to exchange data between the programs, some form of interprocess communication is, hence, required. In the following Section 4.3.1, the realization of such communication methods within *preCICE* is discussed and an evaluation and comparison of the implemented methods is performed in Section 4.3.2. Also, the implemented coupling approach for parallel solvers is evaluated there.

4.3.1 Realization of Communication Methods

In contrast to equation coupling and data mapping, which are numerics based, interprocess communication is dominated by technical aspects of computer science. In particular, we are interested in the aspects of data transfer speed, compute resource usage, compatibility with solver built-in communication libraries, portability to different computing systems such as supercomputers, and suitability for parallel coupling. We first consider these aspects in more detail, before we review the software design of the communication methods and the implemented methods.

Important Aspects

One of the most important aspects of interest is the data transfer speed or throughput of a communication method, i.e., how much data can be communicated in a given time. This property is on the one hand limited by the specific hardware used, e.g., by the bandwidth and latency of provided network interconnections. On the other hand, the communication protocol, the communication pattern, and the specific parts of the hardware used (e.g., a dedicated communication network versus the file system) in the communication method influence the data transfer speed.

Another aspect of importance is the compute resource usage of a communication method. This refers to the idle times which occur when a compute thread needs to be synchronized with a communication partner in order to receive or send data. Some communication methods only support a busy-waiting mechanism which features very short thread activation times but completely blocks the core on which the thread is executed. On the other hand, a non-busy-waiting synchronization sets the thread to be synchronized asleep. This entails a longer wake up time but frees the compute resources associated to the thread. When interfield-sequential equation coupling schemes are used, the solvers compute in an alternating fashion such that only one set of compute resources would be required. Here, the non-busy-waiting allows to use the same compute resources for both solvers.

The compatibility of a communication method with a given solver is also an important issue. Particularly for commercial solvers, where the use of a specific version and type of an internal communication library is prescribed, the use of the same communication library with different version can lead to source code linking or runtime errors. In this case, an alternative communication method has to be chosen.

In order to use a communication method in different computing hardware, it needs to be supported by each of those. The availability of communication ports or dedicated network addresses is of critical importance, thus.

Finally, the suitability of a communication method for comparatively fine grained data exchange as occurring in simulations with parallel solvers is an important characteristic. This relates in particular to the latency of a communication method, i.e., the overhead in every communication call before the communication channel is ready for the actual data transmission.

Software Design

In preCICE, all communication methods are gathered in component `com`. Figure 4.14 shows a class diagram with relevant parts of `com`. To hide the concrete communication mechanism in the other components of preCICE, the interface class `Communication` is used. The concrete communication classes `FileCommunication`, `SocketCommunication`, `MPIDirectCommunication`, and `MPIPortsCommunication` implement that interface. Both, `MPIDirectCommunication` as well `MPIPortsCommunication` use the `send` and `receive` implementation inherited from class `MPICommunication`, they only differ on how they set up the communication connection. The class diagram shows only a generic `send` and `receive` method, the actual implementation has a pair for every needed data type. Note the methods for starting and finishing `send` and `receive` packages. These enable an explicit buffering of data which is (so far only) used in the file communication described in the next paragraph.

File Communication

The file communication mechanism is the most basic form of communication implemented in preCICE. It is based on writing and reading from files located at the harddisk of a computer. Algorithm 4.4 shows the characteristic methods for the implemented file communication. First of all, the file communication is (currently) the only form of communication implemented that makes use of the explicit buffering mechanism provided by the `start/finish send/receive package` methods (lines 1, 8, 11, and 19). This removes the latencies occurring when creating and deleting a file from the harddisk which would otherwise result for every call of `send` and `receive`. The buffered reading and writing requires a synchronization mechanism in order to ensure that a `send file` is finished before it is available for reading. This is done by introducing a `send file` as `hidden` (line 2), i.e., to simply use another filename for it, and to rename it once a `send package` has been finished (line 9). The reader queries for the `send file` (line 12), by performing a busy-waiting while loop. When the `send file` is available, the receiver renames it and reads data from it. In order to be able to distinguish simultaneous file messages, each file is named uniquely including the sender and receiver name as well as a message counter. The implemented file communication only supports a one-to-one communication lay-

Fig. 4.14: Main classes of the component `com` and their relations. Inherited methods are omitted, besides for `MPICommunication` which implements `send` and `receive` operations for its subclasses.

out, i.e., at each communication endpoint only one thread can be involved in the file communication.

One of the main drawbacks of the file communication scheme is its comparatively slow data transfer speed which is owed to the harddisk as communication medium. The big advantage of it is the independence from additional communication libraries which also avoids conflicts with solver communication libraries. As mentioned above, the implementation uses a busy waiting mechanism for the receiver of a message and compute resources are, hence, blocked by a solver in an interfield sequential partitioned simulation. Nonetheless, file communication provides a fall-back solution when other communication methods fail. As long as the message granularity is not too small, as is the case in the solver-to-solver communication of, e.g., FSI simulations, the performance of the file communication is still feasible.

MPI Communication

The message passing interface (MPI) [65] is used to implement a communication method in `preCICE`. The typical usage of MPI is to parallelize software for distributed memory systems. A single program multiple data (SPMD) paradigm is used in that case, i.e., each (parallel) process runs the same code but with different parametrization by its process index. In the frame of this work, MPI has been used according to a multiple

```

1  startSendPackage():
2      create hidden send file
3
4  send(data):
5      write data to hidden send file
6      advance write position in file
7
8  finishSendPackage():
9      make hidden send file available
10
11 startReceivePackage():
12     while send file not available
13     rename send file to receive file name
14
15 receive(data):
16     read data from receive file
17     advance read position in file
18
19 finishReceivePackage():
20     delete receive file

```

Alg. 4.4: Relevant methods for file communication.

program multiple data (MPMD) paradigm, where two different codes are communicating with their own data. Two versions of MPI-based communication methods have been implemented which differ in their way on how to set up the communication connection (or communication space in MPI terminology). The first version (implemented in `MPIDirectCommunication`) uses a more standard MPI approach which is based on the common startup of all executables in the same MPI communication space called communicator world. The processes of each communication endpoint (e.g., a coupled solver) are then grouped into separate communicators and an inter-communicator is used to define the actual communication channel used for exchanging data. Figure 4.15 illustrates that concept. The second MPI-based communication version (implemented in `MPIPortsCommunication`) uses a part of the process creation and management in MPI, which became available only in version 2. There defined API functions allow to establish a connection between processes started individually and in different communication spaces. In order to exchange connection information, the port name is written to a commonly accessible file. The result of the connection is again an inter-communicator, as for the first MPI communication version implemented. Since only the implementation of the connection is different in the two communication versions, a common code base for send and receive methods is shared through superclass `MPICommunication`. Both MPI-based communications support a one-to-many communication layout. The client-server deployment scheme used by preCICE to couple parallel solvers is thus supported.

Fig. 4.15: MPI communicator layout when using the common startup MPI communication version in *preCICE*. The Solver A and the Solver B processes are started up together in a shared communicator world. They are grouped afterwards into subcommunicators A and B. An inter-communicator is used to establish the *preCICE* communication channel used for the data exchange.

MPI is the de-facto standard for distributed memory parallelization and as such features high data throughput rates. Due to its popularity, MPI is supported on practically every scientific compute cluster or supercomputer. The wide use of MPI in solvers makes it necessary to use a corresponding version in *preCICE* in order to avoid runtime conflicts. The MPI implementations such as MPICH2 [99] use a busy-waiting mechanism for process synchronization. Compute resources can, thus, not be shared among two solvers using an interfield-sequential equation coupling scheme.

Socket Communication

A communication scheme based on sockets has been implemented in *preCICE*. The Boost.Asio (asynchronous network and low-level input/output) library [36] has been used to abstract from the platform dependent socket interface such as Pthreads or Winsock. To send and receive data, the transfer control protocol (TCP) is used. This protocol is designed for a failsafe data transfer and involves a handshake mechanism, i.e., a synchronization of sender and receiver. The Asio library provides basic synchronous as well as asynchronous send and receive operations based on the TCP protocol.

In order to support a client-server communication scenario with many client threads, a mechanism to receive a message from any (non-specified) client thread is required. This mechanism has been implemented using an additional execution thread on server side that asynchronously receives send requests from all clients and puts them in a queue for the main server thread. When a receive is issued in the main server thread, a specific client can be chosen or the receive can be expected from any client (associated to the server). In the latter case, an arbitrary client is chosen from the queue. If no client has sent a request, the main server thread needs to wait until the additional thread receives a new request. Both, the waiting on a normal receive and the waiting for a new request

are implemented by using operating system signals, which results in a non-busy waiting. The receive logic for one receive call of the server main thread is shown in Algorithm 4.5.

```

1  client ← not found
2  while client = not found
3      if receive from any client and queries not empty
4          client ← first client in queries
5          delete first client in queries
6      else if queries contain specific client
7          client ← specific client
8          delete specific client from queries
9      if client = not found
10         wait for incoming client request
11 receive data from client
12 async receive next request from client

```

Alg. 4.5: Receive logic of the server thread in the socket communication implementation. Lines 1-10 determine the client to receive from. The server main thread is set asleep on line 10 until a new client request is received by an additional query thread. After receiving data from a chosen client (line 11), a new asynchronous receive operation is started for the chosen client.

The TCP communication protocol used is not typical for HPC software, since it involves a synchronization of sender and receiver and other unnecessary overhead. Interferences with solver communication libraries are a non-issue here, in comparison to MPI. On supercomputers, the ports used by socket communication might be blocked by default. Another difficulty on supercomputers is that each node involved in the computation might have a different network address, not known a priori. This makes an automated check for the network address necessary which involves low-level socket API functions. In preCICE, this is implemented using the Pthreads API only, which is commonly available on supercomputers. The non-busy waiting mechanisms allow to reuse compute resources by several solvers in case when an interfield-sequential equation coupling scheme is used.

4.3.2 Evaluation of Communication Methods and Parallelization Approach

In this section, a comparison of the implemented communication methods in terms of data transfer speed is done. Furthermore, an evaluation of the server approach used for coupling intrafield-parallel solvers is performed. All measurement results shown in the following have been obtained on the MAC Research Cluster hosted at the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre. The Sandy-Bridge partition of the machine has been used, which consists of 28 nodes connected by a QDR Infiniband network. Every node consists

of 2 Intel SandyBridge-EP Xeon E5-2670 processors with 8 cores each. In total, the partition has 448 cores and 128 GB RAM main memory for parallel computations.

First of all, to have a reference for the performance of the pure communication, a measurement using the implemented MPI communication is performed. In this initial experiment, an array of $8 \cdot 10^6$ C++ (8 byte sized) double values is sent 10 times back and forth between two executables running on two different compute nodes. The resulting time measured is 0.397 seconds. Thus, a data throughput of

$$\text{throughput}_{\text{MPI}} = \frac{8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 8 \cdot 8 \cdot 20 \text{ bit}}{0.397 \text{ sec}} = 25,793,450,882 \frac{\text{bit}}{\text{sec}} \approx 24 \frac{\text{Gbit}}{\text{sec}} \quad (4.29)$$

is achieved.

The following measurements are performed using solver proxy executables which do not compute any actual data, but merely call the preCICE API methods with unchanged data arrays. Thus, what is measured is the time preCICE needs to manage and communicate coupling data. A coupling mesh with a controllable number of vertices and, hence, number of data values is used. One set of vector data (with two double entries per vertex) is communicated from the first solver proxy to the second. Another set with the same size is sent in the other direction in every timestep. A total of ten timesteps is performed and averaged to get a runtime measure for one timestep.

Experiment 1. The three implemented communication methods are compared in terms of their data transfer speeds. No data is read or written by the solver proxies from or to preCICE in this experiment, resulting in the mere communication of unchanged data values. Table 4.5 shows the averaged runtimes for one timestep measured for the second solver proxy. The highest number of vertices used is $4 \cdot 10^6$, which corresponds to an amount of $8 \cdot 10^6$ double values. Thus, the MPI timing with the highest vertex number can be compared to the initial experiment and the non-communication preCICE overhead (without reading or writing data) can be estimated to be $3.97/4.63 < 10\%$. Figure 4.16 shows two graphical interpretations of the same results. The left graph shows the absolute runtime, while the right graph shows the runtime divided by the MPI runtime, which is fastest for high vertex numbers. We can conclude from the left graph that the runtime at lower vertex numbers is approximately constant, while it increases linearly for higher vertex numbers. An explanation for the behavior at low vertex numbers is that the constant communication latency outweighs the actual data transmission time there. Considering the right graph, the MPI and the socket based communication are very close to each other, while the file communication is about a factor of 20 slower for higher vertex numbers.

Experiment 2. In the second experiment, one or two of the solver proxies are reading and writing data from and to preCICE. For one of the intrafield-sequential proxies exchanging data with preCICE, a server process is used in addition. The implemented MPI communication method is used for all variants. Here, we only consider graphical results, given in Figure 4.17. The curve with no reading or writing of data and no server (0 rw 0 s) equals the MPI curve of Experiment 1. We focus on the part of the

no vert.	files [sec]	MPI [sec]	sockets [sec]
$4 \cdot 10^1$	$8.07829 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$8.59976 \cdot 10^{-5}$	–
$4 \cdot 10^2$	$8.09469 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.01805 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.11105 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$4 \cdot 10^3$	$8.78201 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.73888 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.53599 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$4 \cdot 10^4$	$1.42318 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.81598 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$6.30498 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$4 \cdot 10^5$	$1.05224 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$4.56340 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.08430 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$4 \cdot 10^6$	$9.34358 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$4.62909 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.04597 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Tab. 4.5: Experiment 1. Comparison of the runtime per timestep using different communication methods without reading or writing of coupling data. A graphical depiction of the results is given in Figure 4.16.

Fig. 4.16: Experiment 1. Comparison of the runtime per timestep using different communication methods without reading or writing of coupling data. In (a), absolute runtimes are compared while in (b), all runtimes are scaled with respect to the corresponding MPI runtimes. The raw data of the experiment are given in Table 4.5.

graphs with higher vertex numbers. In the left graph which shows the absolute runtime, the linear scaling behavior of all variants is visible. The right graph shows differences when compared to the 0 rw 0 s results. According to the results, the reading and writing of data of one solver proxy entails an additional overhead of 50%. When both proxies exchange data with preCICE, the overhead rises to 100% (compared to the 0 rw 0 s values) accordingly. The measurement where one proxy exchanges data with preCICE and uses a server has an overhead of about 200%. Using a server leads to an additional communication of data in both directions. Thus, combined with the overhead of exchanging data with preCICE, 150% overhead would be consistent. The additional

50% are due to the solver-server communication implementation, which involves the repeated creation of temporary buffers (on the heap) for the communicated data. An optimized handling of the buffers employing an intelligent reuse strategy offers potential for improvement here.

Fig. 4.17: Experiment 2. Evaluation of data reading and writing as well as server overhead on the runtime per timestep. The legend shows how many of the two proxies are reading and writing (rw) data (0, 1, or 2) and if a solver (s) is used for a proxy reading and writing data. The left graph contains absolute runtimes while the right graph shows runtimes scaled by the runtimes for not reading or writing data or using a server (0 rw 0 s).

Experiment 3. A strong and a weak scaling scenario is emulated to investigate the effect on the *preCICE* data management and communication overhead. Only one solver proxy employs intrafield-parallelism with a *preCICE* server and exchanges data with *preCICE*. The other proxy runs sequentially without a server and does not exchange data with *preCICE*. Again, the implemented MPI communication method is used. In the strong scaling scenario, the number of coupling mesh vertices is kept at $4 \cdot 10^7$ while the number of solver proxy processes is increased. The coupling mesh vertices are distributed evenly among the solver proxy processes such that for 256 cores each process has 312500 vertices. In the weak scaling scenario, the number of coupling mesh vertices is increased in accordance to the number of proxy processes. While it is kept at a constant 312500 for each proxy process, the total number of vertices rises up to $4 \cdot 10^7$ for 256 cores as in the strong scaling case. For the intrafield-parallel solver proxy, up to 16 cores per node are used, while the server and intrafield-sequential proxy are run on an own node. Figure 4.18 shows graphical results for the strong and the weak scaling runs. In the strong scaling case, the runtime per timestep decreases slightly when

Fig. 4.18: Experiment 3. Strong and weak scaling scenarios with one solver proxy employing intrafield-parallelism using a preCICE server.

increasing the number of cores up to 64 and only then starts to increase. This effect cannot be explained by the communication between the server of the parallel proxy and the sequential proxy, since the communication is always serialized there and the amount of data stays constant in the strong scaling scenario. The amount of data per process exchanged with preCICE and communicated to the server, however, becomes less and less with increasing number of processes. Up to 16 cores the load is just balanced among the cores of two processors on the same node and the available bandwidth within one processor is better utilized. Then, the number of used nodes doubles with every doubling of the number of cores. The runtime still decreases here, since the communicated data are better distributed among the infiniband connected nodes. Finally, the serialization from n solver processes to one server becomes a bottleneck, but only at around 256 used cores. The behavior is completely different in the weak scaling scenario. Here, a linear increase of the runtime dominates the whole range of numbers of cores used. This is simply due to the fact that the amount of data transmitted via the serialized communication between server and intrafield-sequential solver proxy increases in the same way as the number of cores. Other effects such as better use of bandwidth for the intrafield-parallel proxy are negligible here.

In order to give a meaningful conclusion, the measured runtimes need to be put into context with actual solver runtimes. The goal is, of course, that the preCICE overhead is insignificant (or at least acceptable) compared to the solver computation times. In the two-dimensional FSI benchmark simulations described in Section 5.2, the number of FSI interface vertices in Fluent is in the range 100–1000 and the time to compute one timestep in the order of several seconds. Only a few (up to four) cores were used for

parallel computations with Fluent. When considering the results of Experiment 2, it can be concluded that the *preCICE* overhead from reading and writing data as well as using the *preCICE* server approach is insignificant. More challenging cases are obtained when going to a higher number of processes in a weak scaling approach. Then, communication times can indeed become an issue, in particular the serialization of the data between the coupled solvers can become a bottleneck at some point.

4.4 Geometry Interface for Cartesian Grid Solvers

In this section, the geometry interface realization for Cartesian grid solvers is discussed. This functionality is tailored, on the one hand, to the PDE framework Peano [31], but is kept, on the other hand, generic enough to allow the use with other solvers. In the following, we first see how material parameters are implemented for the meshes of *preCICE* in Section 4.4.1. In the same section, we focus on how complex geometries can be created, imported, and exported using the mesh implementation as basis. We consider the implementation of geometrical positional queries and their acceleration by spacetrees in Section 4.4.2. To get an idea of the performance of the queries and the acceleration achieved by the spacetrees, simple test scenarios are set up and computed in Section 4.4.3.

4.4.1 Realization of Mesh Material Parameters and Geometries

In Section 2.5, literature related to boundary represented (BRep) solid geometries has been reviewed. Based on that, the realization of triangulated meshes in *preCICE* was discussed in Section 4.2.1. In a typical simulation scenario, a solver needs to distinguish subsets of the involved geometries in order to apply specific actions such as reading boundary conditions. This functionality can be realized by assigning so-called material parameters to subsets of a mesh. Furthermore, the geometry interface functionality will be used by solvers that are not able to represent complex geometries by themselves. Thus, different as in the coupling context, the solvers will not be able to provide the surface meshes by themselves but expect *preCICE* to perform this task. Material parameters, as well as geometry creation, import, and export are discussed in the following.

Material Parameters

Material parameters are basically IDs assigned to the subsets of a geometry, i.e., parts of its BRep, and relate specific properties to each subset. Since in *preCICE* a triangulated mesh has been implemented as BRep, the material parameters need to be assigned to triangles, edges, and vertices. One mesh element can have several material parameters. This can be necessary, e.g., at the common boundary of two subsets with different

material parameters. The realization in preCICE allows for a decomposition of the mesh elements into groups with same material parameter. A mesh element does not store the material parameters itself, but merely links to so-called property containers. Figure 4.19 shows the class diagram of the property container implementation in preCICE, which is part of the component mesh. The class `PropertyContainer` provides the interface as well as the implementation for the material parameter functionality. `PropertyContainer` objects are created and managed by `Mesh`. Each mesh element class derives from `PropertyContainer` to obtain the proper functionality. This enables to retrieve all properties related to a specific mesh element object from the object itself.

Fig. 4.19: Class diagram of property mechanism in component mesh.

Material parameters have been used to differentiate boundary conditions in Peano fluid in, e.g., [30] and in Section 5.2.3. When a positional geometry query (described in the following Section 4.4.2) is issued to preCICE, it does return not only a positional answer but also information about the properties of the mesh elements related to the query (e.g., those inside a query volume). Peano is responsible to give proper semantics to the property values, which depends on the concrete simulation scenario. A typical case in a pure flow scenario is to distinguish between the inflow, outflow, and wall-type parts of the geometry. In FSI simulations, the FSI boundary needs to be recognized in addition.

Geometry Creation, Import, and Export

A solver using the geometry interface functionality depends on a BRep provided by preCICE. Two mechanisms for providing BRep geometries through preCICE have been realized in this work. The first mechanism explicitly encodes the algorithm for the creation of a geometry. Such a geometry is called built-in. Realistic simulation scenarios often involve geometries that are modeled by a computer aided design (CAD) software. To bring these models into preCICE, a stand-alone CAD file converter and two reader capabilities have been implemented as second geometry mechanism. In the following, we first consider the software design of the mechanisms, before going into more details of each.

The two mechanisms have been realized in the components `geometry` and `io` (i.e., import and export). Figure 4.20 shows a class diagram with a subset of the involved classes. The interface class `Geometry` is used according to the factory method pattern, i.e., every subclass of `Geometry` implements a way to create a geometry, represented by the class `Mesh`. This can be a built-in geometry such as the displayed class `Cuboid`, or an importer for a specific CAD file type. The class `Import` is used as part of the factory method pattern and is further specialized by using the strategy pattern. The factory method pattern enables to configure the geometry types on startup, but to create the actual mesh later when all necessary information has been gathered. Every geometry supports a constant offset and the inversion of its volume defined by the outer normal directions. This allows to use existing geometries in a variety of contexts, e.g., as bounding box or inner obstacle.

Fig. 4.20: Class diagram of (a subset) of the components `geometry` and `io`.

We first consider the built-in geometry types shown in Figure 4.21. A cuboid, sphere, micropump, and bubble geometry have been implemented. The cuboid is an axis-aligned bounding box, where each side is represented by two triangles. In two-dimensional space it is a rectangle modeled by edges. Its dimensions are configurable and, in two dimensions, the side edges can be further sub-divided in the sense of a numerical discretization width. The sphere is created by a recursive subdivision of an icosahedron, i.e., a regular 20-sided polyhedron. Using such a regular shape as starting point results in very evenly sized triangles. The recursive subdivision rule for the triangles leads to a relatively coarse grained control of the resolution compared to other methods. In two-dimensional space, a circle representation composed of edges is used. The radius and refinement level of a sphere or circle can be configured. A micropump geometry has been implemented to support the project described in [27]. There are several parameters regulating the shape of the micropump geometry. Also a two-dimensional version exists which is basically a cut along the longitudinal axis and results in a representation by edges again. The resolution of both version can be configured. A bubble geometry has been implemented for two-dimensional scenarios. It has been used for tests of multi-phase fluid simulations with an explicit representation of the phase interface.

The second way how geometries are provided through `preCICE` is by a file import mechanism. VRML 1.0 (virtual reality modeling language) [18] files can be parsed and converted to a `preCICE` mesh. They have a recursive structure and a high number of possible different elements. In order to handle the complexity of VRML files, the

Fig. 4.21: Example instances of implemented built-in geometry types: (a) a three-dimensional cuboid, (b) a sphere, (c) a micropump, and (d) a two-dimensional bubble geometry, constructed from triangles, edges, and vertices are shown.

Boost.Spirit2 parser framework has been utilized. Boost.Spirit2 allows to use a syntax aligned with the EBNF (extended Backus-Naur form) by C++ operator overloading and uses expression templates to create a recursive-descent parser at compile time. A user-defined section of VRML files has been extended to account for material parameters and vertex data values. An STL import has been planned as a second file format for geometry import, as it is a common export format of CAD software. In order to support additional CAD file formats, the OpenCASCADE library [140] has been used to create a converter for STEP [159] and IGES [5] files into the VRML 1.0 format. Figure 4.22 shows two geometry examples that have been imported into preCICE. The reactor pipe geometry (Figure 4.22a) has been used to investigate cooling effects in flow simulations using Peano with preCICE as geometry interface in [30]. The Stanford bunny geometry (Figure 4.22b) served as a first test case.

In order to visualize geometries (and meshes) provided by preCICE, an export to VTK (visualization toolkit) has been implemented. The geometries of Figure 4.22 have been transformed to VTK using this mechanism. Furthermore, an export to VRML 1.0 has been realized, that enables a checkpointing and restart mechanism described in Section 4.5.2.

Fig. 4.22: Two examples of geometries imported to *preCICE* from file.

4.4.2 Realization of Geometrical Queries and Spacetree Acceleration

So far, we have considered the realization of data structures to describe solid geometries by a BRep. In this section, we are going to review the implementation of positional geometrical queries and their acceleration by spacetrees with respect to the implemented BRep.

Geometrical Queries

In Section 2.5.3, two geometrical queries have been identified to be required to build up a Cartesian grid in the PDE framework Peano. These are positional point and volume queries, where we only consider volumes in the form of axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABBs). A point or volume is classified according to one of the positional predicates: inside (IN), outside (OUT), or neither inside nor outside (NIO), in relation to a given BRep. Here, we are going to review the implementation of the queries in *preCICE*.

First, we consider the positional point queries, since these are used as a building block in the volume queries, too. A point \mathbf{p} is declared to be NIO, if its Euclidean distance to δS is zero. In a numerical context this condition is relaxed using a numerical zero limit ϵ as

$$\text{NIO}(\mathbf{p}; S) := \|\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta S}(\mathbf{p})\| \leq \epsilon. \quad (4.30)$$

Here, $\Pi_{\delta S}(\mathbf{p})$ projects \mathbf{p} onto δS with minimal projection distance, such that

$$\forall \mathbf{x} \in \delta S, \quad \|\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta S}(\mathbf{p})\| \leq \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{x}\|, \quad (4.31)$$

as used in the nearest projection mapping in Section 2.4.3. The orientation of the boundary of S is used to assign the predicates IN or OUT. This orientation can be

encoded by triangle, edge, and vertex normals. For triangles in three dimensions (3D) or edges in two dimensions (2D), the normals are computed taking into account the ordering of the vertices. Lower dimensional BRep entities obtain pseudo-normals by averaging over the area-weighted normals from higher dimensional entities. When using outer normals, i.e., normals pointing outwards of the BRep, the positional predicates are computed as

$$\text{IN}(\mathbf{p}; S) := [\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta S}(\mathbf{p})] \cdot \mathbf{n} < -\epsilon, \quad (4.32)$$

$$\text{OUT}(\mathbf{p}; S) := [\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta S}(\mathbf{p})] \cdot \mathbf{n} > \epsilon, \quad (4.33)$$

where \cdot denotes the dot-product. The implementation in preCICE uses (2.253), page 89, in order to avoid the computation of (4.30) in the case that (4.32) and (4.33) are both evaluating to false. This method requires a consistent orientation of all faces and, hence, an ordering scheme of vertices for each face in the BRep.

The second type of query is the positional volume query, which has been realized for AABB volumes in this work. The positional volume query does not only return a positional predicate for the AABB, but also all BRep elements that intersect the AABB. This is necessary to retrieve the material parameters associated to the mesh elements (as described in Section 4.4.1). Consequently, five types of intersection tests are required in total. In three-dimensional space, the AABB has to be intersected with the triangles, edges, and vertices of the BRep, while in 2D intersections with the edges and vertices are required. The simplest test is to intersect the AABB with a vertex. Here, the distance of the vertex from the AABB center point in every dimension is checked. If it is greater than the half of the side length of the AABB in a given dimension, the vertex is classified as outside. Given a vertex with coordinates \mathbf{p} and an AABB G with center point \mathbf{c} and (positive) extents \mathbf{h} in d -dimensional space. A separation test of the vertex with the AABB can be written as

$$\text{sep}(\mathbf{p}, G) := \exists i : |p_i - c_i| - \frac{h_i}{2} - \epsilon > 0, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, d\}, \quad (4.34)$$

where ϵ has to be chosen greater than zero to include the boundaries of the AABB. The next test is for the AABB intersecting an edge. The separating axis theorem (SAT) described in Section 2.5.3 is used to perform these tests. In 2D, three possible separating axes have to be checked: two are given by the sides of the AABB and one is given by the normal of the edge. In 3D, an additional side of the AABB is given to check. Finally, for 3D, the AABB needs to be checked for intersections with triangles. Here, the method presented in [3] and described in Section 2.5.3 has been implemented.

Spacetree Acceleration

As described in Section 2.5.4, spacetrees can be used to accelerate positional geometrical queries by reducing the number of BRep elements involved in every query. In the optimal case, the number of involved elements per query can be kept constant while their overall

amount increases. Then, if N queries are issued to M BRep elements, the overall complexity can be reduced from $O(NM)$ to $O(N \log M)$, where the logarithm results from the hierarchical decomposition of BRep elements to spacetree cells.

The locality property of a spacetree is beneficial for queries which are issued in the close proximity of the BRep elements. This is due to the fact that the query as well as the BRep elements need to be associated to the same spacetree cell to establish the locality property. With growing distance of a query to the BRep elements, also the spacetree cell size needs to grow. This, in turn, results in an increased number of BRep elements that are associated to the spacetree cell.

When only a positional predicate (such as IN, OUT, or NIO) is to be determined by a query, this predicate can be pre-computed for all empty spacetree cells and then directly set as answer for positional queries. The association of BRep elements and queries to the same spacetree cell is not required anymore then for cells which are IN or OUT. This shifts query classifications to spacetree cell classifications and, as mentioned in Section 2.5.4, these classifications are the most expensive part in the creation of the spacetree. In preCICE, the positional volume query is used to determine intersections of BRep elements with spacetree cells and the positional point query (issued from the center of a cell) to classify non-intersected (i.e., empty) spacetree cells. In the following, an algorithm is derived that uses already classified cells in the environment of an empty cell to avoid the positional point query classification during the spacetree creation whenever possible. An approach with a similar goal has been presented in [92] and is discussed in Section 2.5.4.

Two variants of octrees (or quadtrees) have been implemented within this work. A static and a dynamic version. The static version is built up completely on initialization, taking into account the BRep elements only. The dynamic version is created incrementally, as required when answering the incoming queries. This can yield an advantage compared to the static version, since only the parts of a spacetree actually required to answer the queries are refined. Such a partial refinement can be relevant, e.g., in parallel simulations where a domain decomposition is applied by the solver processes. For a typical geometry scenario, however, the static octree is faster, since its query acceleration algorithms are less complex and lead to faster code. In the following sections, we thus focus on the static octree and quadtree versions.

Spacetree Creation Using Environment Classification

As mentioned above, a method to use already classified spacetree cells in the environment of a cell to be classified has been developed within this work. It is described here. Given an adaptive spacetree consisting of cells C that are axis-aligned bounding boxes (AABBs) including their boundaries $\delta C \subseteq C$ and that form a tessellation of space. We consider two spacetree cells C and A as adjacent if

$$\text{adj}(C, A) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \exists i, j : (\delta C_i \cap \delta A_j = \delta C_i) \vee (\delta C_i \cap \delta A_j = \delta A_j), \quad (4.35)$$

i.e., one side of C has to be contained in or has to be equal to one side of A or vice versa. Note that this excludes diagonally neighboring cells and applies also to cells at different spacetree levels. The environment of C contains all cells which are adjacent to it

$$\text{env}(C) := \{A \in \text{spacetree} : \text{adj}(C, A)\} \quad (4.36)$$

and can be classified with respect to an oriented solid S as

$$\text{ClassEnv}(C; S) := \begin{cases} \text{IN}, & \text{if } \exists A, \text{adj}(A, C) : \text{IN}(A; S) \\ \text{OUT}, & \text{if } \exists A, \text{adj}(A, C) : \text{OUT}(A; S) \\ \text{NIO}, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (4.37)$$

where the IN and OUT classifications for the adjacent cells are defined as in (2.251) and (2.252), page 89. Put in words, the environment of C is classified as IN, if at least one adjacent cell is classified as IN with respect to the solid S . Similarly, the environment is classified as OUT, if at least one adjacent cell is classified as OUT with respect to S . Otherwise, all adjacent cells are intersected by the boundary of S . Note that this definition alone is not well-posed, as it allows for a double classification as IN and OUT if C is classified as $\text{NIO}(C; S)$. If we, however, know that $\neg \text{NIO}(C; S)$ holds, the environment classification is unique, since all IN or OUT cells are connected by cell C then. We can use the environment to classify C as

$$\text{IN}(C; S) \Leftrightarrow \neg \text{NIO}(C; S) \wedge \text{ClassEnv}(C; S) = \text{IN}, \quad (4.38)$$

$$\text{or } \text{OUT}(C; S) \Leftrightarrow \neg \text{NIO}(C; S) \wedge \text{ClassEnv}(C; S) = \text{OUT}. \quad (4.39)$$

A recursive subdividing algorithm has been implemented for the static octree that makes use of the environment classification derived above. The environment information is recursively handed down along the refinement process and used to classify new IN and OUT cells. Using the environment is much cheaper than performing a positional point query for the spacetree cell's center. When $\text{ClassEnv}(C; S) = \text{NIO}$, the classification by the environment is not possible, however. Algorithm 4.6 shows the algorithmic frame for the creation of the static octree in the method `refineAll`. Starting from the spacetree root cell, the algorithm calls the recursive subdividing method `refineRecursively` in line 3, which only uses the environment information to classify IN and OUT cells. The BRep is distributed among the NIO cells without subdividing the BRep elements themselves. This can result in the assignment of the same BRep element to multiple spacetree cells. If an empty cell cannot be classified by the environment, it is skipped for the moment and its parent cell is stored in a queue. A while loop (lines 5–11) finishes the classification of the skipped cells by performing a positional point query (see Algorithm 4.7 for more details on the method `searchDistance`) and then trying to use the environment classification where possible again. This procedure continues until all cells have been classified.

```

1 refineAll():
2   determine environment of root cell
3   left out ← refineRecursively(root cell, environment)
4   queue.push(left out)
5   while queue not empty
6     cell, environment ← queue.pop()
7     for each child of cell
8       if child is not NIO
9         position ← searchDistance(child, child center)
10        update environment
11        left out ← refineRecursively(child, environment)
12        queue.push(left out)

```

Alg. 4.6: Frame for creating the static octree using the cell environment information in a recursive subdivision process.

Implementation of Query Acceleration

After the spacetree has been created and all cells are classified, incoming point and volume queries can be accelerated. In this work, two types of point queries are considered. Both determine a positional predicate for the query point, but one of them also determines the BRep element containing the nearest projection of the query point.

Before going into more details for the point queries, we first consider a problem related to the nearest projection operations performed within spacetree cells. A nearest projection operation has to be performed for both point query types when a spacetree cell containing BRep elements is reached, in order to define the exact position of the query point. All BRep elements not intersecting the spacetree cell are ignored in the projection, which can lead to a deficient result for the nearest projection operation. Figure 4.23 illustrates such a case. There, the problem is that the nearest projection with respect to the BRep elements in the cell is not the closest one, considering all BRep elements. The deficiency only occurs if the projection distance from the query point to the BRep elements δS is bigger than the distance to the boundary of the associated spacetree cell δC . Thus, a deficiency condition for a query point \mathbf{p} , spacetree cell C , and BRep S can be written as

$$\text{def}(\mathbf{p}, C; S) \Leftrightarrow \|\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta S \cap C}(\mathbf{p})\| - \|\mathbf{p} - \Pi_{\delta C}(\mathbf{p})\| > 0, \quad (4.40)$$

where $\Pi_{\delta S \cap C}(\mathbf{p})$ is the nearest projection of \mathbf{p} to the BRep boundary δS intersecting C and $\Pi_{\delta C}(\mathbf{p})$ is the nearest projection to the boundary of the spacetree cell δC . A deficient projection could be resolved by repeating the projection with all BRep elements. This, however, would destroy the locality property of the spacetree in such cases. An alternative is to step up to the parent spacetree cell and to redo the nearest projection and deficiency test there. This might result in a closer, non-deficient projection (as in Figure 4.23) or remove the deficiency due to an increased distance to the cell's boundary.

Fig. 4.23: Deficient nearest projection (red dash-dotted line) and correct nearest projection (blue dashed line) from a query point p (red point). Since only the red part of the BRep intersects the (thick black) spacetime cell C , the nearest projection with respect to these BRep elements can be wrong, i.e., a correct nearest projection can be found when taking into account all BRep elements.

If the deficiency still persists, a recursive ascent to parent cells with repeated projection operations has to be performed. Only in the worst case, all BRep elements have to be considered then.

After having understood the deficiency problem, we now consider the implementation for the acceleration of positional point queries with determination of the nearest projection to the BRep. This type of query is required when the empty spacetime cells are not yet (fully) classified as IN and OUT, as in the creation of the static octree in Algorithm 4.6, or when the information about the BRep elements with nearest projection is essential, as in the nearest projection data mapping presented in Section 2.4.3. Algorithm 4.7 shows the implementation of the query acceleration within the spacetime method `searchDistance`. First, a recursive descent is performed until a leaf cell containing the query point is reached. A nearest projection is performed with respect to the BRep elements contained in that leaf cell and a deficiency check is performed in case a projection was found. Then, the backwards ascent starts, involving a check for a valid nearest projection at every level. If no or only a deficient projection has been found so far, all other child cells of the current cell are involved for the nearest projection (in the method `searchRemainingChilds`). The ascent ends with the root cell of the spacetime, containing all BRep elements.

The second implementation for accelerating positional point queries only returns the positional predicate. This enables to use the classifications cached in the empty spacetime cells and, thus, retains an efficient processing for all queries. Algorithm 4.8 gives the implementation of the query within the static octree method `searchPosition`. Most parts of the algorithm are identical to the point query with nearest projection, since in both cases a nearest projection is required in the case when the query is associated to a NIO cell. A different behavior occurs when the leaf cell at the end of the descent is an IN or OUT cell (line 6). Then, no projections are performed and the cached spacetime

```

1 searchDistance(cell, point):
2   if cell is leaf
3     perform nearest projection in cell
4   else
5     child ← determine child containing point
6     searchDistance(child, point)
7     if no projection found or deficient
8       searchRemainingChilds(cell, point)
9   if projection found
10    check projection for deficiency (4.40)

```

Alg. 4.7: Search distance operation of static octree implementing the accelerated positional point query with determination of the nearest projection to the BRep.

cell position is directly passed upwards in the ascent without deficiency checks.

```

1 searchPosition(cell, point):
2   if cell is leaf
3     if cell is NIO
4       perform nearest projection in cell
5     else
6       point position ← cell position
7   else
8     child ← determine child containing point
9     searchPosition(child, point)
10    if no projection found or deficient
11      searchRemainingChilds(cell, point)
12    if projection found
13      check projection for deficiency (4.40)

```

Alg. 4.8: Search position operation of static octree implementing the accelerated positional point query.

We finally consider the implementation of the accelerated positional volume queries shown in Algorithm 4.9. The query volumes have to be AABBs to be admissible for the algorithm. The result of the query is a positional predicate for the volume with respect to the BRep as well as a set of BRep elements intersecting the volume. To support arbitrary AABBs, the implementation is able to deal with cases where the query AABBs are not aligned with the spacetree cells. In the recursive descent, the query AABB is simply handed down to every child that it overlaps with (lines 15–17). Note that it is not necessary to actually divide the box here, since the same results will be obtained for the full box without additional computational effort. If a leaf cell is reached that is classified as NIO, two cases can occur: either the box covers the whole leaf cell or

just a part of it. In the first case, the content of the leaf cell can be directly added to the box (lines 5–6). In the second case, a geometrical intersection operation has to be performed with the BRep elements contained in the leaf cell (lines 8–11). Here, however, no ambiguities can occur as in for the point queries. If a leaf cell is empty, the cached classification of the spacetree cell can be used (lines 12–13). Due to the possible overlaps with several spacetree cells also several positional predicates are encountered. A NIO predicate outweighs an IN or OUT predicate, since the box is considered to be NIO if it is intersected by BRep elements. It is not possible that IN and OUT predicates occur without a NIO predicate, since the box is a connected volume. When the query volume only overlaps with NIO spacetree cells but no BRep elements intersect with the box, a positional point query needs to be issued succeedingly. In such a case, the center point of the AABB is used as a query point.

```

1  searchContent(cell, box):
2      if cell is leaf
3          if cell is NIO
4              if cell is covered by box
5                  add cell mesh elements to box
6                  set box position to be NIO
7          else
8              determine mesh elements intersecting box
9              if elements found
10                 add elements to box
11                 set box position to be NIO
12          else if box position is not NIO
13              set box position from cell position
14          else
15              for each child of cell
16                  if child overlaps with box
17                      searchContent(child, box)

```

Alg. 4.9: Search content operation of the static octree accelerating the positional volume query. The box has to be an AABB. If the operation could not determine a box position, the `searchPosition` operation is invoked succeedingly.

4.4.3 Performance Evaluation

After describing the implementation of geometrical positional queries and their acceleration by spacetrees, we now come to an evaluation of their performance. As a spacetree, we only consider the static octree (and quadtree) implementation(s), as it has shown to be fastest in practical cases. Only the time of the query operations has been measured, neglecting the initial setup of the geometry and the spacetree. The setup has shown to

consume less than one percent of the overall time. Driver programs have been written in C++ which use the API of *preCICE* shown in Algorithm 3.7, page 115. A cubic and a quadratic domain of unit-length in 3D and 2D are used as test domains. A built-in sphere geometry with radius $r = 0.3$ is placed in the center of the domain. Figure 4.24a shows the three-dimensional domain’s outline with a sphere made up of 80 triangles. The employed spacetree matches the domain. Figure 4.24b shows the mid-plane cuts of a refined spacetree with a maximal cell resolution of $1/64$ and that of a sphere consisting of 1280 triangles. All measurements have been performed on the MAC Research Cluster hosted at the Leibniz Supercomputing Center. The Bulldozer partition of the machine has been used, which consists of quad socket AMD Bulldozer Opteron 6274 processors. As the following tests are all sequential computations, only a single core is used on a reserved compute node.

Fig. 4.24: Geometry of query performance evaluation scenario in 3D. In (a), a low resolution sphere (80 triangles) is shown together with the domain outline. In (b), a midplane-cut of the spacetree (resolution $1/64$) together with a midplane-cut of a higher resolution sphere (1280 triangles) is shown.

Experiment 1. In the first experiment, we evaluate the performance of the positional point queries with determination of the nearest projection BRep elements. We first consider regularly distributed query points, given for 3D as

$$\mathbf{p}_{ijk} = \begin{pmatrix} (i + 0.5)/n \\ (j + 0.5)/n \\ (k + 0.5)/n \end{pmatrix}, \quad i, j, k = 0, \dots, n - 1, \quad (4.41)$$

where n is the number of queries per spatial direction. In 2D, the third component of \mathbf{p} is omitted. The overall number of queries is determined in 3D as $N_{3d} = n^3$ and in 2D by $N_{2d} = n^2$. In this first part of the experiment, the number of queries per direction is kept constant. In 3D, it is $n = 10$ and $N_{3d} = 1000$. In 2D, it is $n = 100$ and $N_{2d} = 10000$.

The resolution of the sphere (or circle) is increased more and more, which leads to an increase in the number of triangles (or edges) of the BRep. The number of triangles in 3D is equal to the number of edges in 2D at each measurement point. For each number of triangles (or edges), the overall runtime is measured and divided by the number of queries, such that an average runtime per query results. Spacetree accelerated queries are compared against plain queries without acceleration. The resolution of the employed spacetree is varied in different measurement series. Figures 4.25a and 4.25b show the results for the three- and two-dimensional runs. The runtime per query without spacetree increases linearly with the number of queries. Considering the results using spacetree acceleration, it is obvious that spacetrees are not of big help here. This comes at no surprise, as the nearest projection operation cannot make use of the locality property of spacetrees when the query points are too far away from the BRep. Also interesting is the difference in runtime of the plain three- versus the plain two-dimensional queries. Each plain three-dimensional query needs a factor 3.5 more time in average when compared to a plain two-dimensional query for the finest resolution BRep.

In the second part of Experiment 1, the query points are no longer distributed regularly, but coincide with the BRep vertices. This can be considered as optimal case for the nearest projection in combination with spacetrees. Now, the number of queries is not constant any more as the number of triangles increases, but increases linearly from 12 to 40962. We only consider the three-dimensional case here. Figure 4.25c shows the results for the runtime per query while Figure 4.25d shows the achieved acceleration factor in comparison to the run without spacetree. First of all, we can conclude that the spacetree resolution plays a big role when trying to achieve optimal performance. In the following experiments, it will become clearer how the query resolution as well as BRep resolution affect the acceleration capabilities of the spacetree. If considering only the best choices of resolutions for the spacetree, the runtime per query varies less than an order of magnitude, while the number of triangles has increased from 20 to 81920. Considering the optimal asymptotic complexity of the spacetree acceleration $O(N \log M)$, where M is the number of BRep elements, the results fit very well, as $\log(81920 - 20) = \log 10^4 \approx 9$ accounts for the increase of one order of magnitude.

Experiment 2. In the second experiment, we evaluate the performance of the positional point queries without nearest projection determination. In this experiment, we only apply a regular distribution of query points as given by (4.41). The experiment is split into two parts. In the first part, we consider the same constant number of queries as in Experiment 1 and perform measurements in 3D and 2D. Figure 4.26a shows the three-dimensional results for the runtime per query and Figure 4.26b its interpretation of an acceleration factor when comparing the spacetree runtimes to that of the plain queries. Similarly, Figures 4.26c and 4.26d show the results for the two-dimensional scenario measurements.

For every chosen spacetree resolution, an optimal acceleration is only achieved for a specific range of the number of BRep elements. This is as expected, since the number of BRep elements can only be kept constant per spacetree cell when the spacetree resolution

is constantly increased. However, from a certain point, which is different in the two- and three-dimensional scenario, choosing a finer spacetime does not yield an improvement anymore. This effect is more difficult to understand and has to do with the amount of queries. For the positional point queries without nearest projection, the spacetime cell classification cache can be used. The processing time for IN and OUT spacetime cells is then independent from the amount of BRep elements and only the runtime for NIO cells increases. Further experiments have been performed which show that the number of queries falling into IN or OUT cells stays almost constant for a given spacetime resolution in the considered scenarios. The fraction of these queries has a major influence on the acceleration factor achievable and fits well to the observed acceleration factors of the three- and two-dimensional runs of this experiment. For the three-dimensional scenario from a spacetime resolution of $1/32$ on and finer, at least 20 times more queries are answered by cached positions than by nearest projection computations. In the two-dimensional scenario, the factor increases up to 100 for spacetimes with a resolution of $1/256$ and finer. Also interesting is the difference between the two- and the three-dimensional runtime per query without using a spacetime. For the finest BRep resolution, each three-dimensional query needs a factor of 3.4 longer in average compared to a two-dimensional query.

In the second part of Experiment 2, we only consider a three-dimensional setup. First, the number of queries is varied while keeping the resolution of the BRep fixed and then, the number of queries and the number of BRep elements is varied simultaneously. For the first case, the BRep consists of 5120 triangles. Figures 4.27a and 4.27b show the results for the runtime per query and the acceleration factor achieved when using a spacetime. The runtime per query is approximately constant when using no spacetime and decreases when using a spacetime. The reduction of runtime per query when using a spacetime cannot be attributed to the locality property and is, hence, not reflected in the asymptotic complexity. Instead, the decrease in runtime per query has to be attributed to the increasing fraction of queries that can be answered using the cached classifications. As in the first part, different spacetime resolutions are optimal for different numbers of queries. In Figures 4.27c and 4.27d, the results for increasing the BRep and the query resolution are shown. The number of queries per spatial direction is doubled in every step, while the number of triangles is increased by a factor of four in every second step (which accounts for the same amount of overall increase in resolution). A more fine-grained adjustment is not possible for the sphere geometry. As a consequence, the number of overall queries grows much faster than the number of BRep elements and the locality property of the spacetime is almost negligible in this case. The achieved acceleration factors are comparatively low.

Experiment 3. The third experiment evaluates the performance of positional volume queries. It is conducted in exactly the same way as Experiment 2. The volume queries are cubes (or squares) centered at the regularly distributed query points and their extents in one direction are chosen to be $h = 1/n$, such that the query domain is tessellated by the query volumes. Figure 4.28 gives the results of the measurements for a constant

number of queries in 3D and 2D. The results are similar to those of Experiment 2, as the volume queries make similar use of the positional cache of the spacetree. The results of the second part of Experiment 3 are shown in Figure 4.29. Also the results of the second part of the experiment resemble those obtained in Experiment 2.

Summary. To summarize the findings of the above described experiments, one can conclude that the implemented spacetree acceleration works well if the BRep resolution is fine enough. For the scenarios considered, a reasonable acceleration up to a factor of 100 was achieved from about 100 triangles (or edges) on. The spacetree locality property could then be exploited well. Furthermore, the positional cache of IN or OUT spacetree cells proved to be very efficient to reduce the average runtime per query, as could be shown by comparing the regularly spread point queries with and without nearest neighbor detection.

(a) regular spread queries runtime in 3D

(b) regular spread queries runtime in 2D

(c) mesh-located queries runtime in 3D

(d) mesh-located queries acceleration in 3D

Fig. 4.25: Experiment 1. Performance evaluation of the positional point queries with determination of the nearest projection BRep elements. Results for regularly spread queries (according to (4.41)) in 3D and 2D are shown in (a) and (b). Results for queries located at the BRep vertex positions (in 3D) are shown in (c) and (d). In (a), the number of queries is kept at $N_{3d} = 1000$, i.e., $n = 10$ per spatial direction. In (b), similarly, $N_{2d} = 100000$ overall queries are performed, which accounts for $n = 100$ per spatial direction. In (c) and (d), the number of queries increases in the same way as the number of triangles, from 12 to 40962. Curves labeled “no” are without a spacetree, the abbreviation “cpd” stands for the number of spacetree cells per coordinate direction, and “opt” means the optimal runtime achieved when using a suitable spacetree resolution (or no spacetree).

Fig. 4.26: Experiment 2 part 1. Performance evaluation of positional point queries without nearest projection determination. A constant number of queries is used, distributed in a regular manner (4.41). In (a) and (b), the number of queries is set to 1000 (10 per spatial direction). In (c) and (d), a total of 10000 queries (100 per spatial direction) is used. Curves labeled “no” are without a spacetree, the abbreviation “cpd” stands for the number of spacetree cells per coordinate direction, and “opt” means the optimal runtime.

Fig. 4.27: Experiment 2 part 2. Performance evaluation of positional point queries without nearest projection determination. In (a) and (b), a constant number of 5120 triangles is used and a varying number of regularly distributed queries (4.41). In (c) and (d), the number of queries per spatial direction is doubled in every step while the number of triangles is multiplied by a factor of four in every second step from 20 to 320. Curves labeled “no” are without a spacetree, the abbreviation “cpd” stands for the number of spacetree cells per coordinate direction, and “opt” means the optimal runtime.

Fig. 4.28: Experiment 3 part 1. Performance evaluation of positional volume queries with a constant number of queries distributed in a regular manner (4.41). In (a) and (b), the number of queries is set to 1000 (10 per spatial direction). In (c) and (d), a total of 10000 queries (100 per spatial direction) is used. Curves labeled “no” are without a spacetree, the abbreviation “cpd” stands for the number of spacetree cells per coordinate direction, and “opt” means the optimal runtime.

Fig. 4.29: Experiment 3 part 2. Performance evaluation of positional volume queries distributed in a regular manner (4.41). In (a) and (b), the number of BRep triangles is kept constant at 5120. In (c) and (d), the number of queries per spatial direction is doubled in every step while the number of triangles is multiplied by a factor of four in every second step from 20 to 320 (which is the minimum refinement factor for the sphere geometry). Curves labeled “no” are without a spacetree, the abbreviation “cpd” stands for the number of spacetree cells per coordinate direction, and “opt” means the optimal runtime.

4.5 Additional Functionality

This last section of Chapter 4 is about two further types of coupling functionality implemented in the software preCICE. First, we consider a collection of useful smaller features called coupling actions and, as a part of these, a Python callback interface in Section 4.5.1. Second, a checkpointing realization for partitioned simulations is presented in Section 4.5.2.

4.5.1 Coupling Actions and Python Callback Interface

While the realization of all major features required for partitioned coupling has been described in the previous sections, real world software to be coupled often exhibits incompatibilities of (mostly unexpected) minor kind. For example, a fluid solver might natively provide only access to its surface forces, but the structure solver to be coupled may be able to deal with stresses only. A scaling of the forces by the associated areas needs to be performed in this case. Sometimes, it can be useful to initially disable the coupling until a stable initial state is achieved. The FSI benchmarks presented in Section 5.2 are very susceptible to initial instabilities when the flow solver is started without a proper flow field. In these and also many other cases, it can be useful to have the possibility to flexibly modify the coupling values exchanged between the solvers. In order to enable the reuse of such functionality and to keep the solver codes clean of code relevant only for the coupling to specific solvers, so-called coupling actions have been introduced into preCICE. In the following, we consider their realization in more detail. Particularly, we focus on one subtype of action which implements a Python callback interface.

A coupling action is basically a piece of functionality that has access to a coupling mesh and the data values associated to it. It also gains access to the current state of time of the simulation, to enable time based modifications. To execute a coupling action, it has to be specified in the XML configuration together with a timing schedule. The timing schedule defines when the action is invoked. The main place of invocation is before or after coupling data are exchanged inside the preCICE API methods `initialize`, `initializeData`, or `advance` (see Section 3.5.2). A set of scheduling options exist, e.g., to perform an action every time data have been written and before they are exchanged with the coupled solver. All actions are implemented within the component `action`, where the abstract class `Action` defines the interface to be derived from when implementing a new coupling action. Currently, only a handful of actions exist that allow to, e.g., modify a mesh's coordinates based on coupling data values, to scale data values according to the areas of the mesh faces, or to perform a data scaling according to the ratio of completion of the current time step for a subcycling solver. The hope is that, with an increasing user base, more and more smaller coupling features can be shared among different users. The action mechanism also provides a comparatively simple way to extend preCICE without needing to go into the details of the more complex functionality

such as equation coupling.

In order to even further simplify the integration of new functionality into preCICE, a Python callback interface has been implemented in the form of a coupling action. The advantage of Python compared to the native language of preCICE, C++, is that Python is an interpreted language and needs no compilation of the preCICE code in order to include new functionality. The callback interface consists of the three (optional) functions shown in Algorithm 4.10, which have to be implemented by the user and are called by preCICE according to the action timing schedule configured. The main function `performAction` gives access to the coupling value arrays, which can be stored in global variables in order to be accessible in the other two functions. The function `vertexCallback` is invoked successively for every vertex of the specified coupling mesh and allows for the use or modification of its geometrical data. Finally, the function `postAction` is invoked and provides the possibility to execute finalizing code after deriving information from the vertices.

```

1 performAction(time, sourceData, targetData)
2 vertexCallback(id, coords, normal)
3 postAction()

```

Alg. 4.10: Python callback interface of the Python action. Any of the methods can be omitted in a Python action script. In the function `performAction()`, the parameters `sourceData` and `targetData` can be selectively omitted.

Overall, the action mechanism has proven to be very useful in practical applications. It provides an easier access to preCICE for non-expert users and also a rapid possibility to adapt solvers for specific couplings without needing to change the solver's codes. It, thus, supports the black box paradigm very well.

4.5.2 Simulation Checkpointing

A typical requirement for realistic simulations is to regularly write simulation checkpoints that allow for the restart of the whole simulation from the point of the checkpoint. This can be used to continue a simulation that was forced to stop or to redo a simulation with changed solver parameters. Particularly for simulations running several days to weeks, checkpointing is a vital feature. Often the solvers already support a checkpointing mechanism. However, in the case of a coupled simulation, additional data might need to be added to a checkpoint. In preCICE, these additional data consist of the coupling meshes as well as their data and state information of the equation coupling schemes. Meshes and data are exported as VRML 1.0 files, which have been described in Section 4.4.1. State information is exported into text files.

An additional requirement for checkpointing in partitioned simulations is that all involved software that write their individual checkpoints do this at the same time. Using

4.5 Additional Functionality

the action API of preCICE described in Section 3.8, the solver checkpoints can be synchronized with that of preCICE and a consistent overall checkpoint be achieved.

5 Benchmarks and Applications

This chapter presents simulations of three different FSI scenarios performed with a couple of different fluid and structure simulation programs. In contrast to the evaluation results of the last chapter, the simulations here combine the different coupling functionality groups such as equation coupling, data mapping, and communication to apply them in the coupling of academic and commercial full-featured simulation software. The scenarios discussed in the following serve, thus, as an integration test for the implemented functionality and also as a proof of concept for the coupling environment preCICE.

We are first going to introduce the employed simulation software in Section 5.1. The first simulation scenarios presented are the FSI Benchmarks [87] in Section 5.2, which are two-dimensional FSI simulations with incompressible flows and large structural deformations. The second group of simulation scenarios, discussed in Section 5.3, consists of two-dimensional floating structures under wave action, which can be stabilized by attaching anti-motion devices to the structures. Finally, we consider three-dimensional simulations of explosives in Section 5.4.

5.1 Employed Simulation Software

The FSI simulations in this chapter are performed using different flow and structure simulation tools. Among them is commercial closed-source software with limited access through APIs and scripting, as well as research and open-source software. In particular, we look at the flow solver implemented in the PDE framework Peano in Section 5.1.1. We consider the commercial fluid solver ANSYS Fluent [4] in Section 5.1.2 and a research flow solver for compressible flows in Section 5.1.3. The commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics [34] is employed as a structure solver and presented in Section 5.1.4. Furthermore, the open-source structure solver Calculix [49] is shown in Section 5.1.5 and the in-house rigid-body motion structure solver Structure0815 is presented in Section 5.1.6. The following sections are not meant to give a comprehensive overview or even summary of every solver, but they highlight important features and show which measures have been necessary to prepare them for coupling with preCICE.

5.1.1 Peano Fluid as Flow Solver with Fixed-Grids

The PDE framework Peano [177, 176] has been discussed already twice within this work, in Sections 2.5 and 4.4. We considered it in the context of the geometry interface functionality there, while we are going to focus on an FSI context now. The flow solver Peano Fluid has been realized in [31, 160] based on the Peano framework. The most distinguishing property of this solver with respect to other flow solvers presented here, is that it is based on fixed Cartesian grids. In the following, we are going to see which consequences this has for the FSI coupling and also briefly review the main concepts of the solver.

Peano Framework and Fluid Solver

Peano is centered around a hierarchical Cartesian grid, organized as a spacetree. Its name comes from the employed Peano spacefilling curve which is used to traverse and order the grid cells. A user of the framework has to implement callback methods in, e.g., C++ that are called during the traversal of the cells and access grid data in a cell-based manner. Static and dynamic grid adaptivity as well as multi-level schemes are natively supported. The implementation concepts opt for a minimal memory footprint during runtime and efficient use of processor caches.

Based on the Peano framework, a flow solver for the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations (see Section 2.1.2) has been realized in [31, 160], called Peano Fluid. The Galerkin FEM has been employed to discretize the fluid equations on the Cartesian grid cells. $Q1Q0$ elements have been used, i.e., d -linear basis functions for the velocity unknowns and constant basis functions for the pressure unknowns, where $d \in \{2, 3\}$. This choice results in a skew pressure stencil, when overall stability without artificial stabilization means is targeted. Chorin's projection method [33] is used to obtain a divergence free velocity field and requires to solve a system of equations for the pressure unknowns per timestep. In the context of this work, only the explicit Euler timestepping scheme has been used. Forces at the boundaries are computed by the consistent forces method [27] which accumulates the cell-based contributions to the momentum equation from adjacent nodes.

Coupling Considerations

Peano Fluid uses the marker-and-cell approach [161] in an Eulerian frame of reference, such that a fixed grid results (as opposed to a moving grid in the ALE approach). To couple the Eulerian frame with the Lagrangian frame (typically) used in a structure solver, dynamic adaptivity of the Eulerian grid is required to adapt it to the deformations of the structure. This entails a change of volume at the FSI interface when more flow cells are added than removed, or vice versa, and leads to a violation of the continuity equation. As a remedy, an additional solve of a pressure system of equations, similar to

the one obtained by Chorin's projection, is performed in [121] to re-establish the validity of the continuity equation. Another problem of the dynamically changing mesh is the missing history of unknowns at the coupling interface. The consistent forces method requires acceleration values for the first term in the moment equation, which cannot be computed from the fluid equations without a history of velocity values. As a workaround, the acceleration values are obtained from the structure in this work. Similarly, velocity values need to be obtained from the structure, since no displacement history is available as for moving meshes.

To support the minimal memory footprint of Peano and its cell-based traversal concept, the incremental mapping version of the nearest projection method has been implemented within this work. Furthermore, incremental methods for reading and writing coupling data and for setting the wet surface mesh nodes have been added to the API of preCICE. Peano fluid has been used to compute the two-dimensional FSI benchmark simulations presented in Section 5.2.

5.1.2 ANSYS Fluent as FVM Flow Solver with Moving Meshes

ANSYS Fluent is a commercial flow solver with a rich feature set. Within this work, it has been used to solve the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations in an ALE point of view, as described in Section 2.1.2. The Lagrangian motion of the wet surface nodes is compensated by a mesh smoothing algorithm for internal nodes. Fluent can be considered as an instance of a typical flow solver.

Fluent is based on the finite volume method and uses unstructured grids. In this work, only triangular meshes have been employed in two-dimensional simulations. Fluent is not able to create a computational grid by itself. Instead, ICEMCFD has been used to generate the grids used for the FSI simulations. The PISO scheme is used to couple pressure and velocity unknowns by an iterative solution process. A first-order backward Euler scheme is chosen for time integration. Fluent employs the volume of fluid (VOF) method to perform multi-phase fluid simulations. More about the theoretical background of Fluent can be found in [4].

Fluent provides a C API in order to write so-called user-defined functions (UDFs). A UDF can be registered in Fluent and is called at specific occasions, such as at initialization or mesh movement. Furthermore, it is possible to write scripts in the Scheme language that steer Fluent and, e.g., define an iteration process that depends on variables from the UDFs. Combining the scripting and UDF capabilities, it is possible to use Fluent in explicit as well as implicit coupled simulations. The preCICE C API has been integrated in UDFs and could be loaded by Fluent at runtime. Fluent has also been used to perform intrafield-parallel simulations. Here, a possibility to redistribute the FSI interface nodes among the Fluent processes during runtime and on startup from a simulation checkpoint has been realized. Fluent is used in Section 5.2 to compute FSI benchmark scenarios as well as for the floating structure simulations shown in Section 5.3.

5.1.3 A FVM Flow Solver to Capture Blast Shockwaves

A research solver for flow simulations of three-dimensional shock waves has been developed in [123]. The fluid model used is described by the compressible Euler equation, i.e., the compressible Navier-Stokes equations (as in Section 2.1.2) neglecting the viscous term. In addition to the continuity and the momentum equations, a conservation equation for the specific internal energy ρe in integral form is required. The equation reads

$$\int_{V(t)} \rho e \, dV - \int_{S(t)} (\rho e \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{v} p) \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS = 0, \quad (5.1)$$

where the used variables are consistent with those in Section 2.1.2. In addition to the energy conservation equation, an assumption about the fluid being a calorically perfect gas¹ is made to close the equations. This results in the relation $p = \rho RT$, with the ideal gas constant R and the temperature T . The ratio of specific heats is given for air at standard condition as $c_p/c_v = 1.4$.

Fig. 5.1: Example control volume of the dual grid associated to an internal node I . The n_{Γ_I} facets surrounding node I are denoted by Γ_I^k with outward normals \mathbf{n}_I^k and $k = 1, \dots, n_{\Gamma_I}$. Each facet Γ_I^k touches exactly one edge of the original mesh, which allows to assign a set of connected facets to a specific edge. One such set of facets Γ_{IJ} is highlighted in gray and forms the common boundary of the control volumes of nodes I and J .

¹A calorically perfect gas is a simplification made to a real gas, based on the following premises: It is assumed to be in thermodynamic equilibrium, i.e., in thermal, mechanical, radiative, and chemical balance. Moreover, an internal energy e , an enthalpy h , and a constant volumetric heat capacity c_v exist.

The fluid equations are discretized in space by a second order finite volume method with unstructured tetrahedral grids. A vertex centered approach is employed supported by a dual grid that allows to associate control volumes to vertices. The dual grid is created by connecting edge midpoints, element centroids, and face centroids. Figure 5.1 shows an example control volume for an internal node.

The details of the computation of the inviscid flux terms and the ALE terms are omitted here and a reference to the original paper is given [123]. The second order discretization scheme requires special stabilization measures. The compact Harten-Lax-van Leer (HLLC) flux scheme is employed with hybrid slope limiters, which allows to accurately capture shock waves while pertaining the second order accuracy. A total variation diminishing (TVD) k -th order explicit Runge-Kutta (ERK) method is employed for time discretization.

The flow solver has been coupled by inserting the preCICE C++ API into its source code. To enable efficient parallel simulations, the array-based coupling value API of preCICE has been used, minimizing communication calls to the preCICE coupling server. The three-dimensional explosive blast FSI simulations in Section 5.4 have been simulated using the solver.

5.1.4 COMSOL Multiphysics as FEM Structure Solver

COMSOL Multiphysics is a commercial software platform for the simulation of various physical fields and their interaction. In this work, the structural mechanics module described in [34] is used which allows to handle large deformations.

The employed structural mechanics solver is based on a Saint-Venant-Kirchhoff material model (see Section 2.1.3) in Lagrangian point of view. The Galerkin FEM is used with second order elements to discretize the equations on unstructured triangular grids (in two dimensions). A first order backward Euler time integration scheme is applied. COMSOL offers (a merely documented) C API that allows to extract displacements and to set pressures. This API can be combined with COMSOL script files to steer a COMSOL simulation. In order to do so, the adapter combining the preCICE and the COMSOL API needs to be loaded as dynamic library into the COMSOL scripting environment. Unfortunately, it was not possible to directly load an adapter using the preCICE C API. The C++ part of preCICE seems to cause problems here, which could not be identified due to the limited debugging information available. Instead, as a workaround, a C library has been used that employs socket communication to connect to an intermediate driver program, representing the actual preCICE adapter. COMSOL is used in a two-dimensional plain-strain mode to simulate the FSI Benchmark scenarios with Peano Fluid and ANSYS Fluent, respectively, as described in Section 5.2.

5.1.5 Calculix as FEM Structure Solver with Plastic Deformations

The open-source simulation software Calculix has been developed in [49] with a focus on structural mechanics. It uses a non-linear geometric description allowing for large deformations. As constitutive relations, it offers an incremental isotropic elasto-plastic material behavior, which is derived in [146]. The basic idea is to perform a multiplicative splitting of the deformation gradient

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^e \mathbf{F}^p \quad (5.2)$$

into an elastic part \mathbf{F}^e and a plastic part \mathbf{F}^p . The plastic deformation part conserves the volume of the material. In addition to the material parameters described in Section 2.1.3, the yield stress σ_0 which marks the limit of purely elastic deformation has to be given to describe the material.

Calculix uses the Galerkin FEM to discretize the structural equations in space. For time integration, the α -scheme is employed which computes displacements \mathbf{u} and velocities \mathbf{v} of the next timestep $n + 1$ as

$$\mathbf{v}^{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{n+1} + \gamma \Delta t \mathbf{a}^{n+1}, \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1} + \beta \Delta t^2 \mathbf{a}^{n+1}. \quad (5.4)$$

Here, $\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{n+1}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1}$ are predictors, computed by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}^{n+1} = \mathbf{v}^n + \Delta t(1 - \gamma) \mathbf{a}^n \quad (5.5)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^n + \Delta t \mathbf{v}^n + \frac{1}{2} \Delta t^2 (1 - 2\beta) \mathbf{a}^n \quad (5.6)$$

where \mathbf{a} are the accelerations. Inserting (5.3) and (5.4) into the semi-discrete system of equations resulting from the FEM, a system of equations for the accelerations \mathbf{a}^{n+1} can be derived. Calculix has been used as a structure solver with plastic material behavior to perform the explosive blast FSI simulations in Section 5.4.

5.1.6 Structure0815 as Rigid Body Structure Solver

The structure solver Structure0815 has been developed within this work to provide a simplistic rigid-body motion solver for first coupling tests of flow solvers and for scenarios where the structure undergoes only translations and rotations.

Structure0815 uses the BRep of preCICE to define its simulation domain. An API method in preCICE allows to iterate over the vertices of a surface mesh. Using that information, Structure0815 computes translational and rotational forces acting on the rigid body. In order to relate the forces to a movement, the center of gravity, the overall volume, and the density have to be available. These can either be set manually by the user or are computed automatically. The automatic computation requires that the

coordinate origin is visible (in a direct line) from every surface mesh vertex in order to perform the computations explained in the following.

In two dimensions, the edges of the preCICE surface mesh are virtually extended to triangles by taking the coordinate origin as a third vertex, in addition to the edge vertices \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . For each triangle, the (two-dimensional) volume V and the center of gravity \mathbf{CoG} are computed according to

$$V = \frac{1}{2}(a_x b_y - a_y b_x) \quad (5.7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{CoG} = \frac{1}{3}(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}), \quad (5.8)$$

i.e., the third component of the cross product is used for the volume and the arithmetic average of the vertex coordinates for the center of gravity. In three dimensions, each surface triangle is extended to a tetrahedron. The volume and the center of gravity of a tetrahedron are computed as

$$V = \frac{1}{6}[(\mathbf{b} - \mathbf{a}) \times (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{a})] \cdot (-\mathbf{a}) \quad (5.9)$$

and

$$\mathbf{CoG} = \frac{1}{4}(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{c}), \quad (5.10)$$

i.e., the triple product is used to compute the volume of the parallelepiped for V and the arithmetic average of the vertex coordinates scaled by the volume for the \mathbf{CoG} . If the coordinate origin can be connected by a line from every mesh vertex without intersecting any mesh face (edge or triangle), then the overall volume and center of gravity can be computed by summations over all n partial results as

$$V_{tot} = \sum_i^n V_i, \quad (5.11)$$

$$\mathbf{CoG}_{tot} = \frac{1}{V_{tot}} \sum_i^n V_i \mathbf{CoG}_i. \quad (5.12)$$

A translational acceleration \mathbf{a}_t is then computed for the whole rigid body by summing up the m vertex forces as

$$\mathbf{a}_t = \frac{\sum_i^m \mathbf{f}_i}{V_{tot} \rho} \Delta t, \quad (5.13)$$

where ρ is the structure density and Δt the discrete timestep. Any spatial component of the translational velocity delta can be set to zero to model a fixture.

A rotational velocity change has to be computed for each vertex individually, as it depends on the distance from the center of rotation \mathbf{CoR} . By default, the center of rotation is the center of gravity. However, it is possible to define a fixed center of

5 Benchmarks and Applications

rotation, too. In any case, first, the overall moment of torque has to be computed by summing up the individual moments of torque over all m vertices with coordinates \mathbf{d}_i as

$$\mathbf{M}_{tot} = \sum_i^m (\mathbf{d}_i - \mathbf{CoR}) \times \mathbf{f}_i. \quad (5.14)$$

The rotational velocity delta \mathbf{a}_r for a vertex is then computed as

$$\mathbf{a}_r = \frac{\mathbf{M} \times (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{CoR})}{V_{tot} \rho} \Delta t \quad (5.15)$$

and the overall acceleration \mathbf{a} for a vertex is computed as the sum of translational and rotational velocity deltas as

$$\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{a}_t + \mathbf{a}_r. \quad (5.16)$$

The velocity \mathbf{v}^{n+1} and the displacement \mathbf{u}^{n+1} of each vertex at timestep $n + 1$ is then computed as

$$\mathbf{v}^{n+1} = \mathbf{v}^n + \mathbf{a} \Delta t, \quad (5.17)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^n + \mathbf{v}^{n+1} \Delta t^2. \quad (5.18)$$

If the forces are at timestep $n + 1$, then also the overall velocity delta is from the next timestep and the timestepping rule can be considered as an implicit integration. Note that the scheme conserves the rigid body's volume only in the limit case of $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, due to the computation rule for the rotations. Structure0815 has been used in the simulations of floating structures in Section 5.3.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

A two-dimensional benchmarking scenario for laminar incompressible flow FSI has been proposed in [87]. Despite being only two-dimensional, the scenario has proven to be quite demanding, since it involves large deformations of an elastic structure and, hence, also large deformations of the FSI boundary in the fluid domain. Since the simulations involve the onset and saturation of oscillations, many oscillation periods have to be simulated until a quasi-stationary state is reached. This makes the simulations comparatively time consuming and also requires a certain degree of robustness.

In the following, the scenario details are described in Section 5.2.1. In Section 5.2.2, results are given for the moving mesh flow solver Fluent coupled to the structure solver COMSOL. The benchmarks have also been computed with the fixed-grid flow solver Peano coupled to COMSOL. Results of these simulations are presented in Section 5.2.3.

5.2.1 Benchmark Scenario Description

The FSI benchmark scenario is derived from the “flow around cylinder” benchmarks presented in [164]. It consists of a fixed cylinder with attached flexible cantilever, submerged into a channel flow (in x -direction), as depicted in Figure 5.2. Since the flow is surrounding the deformable structure while the outer boundaries are fixed, it can be categorized as an external flow FSI scenario.

Fig. 5.2: Geometrical layout of the FSI benchmark scenarios, consisting of a channel with an obstacle placed inside. The coordinate origin is placed in the lower left corner of the channel and the channel is displayed truncated, indicated by dotted lines. Point $C = (0.2 \text{ m}, 0.2 \text{ m})$ marks the placement of the cylinder with attached flexible cantilever, which is slightly off-centric in y -direction to foster oscillations. Measurements of displacements are done at point $A = (0.6 \text{ m}, 0.2 \text{ m})$, which is at the center of the backside of the cantilever. Note that this point moves with the cantilever such that its coordinates change during the simulation.

The physical properties of the flow are described by incompressible Newtonian fluids, as modeled by the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations introduced in Section 2.1.2. Material parameters of interest are the fluid density ρ^f , the kinematic viscosity ν^f , and the mean inflow velocity \bar{U} . As derived quantity, the dimensionless Reynolds number can be computed by $Re = \bar{U}d/\nu^f$, where $d = 0.1 \text{ m}$ is the diameter of the cylinder. The inflow velocity is prescribed at the left channel edge ($x = 0$, $0 \leq y \leq H = 0.41 \text{ m}$) as

$$v_{in} = 1.5\bar{U} \frac{y(H-y)}{(H/2)^2}, \quad (5.19)$$

resulting in a parabolic inflow profile given by the vectorial flow velocity $\mathbf{v} = (v_{in}, 0)$. The structural physics model has to be able to describe large elastic deformations and compression. A St. Venant-Kirchhoff material as introduced in Section 2.1.3 is a proper choice. Physical parameters of interest are the structural density ρ^s , Young’s modulus E , and Poisson’s ratio ν^s . No damping is applied for the structure.

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The overall benchmark consists of nine scenarios, where only three are actual FSI benchmarks. The first six are preparatory scenarios for the flow or the structure solver only. The flow scenarios are named CFD1–3 and, within these, the structure is fixed. While CFD1 is stationary, the flowfield in CFD2 and 3 shows quasi-stationary oscillations. The scenarios for the structure only are called CSM1–3. They consider the cylinder and the cantilever without the channel and apply a gravitational body force $\mathbf{g} = (0, -2) \text{ m/s}^2$ only. While CSM1 and 2 require the computation of steady state solutions, CSM3 is time-dependent and leads to quasi-stationary oscillations. The physical parameters for the CFD and CSM test cases are given in Table 5.1. Finally, the FSI benchmark scenarios are denoted by FSI1–3 and consist of one stationary (FSI1) and two quasi-stationary scenarios. The structure is at rest initially and no loading is applied besides forces from the flow acting on the cantilever. Self induced-oscillations emerge in scenarios FSI2 and 3. The structure and flow physical parameters for the FSI scenarios are given in Table 5.2.

	CFD1	CFD2	CFD3		CSM1	CSM2	CSM3
$\rho^f [10^3 \frac{kg}{m^3}]$	1	1	1	$\rho^s [10^3 \frac{kg}{m^3}]$	1	1	1
$\nu^f [10^{-3} \frac{m^2}{s}]$	1	1	1	$\nu^s [1]$	0.4	0.4	0.4
$\bar{U} [\frac{m}{s}]$	0.2	1	2	$E [10^6 \frac{kg}{ms^2}]$	1.4	5.6	1.4
$Re [1]$	20	100	200				

Tab. 5.1: Physical parameters for the flow scenarios CFD1–3 and structure scenarios CSM1–3.

	FSI1	FSI2	FSI3
$\rho^f [10^3 \frac{kg}{m^3}]$	1	1	1
$\nu^f [10^{-3} \frac{m^2}{s}]$	1	1	1
$\bar{U} [\frac{m}{s}]$	0.2	1	2
$Re [1]$	20	100	200
$\rho^s [10^3 \frac{kg}{m^3}]$	1	10	1
$\nu^s [1]$	0.4	0.4	0.4
$E [10^6 \frac{kg}{ms^2}]$	1.4	5.6	1.4

Tab. 5.2: Physical parameters for the fluid-structure scenarios FSI1–3.

From the results obtained in the benchmark simulations, a few are picked for comparison. As a first value, the vectorial displacement $\mathbf{u} = (u_x, u_y)$ of point A (see Figure 5.2) is taken. The second value of interest is the vectorial integral of lift and drag forces on the submerged obstacle, i.e., cylinder and cantilever, written as

$$\mathbf{F} = (F_D, F_L) = \int_{\Gamma} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS, \quad (5.20)$$

where \mathbf{n} is the surface normal and $\Gamma = \Gamma_{cylinder} \cup \Gamma_{cantilever}$ is the boundary formed by the cylinder and the cantilever. When quasi-stationary oscillations are occurring, the resulting values are given in form of mean, amplitude, and frequency f as

$$\text{mean} = \frac{\max + \min}{2}, \quad (5.21)$$

$$\text{amplitude} = \frac{\max - \min}{2}, \quad (5.22)$$

$$f = \frac{1}{T}. \quad (5.23)$$

The oscillation minimum (min), maximum (max), and period T are determined by averaging over several oscillation periods in this work. This is done, since even at quasi-stationary and fully developed state, the oscillation characteristics vary slightly from period to period. This variation is, however, not a directed movement as for the onset of the oscillations, but occurs around a constant average level.

In [87], reference values are determined for the results of the benchmarks simulations. These reference values are supported by the results of other research groups in, e.g., [53, 142, 74, 120]. Particularly, the FSI1 and FSI3 benchmark results of different research groups have been gathered in [163]. In this work, the reference values from [87] are taken for comparison to the own obtained results presented in Sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3.

5.2.2 Simulations with Fluent and COMSOL

This section presents the results of the CFD, CSM, and FSI benchmarks, computed with Fluent as flow solver, COMSOL as structure solver, and preCICE as coupling tool. The results of various configurations are given quantitatively in tables, where a comparison to the reference values is possible. Furthermore, graphical results in form of contour plots of the flow field pressures and velocity magnitudes, as well as x - y -graphs of the forces acting on the structure and of the displacement of the cantilever tail are given at corresponding places.

CFD Benchmark Simulations with Fluent

Figure 5.3 shows the unstructured triangular meshes created for Fluent to compute the CFD (and FSI) benchmark scenarios. A part of them is regularly refined, some are adaptively refined close to the FSI surface, and some are adaptively refined in a given rectangular domain around the FSI surface. The mesh index I_h defined in Figure 5.3 is used in the following to identify the used meshes.

The results of the CFD1 and 2 benchmarks are given in Table 5.3a and Figure 5.4. Both simulations should lead to a stationary state, which has been obtained for all performed simulations. A comparison of the results obtained with $I_h = 5$ and the

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reference results in Table 5.3a reveals a maximum deviation of 1.9% for CFD1 and of 4.0% for CFD2. The results seem to converge to the reference values. Only for mesh $I_h = 4$ the forces in y -direction are slightly off. This could be an effect of mesh distortions in the adaptive mesh employed.

The simulation of CFD3 leads to quasi-stationary oscillations. The shown results in Table 5.3b are decomposed into an oscillation mean and amplitude, as described above. The graphical results in Figure 5.5 show a snapshot of the pressure and velocity magnitude contours in the quasi-stationary state and, additionally, a transient graph of the forces acting on the structure. When comparing the results for $I_h = 5$ of Table 5.3b with the reference values, a maximum deviation of 0.3% is obtained for the drag force F_x and of 7.8% for the lift force F_y , when relating the computed values to the dominating part (either average or amplitude) of the reference values. The maximum deviation in the frequency is 1.6%. Similarly as for the CFD1 and 2 benchmarks, also here mesh $I_h = 4$ slightly disturbs the otherwise good convergence of the results to the reference values.

Overall, the results show a good agreement with the reference values and suggest that Fluent is capable of handling the pure flow part of the benchmark scenarios.

CSM Benchmark Simulations with COMSOL

Figure 5.6 shows selected unstructured triangular meshes employed for simulations of the structure with COMSOL. All meshes are refined in a regular manner. Note that the shown meshes differ in their resolution numbers from the meshes used for the CSM simulations in this section. However, they are used for the FSI simulations and give an idea also for the resolutions used in the CSM scenarios. The resolution and the number of degrees-of-freedom used are given for each of the following results. The number of degrees-of-freedom is higher than the number of mesh elements, since second order finite elements have been used.

In Table 5.4, all results of the CSM benchmark simulations with COMSOL are gathered. Table 5.4a shows the results of the stationary CSM1 benchmark. Here, the displacement reference values could be reached for the given accuracy. Similarly, the results of the CSM2 benchmark simulations shown in Table 5.4a equal the reference values given for the finest resolution. The transient CSM3 simulations, leading to quasi-stationary oscillations, are more difficult to compute. Here, the reference values could be reached with a maximum deviation of 0.5% for the x -displacement, of 1.3% for the y -displacement, and of 0.5% for the oscillation frequencies. Figure 5.4d shows the x - and y -displacements over time. Due to the lack of physical damping, the cantilever always returns to its initial position.

The results of the structural benchmark simulations done with COMSOL are in very good agreement with the reference results and suggest a valid basis for the now following FSI benchmark simulations.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

Fig. 5.3: Unstructured triangular meshes created for Fluent to compute the benchmarks CFD1–3 and FSI1–3. I_h serves as a mesh identifier, N_Ω is the total number of triangles in a mesh, and $N_{\Gamma,FSI}$ is the number of mesh edges at the FSI surface, i.e., at the cylinder and the cantilever.

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(a) CFD1 pressure and velocity magnitude contours.

(b) CFD2 pressure and velocity magnitude contours.

Fig. 5.4: CFD1 and CFD2 benchmark results computed with Fluent using the mesh $I_h = 5$. Pressure values are given in Pa while velocity magnitudes are given in m/s. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.3a.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

(a) Snapshots of pressure and velocity magnitude contours at $t = 10$ sec. Pressure values are given in Pa while velocity magnitudes are given in m/s.

(b) Drag and lift force over time.

Fig. 5.5: CFD3 benchmark results computed with Fluent using the mesh $I_h = 5$. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.3b.

I_h	CFD1		CFD2	
	F_x [N]	F_y [N]	F_x [N]	F_y [N]
1	15.93	0.981	169.7	1.415
2	15.05	1.115	157.4	10.56
3	14.80	1.157	147.9	11.58
4	14.68	1.158	144.1	12.63
5	14.56	1.126	142.3	10.37
ref.:	14.29	1.119	136.7	10.53

(a) CFD1 and CFD2. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.4.

I_h	F_x [N]	F_y [N]	f_x [Hz]	f_y [Hz]
1	401.4	26.83	—	—
2	462.9 ± 6.361	-36.71 ± 485.0	4.499	4.499
3	446.6 ± 4.962	-28.51 ± 421.8	4.499	4.471
4	441.3 ± 4.650	-28.55 ± 395.6	4.250	4.468
5	440.8 ± 4.849	-27.77 ± 403.6	4.465	4.465
ref.:	439.5 ± 5.618	-11.89 ± 437.8	4.396	4.396

(b) CFD3. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.5.

Tab. 5.3: Results of the CFD1–3 benchmark simulations computed with Fluent. For each mesh I_h the integral of the forces in x - and y -direction, F_x and F_y , acting on the submerged structure is given. The quasi-stationary results of CFD3 (b) have been computed using a timestep $\Delta t = 10^{-3}$ sec and are written as average \pm amplitude. The oscillation frequency f of the forces is given decomposed in an x - and y -component. For mesh $I_h = 2$, no oscillations occurred. The reference results are shown in the last row of the tables.

FSI Benchmark Simulations with Fluent and COMSOL

We now come to the actual FSI simulations, where we first look at the coupling techniques employed and then consider the obtained results. The coupling of Fluent with COMSOL corresponds to the coupling of an ALE point of view with a Lagrangian point of view (see Sections 5.1.2 and 5.1.4 for more information on the solvers). For both solvers, triangular meshes have been used, which are non-matching at the FSI surface. Thus, a data mapping becomes necessary. Fluent provides forces as output at the mesh edge centers of the FSI surface and COMSOL takes pressures at its integration points as input. COMSOL in turn provides displacements, which have to be turned into displacement-deltas for Fluent in order to compute its mesh motion. The chosen data mapping scheme is the nearest projection method (Section 4.2.2) and has been employed to map displacements consistently and forces conservatively. On the side of COMSOL,

Fig. 5.6: Selected unstructured triangular meshes employed in COMSOL to perform the FSI benchmark simulations coupled with Fluent or Peano Fluid. The mesh identifier I_h , the number of total triangles N_Ω , as well as the number of boundary edges $N_{\Gamma,FSI}$ is given for each mesh.

the forces are scaled by the surface edge lengths using a preCICE action. The IQN-ILS equation coupling scheme has been employed to overcome the coupling instabilities and to have a fast convergence (typically around 5 coupling iterations per timestep). Since Fluent comes as binary distribution with an older MPI library to perform parallel simulations, the preCICE socket communication scheme has been employed instead of an MPI communication to avoid incompatibilities.

In order to record the movement of the tail of the cantilever, a functionality called watch-point has been implemented in preCICE, which allows to follow the coupling data values of a given point at a preCICE coupling mesh. The coupling data values are interpolated to the watch-point using the nearest projection mapping and written to a file at the end of every coupling timestep.

Fluent was run with up to four processes on quad-core workstations, using the preCICE server deployment scheme. The simulations had to deal with several shortcomings of Fluent. First of all, the mesh motion schemes available in Fluent were unable to deal with the amount of mesh deformation present in the FSI2 and FSI3 benchmarks. A breakdown of the simulation occurs due to bad Jacobi matrices in the ALE formulation when the cantilever oscillations build up. As a remedy, local remeshing can be used in Fluent. The remeshing, however, can not be adjusted such that the mesh resolution is kept comparable to the original refinement. Instead, it leads to a slight coarsening of the mesh around the cantilever, where the highest mesh distortions occur. Another

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no.el.	no.dof	$\Delta x[10^{-3}]$	$\Delta y[10^{-2}]$	no.el.	no.dof	$\Delta x[10^{-4}]$	$\Delta y[10^{-2}]$
183	840	-7.147	-6.589	69	348	-4.659	-1.691
723	3142	-7.177	-6.604	276	1246	-4.682	-1.696
2928	12138	-7.184	-6.608	1104	4698	-4.686	-1.697
11712	47698	-7.186	-6.610	4416	18226	-4.688	-1.697
187392	752962	-7.187	-6.610	17664	71778	-4.690	-1.697
reference:		-7.187	-6.610	reference:		-4.690	-1.697

(a) CSM1.

(b) CSM2.

$\Delta t[\text{sec}]$	no.el.	no.dof	$\Delta x [10^{-2}\text{m}]$	$\Delta y [10^{-2}\text{m}]$	$f_x [\text{Hz}]$	$f_y [\text{Hz}]$
1×10^{-3}	183	840	-1.414 ± 1.414	-6.436 ± 6.344	1.098	1.097
1×10^{-3}	723	3142	-1.416 ± 1.416	-6.437 ± 6.363	1.094	1.093
1×10^{-3}	2928	12138	-1.418 ± 1.418	-6.435 ± 6.365	1.095	1.095
1×10^{-3}	11712	47698	-1.422 ± 1.422	-6.439 ± 6.381	1.094	1.094
1×10^{-3}	46848	189090	-1.416 ± 1.416	-6.427 ± 6.363	1.095	1.094
5×10^{-4}	46848	189090	-1.438 ± 1.438	-6.450 ± 6.430	1.094	1.094
reference:			-1.431 ± 1.431	-6.361 ± 6.516	1.100	1.100

(c) CSM3.

(d) CSM3 x - and y -displacement.

Tab. 5.4: Results of the CSM1–3 benchmarks computed with COMSOL. The total number of mesh elements (no.el.), the total number of degrees of freedom (no.dof), and the displacement of point A (see Figure 5.2) in x - and y -direction (in meters) is given for every simulation in (a)–(c). Only the CSM3 scenario (c) results in a non-stationary oscillation state. There, the results are given in form of average \pm amplitude and the oscillation frequencies in x - and y -direction are added. The used discrete timestep length is listed for the CSM3 simulations. In (d), the displacement of point A over time for the last simulation of the CSM3 scenario in (c) is shown.

problem with the remeshing is that Fluent automatically applies a load balancing, which leads to a repartitioning of the FSI surface among the Fluent processes. It is possible to redistribute interface nodes and coupling data during the simulation in the server approach of preCICE. However, there seems to be a problem in forwarding every load balancing in Fluent to its application programming interface, which lead to a breakdown of the simulation after every couple of timesteps. Eventually, simulations of the benchmarks were performed by first disabling the remeshing and, hence, load balancing and using a high number of processes. Then, the simulation was restarted and finished from a point with still small enough mesh deformations using only two processes that do not partition the FSI surface. For the restarts, the preCICE checkpointing mechanism was employed.

The flow equations of Fluent are solved by an iterative solver, where the number of required iterations decreases when the FSI iterations converge, since the FSI boundary conditions for the flow converge. This has been utilized by limiting the number of flow solver iterations to an amount that does not fulfill the accuracy requirements in the first coupling iterations of a timestep, but on convergence of the FSI iterations. When carefully choosing the number of flow solver iterations, a reduction of the overall computational effort could be achieved.

Table 5.5 shows the characteristic results for all FSI benchmark computations performed with Fluent and COMSOL. The FSI1 results are gathered in Table 5.5a. Here, the best results obtained are those with meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 5/4$, where the deviation from the reference values of the x -displacement is 6.7% and 0.2% for the y -displacement. F_x deviates by 1.8% and F_y by 1% from the reference values. A snapshot of the converged state of the FSI1 benchmark flow field is given in Figure 5.7.

Table 5.5b summarizes the results of the FSI2 benchmark simulations. These turned out to be most difficult for Fluent and COMSOL in terms of the overall stability. In particular, problems occurred when trying to perform a restart from a simulation checkpoint. Hence, only a small number of runs is presented. The results with meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 3/3$ deviate in the x -displacements by maximally 12% and in the y -displacements by maximally 7.5%. The forces of this run deviate from the reference by maximally 5.4% for F_x and by 13.8% for F_y . The frequencies deviate by 1.6% for f_x and by 7.0% for f_y . A snapshot of the flow field of the FSI2 benchmark and graphs of the displacements and forces in the quasi-stationary state are given in Figure 5.8.

Finally, Table 5.5c summarizes the results of the FSI3 benchmark simulations. The FSI3 benchmark reaches a quasi-stationary state much earlier than the FSI2 benchmark and showed less instabilities. Thus, more simulation runs could be achieved. The simulation with meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 1/1$ did not show oscillations. Again, compared to the reference results, the meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 8/*$ achieved the best results for almost all values, but for some reason deviates quite much in the average x -displacement. Thus, we focus on the results achieved with the meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 7/3$, which are almost as good. For those meshes, the maximal deviation of the x -displacements is 7.2% and for the

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y -displacements 6.1%. The forces deviate by maximally 1.5% for F_x and by 1.9% for F_y . The frequencies deviate by 0.9% for f_x and by 3.6% for f_y . As already noted for the CFD benchmarks, the Fluent mesh $I_h = 4$ shows inconsistencies for the forces in y -direction. The flow field of the FSI3 benchmark in quasi-stationary state and graphs of the displacements and forces are given in Figure 5.9.

Overall, the errors for the FSI benchmark simulations are around 10% or better and a trend towards the reference results is clearly visible. Considering the single-physics results with similar resolutions, these results seem to be reasonable. Finer meshes would be required for even better accuracies, requiring an increased number of processors and better algorithms for remeshing and mesh movement in Fluent. The obtained results compare well to others found in literature [94, 163, 87]. They show the capabilities of preCICE to perform FSI simulations with commercial solvers in scenarios with high deformations and instabilities.

Fig. 5.7: FSI1 benchmark pressure and velocity magnitude contours computed with Fluent and COMSOL, taking the finest mesh $I_h^{F/S} = 5/4$. Pressure values are given in Pa, while velocity is given in m/s. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.5a.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

$I_h^{F/S}$	Δx [10^{-5} m]	Δy [10^{-4} m]	F_x [N]	F_y [10^{-1} N]
1/1	2.767	3.043	16.03	4.089
2/1	2.472	7.801	15.08	7.757
3/3	2.444	8.449	14.81	7.830
4/4	2.453	8.139	14.69	7.961
5/4	2.422	8.197	14.56	7.561
6/3	2.896	7.648	16.24	10.21
7/3	2.597	7.817	15.20	7.980
8/3	2.464	7.943	14.76	7.745
ref.:	2.27	8.21	14.30	7.638

(a) FSI1. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.7.

$I_h^{F/S}$	Δx [10^{-5} m]	Δy [10^{-4} m]	F_x [N]	F_y [10^{-1} N]	$f_{x/y}$ [Hz]
1/1	-0.513 ± 0.846	0.060 ± 52.70	192.5 ± 29.78	7.310 ± 97.94	3.6/1.8
2/3	-1.389 ± 1.242	1.320 ± 75.80	222.1 ± 59.62	-0.490 ± 196.1	3.6/1.8
3/3	-1.283 ± 1.145	0.980 ± 74.55	210.1 ± 62.29	2.658 ± 201.8	3.74/1.86
ref.:	-1.458 ± 1.244	1.23 ± 80.6	208.8 ± 73.75	0.88 ± 234.2	3.8/2.0

(b) FSI2. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.8.

$I_h^{F/S}$	Δx [10^{-3} m]	Δy [10^{-3} m]	F_x [N]	F_y [10^{-1} N]	$f_{x/y}$ [Hz]
1/1	—	—	—	—	—/—
2/3	-2.824 ± 2.717	1.733 ± 34.46	482.9 ± 28.32	-1.185 ± 158.5	11.1/5.52
7/3	-2.494 ± 2.480	1.700 ± 32.30	464.4 ± 25.22	-0.539 ± 152.7	11.0/5.49
8/*	-1.226 ± 2.474	1.549 ± 33.23	461.1 ± 25.67	2.982 ± 143.0	11.0/5.46
4/4	-1.201 ± 1.131	1.420 ± 21.75	461.8 ± 11.16	7.229 ± 109.1	10.4/5.15
5/4	-1.975 ± 1.896	1.451 ± 28.37	465.4 ± 18.45	1.645 ± 142.3	10.6/5.26
ref.:	-2.69 ± 2.53	1.48 ± 34.38	457.3 ± 22.66	2.22 ± 149.8	10.9/5.3

(c) FSI3. For the mesh combination $I_h^{F/S} = 1/1$, no oscillations arose. The COMSOL mesh $I_h^S = *$ has a resolution of $N_\Omega = 15852$, $N_{\Gamma, \text{FSI}} = 512$. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.9.

Tab. 5.5: Quantitative results of FSI1–3 benchmark simulations computed with Fluent and COMSOL. All simulations of the FSI2 and 3 benchmarks have been done with a timestep $\Delta t = 10^{-3}$ sec.

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(a) Snapshots of pressure and velocity magnitude contours at $t = 10.4$ sec. Pressures are given in Pa while velocities are given in m/s.

(b) Drag and lift force, as well as x - and y -displacement of point A over time.

Fig. 5.8: FSI2 benchmark results computed with Fluent and COMSOL, using the meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 3/3$. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.5b.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

(a) Snapshots of pressure and velocity magnitude contours at $t = 10$ sec. Pressures are given in Pa while velocities are given in m/s.

(b) Drag and lift force, as well as x - and y -displacement of point A over time.

Fig. 5.9: FSI3 benchmark results computed with Fluent and COMSOL, using the meshes $I_h^{F/S} = 2/3$. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.5c.

5.2.3 Simulations with Peano Fluid and COMSOL

After having applied a more or less standard approach to FSI simulations in the last section by using a moving mesh flow solver with an ALE approach, we now consider the flow solver Peano Fluid which is based on fixed grids, i.e., an Eulerian setting. To complete the FSI simulation, COMSOL is used again as structure solver. Thus, in the following only the results for the CFD and FSI benchmarks are discussed, while the CSM results for COMSOL can be found in the previous section.

CFD Benchmark Simulations with Peano Fluid

To provide the CFD benchmark geometry (see Figure 4.4) for Peano Fluid, the geometry interface functionality of preCICE has been employed. The channel itself as well as the cylinder with attached cantilever have been constructed by the builtin two-dimensional versions of the cuboid and sphere geometries, where the circle and rectangle modeling the structure surface overlap to create a gapless surface. Peano Fluid provides three criteria to set the mesh width of the Cartesian grid to be created from the surface geometries. First, a global mesh width can be defined. Second, different mesh widths can be defined for parts of or complete surface geometries. Third, axis-aligned refinement boxes can be defined. At any point in the Peano domain, the minimal mesh width of the three criteria drives the automatic refinement process. For the benchmark simulations, the highest refinement is chosen to be around the obstacle.

Figure 5.10 shows parts of four example Peano Fluid meshes used in the following CFD and FSI simulations. The meshes are only refined around the submerged structure, such that the global mesh width applies at the rest of the domain interior and the channel boundaries. A mesh is referenced by its maximum and minimum mesh refinement level l_{max}/l_{min} with respect to the root spacetree cell of the Peano mesh. In case of a refinement box, the maximal refinement level is attached with a subindex b , as for the last mesh in Figure 5.10. From the first three meshes, it can be seen that a higher maximal refinement level does not change the coarser level meshes, but only adds a layer with finer resolution at the structure surface.

Quantitative results of the CFD1–3 benchmark simulations are listed in Table 5.6. Drag and lift forces are measured using an integral over the structure surface. For the CFD3 scenario, quasi-stationary oscillations result, which are given as mean \pm amplitude and a frequency value. Compared to the reference values, the best CFD1 result deviates by maximally 2.1%. The best CFD2 result deviates by maximally 2.0%. The best CFD3 result deviates by 2.2% in the forces and by 0.6% in the frequency. Further graphical results of the CFD1 and the CFD2 simulations can be found in Figure 5.11 and for the CFD3 simulations in Figure 5.12.

Fig. 5.10: Parts of the Peano meshes used to compute CFD1–3 and FSI1–2. The meshes are characterized by the maximal and minimal refinement levels l_{max}/l_{min} with respect to the spacetree root cell. A refinement box is indicated by a subindex b at the maximal refinement level. In addition to the refinement levels, the number of mesh cells N_{Ω} is given for each mesh.

	CFD1		CFD2		CFD3		
l_{max}/l_{min}	F_x [N]	F_y [N]	F_x [N]	F_y [N]	F_x [N]	F_y [N]	f [Hz]
6/6	15.35	1.854	141.7	15.60	-	-	-
7/6	15.58	1.243	149.3	11.44	-	-	-
7/7	15.57	1.248	149.5	11.57	494.8 ± 7.57	-12.97 ± 479.8	4.407
8/6	14.48	1.137	137.1	10.46	433.0 ± 4.79	-23.33 ± 328.7	3.997
8/7	14.48	1.146	137.3	10.81	434.6 ± 5.14	-8.430 ± 381.7	4.332
$8_b/6$	14.46	1.143	137.2	10.74	439.3 ± 6.25	-7.250 ± 447.6	4.421
reference:	14.29	1.119	136.7	10.53	439.5 ± 5.62	-11.89 ± 437.8	4.396

Tab. 5.6: CFD1–3 benchmark results computed with Peano Fluid. Results of the CFD3 benchmark have only be computed for mesh $l_{max}/l_{min} = 7/7$ and finer meshes, and are written as average \pm amplitude. The oscillation frequencies occurring for CFD3 are identical in x - and y -direction. Further graphical results for the CFD1 and the CFD2 benchmarks are given in Figure 5.11 and for the CFD3 benchmark in Figure 5.12.

(a) CFD1 pressure and velocity magnitude contours.

(b) CFD2 pressure and velocity magnitude contours.

Fig. 5.11: CFD1 and CFD2 benchmark results computed with Peano Fluid. Pressure values are given in Pa, while the velocity magnitude is given in m/s. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.6

(b) Drag and lift force acting on the structure over time.

Fig. 5.12: CFD3 benchmark results computed with Peano Fluid using the box adaptive mesh $l_{max}/l_{min} = 8_b/6$. Pressure values are given in Pa, while the velocity is given in m/s. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.6.

FSI Benchmark Simulations with Peano Fluid and COMSOL

Peano Fluid uses the Eulerian point of view by employing fixed Cartesian grids. Already for the CFD simulations, preCICE has been used as geometry interface for Peano Fluid. For the FSI benchmark simulations, preCICE continues to be a geometry interface, but now the surface geometry is created by COMSOL using the preCICE mesh API. The preCICE surface mesh on Peano Fluid side is then moved according to the displacements of COMSOL and Peano Fluid uses the geometry interface functionality to update its own mesh according to the changed surface.

To couple the equations of Peano Fluid and COMSOL, the IQN-ILS scheme provides the best performance. For data mapping, the nearest projection scheme has been employed as for the coupling of Fluent with COMSOL. The MPI ports based communication has been used as Peano could be compiled using the same MPI library. A watch-point has been employed to record the displacements of the cantilever.

Peano Fluid only uses the incremental API methods of preCICE, i.e., every data value is written and read by an individual call of an API method. This avoids the allocation of additional data vectors for collecting coupling values and fits well with the minimal memory approach taken in Peano. Furthermore, the geometry queries for the mesh generation in Peano depend on each other within each Peano process. This is due to the spatial traversal order of the Peano spacefilling curve where refined cells are traversed immediately. As a result, the geometry queries can only be executed incrementally. The downside of this approach is that it does not work well with the server approach used in preCICE to support intrafield-parallel execution of solvers. There, most API calls related to coupling data and geometry information translate to a communication between a solver process and the preCICE server for the solver. Tests have shown, that the overhead of the communication outweighs the solver intra-parallel speedup. As a consequence, Peano Fluid has been used sequentially only within this work.

While performing the FSI simulations, a drawback of the fixed Cartesian grid cells used in Peano Fluid became apparent. Since there is no subgrid modeling applied currently (as in [20]), the amount of change of the flow domain geometry is directly proportional to the cell width at a moving boundary. This can be a problem for the implicit coupling iterations when a geometry change happens close to the converged state of the coupling iterations. Then, the geometry change also changes the solution of the converged state. This can lead to oscillations between two (or more) states instead of convergence of the coupled solution and influence the results quite significantly, as observed in the FSI1 benchmark. In theory, when the mesh size decreases far enough, a change in the Peano Fluid mesh does not disturb the convergence of the coupling iterations for a fixed convergence criterion. In two dimensions, the adaptive refinement at the FSI surface does not increase the total number of cells significantly and represents, thus, no computational problem. However, the employed version of Peano Fluid does currently only support explicit timestepping and a decrease of the cell size requires the simultaneous decrease of the timestep size used, in order to fulfill stability conditions.

This limited the amount of applicable mesh refinement such that the discontinuous geometry changes still caused convergence problems in many simulation scenarios.

To circumvent the convergence problems encountered, a semi-implicit coupling approach is proposed in this work. In this approach, the coupling velocities and accelerations are updated in every implicit coupling iteration, while the displacements are only updated after convergence of the coupling iterations, when advancing Peano Fluid to the next timestep. This allows to compute solutions for the FSI benchmark scenarios in a stable way. The solutions, however, show a decreased accuracy when compared to the fully implicit results. The delayed updating of the displacement was technically achieved by using preCICE Python actions, i.e., without adapting the Peano source code.

Table 5.7 shows the results of the FSI1 scenario computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL. Simulations marked with a star (*) use the semi-implicit coupling approach. For the Peano mesh $l_{max}/l_{min} = 8/6$, no results could be obtained due to the convergence problems described above. The best results are achieved for the 9/6 Peano mesh. There, the maximal deviation from the reference values of the displacements is 7.3% and 1.2% for the forces. Graphical results of the FSI1 benchmark simulations can be found in Figure 5.13.

The FSI2 quantitative results are shown in Table 5.8. Here, most simulations have been performed using the semi-implicit approach (indicated by a star *). While the displacements are in good alignment with the reference values, the forces are factors to large. The source of these errors could not be found within this work. Most probably it is related to the influence of the FSI velocities and accelerations on the forces computed in Peano Fluid, since the results of the FSI1 benchmark computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL as well as the results for the FSI2 benchmarks computed with Fluent and COMSOL are both in good agreement with the reference values. Graphical results of the FSI2 computations are shown in Figure 5.14.

l_{max}/l_{min}	Δx [10^{-5} m]	Δy [10^{-4} m]	F_x [10^1 N]	F_y [10^{-1} N]
7/6	2.028	16.47	1.572	12.59
8/6	–	–	–	–
9/6	2.328	8.813	1.442	7.732
* 7 _b /6	1.997	16.60	1.572	12.64
* 8 _b /6	2.352	6.638	1.472	9.620
reference:	2.27	8.21	1.430	7.638

Tab. 5.7: Results of the FSI1 benchmark computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL. The COMSOL mesh used in all simulations has a total of 155 internal and 51 boundary elements. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.13.

Fig. 5.13: FSI1 benchmark pressure and velocity magnitude contours computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL. Pressure values are given in Pa, while velocity magnitude is given in m/s. Pressure oscillations arise at the upstream boundary of the cylinder due to the skewed pressure stencil applied in Peano Fluid. This leads to an increased range of occurring pressures when compared to the results obtained with Fluent. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.7.

l_{max}/l_{min}	Δx [10^{-5} m]	Δy [10^{-4} m]	F_x [10^1 N]	F_y [10^{-1} N]	$f_{x/y}$ [Hz]
* 8/6	1.090 ± 1.234	0.357 ± 48.21	182.6 ± 38.00	2.229 ± 374.5	4.3/2.2
* 7/7	1.756 ± 1.513	1.421 ± 76.96	278.6 ± 66.47	3.527 ± 817.3	4.3/2.1
* 8/7	1.163 ± 1.093	1.259 ± 55.48	195.7 ± 45.05	8.663 ± 509.1	4.6/2.3
* 8/8	1.397 ± 1.397	2.272 ± 59.84	211.7 ± 46.55	5.900 ± 516.6	4.7/2.2
8/7	1.760 ± 1.760	1.420 ± 75.77	251.3 ± 66.67	3.964 ± 774.4	4.3/2.1
reference:	-1.458 ± 1.244	1.23 ± 80.6	208.8 ± 73.75	0.88 ± 234.2	3.8/2.0

Tab. 5.8: Results of the FSI2 benchmark computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL. Simulations marked with a star (*) are semi-implicit. The COMSOL mesh used in all simulations has a total of 155 internal and 51 boundary elements. Peano Fluid uses a subcycling timestep of $\approx 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ sec, while preCICE prescribes a global timestep of $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ sec. Further graphical results are given in Figure 5.14.

5.2 Fluid-Structure Interaction Benchmarks

(a) Pressure and velocity magnitude contours at $t = 9.8$ sec. Pressure values are given in Pa, while velocity magnitude is given in m/s.

(b) Drag and lift force, as well as x - and y -displacement of point A over time.

Fig. 5.14: FSI2 benchmark results computed with Peano Fluid and COMSOL. Further quantitative results are given in Table 5.8.

5.2.4 Summary of the Benchmark Simulations

In the previous sections, we have considered simulations of fluid, structure, and fluid-structure interaction benchmarks. Three solvers have been involved in two coupling pairs: first, Fluent coupled to COMSOL and, second, Peano Fluid coupled to COMSOL. The single-physics CFD and CSM benchmarks have been computed with all three solvers, respectively, and a very good agreement of the obtained results with the reference values could be observed. All FSI benchmarks have been computed with Fluent and COMSOL and a good agreement ($\approx 10\%$ error) with the reference results was observed, again. The FSI1 simulations with Peano Fluid and COMSOL also showed good agreement with the reference values, while the FSI2 results are lacking overall consistency of the forces due to an unknown error in Peano Fluid.

The simulations involved coupling functionality from all important categories (equation coupling, data mapping, data communication) and also used the geometry interface functionality of preCICE. Thus, the results suggest that preCICE is capable of performing the coupling of commercial as well as open-source solvers for FSI simulations and obtain valid results. Furthermore, the utility features of preCICE such as data actions, checkpointing, or watch-points proved to be very helpful in the course of coupling the solvers. The following sections take the coupling from a pure benchmarking to a more engineering related context.

5.3 Floating Structures under Wave Action

In this section, we consider the second FSI application scenario of this work. The scenario consists of a structure which is floating on water and subjected to incoming waves. If so-called anti-motion devices are attached to the structure, its wave-induced rotations can be reduced. This is of interest for engineering applications such as very large floating structures [175, 126] where rotations should be minimal. Despite the engineering context, the scenario still remains more of an academic test case and the obtained results are mainly meant to show the principle capabilities of the developed software.

In the following sections, we first go into some theory that explains why and how structures are floated in Section 5.3.1 and derive the equations for linear wave theory in Section 5.3.2, which are used as boundary conditions and for validation purposes in the later performed simulations. These sections are based on [37]. Then, we consider the simulation of a wave channel without a floating structure in Section 5.3.3. Finally, we get to the actual FSI simulation involving a floating structure in Section 5.3.4, where we are going to investigate the influence of so-called anti-motion devices on the amount of rotation the floating structure undergoes.

5.3.1 Hydrostatic Pressure and Buoyancy Force

Shear stresses applied to a fluid lead to a continuous deformation. On the contrary, a fluid at rest must be free of any shear stresses. If a such fluid is subjected to gravity, the only forces acting are normal forces caused by the weight of the fluid and they are balanced by the *hydrostatic pressure*. In the following, we start from the static force equilibrium and derive that the pressure is a scalar, i.e., of equal magnitude in each direction. From that, we obtain the hydrostatic pressure equation by considering a finite volume of fluid. Finally, we arrive at an equation for the buoyancy force, that enables rigid bodies to float.

Fig. 5.15: Hydrostatic pressure acting on a prism (a) and on a small cube (b).

We consider a container filled with a fluid at rest, as depicted in Figure 5.15a. Thus, only gravity (in direction $-z$) and the hydrostatic pressure act on the fluid. We isolate a prism of fluid with dimensions $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$, $\Delta l = \sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta z)^2}$ and look at the balance of forces acting on its boundaries. A balance equation can be derived for each spatial direction. For the x -direction we get

$$p_x \Delta z \Delta y = p_n \sin \theta \Delta l \Delta y. \quad (5.24)$$

We omit the balance in the y -direction here, since it is trivial. For the z -direction, we get

$$p_z \Delta x \Delta y = p_n \cos \theta \Delta l \Delta y + \frac{1}{2} \rho g \Delta x \Delta y \Delta z, \quad (5.25)$$

where the weight of the prism has to be taken into account as volume multiplied by the prism density ρ and the gravity constant g . By inserting the sine and cosine law

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$\sin \theta = \Delta z / \Delta l$ and $\cos \theta = \Delta x / \Delta l$, we get

$$p_x = p_n \quad (5.26)$$

$$p_z = p_n + \frac{1}{2} \rho g \Delta z. \quad (5.27)$$

Shrinking the size of the prism to zero also nullifies its weight and results in

$$p_x = p_z = p_n, \quad (5.28)$$

showing the independence of pressure from the angle θ . Moreover, since the prism could also be rotated around the z -axis, the results are equally valid for y direction, such that

$$p_x = p_y = p_z. \quad (5.29)$$

Now, we consider a small but finite axis-aligned cube of fluid with sidelengths $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$ and midpoint (x, y, z) , as depicted in Figure 5.15b. The pressure forces acting on two parallel sides of the cube have to cancel each other to satisfy the force equilibrium. Expanding a Taylor series from the midpoint of the cube to obtain an approximation for the pressure forces at the cube faces, we obtain for the x -direction

$$p \left(x - \frac{\Delta x}{2}, y, z \right) \Delta y \Delta z = p \left(x + \frac{\Delta x}{2}, y, z \right) \Delta y \Delta z \quad (5.30)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left(p(x, y, z) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \frac{\Delta x}{2} + \dots \right) \Delta y \Delta z = \left(p(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \frac{\Delta x}{2} + \dots \right) \Delta y \Delta z \quad (5.31)$$

Assuming a small enough cube such that fourth-order terms of the Taylor series can be truncated, we find for the change of pressure

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0. \quad (5.32)$$

The same derivation can be done for the y -direction, resulting in

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = 0. \quad (5.33)$$

In z -direction, gravity again plays a role, yielding the following equality of forces

$$\left(p(x, y, z) + \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \frac{\Delta z}{2} \right) \Delta x \Delta y = \left(p(x, y, z) - \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \frac{\Delta z}{2} + \rho g \Delta z \right) \Delta x \Delta y \quad (5.34)$$

which, reordered, results in the change of pressure in z -direction

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = -\rho g. \quad (5.35)$$

Integrating this equation and setting the pressure at the fluid surface to $p(x, y, 0) = 0$ leads to the hydrostatic pressure equation

$$p = -\rho g z. \quad (5.36)$$

The *buoyancy force*, responsible for lifting up objects immersed into a fluid under gravitational influence, is a direct result of the hydrostatic pressure acting on the surface of the immersed object. To understand this effect, we again isolate some fluid volume, e.g., the prism or cube from Figure 5.15. The pressure on the surface of the isolated fluid increases linearly with water depth and cancels the gravitational forces acting on the fluid volume exactly. If we replace the isolated fluid with an object of different density, the same forces are acting on the surface of it. However, due to the different density, the gravitational forces change. If the object is lighter than the mass of the displaced fluid volume, it will be lifted upwards. If it is heavier, it will float downwards. The important ratio is, thus, the total weight of the immersed body versus the weight of the fluid it displaces. To express the buoyancy force mathematically, we simplify the force balance of equation (5.34) to obtain

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} \Delta x \Delta y \Delta z = \rho g \Delta x \Delta y \Delta z = \rho g \Delta V = F_{\text{buoyancy}}. \quad (5.37)$$

5.3.2 Introduction to Linear Water Wave Mechanics

In order to obtain valid boundary conditions for the water wave scenarios under consideration, we use linear water wave mechanics. Gravity is the driving force for linear water waves, as it creates the restoring forces pushing down wave crests and lifting up wave troughs in order to regain the equilibrium state of a flat water surface. This process constitutes the illusion of continuously moving waves. However, each water particle is actually moving in a local ellipsoid with size up to that of the wave. A regular linear wave, as depicted in Figure 5.16, has a height H which is defined as the distance from crest to trough, a wavelength L , and travels along x -direction at (average) water height h . The water surface elevation η is measured at a certain point x at time t and the wave period T defines the time the wave crest needs to advance by a distance of L in x direction. Further derived values of interest are the wave number $k = 2\pi/L$ and the rate of rotation $\sigma = 2\pi/T$.

Fig. 5.16: Schematic drawing of a water wave with wavelength L , wave height H , water depth h , and water surface elevation η measured at position x and time t .

In the following, we derive the linear water wave equations from potential flow theory, which allows to compute analytical results for the flow domain. In the FSI simulations presented later, we use the linear wave equations at the boundary of the domain and let the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations model the rest of the flow domain.

Velocity Potential and Bernoulli Equation

The results of linear wave theory are solutions of the potential flow equations for incompressible flows with special boundary conditions using the Bernoulli equation. We first derive the velocity potential and use that to derive the Bernoulli equation relating pressure and potential.

A scalar velocity potential ϕ in three spatial coordinates $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z)$ can be defined when the flow is irrotational, or in other words, when its vorticity equals zero. In three-dimensional space, this is expressed by the curl of the velocity $\mathbf{v} = (v_x, v_y, v_z)$ being zero

$$\mathbf{0} = \nabla \times \mathbf{v} = \left(\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial z} \right) \mathbf{e}_x + \left(\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial x} \right) \mathbf{e}_y + \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \right) \mathbf{e}_z. \quad (5.38)$$

Every spatial direction \mathbf{e}_i yields an independent condition for a rotation equilibrium

$$\frac{\partial v_z}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial z}, \quad \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial z} = \frac{\partial v_z}{\partial x}, \quad \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y}. \quad (5.39)$$

If (5.39) are fulfilled, a scalar velocity potential exists and the vectorial velocity field can be expressed by the gradient of the potential as

$$\mathbf{v} = -\nabla\phi, \quad (5.40)$$

where the minus sign is a convention simplifying notation in the following. According to (5.40), flow occurs in the direction of the negative gradient of the flow potential. Inserting this relation into the continuity equation for incompressible flows (2.20), page 16, yields a Laplace equation for the velocity potential

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = \nabla \cdot (-\nabla\phi) = -\Delta\phi = 0. \quad (5.41)$$

This equation suffices to describe the velocity field of an irrotational flow and is the governing equation to be solved to obtain an analytical wave solution.

The *Bernoulli equation* is an integrated form of the Euler equations for fluid flow. The Euler equations can be derived from the Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible flows by removing the viscosity term from the momentum equation (2.28), page 17, yielding

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p - \mathbf{g}, \quad (5.42)$$

where \mathbf{g} is the gravitational body force vector. Inserting the irrotationality conditions from (5.39) and using the chain rule for differentiation, we get

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2}\nabla(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{v}) = -\frac{1}{\rho}\nabla p - \mathbf{g} \quad (5.43)$$

Further inserting the flow velocity potential (5.40), we get

$$\nabla \left(-\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \nabla \phi \cdot \nabla \phi + \frac{p}{\rho} \right) = -\mathbf{g}. \quad (5.44)$$

Integrating this equation and evaluating the constants leads to the transient Bernoulli equation

$$-\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \nabla \phi \cdot \nabla \phi + \frac{p}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x} = C(t) \quad (5.45)$$

where the constant $C(t)$ has to be determined from the boundary conditions.

Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions required to describe linear waves are called the kinematic free surface condition, the dynamic free surface condition, the bottom condition, and the lateral boundary conditions. The kinematic free surface condition is based on the idea that the fluid particles at the free boundary define the wave surface. This surface is expressed mathematically by the zeros of a function

$$S(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0. \quad (5.46)$$

Moving with the surface means that the surface does not change. This can be expressed by the material derivative (2.6), page 11, as

$$\frac{dS(\mathbf{x}, t)}{dt} = \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)S = 0, \quad \text{at } S(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0. \quad (5.47)$$

Defining the surface unit normal as

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\nabla S}{\|\nabla S\|}, \quad \text{at } S(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0, \quad (5.48)$$

we get

$$-\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)S = \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} \|\nabla S\|, \quad \text{at } S(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0 \quad (5.49)$$

and, by doing some further rearrangements, we arrive at the final form of the kinematic boundary condition

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\frac{1}{\|\nabla S\|} \frac{\partial S}{\partial t}, \quad \text{at } S(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0. \quad (5.50)$$

This simply means that, if the surface changes with time, there must be a fluid velocity in the direction of the surface normal.

Using this boundary description, we can derive the boundary conditions for the linear wave scenario. We do not go through the exact derivations here and refer the interested reader to [37]. The surface equation for the bottom is

$$S(\mathbf{x}) = y + h(x) = 0, \quad (5.51)$$

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where $h(x)$ is the water depth at position x , as illustrated in Figure 5.16. The bottom should be impermeable, hence

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0. \quad (5.52)$$

Replacing \mathbf{n} by its definition (5.48) yields the *bottom boundary condition*

$$v_y = -v_x \frac{dh}{dx}, \quad \text{at } y = -h(x). \quad (5.53)$$

The free surface needs two boundary conditions. First, we prescribe a kinematic condition by using the wave elevation $\eta(x, t)$, as in Figure 5.16, to form the boundary equation

$$S(\mathbf{x}, t) = y - \eta(x, t) = 0. \quad (5.54)$$

With the same assumption of zero penetration as for the bottom boundary condition, we obtain the *kinematic free surface boundary condition*

$$v_y = \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} + v_x \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x}, \quad \text{at } y = \eta(x, t). \quad (5.55)$$

Second, a dynamic boundary condition has to be prescribed. The Bernoulli equation (5.45) is used with a constant surface gauge pressure p_η to form the *dynamic free surface boundary condition*

$$-\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \nabla \phi \cdot \nabla \phi + \frac{p_\eta}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x} = C(t), \quad \text{at } y = \eta(x, t). \quad (5.56)$$

Finally, we need to specify lateral boundary conditions. Since we assume waves propagating in x -direction only, we can simply specify periodicity conditions for space and time to

$$\phi(x, t) = \phi(x + L, t), \quad (5.57)$$

$$\phi(x, t) = \phi(x, t + T), \quad (5.58)$$

with L as wavelength and T as wave period.

Linear Progressive Water Wave Solution for Horizontal Bottom

To solve the boundary value problem, separation of variables can be used for the flow potential, reading

$$\phi(x, y, t) = X(x) Y(y) T(t). \quad (5.59)$$

Note that the z -direction is ignored here, since there is no potential in that direction when the wave is moving in x -direction. As a solution basis, we use linear combinations of sines and cosines, since they fulfill the time periodicity condition (5.58). By using the remaining boundary conditions, one solution of the Laplace equation for the velocity potential (5.41) is that of the progressing wave

$$\phi(x, y, t) = -\frac{Hg \cosh(k(h+y))}{2\sigma \cosh(kh)} \sin(kx - \sigma t). \quad (5.60)$$

The velocities of the progressive wave in x - and y -direction are obtained by taking the gradient of the potential, i.e.,

$$v_x(x, y, t) = \frac{H g k}{2\sigma} \frac{\cosh(k(h + y))}{\cosh(kh)} \cos(kx - \sigma t) \quad (5.61)$$

and

$$v_y(x, y, t) = \frac{H g k}{2\sigma} \frac{\sinh(k(h + y))}{\cosh(kh)} \sin(kx - \sigma t). \quad (5.62)$$

A formula for the water wave elevation $\eta(x, y, t)$ can be obtained by linearizing the dynamic free surface boundary condition (5.56), resulting in

$$\eta(x, t) = \left. \frac{1}{g} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \right|_{y=0} = \frac{H}{2} \cos(kx - \sigma t). \quad (5.63)$$

An additional condition, relating the wave rotation rate σ , the wave number k , and the water depth h , is obtained from the kinematic free surface boundary condition (5.55) as

$$\sigma^2 = gk \tanh kh. \quad (5.64)$$

Now, where we have the analytical solutions (5.61)–(5.64) for linear progressive water waves, we can use them as boundary conditions for fluid simulations performed with the full Navier-Stokes equations. In the following section, simulations of a wave tank scenario are done and the created water waves are compared to the analytical wave solutions.

5.3.3 Simulations of Water Waves

In this section, we are considering two-dimensional fluid dynamics simulations of water waves in a wave tank, similar to those discussed in [77]. ANSYS Fluent (see Section 5.1.2) is used to compute solutions to the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations with a volume of fluid (VOF) method used to track the water and air phase of the fluid. In fact, taking into account the water phase only by, e.g., a free-surface model would have been sufficient, since the air phase has negligible influence on the simulation results. However, such a model is not provided by Fluent. The obtained results are analyzed and compared to the results obtained by linear and second order wave theory. Linear wave theory has been discussed above, while we just use the results of the second order wave theory which can be found, e.g., in [77].

First, the scenario geometry and the boundary conditions are described. Figure 5.17 shows the rectangular wave channel geometry with extents l_x and l_y . A constant water depth h is used in all simulations. On the left channel wall ($x = 0$) the linear wave

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conditions for the fluid velocity and the wave elevation (5.61)–(5.63) are applied as

$$v_x(y, t) = \frac{H g k \cosh(k(h + y))}{2\sigma \cosh(kh)} \cos(-\sigma t + s), \quad (5.65)$$

$$v_y(y, t) = \frac{H g k \sinh(k(h + y))}{2\sigma \cosh(kh)} \sin(-\sigma t + s), \quad (5.66)$$

$$\eta(t) = \frac{H}{2} \cos(-\sigma t + s), \quad (5.67)$$

where s is a shift set to $s = \pi/2$ such that the first wave starts at water depth level. The velocity values at the left boundary above the water phase ($y > \eta(t)$) are constantly extrapolated from the wave surface. The bottom and right channel walls are set to no-slip Dirichlet boundary conditions. The upper channel wall is a pressure outlet.

Fig. 5.17: Geometry of the wave channel with dimensions l_x , l_y and a constant water depth h .

A wave channel of dimensions $l_x = 100$ m and $l_y = 1.3$ m has been used to perform an evaluation of the resulting waves. At a water depth of $h = 1$ m, linear waves with $L = 3.4$ m, $H = 0.14$ m, and $T = 1.5$ sec are created at the domain inflow for 24.6 sec simulation time. Figure 5.18 shows three visualizations of a part of the wave channel taken at the end of the simulation time. An adaptively refined triangular mesh is used in order to have the finest resolution at the water surface, while keeping the overall number of mesh elements low. The velocity vectors in Figure 5.18c show the ellipsoidal movements of the water particles.

In Figure 5.19, the simulated waves are compared to the results of first and second order wave theory. Figure 5.19a shows the wave height at position $x = 20$ m over time. In an initial phase of up to $t \approx 20$ sec, the wave height increases and even overshoots slightly. Then, the results compare well to the theoretical results, where the biggest discrepancy occurs at the wave troughs, which are too high in the simulated results.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5.18: Snapshots of a part of the wave channel at $t = 24.6$ sec with visualization of the mesh in (a), of pressure contours and the wave surface (black line) in (b), and of velocity magnitude contours with velocity vectors of the water phase in (c). Note that the water surface in (c) is created by removing all cells with a water ratio of less than 50%.

Note, however, that the theoretical results are based on different modeling assumptions as in the simulation. The simulation model involves viscosity, which leads to a zero velocity at the bottom. Figure 5.19b shows the wave crests and troughs at the end of the simulation ($t = 24.6$ sec). Fully established waves occur until position $x \approx 20$ m and are to be propagated to the right. The same discrepancies as in Figure 5.19a are observed.

Fig. 5.19: Simulated water surface height at $x = 20$ m over time in (a) and measured wave crests and troughs at $t = 24.6$ sec over space in (b).

5.3.4 Simulations of Floating Structures with Anti-Motion Devices

We are now using the wave channel presented in the previous section to perform FSI simulations of a floating structure. As fluid solver, ANSYS Fluent is used as for the pure wave scenarios. The rigid-body solver Structure0815 (see Section 5.1.6) handles the floating structure. The goal of the simulations is to determine the amount of rotation the structure undergoes due to the interaction with the water waves and to examine how anti-motion devices can reduce the rotations. Such investigations are relevant for, e.g., very large floating structures [175, 126]. A similar effort has been done in [10], but using a structure with prescribed movements. The following simulations are based on the same geometrical setup as in [10] and involve similar anti-motion devices called bilge-keels.

The coupling between Fluent and Structure0815 is established by exchanging forces and displacements as in the Dirichlet-Neumann decomposition. The surface mesh description of the floating structure with bilge-keels, as needed by Structure0815, is created and stored in a VRML 1.0 file, which is imported by preCICE at runtime. A nearest-projection data mapping is employed at the side of Fluent, with conservative mapping of forces and consistent mapping of displacements. To couple the equations, the IQN-ILS scheme described in Sections 2.3.2 and 4.1 is employed. An inter-process communication is established using the socket communication mechanism described in Section 4.3. To measure the rotation of the structure, the two lower corner points of the floating structure are marked by preCICE with so-called watch-points (defined in the XML configuration) and the coupling data at these points is exported to a file in each timestep. Since the structure is rigid, the direction of the vector defined by the two points can be used to obtain the rotation angle.

The wave channel geometry from the previous section (see Figure 5.17) is used in the following, with dimensions $l_x = 10$ m and $l_y = 1$ m and a constant water depth of $h = 0.5$ m. Incoming waves are characterized by the length $L = 1.513$ m, periods $T = \{1, 2\}$ sec, and heights $H = \{0.05, 0.025, 0.0125\}$ m. The floating structure without anti-motion device has a rectangular shape with extents $a_x = 0.5$ m and $a_y = 0.1$ m. It is placed horizontally and vertically centered in the channel, such that it is submerged into the water by $d = 0.05$ m. This vertical placement balances buoyancy and gravitational forces acting on it. In order to model a mooring system typical for floating structures, the structure's movement in x -direction is fixed. Similar as for the pure wave simulations, an adaptively refined mesh is used. Figure 5.20 shows the left and middle part of the mesh used for the simulations. The adaptive refinement is applied only on the left side of the domain including the structure, since the waves are created there. The right part of the domain is necessary only to minimize the influence of waves reflected from the right boundary of the domain.

The employed anti-motion devices are bilge-keels, i.e., structural extensions at the submerged corners of the floating structure. In the following, different bilge-keels are investigated according to the types depicted in Figure 5.21.

Fig. 5.20: Left and middle part of the wave channel mesh with the floating structure (white) in its initial configuration.

Fig. 5.21: Bilge-keel geometries for the left bottom corner of the floating structure geometry (grey). All bilge-keel geometries are created by rotating a virtual bar with length $a + b$ and width b , fixed at point c . Only the non-overlapping (white) parts of the bar constitute the bilge-keel. Configuration (a) shows the horizontal layout, (b) the vertical layout, and (c) a layout with a rotation angle of 45 degrees. The bilge-keel geometries for the lower right corner are obtained by mirroring these configurations.

Experiment 1. In the first experiment, a structure without bilge-keels is subjected to waves of three different heights $H = \{0.05, 0.025, 0.0125\}$ m with a period of $T = 1$ sec. Figure 5.22a shows the rotation of the floating structure over time and Table 5.9 the

corresponding average and maximal (absolute) rotation values. All obtained results are proportional to the wave height, i.e., as the wave height doubles also the amount of rotation doubles.

Experiment 2. Experiment 2 examines the influence of the length of the bilge-keels. Waves of height $H = 0.05$ m with a period of $T = 1$ sec are used. The horizontal bilge-keel geometry of Figure 5.21a with two lengths $a_1 = 10$ mm, $a_2 = 20$ mm, and width $b = 5$ mm are employed. The results are shown graphically in Figure 5.22b and quantitatively in Table 5.10. The 10 mm bilge-keels reduced the average rotation by 20% and the maximum rotation by 26% when compared to no bilge-keels. The 20 mm versions improved this to a reduction of the average rotation by 23% and of the maximum rotation by 28%. A conclusion from this experiment can be, first, that the bilge-keels provide a significant amount of rotation reduction. Second, the 20 mm bilge-keels do not provide a much better reduction of the rotations than the 10 mm versions. In the following experiments, we only consider 10 mm bilge-keels.

Fig. 5.22: Experiment 1 and 2. In (a), the rotations of the floating structure (without bilge-keels) for a wave period $T = 1$ s and varying wave heights H are shown. Corresponding quantitative data is gathered in Table 5.9. In (b), for a wave height $H = 0.05$ m and a period $T = 1$ s, the length of the horizontal bilge-keels is varied. Corresponding quantitative data is shown in Table 5.10.

Experiments 3 and 4. In the two last experiments, we examine all three types of bilge-keels shown in Figure 5.21. We refer to the horizontal version as the one with 0 degree rotation and to the vertical version as the one with 90 degree rotation. In Experiment 3, a wave period of $T = 1$ sec is used, while in Experiment 4 a period of

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H [m]	Average rot. [deg] (scaled)	Max. rot. [deg] (scaled)
0.05	0.400 (1.000)	1.325 (1.000)
0.025	0.179 (0.448)	0.650 (0.491)
0.0125	0.085 (0.213)	0.316 (0.238)

Tab. 5.9: Experiment 1. Rotation average and maximum of the floating structure without bilge-keels for a wave period $T = 1$ s and varying wave heights H . Transient results of this comparison are depicted in Figure 5.22a.

l [mm]	Average rot. [deg] (scaled)	Max. rot. [deg] (scaled)
0	0.400 (1.000)	1.325 (1.000)
10	0.320 (0.800)	0.977 (0.737)
20	0.306 (0.765)	0.947 (0.715)

Tab. 5.10: Experiment 2. Rotation average and maximum of the floating structure with horizontal bilge-keels of lengths 10 mm and 20 mm. A wave height $H = 0.05$ m and a period $T = 1$ sec are used. Transient results of this comparison are depicted in Figure 5.22b.

$T = 2$ sec is applied. In both experiments, waves of height $H = 0.05$ m are created, as before. The results of the experiments are shown in Figure 5.23 and Tables 5.11 and 5.12. Considering the average and maximum rotation values, the difference between the angles of the bilge-keels plays a bigger role than doubling their length. In both experiments, the horizontal and the vertical bilge-keels perform roughly the same, with a maximum difference of 4% in the average rotation of Experiment 3. The 45 degree bilge-keel manages to reduce the average rotation in Experiment 3 by 31% and the maximum rotation by 30%. Slightly worse results are obtained for Experiment 4 for all bilge-keel versions, due to the twice-as-long wave period.

leg angle [deg]	Average rot. [deg] (scaled)	Max. rot. [deg] (scaled)
no legs	0.400 (1.000)	1.325 (1.000)
0	0.306 (0.765)	0.947 (0.715)
45	0.275 (0.688)	0.923 (0.697)
90	0.322 (0.805)	1.095 (0.826)

Tab. 5.11: Experiment 3. Rotation average and maximum of the floating structure for the wave period $T = 1$ s and varying bilge-keel angles. Transient results of this comparison are depicted in Figure 5.23a.

Summary. The performed experiments show that the developed software is able to perform simulations with real-life application, involving complex physics such as multi-phase flows of water waves. The approach of creating water waves by an inflow profile derived from linear wave theory has shown to give results in good agreement to theoret-

Fig. 5.23: Experiment 3 and 4. In (a) and (b), the three bilge-keel types with angles 0 degree (horizontal), 45 degree, and 90 degree (vertical) are compared to the plain floating structure. A wave period of $T = 1$ sec is used in (a) and of $T = 2$ sec in (b), together with a wave height $H = 0.05$ m. Quantitative data is gathered in Tables 5.11 and 5.12.

leg angle [deg]	Average rot. [deg] (scaled)	Max. rot. [deg] (scaled)
no legs	1.201 (1.000)	4.520 (1.000)
0	1.026 (0.854)	3.668 (0.812)
45	0.912 (0.759)	3.200 (0.708)
90	0.987 (0.822)	3.621 (0.801)

Tab. 5.12: Experiment 4. Rotation average and maximum of the floating structure for the wave period $T = 2$ s and varying bilge-keel angles. Transient results of this comparison are depicted in Figure 5.23b.

ical results. Furthermore, it could be shown that the bilge-keel type anti-motion devices are capable of reducing the amount of the structure rotation significantly. The best reduction of 31% was achieved by the bilge-keels with an angle of 45 degrees. Further investigations, in particular with a three-dimensional scenario and different anti-motion devices would be interesting. We will see in the following section, that three-dimensional scenarios are possible with the coupling environment preCICE.

5.4 Simulation of Explosive Impacts on Deformable Structures

To gain insight into explosive impacts on deformable structures is of high interest when designing protective measures to shield or at least mitigate the effects of the explosion. This section shows three-dimensional FSI simulations of high velocity explosive shocks interacting with structures that undergo plastic deformations. Two scenarios are considered: the first scenario investigates the influence of an explosive blast onto a square plate. In the second scenario, an explosion in a cylinder is considered.

The knowledge and results of this section originate in a cooperation with researchers from the Institute of High-Performance Computing (IHPC) at the A*STAR institute, Singapore. The flow solver described in Section 5.1.3 has been developed there and the structure solver Calculix described in Section 5.1.5 has been modified to be able to perform FSI simulations. The coupling with preCICE and first simulations of the cylinder explosion scenario have been done together during a research visit, while the plate scenario has been run succeedingly by the researchers at the IHPC.

As the flow solver uses the compressible Navier-Stokes equations and requires rather small timesteps to capture the shock-waves of the explosion, the explicit CSS equation coupling scheme is applied (see Section 2.3.1). To decouple the flow solver's timestep requirements from the structure solver, subcycling is employed by the flow solver and the global timestep is prescribed by preCICE. Matching meshes have been used at the FSI coupling surface such that no data mapping was necessary. Nonetheless, for later simulations with non-matching meshes, Calculix provides its coupling surface to preCICE. As communication means for the coupling data between the solvers, the MPI port-based communication is used (see Section 4.3). Calculix only provides displacement values at the interface. However, the flow solver requires displacement deltas to perform the mesh update. Furthermore, Calculix and the flow solver have different definitions for the normal directions at their common FSI interface, which requires an inversion of the directed pressures coming from the flow solver. To avoid a hardcoding of this special requirements, the preCICE Python action scripting capabilities are used (see Section 4.5.1). To compute the displacement deltas, first, an additional data set for the displacements of the old timestep is added to the preCICE configuration for the flow solver. A Python action script is invoked every timestep to store the current displacements. As second step, another Python script is used to compute and store the displacement deltas from the old and current displacement data. To invert the direction of the vectorial pressures coming from the flow solver, a third Python action script is used.

In the following, we first consider results for the plate scenario in Section 5.4.1, which serve as benchmark for the coupled tools. Then, we look at the cylinder explosion scenario in Section 5.4.2.

5.4.1 Blast Impact on a Square Plate

As first simulation scenario, the impact of an explosive blast on a clamped flat plate is considered. This scenario is taken from [150], where actual as well as numerical experiments have been performed and analyzed. Figure 5.24 gives an idea of the setup of the experiment. The scenario serves as a benchmark for explosive blast simulations and is also studied by others, e.g., in [122].

Fig. 5.24: Setup of plate blast experiment (image taken from [150]). An explosive charge (small red ball) is placed behind a steel plate mounting with a cavity, covered by a clamped flat aluminum plate that is supposed to be deformed by the blast.

Simulation Scenario

The geometrical layout of the simulation scenario is illustrated in Figure 5.25. It consists of a cubic flow domain, where the side at $z = 0$ represents the steel plate mounting with a square cavity in the center. The cavity is covered by a larger aluminum plate, which is to be deformed by the blast. In the simulation, the aluminum plate is aligned with the (inner) domain boundary and extends outwards. Since the aluminum plate is larger than the cavity, only the inner part of it is able to deform freely. The blast is placed centered at some distance from the aluminum plate inside the flow domain. Planes of symmetry are denoted by dash-dotted lines, and are utilized in the following to compute only the upper left quarter of the domain (shown in the left view of the figure).

The flow domain has free outflow boundary conditions at the outer sides of the overall domain. The side of the steel plate has a no-slip boundary condition and the square cavity of the aluminum plate obtains the kinematic FSI boundary conditions prescribed by the structure solver. Symmetry boundary conditions are applied at the inner domain sides. For the structure, dynamic FSI boundary conditions are applied at the inner cavity region and fixed displacement degrees of freedom are used at the overlap of the aluminum plate with the steel plate.

Fig. 5.25: Geometrical layout of the plate blast scenario shown in a front view (left) and a side view (right). A $1.5 \text{ m}^2 \times 75 \text{ cm}$ flow domain contains a centered square 30 cm^2 cavity at the side $z = 0$. A square $30 \text{ cm}^2 \times 3 \text{ mm}$ aluminum plate (blue) to be deformed is placed centered over the the cavity. The inner sides of the aluminum plate and the flow domain are aligned. The blast origin center is at $z = 25 \text{ cm}$.

A blast with an energy equivalent to a 40 g C4 explosion is used. The blast is initialized by using a bursting sphere model, where a ball of radius $r = 1.8 \text{ cm}$ and of even high density contains the blast energy. The aluminum structure is characterized by a density $\rho = 2706 \text{ kg/m}^3$, a Young's modulus $E = 69 \text{ GPa}$, a Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.33$, and a yield stress $\sigma_0 = 83 \text{ MPa}$. An elasto-plastic material model is used with incremental plasticity and isotropic hardening. The structure solver uses tetrahedral volume elements of second order.

Simulation Results

In the following, we first consider the plastic deformations of the aluminum plate, caused by the explosive blast in a static and a transient point of view. Figure 5.26a shows the fluid and structure simulation domains and their deformations due to the blast. As noted before, the simulation domain is only the upper left quarter of the actual domain, due to symmetry considerations. Figure 5.26b shows the corresponding plastic deformations of the aluminum plate after the blast has decayed. The full representation of the plate is obtained by mirroring the simulation results. The maximum deformation of the plate occurs in its center, as expected, since the blast origin is centered at the plate. The maximum deformation magnitude is 2.002 cm.

A history of the plate center displacements in z -direction blast is shown in Figure 5.27.

Fig. 5.26: In (a), the fluid (grey) and structure (red) domains with overlaid mesh are shown. The mesh is deformed at the aluminum plate due to the shock of the blast. In (b), the results of the plate deformation magnitude (in meters) are mirrored along the y - and x -axis to obtain the full plate plastic deformations.

There, the own results obtained in this work are compared to simulation and experimental results obtained in [150]. The own results are between those obtained by the commercial simulation software LS_DYNA and AUTODYN. LS_DYNA is just a structure solver and an analytical blast model was used to obtain loading conditions for a transient structural simulation with it. AUTODYN was first used to compute the results of the flow domain and then, in a second step, taking the boundary forces on the plate to compute the deformations on the aluminum plate. All simulation results are comparable to the experimental data in the initial deformation phase ($t < 10^{-3}$ sec), but yield a slightly larger final plastic deformation compared to the two experiments. The source of the discrepancies between the simulation models and the experiments is not completely clear, as also the simulation results vary by an amount similar to the amount the simulation results are off. Four snapshots of the flow pressure and structure deformation at succeeding times are given in Figure 5.28.

5.4.2 Blast Impact on Cylinder

In the second experiment, a three dimensional cylinder with open ends is considered. The cylinder has a total length of $L = 40$ m and an inner radius of $r = 5$ m. The wall thickness is $d = 2.48$ mm. A copper-like material is used for the cylinder walls, characterized by $E = 117$ GPa, $\nu = 0.34$, $\sigma_0 = 50$ MPa, and $\rho = 8920$ kg/m³. A blast

Fig. 5.27: Center plate z -displacement histories of own results compared to experiments and simulations performed in [150].

equivalent to a 100 kg TNT explosion is centered in the middle of the cylinder using the spherical burst model as in the plate blast scenario of the last section. As in the plate blast scenario, symmetry conditions are used such that only half of the cylinder has to be simulated. Also the structural plasticity model is the same as in the plate blast scenario.

Figure 5.29 depicts the pressure and displacement results obtained at the inner surface of the cylinder at six succeeding times during the simulation. The front parts in the visualization correspond to the cylinder center, while the back parts are one end of the cylinder. Plastic deformations occur with some delay with respect to the blast shockwave hitting the cylinder wall.

The blast simulations show the capabilities of preCICE to perform three-dimensional partitioned FSI simulations. Furthermore, the applicability of the CSS scheme for simulations involving shock waves in compressible flows has been demonstrated.

5.4 Simulation of Explosive Impacts on Deformable Structures

Fig. 5.28: Snapshots of flow pressure (in Pascal) and structure deformation magnitude (in meters) at times $t = \{0.6, 1.7, 2.5, 4.4\} \cdot 10^{-3}$ sec are shown in (a), (b), (c), and (d). The flow visualizations are obtained by mirroring the actual results of the simulation, taking into account symmetry conditions.

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Fig. 5.29: Snapshots of the displacement magnitude contours (left parts) and the pressure contours (right parts) on the cylinder surface under blast impact.

5.5 Summary and Evaluation

preCICE has been applied to three different groups of FSI simulation scenarios in this chapter. The scenarios successfully show the combined application of partitioned coupling functionality for the equation coupling, data mapping, and communication between the solvers. Furthermore, preCICE utility features such as the Python action interface, watch-points, or simulation checkpoints have been applied successfully. The coupling of intra-parallel solvers has been achieved by using the implemented solver-server approach. A total of six different solvers for flow and structure have been coupled, involving open-source and closed source commercial solvers, as well as moving- and fixed-grid flow solvers in different combinations.

The FSI benchmark simulations computed with two solver combinations show that partitioned simulations with preCICE deliver consistent and accurate results. With this validation as a basis, floating structure scenarios have been computed that apply the coupling capabilities to an engineering relevant scenario with more complex flow physics. Finally, the explosive blast simulations showed another scenario with complex physics and demonstrated the capabilities of preCICE to successfully perform three-dimensional simulations.

Overall, preCICE can be regarded as a mature software tool that is ready to be applied in a great variety of partitioned coupling scenarios. The coupled solvers can be reused in different contexts and provide a basis for further simulation scenarios.

6 Summary and Outlook

After a presentation of the contents of this work, we are now going to review and evaluate what has been achieved in Section 6.1 and consider interesting future extensions and research directions related to this work in Section 6.2.

6.1 What has been achieved

This thesis' main goal was to provide a coupling software for the partitioned approach to FSI simulations. State of the art methods for all major coupling tasks should be provided in a way that leverages the flexibility coming with the partitioned approach. The software should be designed and implemented using best-practices from software engineering such that it is easy to maintain and extend. Working on algorithms for partitioned coupling was another goal of this work, as well as to provide a geometry interface for Cartesian grid solvers. In the following paragraphs, we are going to review and evaluate the achieved goals and other outcomes of this work.

Besides the coupling software and improvements of numerical methods, a noteworthy achievement of this work is to provide a comprehensive overview of partitioned equation coupling schemes for black box coupling in Section 2.3. Many of the more interesting equation coupling schemes regarding implicit coupling were published only in recent years and, to the best of the author's knowledge, no comparable attempt to create such an overview has been done.

Another important contribution is the analysis and comparison of existing coupling tools and approaches in Section 2.6 and Chapter 3. In particular, the central supervisor deployment scheme was compared to the peer-to-peer scheme. Furthermore, different deployment schemes for coupling intra-parallel solvers were investigated. Based on these theoretical considerations, a new high-level API for solver adaption has been developed which better abstracts from actual choices of coupling functionality than the message-passing-based interface present in most existing coupling software. E.g., the subcycling logic can be integrated easily into the developed coupling tool.

The main achievement of this work, however, is the design and implementation of the coupling environment preCICE according to the suggestions derived in the performed analysis (see Chapters 3 and 4). A focus on software engineering principles has been taken, resulting in a clear structuring of the sources into components for different cou-

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pling functionality and further utility components. The components such as equation coupling, data mapping, and communication have well-defined interfaces and are further substructured by applying paradigms of object-oriented programming. Automated unit tests, runtime assertions, as well as the extensive use of logging and tracing guarantee a low level of programming errors and quick detection of the sources of errors. They foster further extensions or refactorings of existing code and, thus, allow a long term maintainability of the software.

State of the art algorithms for explicit and, in particular, implicit equation coupling schemes have been implemented. Data mapping methods based on triangular meshes and point clouds have been realized, supporting also higher order solver discretizations. Conservative and consistent data mapping approaches are supported by all implemented mappings. Several communication methods have been implemented and provide flexibility with respect to the solvers' internal communication mechanisms and the computational environment. Not only the core functionality has been realized in preCICE, but also additional utility features and programs have been developed and implemented. E.g., a Python action mechanism for quick manipulation of coupling data, the configuration via XML files, a checkpointing synchronization mechanism, and visualization scripts for table based output data. preCICE is able to couple intra-parallel solvers with its server concept which provides a scalable solution for up to hundreds of solver compute cores. Also, going into the direction of multi-physics simulations with several fields, a methodology for coupling more than two solvers has been investigated and implemented. Overall, the provided set of tools forms a comprehensive coupling environment.

A new algorithm for data mapping in FSI simulations has been developed, implemented, and tested within this work (in Section 4.2.3). The algorithm is based on the consistent approach and performs a post-processing of the mapped pressures to also fulfill the balance of virtual work. It is an alternative to the conservative approach and shows several advantages compared to it. One of its main advantages is that it allows to use two consistent mappings, which avoids pressure oscillations arising for many mappings when used in the conservative mode. Furthermore, it can work with pressures or forces on the structure side, providing more flexibility. The new approach has been tested successfully in academic scenarios.

An additional requirement of this work was to provide a geometry interface for Cartesian grid solvers such as Peano Fluid. Its implementation is described in Section 4.4, where polygonal or triangular boundary representations are used in two or three dimensions, sharing a common code-base with the data mapping coupling functionality. The implemented nearest projection operators are combined with spacetrees to accelerate the processing of positional point and volume queries. Furthermore, algorithms have been developed to cache positional information in the spacetree cells and to further speed up the spacetree creation and query processing. The geometry interface has been used stand-alone within Peano Fluid to perform simulations of reactor cooling pipes and of computer housings. Furthermore, it has been used in combination with the FSI functionality to perform coupled simulations.

A substantial part of this work is dedicated to the validation and evaluation of the implemented functionality. The computational performance and accuracy of the equation coupling schemes, the data mapping methods, and the communication methods, as well as the geometry interface have been analyzed in suitable academic scenarios (in Chapter 4). Furthermore, to evaluate the combination of the features, FSI simulations have been performed with different solver combinations (in Chapter 5), involving several commercial and non-commercial solvers with different levels of access to the solver internals. FSI benchmark simulations have been performed and show a good agreement with reference results. Furthermore, two engineering scenarios have been considered. First, the simulation of floating structures under the influence of water waves and, second, explosive blasts and their impact on structures with plastic deformations. The simulations involved two- as well as three-dimensional scenarios. This set of simulated scenarios together with the different pairs of coupled flow and structure solvers nicely shows the robustness and flexibility of the software and the provided numerical methods.

6.2 Ideas for Extensions

The implemented feature set enables the simulation of a big variety of scenarios and use cases. However, there is still potential for improvement. Also, some new concepts developed within this work need to be applied in more realistic scenarios to allow for a better judgment of their impact. This section serves as a pool of ideas for future extensions and research directions.

While preCICE supports coupled simulations with intra-parallel solvers employing a client-server decomposition of solver and coupling data, the coupling features themselves are not yet parallelized. In particular, schemes involving matrix vector operations such as the IQN-ILS equation coupling scheme or involving the solution of systems of equations such as the radial basis function data mapping, where the number of unknowns is proportional to the number of coupling nodes, represent a bottleneck compared to other coupling functionality. Here, a shared memory parallelization would extend the boundary of computable problem sizes without too much parallelization efforts.

Another bottleneck when coupling intra-parallel solvers is contained in the client-server concept employed by preCICE (see Section 3.4.2). There, the solver-server acts as a sequentialization for all solver processes. Ideas to avoid this sequentialization within the overall solver peer-to-peer communication approach have been presented in this work, but still need to be realized. The communication tests have shown that the bottleneck only becomes significant when hundreds of solver processes are handled by a server and when the parallelization of the coupled solver itself scales accordingly.

When employing highly intra-parallel solvers, the inter-sequential nature of the implemented coupling schemes results in a low overall compute core usage efficiency. To improve the situation, inter-parallel schemes have to be developed which show better

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performance than existing schemes. One very interesting direction has been presented in [165] and implemented in preCICE. This demonstrates the capability of the high-level coupling API in preCICE to abstract from the actual solver-to-solver communication pattern.

Not only parallelization can be used to improve the performance of some of the implemented functionality. E.g., the implemented data mapping methods could make use of the spacetrees implemented for the geometry interface (see Section 4.4.2). The operations of the nearest projection mapping are very similar to those of the positional geometry queries. Furthermore, the radial basis function mappings using local support functions could benefit from the spacetrees. There, the number of involved nodes when setting up the weight matrices could be kept constant by the locality property of the spacetrees. The resulting sparse matrices could be solved more efficiently taking into account suitable methods. In order to enable these benefits, only the connection between the spacetrees and the data mapping methods needs to be added to preCICE.

Multi-coupling capabilities have been built into preCICE to support more than one coupling and two solvers (see Section 4.1.5). Within this work, however, only functional multi-coupling tests have been performed. An interesting opportunity would now be to perform simulations of relevant scenarios such as fluid-structure-acoustic couplings or multi-fluid (or structure) FSI scenarios.

The simulations of floating structures (Section 5.3) can provide insights with engineering relevance. To increase the realism for such scenarios three-dimensional simulations would be necessary. The involved solvers as well as preCICE are capable of performing such simulations, which opens up interesting possibilities for further research in this direction.

Implicit equation coupling schemes have been the focus of this work and only a basic CSS procedure has been implemented for explicit coupling (see Section 4.1.2). More advanced higher-order explicit schemes have been derived recently (Section 2.3.1) and their integration into preCICE could make it more attractive for scenarios with negligible added mass effects.

Overall, the coupling environment preCICE already provides a good feature set that can be applied to solve many partitioned problems. Due to its design it is open for further extensions and, thus, suitable for future research in areas also outside of FSI simulations.

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